
A Work Life Balance of Employees and Its Effect on Emotional Intelligence

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Abstract

Work Life Balance (WLB) got more attention in all Educational sectors especially in Primary school teachers. However, there is a important to investigate increasing cases of work life problems of school teachers. The main purpose of this study is to analyse the relationship between work life balance and emotional intelligence. This study is based on the responses of teaching staffs both men and woman from primary schools. Research instrument designed on the basis of literature survey and then data was collected. In all 150 responses were generated. In this scale refinement was done using percentage analysis. The percentage of analysis from the table was found majority of teaching staffs on the any WLB dimensions. Inter item Convergent validity was high. This study may give insight regarding the relationship between work life balance and emotional intelligence. Balance should be established between workload distribution, time and extra-curricular activities so as to inculcate efficiency among teaching staffs. The study results that there is significant relationship existed between work life balance and emotional intelligence with the limited sample size. There is a need to carry out studies with a larger sample size to make results more generalized.

1. Introduction

The term 'Work-life Balance' word familiarised after 1986. Striking a balance between work and family life is one of the major problems faced by every employee. Employees are who take time off or reduce working hours for taking care of the family experiences more discrimination. Most of employees both male and female lives are becoming more consumed with a host of family and other personal responsibility and interests today. Therefore, in an effort to retain employees, it is increasingly important for organizations to recognize this balance.

Today's married worker is typically part of dual-career couples, which makes it difficult to find time to meet commitments to family, friends and community. But if you're spending most of your time at work, your home life will likely pay the price. Consider the pros cons of working extra hours on your work-life balance. They may miss out on important events, such as your child's first bike ride, your father's 60th birthday or your high school reunion. Missing out on important milestone may harm relationship with your loved ones. Trusted friends are a key part of your support system. But if you're spending time at the office instead of with them, you'll find it difficult to nurture those friendships. If you're regularly worked

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extra hours, you may be given more responsibility. This could create a never-ending and increasing cycle, causing more concerns and challenges.

2. Review of literature

2.1 Roberts et al(2003). Investigated Psychological assessment of emotional intelligence and explores the myth regarding the reduction of working hours in order to enhance work-life balance. The author asserts that work-life policies designed for the reduction of working hours are of particular interest to workers with family responsibilities.

2.2 Abraham Carmeli, (2003) studied the relationship between emotional intelligence and work attitudes, behavior and outcomes: An examination among senior managers. The literature suggests that managerial skills in general and emotional intelligence in particular, play a significant role in the success of senior managers in the workplace. This study attempts to narrow this gap by empirically examining the extent to which senior managers with a high emotional intelligence employed in public sector organizations develop positive work attitudes, behavior and outcomes. The results indicate that emotional intelligence augments positive work attitudes, altruistic behavior and work outcomes, and moderates the effect of work-family conflict on career commitment but not the effect on job satisfaction.

3. Statement of problem

The present study is to analyse the relationship between work life balance and emotional intelligence of the primary school teachers working in villupuram.

4. Objectives of the study

- To assess the relationship between work life balance and emotional intelligence of the primary school teachers
- To discuss the effect of work life balance and emotional intelligence of the primary school teachers

5. Research methodology

The study is carried out under convenient sampling method. The samples are primary school teachers and the sample size is 150 Employees from 5 School in Villupuram. The questionnaire is framed and data is collected. The questionnaire consists of 14 items to evaluate how far the emotional intelligence affects the work life balance. The secondary data were collected from various online resources.

5.1 Data Analysis, Interpretation & Discussion

Hypothesis

H0 – There is no significant relationship between Emotional Intelligence of the respondents with work Life balance

H1 - There is significant relationship between Emotional Intelligence of the respondents with work Life balance

Regression

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	F	Sig.
1	.463(a)	.214	.192	9.867	.000(a)

Coefficients(a)

	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std Error	Beta		
(Constant)	2.747	.108		25.483	.000
Negative feelings help me to address what I need to change in my life.	-.079	.019	-.222	-4.116	.000
I am calm under pressure.	.053	.023	.116	2.351	.019
I have the ability to monitor my feelings from moment to moment	.006	.023	.011	.241	.810
When challenged, I am good at getting calm and focused to flow with life's demands.	-.055	.023	-.124	-2.421	.016
After something has upset me, I find it easy to regain my composure.	.083	.019	.212	4.501	.000
I am effective at listening to other people's problems.	.010	.018	.028	.569	.570
I am able to motivate myself to try and try again in the face of setbacks.	.064	.023	.148	2.763	.006
I try to be creative with life's challenges	-.037	.022	-.097	-1.642	.101
I respond appropriately to other people's moods, motivations, and desires.	-.031	.023	-.068	-1.365	.173
I am capable of soothing myself after an upsetting event.	-.044	.021	-.101	-2.127	.034
I am good at understanding the emotions of other people, even when the emotions are directly expressed.	-.126	.022	-.322	-5.815	.000
People view me as an effective coach for other's emotions.	.054	.024	.106	2.209	.028
I am often able to improve the mindset of others.	.091	.024	.214	3.787	.000
I can easily shake off negative feelings.	.011	.020	.027	.561	.575

a Dependent Variable: WLB_mean

It is deduced from the Model Summary table. This table provides the Multiple Correlation (R = .463), the Multiple Correlation squared (R² = .214), the adjusted Multiple Correlation

squared ($\text{adj.R}^2 = .192$), and the Standard Error of the Estimate. The multiple correlations refer to the combined correlation of each predictor with the outcome. The multiple correlations squared represent the amount of variance in the outcome which is accounted for by the predictors; here, 21.4% of the variance in work life balance is accounted for by overall Emotional intelligence. However, the multiple correlation squared is a bit pessimistic, and therefore, the adjusted R^2 is less appropriate. The summary table, indicates that our model's R^2 is significantly different from zero, $F = 9.867$, $p < 0.000$.

It is deduced from the coefficients table. This table provides the regression analysis that among the 14 independent variables taken for the study, only 9 items significantly influence work life balance. Let's focus on the 9 predictors, whether Employees are statistically significant and, if so, the direction of the relationship. This result also makes sense. This would seem to indicate that the percentages of Emotional intelligences are predicting work life balance. Hence H_0 is rejected, H_1 is accepted.

Discussion

It describes the ability, capacity, skill or, in the case of the trait EI model, a self perceived grand ability to identify, assess, manage and control the emotions of one's self, of others and of groups. Different models have been proposed for the definition of EI and disagreement exists as to how the term should be used. Despite these disagreements, which are often highly technical, the ability EI and trait EI models (but not the mixed models) enjoy support in the literature and have successful applications in different domains. It is believed that employees' emotions matter because they drive one's performance. Emotions at work place, generally, fall into the category of positive (good) and negative (bad) emotions. Positive emotions are those feelings of an individual that are favorable to the attainment of organizational goals while negative emotions are those that are perceived to be destructive for the organization. The negative feeling help the respondents to addresses what they need to change in their life. Negative feeling helps to do self analysis. Self analysis identifies the strengths and weakness of the individual. If one knows about their strength and weakness, they will take step to add the strength and reduce the weakness. They adapt measures to change our weakness into strengths in other hand they reduce it. Work life balance exist when the negative feeling of the respondents to address their need to change in their life. Jyothi & Jothi (2012) Emotions influence the task on which an employee is working, the efforts he/she puts and how he influences other employees around him. In other words, what employees feel and how they express their emotions affects their performance. George (2000) The author tells that an effective Teacher is one who can calmly set aside feelings and pressures and make sound and good decisions. Most of the women were feel calm under pressure than the men especially married. Emotions are an intrinsic part of our biological makeup, and every morning they march into the office with us and influence our behaviour. Silence can change the world, face the problem and find a solution. Silence can talk thousands of words and make the problem into zero. When a challenge arises, one should keep calm and focusing for life's demand that may be real strength to them. Life's demand creates commitment among employee and makes them to pass the problems with or without solution. Silence can protect us from the upsetting event. Upsetting event and failure of solution to the problem is not a destination. Employee can rise up with fresh breathe because they are capable of soothing themselves after an upsetting event. Mostly men can sooth themselves after an upsetting event compared to women. Women especially married have the capability of sooth themselves but it will take time. The pace between the event and revoking should be

considerable. Antonakis (2003) argues that when personality characteristics and general intelligence are controlled EI uniquely contributes little or nothing to the work life balance. Further he also point out that it is not EI competencies or abilities that are required to understand that students will have positive feelings when given a raise and that they will suffer from anxiety and have negative feelings when given a poor performance report. Further he goes on to say that a Teacher having controlled emotions is not always the best way to be effective; sometimes a teacher's passionate, angry outburst can be more memorable and effective than remaining controlled and empathic. It is good at understanding the emotions of other people, even when the emotions are directly expressed. Teachers – students- parents' relationship is bonded emotionally in sometime.

Parents have positive or negative emotion towards school and its teachers similarly students. Parents may express their emotions directly, Teachers is in the position to understand the emotion and give the good solutions. Compared to men, women employee can understand the emotion of others, even when the emotions are directly expresses. Gender is also play considerable role. Expression of feeling and emotion with the same gender is quite easier than the different gender. Blau (1964) further emotional understanding, regulation, and utilization would help to cultivate positive social interactions and exchanges in an organization and as a result facilitate employee performance. Teachers can counsel the student and parents if need arise. Mostly the teachers are good counselors. They can understand the other's emotion and act as coach for their feelings. Their heartwarming words can help them to regain the energy and new blood. People views the teachers are the effective coach to others emotions. The respondents can be able to improve the mind setup of others often. Goleman (2003) Emotional intelligence stimulates motivation, eases change, reduces stress improves communication and enhances rational decision making. It impacts people's ability to sustain both physical and psychological health. It enables to identify and express feelings in right way. It develops positive thinking towards self and others. It protects people from threats of psychological nature generated by criticism. It allows people to address fears by using reasons rather than avoiding them or allowing them to paralyse. It encourages people to be empathic, thereby understanding the feelings of others in right perspective. High emotional intelligence is very relevant for improving neutralize the work and life. Work life balance is a person's control over the condition in their work place. It mutually benefit the individual business and society when a person's personal life in balanced with his or her own job. Work life is concerned with the impact of work on people as well as on organizational effectiveness, and the idea of participation in organizational problem solving and decision making. Thus the result indicates that overall emotional intelligence affect the work life balance.

6. Suggestions

The School can provide basic facilities yoga, meditation, temples, crèches which will cope up the issues like negative feelings, emotional imbalance arised out of work and family imbalance issues. The school can make arrangements for conducting health programs, counseling educations, parenting and family support programs to reduce the employees stress, inferiority complex, fear of failures, emotion and angry. Female teaching staffs have to be support by their family members, which will help them to reduce the personal life stresses.

7. Conclusion

Work-life balance is about creating and maintaining supportive and healthy work environments, which will enable to have balance between work and personal responsibilities and thus strengthen employee loyalty and productivity. The present study is aim at identifying the work-life balance and emotional intelligence on their working institution. From this study it is apparent that the teaching staffs are aware about their work-life balance which is evident from the response of the respondents. The majority of the respondents have the positive attitude towards the prevailing work-life balance. The most respondents perceive that the work-life balance is favorable for them. The overall assessment of the work-life balance states that the most of respondents have a positive perception of the various dimensions of their institution. The most the employees perceived the work-life balance has positive influence on the Institutional development.

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Three Dimensional MHD Boundary Layer Flow And Heat Transfer Along Porous Flat Plate With Transpiration

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Abstract : This paper deals with the laminar flow of viscous incompressible fluid of small electrical conductivity along a porous flat plate with uniform suction under the transverse magnetic field of constant strength has been analysed. The porous plate is subject to a slightly sinusoidal transverse suction velocity distribution. Due to this the flow becomes three-dimensional. Expression for velocity distribution and temperature distribution are obtained with the aid of these the Nusselt number is obtained and numerically computed for various values of suction parameter. Results of numerical calculations have been analysed.

Key words : Eckert number, Nusselt number, Prandtl number, Heat transfer rate

1. Introduction

Many natural phenomena and technological problems are susceptible to MHD analysis. Study of heat transfer in liquid metals is gaining importance because of their wide use in power generation system. As they possess high heat conductivity and realise low Prandtl numbers ranging 0.005 to 0.5, are used as a powerful means in ablation cooling (8,9). The effect of the three dimensional flow caused by the periodic suction perpendicular to the main flow when the difference between the wall temperature and free stream temperature gives rise to buoyancy force in the direction of the free stream on heat transfer characteristics was investigated (1,2,3,4,5). An analytical solution to the problem of the three-dimensional free convective flow of an incompressible viscous fluid past a porous vertical plate with transverse sinusoidal suction velocity taking into account the presence of species concentration (6). In the presence of magnetic field and suction reduces the viscous drag at the plate surface (7).

2. Governing equations and the Mathematical formulation of the problem

The laminar flow of an electrically conducting viscous incompressible fluid past a porous plate is subject to a slightly sinusoidal transverse suction velocity distribution. The infinite porous flat plate is taken lying horizontally $x' - z'$ plane. Here x' -axis is assumed to be along the horizontal porous infinite flat plate in the horizontal direction and z' - axis is taken perpendicular to it. The origin of the co-ordinate system is assumed to be at a point on the plate. Since the length of the plate is very large, therefore, all the physical variables are independent of x' . The uniform magnetic field B_0 is applied perpendicularly to the plane $x' - z'$ of the plate.

The fluid is viscous, incompressible and of small electrical conductivity so, The density (ρ) and the kinematic viscosity (ν) is constant. The magnetic Reynolds number (Re) is taken very small. Due to this the induced magnetic field is neglected, Hall effects, electrical and polarization effects, Joule heating effects in the energy equation are neglected. Then the

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steady free convection flow of an electrically conducting viscous incompressible fluid is given by the following set of non-dimensional equations

$$\frac{\partial v}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial w}{\partial z} = 0 \tag{1}$$

$$v \frac{\partial u}{\partial y} + w \frac{\partial u}{\partial z} = \frac{1}{\text{Re}} \left(\frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial y^2} + \frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial z^2} \right) - \frac{M^2 u}{\text{Re}} \tag{2}$$

$$v \frac{\partial v}{\partial y} + w \frac{\partial v}{\partial z} = -\frac{\partial p}{\partial y} + \frac{1}{\text{Re}} \left(\frac{\partial^2 v}{\partial y^2} + \frac{\partial^2 v}{\partial x^2} \right) \tag{3}$$

$$v \frac{\partial w}{\partial y} + w \frac{\partial w}{\partial z} = -\frac{\partial p}{\partial z} + \frac{1}{\text{Re}} \left(\frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial y^2} + \frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial z^2} \right) - \frac{M^2 w}{\text{Re}} \tag{4}$$

And,

$$v \frac{\partial T}{\partial y} + w \frac{\partial T}{\partial z} = \frac{1}{P_r \text{Re}} \left(\frac{\partial^2 T}{\partial y^2} + \frac{\partial^2 T}{\partial x^2} \right) + \frac{\text{Ec} \theta}{\text{Re}} \tag{5}$$

Where,

$$\theta = 2 \left[\left(\frac{\partial v}{\partial y} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\partial w}{\partial z} \right)^2 \right] + \left(\frac{\partial u}{\partial y} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\partial w}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial v}{\partial z} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\partial u}{\partial x} \right)^2 \tag{6}$$

Where u is The velocity component parallel to the plate in x' - direction, v is the velocity component normal to the plate in y' - direction, w is the velocity component in z' -direction, M is Hartmann number, p is the pressure of the fluid , T is the temperature distribution inside the boundary layer, P_r is Prandtl number and Ec is the Eckert number.

The boundary condition in non-dimensional form is

$$\left. \begin{aligned} y=0; u=0, v=-\alpha(1+\epsilon \cos \pi z), w=0, T=1 \\ y \rightarrow \infty; u=1, v=-\alpha, w=0, p=P_\infty, T=0 \end{aligned} \right| \tag{7}$$

where α is non zero constant suction velocity, ϵ is small positive constant, N in, $v=-\alpha(1+\epsilon \cos \pi z)$, indicates that the suction velocity normal to the wall is directed towards the wall.

For the solution , we assume the following expressions for u, v, w, p and T

$$\begin{aligned} u(y, z) &= \sum_{r=1}^n [u_o(y) + \epsilon^r u_r(y, z)] \\ v(y, z) &= \sum_{r=1}^n [v_o(y) + \epsilon^r v_r(y, z)] \\ w(y, z) &= \sum_{r=1}^n [w_o(y) + \epsilon^r w_r(y, z)] \end{aligned} \tag{8}$$

$$P(y, z) = \sum_{r=1}^n [P_o(y) + \epsilon^r P_r(y, z)]$$

And,

$$T(y, z) = \sum_{r=1}^n [T_o(y) + \epsilon^r T_r(y, z)]$$

Putting equation (8) in equations (4) and (5), and equating the co-efficient of like power of ϵ , we get

$$v_0 \frac{\partial w_0}{\partial y} = \frac{1}{Re} \frac{\partial^2 w_0}{\partial y^2} - \frac{M^2}{Re} w_0 \tag{9}$$

$$-\alpha \frac{\partial w_1}{\partial y} = -\frac{\partial p_1}{\partial z} + \frac{1}{Re} \left(\frac{\partial^2 w_1}{\partial y^2} + \frac{\partial^2 w_1}{\partial z^2} \right) - \frac{M^2}{Re} w_1 \tag{10}$$

$$v_0 \frac{\partial T_0}{\partial y} = \frac{1}{Pr Re} \frac{\partial^2 T_0}{\partial y^2} + \frac{Ec}{Re} \left(\frac{\partial u_0}{\partial y} \right)^2 \tag{11}$$

And

$$v_1 \frac{\partial T_0}{\partial y} - \alpha \frac{\partial T_1}{\partial y} = \frac{1}{Pr Re} \left(\frac{\partial^2 T_1}{\partial y^2} + \frac{\partial^2 T_1}{\partial z^2} \right) + \frac{2Ec}{Re} \frac{\partial u_0}{\partial y} \frac{\partial u_1}{\partial y} \tag{12}$$

The corresponding boundary conditions becomes
at $y=0$; $u_0=0, v_0=-\alpha, w_0=0, T_0=1, u_1=0$

$$v_1=-\alpha \cos \pi z, w_1=0, T_1=0$$

$$\text{at } y \rightarrow \infty; u_0=1, v_0=-\alpha, w_0=0, p_0=p_\infty, T_0=0$$

$$(13)$$

$$u_1=0, v_1=0, w_1=0, p_1=0, T_1=0$$

With the help of above boundary conditions, solution of equation (12) is

$$T_0(y) = e^{-Pr Re y} + h_1 (e^{-\alpha Pr Re y} - e^{-2r_1 y})$$

$$(14)$$

Where,

$$h_1 = \frac{Pr Ec r_1}{2(2r_1 - \alpha Pr Re)} \tag{15}$$

and,

$$r_1 = \frac{\alpha Re + \sqrt{Re^2 \alpha^2 + 4M^2}}{2} \tag{16}$$

Equation (14) gives the Temperature distribution for zeroth order.

3. Heat Transfer in Three dimensional MHD flow along permeable flat plate

The rate of heat transfer at the surface of the plate interms of Nusselt number is given by .

$$Nu = \left(-\frac{\partial T_0}{\partial y} \right)_{y=0}$$

Therefore,

$$\frac{1}{\alpha Re P_r} \left(\frac{\partial T_0}{\partial y} \right)_{y=0} = 1 + h_1 - \frac{2r_1 h_1}{\alpha Re P_r}$$

(17)

4. Results and Discussions

Expression for temperature distribution has been derived and with the aid of this the expression for Nusselt number has been obtained. The calculation for temperature distribution (zeroth order) are made for suction parameter α , Magnetic parameter M , Magnetic Reynolds number Re , Eckert number Ec and Prandtl number $P_r = 0.0643$ for lithium at $200^\circ C$. The results of calculation are entered in table (1) and (2).

Numerical calculation enable us to observe the impact of these parameters on the flow. For all values of suction parameter α and P_r , the Nusselt number Nu decreases as magnetic parameter M increases for fixed value of Reynolds number Re . For a fixed value of Re and M , Nu increases as suction parameter α increases.

For a fixed value of the suction parameter α , the Nusselt number Nu increases as the Reynolds number Re increases for all values of M . Results, have also been derived for non-conducting fluid ($M=0$). In this case, Nu remains almost unaltered for all values of suction parameter α , Reynolds number Re and Prandtl number P_r .

Table 1

Re	Nu			
	M=0	M=3	M=5	M=10
0.01	0.994999	-2.002499	-4.002499	-9.002500
0.1	0.994999	0.697489	0.497494	0.002518
1	0.995000	0.967396	0.947437	0.897469
10	0.995000	0.993595	0.991909	0.987192
50	0.995000	0.994929	0.994806	0.994298
100	0.995000	0.994982	0.994950	0.994807
200	0.995000	0.9949955	0.9949886	0.9949503
500	0.995000	0.994999	0.9949980	0.9949202
1000	0.995000	0.9949998	0.9949994	0.9949980

Variation of Nu against Re when $P_r = 0.0643$ and $Ec = 0.01$ for various values of M and $\alpha = 0.5$

Table 2

Re	Nu			
	M=0	M=3	M=5	M=10
0.01	0.994999	-0.502503	-1.502500	-4.002500
0.1	0.994999	0.847479	0.747495	0.497494
1	0.995000	0.982293	0.972375	0.947437
10	0.995000	0.994585	0.993964	0.991909
50	0.995000	0.994982	0.994951	0.994807
100	0.995000	0.994996	0.994988	0.994950
200	0.995000	0.9949989	0.9949968	0.9949872
500	0.995000	0.9949998	0.949995	0.9949981
1000	0.995000	0.9949999	0.9949998	0.994999

Variation of Nu against Re when $P_r = 0.0643$ and $Ec = 0.01$ for various values of M and $\alpha = 1$.

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Analysis Of Eco Friendly Practices Adopted By The Hotels For Their Sustainability

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Abstract

Certain eco-friendly practices are considered in all over the world in hospitality sector, which is based on the data analysis of different hotels of India. Now a day's eco –friendly practices are very common, which helps in reducing total overall cost as well as it is used for sustainability. Among all eco –friendly practices water conservation, reuse of linen, grey water use, using of fixtures and furniture's are commonly used.

In today's scenario customers prefer to be a part of eco-friendly or sustainability programmes. The eco-friendly practices adopted by hotels are most preferred choices of the customers for participating in the programmes to save environment for the future generation. There is a strong preference by customers towards eco-friendly activities adopted by hotels. The Hotels, which are implementing new features in rooms, bathrooms, lobby, restaurant, banquets and surroundings for the sustainability programmes for environment that enhance the customer satisfaction.

In today's scenario, Customers and Hospitality leaders, Government are also motivated towards "Green hotels" concept in this reference the growing awareness for the environmental damage, excessive consumption of goods and reuse of water are all main concerns for sustainability of hospitality sector. This study will focus on analysing the eco-friendly practices adopted by the hotels for their sustainability.

Keywords:-Hospitality Industry, Sustainability, Eco friendly etc.

Introduction

The hotel industry was established many decades ago and it has been implementing different techniques to save cost, but now they practice of the sustainability for the future and adopted different eco-friendly practices. Sustainability is not short time process it is a long time process. It's the continuous efforts to control cost by several eco friendly practices as limiting of energy and water use, HLP (heat , light, power) is a main concern on which hospitality sector specialists are researching and which is major part of eco-friendly activities , Through eco friendly activities Hotels are being successful in saving HLP.

Now consumers are turning to be more concerned in using those hotels, which are environment friendly, and they are more interested to be a part of eco friendly activities. Customers prefer to spend more to be part in sustainable activities to save earth, they do understand the significance the environment friendly practices.

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All over the world, especially among the developing nations, Tourism is rapidly growing in economic development and employment generation. Beside that sustainability has been challenge for tourism industry therefore the several unpleasant effects of tourism, most significantly on sustainable tourism, which depicts environment .Though there are notable initiatives added for long-term sustainability.

Now days, all level of hotels in the world are facing environmental issues, which incorporate worldwide environmental change, ozone exhaustion, contamination, high utilization of assets and expanding wastage system of hotels, as a component of the tourism industry, apply a huge effect on nature. While the degree and scope of the effect that hotels apply on nature propose a critical need to address this issue, the inquiry that emerges is whether hoteliers value the requirement for naturally cordial activities in their foundations.

Literature Review

Mbaser (2016) mentioned that there is an increasing concern for “Green” hotel in the view of customers as they considered an improved consciousness of environmental harm and unnecessary spending of goods, energy and water. This paper has put some emphasis on environmental issues like global climate change, ozone depletion, greenhouse gasses, high consumption of resources and rising amounts of solid waste. Hospitality and tourism sector make use of an important impact on the environment. At the same time the amount and collection of the impact that hotels apply on the environment proposed an immediate need to deal with this problem, the problem that arises is whether hoteliers welcome the requirement of environment and eco friendly initiatives in the establishments.

Londono and Maskivker (2016) said that Green or eco-friendly practices in the lodgings segment are boosting up around the world. The conception of the green practices implemented by hotels, but also, customer acknowledgment and awareness about those practices related to sustainability. The green practices implemented by hotels is based on the knowledge, advancement and growth, the eco friendly environment is developed by hotel only, few influential factors like gender, nationality, hotel category, city etc plays a reasonably huge role .The author concluded that customers can create optimum influence on hotel category, online surveys by customers for eco friendly practices plays a very important role in selecting a hotel or stay.

N.Fukey & S Issac (2014) wrote that many hotels are getting benefited from green management by using environment friendly practices which lessens their business cost which thereby results in the guest, investing more amount in advertisement and promotions , employees recognitions towards the business. It also helps in earth support system in surplus ways and discusses about the environment concern for the coming future to create awareness for sustainable development. Green initiatives and programmes for sustainability are very useful tools for marketing mechanism .Group hotels will make it more feasible to make it more productive by their task would be more flawlessly accomplished.

Lauren Doherty (2013) stated that hospitality sector industry is developing very fast by its execution of green initiatives to save the natural environment and meet the requirement of green initiatives for the eco friendly customers. The findings are specifying that the all hotels are willingly taking part in environmental sustainability practices and would like to be a part of it by getting further information with continuously seeks further enhancement. These hotels are using variety of sustainability practices in hotel operations , services ,products and events, meetings and also they are using sustainability practices for the pride to save

natural environment , preserve resources, economic benefits, positive marketing with public relations by providing customers best possible services.

Eggeling (2010) stated that notice for eco friendly initiatives in form of green environment , eco-friendly products and service trends has been upraised and the certain trend is for tourism related products. The sustainability issues arising in the hospitality industry and sustainable tourism and development are all part of eco tourism are also interchangeably at times. With the detailed, overview of sustainable practice benefits in hospitality sector, the role and importance of eco friendly practices are analyzed .The findings show that by implementing various sustainable practices in their daily operations, the business believes that by inculcating the concept of sustainability in maximum areas will turn into profits from the benefits. Scandic are very much clear when it comes to sustainability efforts in the hospitality sector.

P K (2009) emphasised on the growth of tourism in India, which is recognized by the governments of the world for economic development and to provide employment. It is also stated by World Tourism Organization (WTO) , it mentions that still we have a great potential for further more upgrading in tourism , specially for a developing nation like India in Asia Pacific region has been rather insulation behind the world. Whereas it shows that tourism is a main resource of earning at few places, which plays a very vital role for local people. In this reference, we must defend tourism places for future and we must stick the environmental practices for the growth of nation.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY :- In the study two categories of hotels were taken into consideration that is budget hotels and luxury hotels , in these hotels 120 respondents of managers levels were taken out of that 113 were male and 7 were females .These were taken randomly from the above two types of category.

A modified questionnaire was constructed in which 24 items were included .the validity of questionnaire is thoroughly checked by hotel chief managers, academicians and experts. 20 respondents filled the questionnaire and reliability was calculated by using SPSS, the cronbach's Alpha (α) was calculated which was 0.751. The questionnaire is used to find out the frequency of their 24 items. Ranking method is used to identify the best eco-friendly practices list adopted eco –friendly practices. Some demographic data is also obtained with the optimum about benefits of eco-friendly practices.

Some statistical technique that is t-Test, analysis of variance is used to find out the more significant differences of the opinion about eco-friendly practices with respect to hotel category, with respect to management level with the level of their experiences .the perception was obtained on LINKERT 5 .(Point) scale, where 5 means strongly agree whereas 1 means strongly disagree.

Analysis Of Data: - Respondents were asked to indicate the eco friendly practices adopted by their respective hotels. Total 3 categories of management were taken as management that is upper level management, middle level management and lower level management .lower level management were 34, middle level management were 55 and upper level management were 31. There were 2 categories of hotels were considered that is budget and luxury .budget were 25 and luxury were 95.out of total 120 managers 113 were male and 7 were females. Descriptive statics of eco-friendly practices by the two types of hotel are as follows:-

Table 1. - Eco Friendly Practices Adopted by the Hotels

Eco friendly practices	Adoption			
	Yes		No	
	N	Percentage	N	Percentage
Water saving taps and flush / W.C. in bathrooms	113	94.17	7	5.83
Rain water harvesting system	93	77.50	27	22.50
Water treatment plant	107	89.17	13	10.83
CFL , LED and other energy saving appliances	110	91.67	10	8.33
Solar water heating system	96	80.00	24	20.00
Solar lighting in gardens and open area	90	75.00	30	25.00
Occupancy/ motion sensors that switch on when guest is inside the room	108	90.00	12	10.00
A.C with remote control to adjust the temperature	107	89.17	13	10.83
Organic, biodegradable soap and shampoo, cleaning agents	101	84.17	19	15.83
100% cotton bed sheets, towels, mattresses, napkins, tablecloth, soft furnishings, curtains etc	111	92.50	9	7.50
Bamboo and cane furniture	79	65.83	41	34.17
Recycled paper bags, envelopes, stationery,	110	91.67	10	8.33
Print on both sides of paper to save paper	103	85.83	17	14.17
Has setup Sewage Treatment Plant(STP) to treat toilet waste	105	87.50	15	12.50
Liquid soap instead of soap cake	106	88.33	14	11.67
Segregate the waste in different bins (biodegradable, non biodegradable, solid/ liquid)	108	90.00	12	10.00
Organic manure, cow dung is used for gardening	103	85.83	17	14.17
Hotel Building is as per Vastu principles for environment	99	82.50	21	17.50
Double paned/ glazed window panes for better insulation	98	81.67	22	18.33
Lush greenery near the building to keep temperature low	102	85.00	18	15.00
Noiseless diesel generator	110	91.67	10	8.33

Train the staff to follow eco friendly practices	115	95.83	5	4.17
Has a written policy for environment management	108	90.00	12	10.00
Motivate staff and guests by posters to follow eco friendly practices	109	90.83	11	9.17

According to results of table 2 the most three used eco-friendly practices are eco-friendly practices training to employees (N=115, Percentage=95.83), Water saving taps and flush / W.C. in bathrooms (N=113, Percentage=94.17) and 100% cotton bed sheets, towels, mattresses, napkins, tablecloth, soft furnishings, curtains etc (N=111, Percentage=92.50). The practices adoption of which were indicated by minimum number of employees were Bamboo and cane furniture (N=79, Percentage=65.83), Solar lighting in gardens and open area (N=90, Percentage=75) and Rainwater harvesting system (N=93, Percentage=77.50).

Table 2.-Top Three Most and Least Adopted Eco-Friendly Practices

Top 3 Eco friendly practices of High Use	N	Percentage	Top 3 Eco friendly practices of Low Use	N	Percentage
Train the staff to follow eco friendly practices	115	95.83	Bamboo and cane furniture	79	65.83
Water saving taps and flush / W.C. in bathrooms	113	94.17	Solar lighting in gardens and open area	90	75.00
100% cotton bed sheets, towels, mattresses, napkins, tablecloth, soft furnishings, curtains etc	111	92.50	Rain water harvesting system	93	77.50

Hotelier's opinions about benefits of eco-friendly practices are taken and three hypotheses were tested regarding management levels, experience and categories.

The hypotheses are-

1. There is no significant difference in the opinion of benefits of eco-friendly practices between the categories of the hotel.
2. There are no significant differences in the opinion of benefits of eco-friendly practices among the manager level.
3. There are no significant differences in the opinion of benefits of eco-friendly practices among their experiences.

Table 3. - T-test results to measure significant difference in Staff opinion about Benefits of Eco-friendly Practices with respect to Hotel Category.

Impact of Hotel category on Staff opinion about Benefits of Eco-friendly Practices

The mean opinion scores table:-of employees working at all level of hotel category are approximately same and all the scores fall in strongly agreeing category. It shows that all the employees working at lower hotel category, middle hotel category and upper hotel category strongly opined that adoption of eco-friendly practices is beneficial for hotels

Hotel Category	Mean	S.D
Luxury Hotel	28.12	2.09
Budget Hotel	27.64	3.12
t-Statistic	0.908	
Significance	0.368	

Level of Significance=5%

Impact of Management Level on Staff opinion about Benefits of Eco-friendly Practices

The mean opinion scores table:-of employees working at all level of management are approximately same and all the scores fall in strongly agreeing category. It shows that all the employees working at lower management, middle management and upper management strongly opined that adoption of eco-friendly practices is beneficial for hotels

Table 4.-ANOVA results to measure significant difference in Staff opinion about Benefits of Eco-friendly Practices with respect to their management level

Source of Variation	Sum of Squares	Degree of Freedom	Mean Sum of Squares	F-Ratio	Significance
Between Samples	7.636	2	3.818	0.439	0.646
Within Samples	1017.36	117	8.695		
Total	1024.99	119			

Above Table is presenting the ANOVA results used to measure significant difference in Staff opinion about Benefits of Eco-friendly Practices with respect to their management level. The value of F-statistic is insignificant which proves that there is no impact of Management Level on Staff opinion about Benefits of Eco-friendly Practices.

Table 5.-ANOVA results to measure significant difference in Staff opinion about Benefits of Eco-friendly Practices with respect to their Experience

Source of Variation	Sum of Squares	Degree of Freedom	Mean Sum of Squares	F-Ratio	Significance
Between Samples	57.543	2	28.772	3.48	0.034
Within Samples	967.448	117	8.269		
Total	1024.99	119			

To measure the impact of work experience on opinion of employees ANOVA test was applied as presented in table 5 at 5%, level of significance the F-ratio is significant which indicates that significant difference exist in opinion of respondents with respect to their Experience.

Interpretation Of The Result

From the above discussion and various tests applied, it can be easily deduced that the different categories of hotel perceives the equal benefits from the adoption of eco-friendly practices.

Further, it is also clear that employees working at various levels of management have same opinion about the adoption of eco friendly practices. They all feel that the adoption of such practices is beneficial for their hotels. Thus, it may also be inferred at the same time that the level of management does not affects the opinion of employees towards the benefits derived by the adoption of eco friendly practices.

It can be further seen that the experience has an impact on the opinion about the adoption of eco friendly practices. It is seen that there exists a significant difference exist in opinion of respondents with respect to their Experience.

Conclusion

All the industries around the globe are facing environmental issues incorporating changes like global warming, ozone depletion and above all the wastage of resources. The concern in hotel industry is much deeper as the wastage of all the resources like water, electricity and others is at high rate, in this industry. The hotel industry has stated long time back and they started different technique to save cost but now they have well aware of the sustainability practices for the future and started adopted different eco-friendly practices for the sustainability. Sustainability in not for short time period it is a long time process.

Through the above study, it may be concluded that the hoteliers are admiring the benefits of eco friendly practices. It may be concluded that the employees at all the levels and in all category of hotels, hoteliers have an opinion that eco friendly practices are beneficial for the sustainability of hotels.

Finally, it may be recommended that hotels need to convince people with varied years of experiences and try to adopt new eco friendly practices to stand competitive and sustainable in this era.

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Corporate Sustainability Reporting Practices Among Indian Companies

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Abstract

The challenge posed by sustainability and sustainable development cannot be sorted out by the efforts of any particular section of the society, it requires collective effort of business, civil society and government. Effective utilization of scanty resources by the corporates can bring out radical change in the society. Global reports emanating from several multilateral institutions present a picture which requires extreme and immediate concern. India is the second largest country in terms of population. Large population of India has taken environmental resources under huge stress. Climate change and global warming has also adversely affected the environmental balance. The need for sustainable development has never been more critical and urgent. Corporates can indeed play an extremely meaningful role in fulfilling the aim of sustainable development. Corporate's superior innovative capacity, diverse managerial capability and entrepreneurial vitality can pave the path of sustainable future. Recently, large global companies have faced increased accountability pressure. This increased pressure for accountability and transparency has facilitated in the growth of sustainability reporting. Day by day organisations are striving to be transparent and accountable to various stakeholders of the organization to preserve their reputation and brand image. Sustainability reports are intended to improve internal processes, engage stakeholders and influence investors. Indian economy is developing at a rapid pace like never before. Sustainable development is the key to organisation's success, because only sustainable development can provide long term holistic benefits to current and future generations. Importance of sustaining the environment and the urgency of the situation cannot be disregarded in today's era of environmental concerns and global warming. The most important challenge is to achieve a sustainable balance between environment management and economic growth. This paper provides an overview of sustainability reporting, its importance in today's scenario and the sustainability reporting practices being followed by Indian companies.

Keywords: Sustainability Reporting, Accountability, Transparency, Indian Companies

Introduction

The indiscriminate progress made by industries has adversely affected the environment and at the same time it has left a large number of population in extreme poverty. This progress cannot be called sustainable in any way. Sustainability is of extreme importance in context of development in India. As India has set a target of achieving high economic growth, it is extremely necessary to assess the impact of such high growth on the environment and society. Economic growth will result in sustainable development only when it includes all,

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it should include even the marginalised sections of the society. Enriching environmental capital is the only way of achieving sustainable development.

The steep decline in fresh water availability, high levels of water and air pollution, reduction in forest cover due to indiscriminate deforestation, higher dependence on fossil fuels and increased wastelands are some of the prominent issues which requires immediate concern so that India can achieve desired sustainable growth.

Corporates are an integral part of any society and they must make endeavours for dealing with this global challenge. Contributions made by the corporates should be measured by “triple bottom line” which consist of three dimensions. These three dimensions are: ecological, economic and social. Corporates largely depends on societal resources. Hence, it is utmost important that corporates should make continuous disclosures to all the stakeholders and civil society as well. These disclosures should throw light on efficiency with which these societal resources are being consumed, and they should also reveal about the contribution made by the corporates towards triple bottom line.

Corporate sustainability reporting is based on the fundamental of give and take. Companies use natural resources from the environment to provide products and services to the people and to earn profit. But from the last two decades there has been a constant realization of the fact that the activities of the companies are damaging the environment because of the continuous pressure on the natural resources to satisfy the demands of the society which in turn is disturbing the ecological balance within the environment. All these concerns paved the way for sustainable development. Sustainable development is based on the idea of economic growth along with ecological balance and social progress. Reports based on sustainable practices of the companies form the sustainability reports. Sustainability reports include details about the contribution of the companies towards sustainable development which includes both positive and negative contributions. Sustainability reporting can be voluntary or mandatory. Mandatory reporting and voluntary reporting have their own set of merits and demerits.

Earlier the importance was given towards development but from the past three decades after observing the repercussions of our actions on the environment in the form of global warming, greenhouse effect and climate change, the focus has somehow shifted in the positive direction of sustainable development.

Sustainable development can be defined as “development that meets the need of the present without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own” (Brundtland Commission).

Sustainability Reporting

Report published by an organisation regarding impact of its activities on the environment, economy and society is known as sustainability report. Sustainability report reflects about the governance model and values of the organization, it also indicates the link between strategy of the organisation and commitment towards sustainable global economy. It can also help organisations in understanding, measuring and communicating their environmental, economic and social performance, and then setting goals accordingly and managing change in more effective way. It is a chief platform for conveying sustainability performance and both negative as well as positive impacts.

Sustainability reporting is another form of non-financial reporting like corporate social responsibility reporting, triple bottom line reporting and more. Sustainability reporting is

also an essential part of recent development which makes use of both financial as well as non-financial performance analysis, also known as integrated reporting.

Sustainability reporting ensures that corporates are vigilant about impacts made by them on various sustainability issues and also makes sure that corporates are transparent about opportunities and risks faced by them. Increase in transparency results in effective decision making which further leads to building and maintaining trust in governments and businesses. Focus of sustainability reporting is on management and organization of the company, corporate social responsibility and its core business practices and operations.

Corporates became member of three global sustainability initiatives, namely, United Nations Global Compact (GC), Carbon Disclosure project and Global Reporting Initiative (GRI) Sustainability Reporting Framework. Members of these institutions should follow the principles and guidelines of these initiatives for reporting about sustainable business practices.

Global Reporting Initiative And Sustainability Reporting

GRI is an international organization which works independently since 1997 and it is the pioneer organization for sustainability reporting. Sustainability Reporting Standards devised by GRI, also known as GRI standards are adopted worldwide for sustainability reporting. The purpose of GRI is to enhance the quality and utility of sustainability reporting all over the world. The Global Reporting Initiative (GRI) is international, multi-stakeholder and long-term process which aims at developing and disseminating Sustainability Reporting Guidelines which can be adopted globally. Organisations voluntarily use these guidelines for reporting the environmental, social and economic dimensions of their products, services and activities. These guidelines also aims at assisting corporates and their stakeholders in understanding and articulating the contributions made by them towards sustainable development. GRI focuses on four areas in order to achieve its purpose, namely, harmonizing the sustainability landscape, creating standards and providing guidance for propelling sustainable development, driving productive use of sustainability information for enhancing performance and leading effective and efficient sustainability reporting. First global standards for sustainability reporting were launched by the GRI in October 2016. Global Sustainability Standards Board (GSSB) develops the GRI standards and these standards help corporates in publically reporting about impact made by them on environment, economy and the society; and also reflects on the contributions made by them towards sustainable development. Modular structure of GRI standards assists in keeping them relevant and up-to-date, these standards also serve as the parameter for policy makers.

Importance Of Sustainability Reporting

Corporate Sustainability Reporting, which is also called CSR reporting, is the reporting method where companies, whether public or private; large or small, provides report about their non-financial performance. Sustainability reports helps corporates in determining the effect of their actions on the community, society, environment and over-all sustainability. Sustainability reports should report not only about sustainability objectives and targets but also about company's sustainability performance.

Sustainability reporting is the first and most important step towards devising a strategy which can help an organization in apprehending the effect on its stakeholders, and finding out the ways which can help in reducing the negative effect on the society, economy and the environment. Considering all these factors, in Indian context, where CSR reporting is not a mandatory requirement, the question arises, how easy-going it is for Indian companies, is it

really worth spending all that time and money in getting the auditing done and publishing the reports regularly?

Review Of Literature

Brief summary of studies on sustainability reporting practices is provided below.

Neeraj Goyal (2014) aimed to study the level of environmental disclosures among Indian companies. The study gives an insight on the concept of sustainability and its origin and also discusses mandatory and voluntary environmental disclosures. The study focused on finding the status of corporate disclosure in India. Top ten companies from five sectors namely Cement, Textile, FMCG, Petroleum and Pharmaceutical are selected (BSE 500 India is taken as base). The study found out that the level of disclosure among different companies and different industries vary to a large extent.

P D Jose, Saurabh Saraf (2013) in their working paper analysed the sustainability initiatives of top 100 of the most valuable private sector companies, as ranked in 2010 by Business Today (BT 500) and these companies were categorized under 15 sectors. Findings of the research were reported under three sections, namely, and Core Business Practices and Operations, Management and Organisation and Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR). Corporate governance was a strong focus point among all the companies surveyed. Heavy sectors outperformed other sectors on most indicators. Researcher found out that top 25 companies gave reports on higher number of variables as compared to the bottom 25 companies, which means that there is higher degree of transparency in reporting by the top companies. Almost 80% of all the companies in this study reported on minimum of one aspect regarding greening of operations under Core Business Practices and Operations. Energy conservation being most popular initiative. Under management and organization, approximately 85% of the companies had a published corporate governance policy. Voluntary sustainability reporting is still limited. Around 70% of the companies considered for this study, focused primarily on four major CSR areas, namely, healthcare, education, infrastructure development and community livelihood under Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR). These companies can further improve sustainability reporting by increasing transparency in Corporate Social Responsibility donations and finances which would lead to greater efficiency in Corporate Social Responsibility programmes.

P D Jose, Haimashree (2014) carried out a study on the sustainability initiatives of 100 most valuable private sector firms rated by Fortune 500 in the year 2013 and classified the companies into 12 different sectors. The data was then compared against the findings of another study on the reporting practices of 100 most valuable Indian private sector companies as rated by Business Today (BT 500) in 2010 which were classified into 15 different sectors. The study shed light on some interesting trends. There is a strong focus on green operations, environmental conservation and philanthropy among the firms surveyed. Disclosures related to CSR finances and infrastructural development is low in both the Indian and global cases. The study indicates that global companies did slightly better in reporting green manufacturing initiatives.

Objective Of The Study

The objective of this study is to examine the status and pliability of sustainability reporting among Indian firms.

State Of Sustainability Reporting In India

Recent analytical study of 46 companies suggested that there is significant progress in the quality of corporate sustainability reporting in India. A study titled 'Sustainability

Integration – Corporate Reporting Practices in India' was presented collectively by Indian Institute of Management Bangalore, GRI Regional Hub South Asia and Tata Consultancy Services Ltd in November 2016. Study found out that Indian companies have started to comprehend the links between corporate performance, sustainability practices and competitive advantage, which in return has resulted in increased level of disclosure. However, the research also suggests that there is disinterest in sustainability on the part of senior management and they do not want create greater value.

As per another report by KPMG, Most of the Indian reporters use Global Reporting Initiative (GRI) guidelines to prepare the sustainability report while referring to other international standards and charters like UNGC guidelines, IFC standards on sustainable development, WBCSD focus areas and sector specific frameworks such as API/IPIECA guidelines and ICMC sustainable development framework. Of the companies declaring GRI application level, it has been observed that almost all companies declare the A/A+ application level. Most reporters believe that a higher application level is equivalent to better sustainability performance and in this process they lose out on communicating key priorities to the stakeholders. Also, very few companies use the feedback from stakeholders to define the report content. Use of company's risk assessment framework and company's sustainability strategy to select report content is extremely low which reaffirms the fact that sustainability issues do not have clear linkage with the business strategy of the companies.

Considering the current scenario of sustainability reporting as mentioned in above reports, it is evident that corporate sustainability reporting has become a buzzword among companies in India. Below are few examples of Indian companies on their approach towards sustainability reporting.

Sustainability Reporting in Indian companies:

Tata Consultancy Services (TCS) publishes sustainability report annually. The reports are prepared according to the Sustainability Reporting Guidelines of Global Reporting Initiative's (GRI) G4, as per the Core reporting option while emphasising on principles of stakeholder inclusiveness and materiality. It includes chief sustainability aspects environmental, economic and social impact of company's activities.

Triple-bottom-line approach is used by TCS for reporting on corporate sustainability, it seeks to nurture long term value for stakeholders by managing environmental, economic and social risks while embracing business opportunities.

Maruti Suzuki also prepares sustainability report according to the guidelines mentioned in GRI G4 as per the Core reporting option. Reports are published annually and most recent one was published in 2015-2016.

The company uses certain aspect boundaries and defining report content for preparing its reports. Contents of the report are defined through internal materiality assessment exercise. Materiality matrix is jointly created by a cross-functional team with the help of an external sustainability expert. Following are the aspect boundaries considered in preparing each report:

Marketing communications, Compliance, Procurement practices, Emission Effluents & waste, Energy, Materials, Supply chain, Products & services, Economic performance, Training and education, Employment, Collective bargaining and freedom of association, Occupational safety and health Labour and management relations, Compulsory or forced labour, Child labour, Customer safety & health, Local community.

Reliance Industries Limited: Their annual sustainability report looks into both internal as well as external perspectives for identifying and helping them understand the opportunities and risks related with new and emerging issues in better way. Identified issues are examined for their significance to Reliance Industries Limited and their effect on social, environmental and economic aspects. Disclosure through reports aims at their stakeholders like customers, investors, employees, business partners, joint venture partners and the community. The report is focused on their endeavours towards tactical pillars sustainable development: environment, energy management, social institution building, product stewardship and occupational health and safety.

Main activities carried out under each of the tactical pillars are based on the success they have already achieved in reducing impact on environment and contribution made to the society through investment in meaningful ventures.

Conclusion

Our planet Earth provides all the resources for the life and development of mankind. But we humans have forgot to take care of our planet and resources and are blindly following the path of development without looking at the impact of our actions on the natural resources, climate and on the whole environment.

Sustainability challenges all over the world and those pertinent in developing economies like India requires a new model of growth. New era of sustainable world will be marked by unprecedented growth in livelihood opportunities and jobs creation. A safe and healthy work environment is a basic requirement for ensuring employee wellbeing which enhances the company's overall performance. Healthy work environment and workplace safety is one of the prime requisite for safeguarding wellbeing of the employees, this leads to increase in overall performance of the company. Technology must create livelihood opportunities for all the participants of value-chain. Simultaneously, growth models should focus on combating the climate change and need of replenishing the environment.

Overall, there is ample indication that Indian companies are now paying boosted attention to sustainability concerns and large companies have started to establish a well-defined link between sustainability and risk management. A latest trend observed is to incorporate sustainability elements as part of internal audit so that the issues are reviewed at the administrative level. However, there is still a long way to go before sustainability is fully assimilated into business strategy. Although corporate responsibility seems to be in the experimental phase in India as of now, meaningful progress in both the number of reporters and quality of information reported is expected, in the coming years.

There is no doubt that corporate responsibility is here to stay and businesses have realized the value of including sustainability and more so making it a part of their overall business strategy.

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Adoption of IFRS in India: Pros and Cons

Md. Moneef Ahmad*

Abstract

The adoption of IFRS is a general topic across the world as IFRS is a single set of international accounting standards which assist stakeholders and companies in communicating and comparing corporate financial information. In this globalised era, the cross country investment, trade of goods and services and technology has increased over the time. All the countries are following their respective accounting policies which give rise to conflict so there was a need of one accounting standard which will be followed by all countries. This single accounting standard will help in getting accounting information more transparent, comparable, relevant and widely accepted. In India adoption of IFRS is not new, the discussion about its adoption is going for past decade but it has not been followed completely. India has adopted IFRS as Ind AS which is a converged form of IFRS. The IFRS adoption gives improved disclosure, better comparability, high quality transparency, raising capital from abroad and also help in competing with the foreign companies. Its challenges are difference in IGAAP and IFRS, training and education, legal and regulatory consideration.

Keywords: IFRS, IGAAP, Transparency, cross border investment, IASB.

Introduction

The significance of international accounting practices has augmented over the last few years as there is rise in the capital rising from various parts of the world. In the present era of globalization, the world has now become a global village because of inter country trade i.e. exchange of goods and services, technology, manpower and the capital across the boundaries of a country. They are results of ever increasing international shareholdings and trade and are specifically significant for companies that operate in various countries. In this context, one of the most principal preconditions to run a successful business is to implement a quality financial reporting system. Each country has different set of rules and regulations for financial reporting and accounting which gives a rise of conflict due to difference in the accounting policies. So there was a need of common or single set of standard which can be followed by all the country in order to achieve greater uniformity, transparency, comparability and relevance of the financial accounting information. Hence, this gives the rise to a new international standard i.e. International Financial Reporting Standards(IFRS). International Financial Reporting Standards (IFRS) have been formulated as a universal platform for all the business dealings so that the financial accounts of various entities in different parts of the world are understandable and comparable. Accountants have to follow rules in maintaining books so that they are understandable, comparable, relevant and reliable for the users of accounting information, that is, both internal as well as external users. IFRS is a set of international financial reporting and accounting standards that helps in harmonizing financial information of companies, leads to better transparency in accounting and also makes sure that investors get more consistent and accurate report. IFRS started with

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an objective to harmonize accounts across all the nations of European Union (EU) but the benefits of harmonization quickly attracted other nations as well. However, it is still a topic of discussion that whether this harmonization is de-facto or not. Standards which were presented by IASC (precursor of IASB) and are used till date are known as International Accounting Standards (IAS), whereas standards presented by IASB are known as IFRS. Board of International Accounting Standards Committee(IASC) issued IAS during 1973-2001. On 1st April 2001, responsibility for establishing International Accounting Standard was taken over by the new International Accounting Standard Board (IASB) from the IASC. IASB continues developing new standards and they are known as International Financial reporting Standards.

IFRS consists of

- International Financial reporting standards (IFRS_S) developed by the IASB.
- International accounting Standards (IAS) adopted by IASB.
- Interpretations originated from the International Financial Reporting Interpretations Committee (IFRIC_S).
- Standing interpretation Committee (SIC_S).

IFRS in India

International Accounting Standards is a relatively old idea, the concept first came to light by the end of 1950's when industrialized nations wanted to develop a standard that could be adopted by developing nations and smaller countries. With the advent of globalization, business world turned more global and global auditing firms and large companies started to realize the significance of adopting single global accounting standards. In 2007 International Federation of Accountant(IFAC) conducted a survey on 143 nations (Hundred and forty three) all over the world on the theme of necessity of single accounting standards, approximately 90% respondents responded positively that adoption of International Standards will help in the growth of their respective countries. In India, significance of International Accounting Standards (IAS) was highlighted when new economic policy, that is, Liberalization, Privatization and Globalization was announced by the Prime Minister Narsimha Rao's government. It was revealed through the survey conducted by the Ernst & Young in 2009 that 79% of the Indian corporates are anticipating IFRS conversion because of its accountability, transparency and global acceptability. Based on this, in 2010 Ministry of Corporate Affairs (MCA) officially put forward phase approach with respect to adoption of IFRS in India. In the initial phase, they have taken into account the conversion of opening balance sheet as on 1st April 2011 by classifying the Indian companies into four groups. These groups are:

Group A: Companies that are part of NSE 50(NIFTY50)

Group B: Companies that are part of BSE-SENSEX(BSE30)

Group C: Companies whose shares or other securities are listed on a stock exchange outside India

Group D: Companies listed or not having Net worth exceeding Rs.1000 Crore.

Till 2014, it was not been feasible to make it compulsory in India because of legal roadblocks and substantial changes in international standards. On 16th Feb, 2015 the MCA notified the amended guidelines for enacting Ind AS which is relatively merged form of IFRS for Indian companies except insurance companies, banking companies and non-banking finance companies. The final strategy announced by the MCA for implementation of Ind AS, is as below:

Threshold	First Period of Reporting	Comparative Information
All companies, with Net worth of rupees 500 Crore or more (listed or unlisted)*	Financial Year commencing on or after 1 st April, 2016	Opening balance sheet as on or after 1 st April, 2015 and Financial year closing on or after 31 st March, 2016
Other companies whose equity and /or debt securities are already listed or are in the process of being listed on any stock exchange in India or outside India*	Financial Year commencing on or after 1 st April, 2017	Opening balance sheet as on or after 1 st April, 2016 and Financial year closing on or after 31 st March, 2017
Unlisted companies with net worth of rupees 250 Crore or more, but less than rupees 500 Crore*	Financial Year commencing on or after 1 st April, 2017	Opening balance sheet as on or after 1 st April, 2016 and Financial year closing on or after 31 st March, 2017

*Including Subsidiary, Holding, Associate Companies or Joint Ventures of such companies.

List of Effective IFRS

S. No.	TITLE	ISSUED
IFRS 1	First-time adoption of international financial reporting standards	2003
IFRS 2	Share based payment	2004
IFRS 3	Business combinations	2004
IFRS 4	Insurance contracts	2004
IFRS 5	Non-current Assets held for sale of discontinued operations	2004
IFRS 6	Exploration for and evaluation of Mineral Resources	2004
IFRS 7	Financial instruments: Disclosures	2005
IFRS 8	Operating Segments	2006
IFRS 9	Financial Instruments	2009
IFRS 10	Consolidated financial statements.	2011
IFRS 11	Joint arrangements	2011
IFRS 12	Disclosure of interests in other Entities	2011
IFRS 13	Fair value measurement	2011
IFRS 14	Regulatory Deferral accounts	2014
IFRS 15	Revenue from contracts with customers	2014
IFRS 16	Leases	2016

Literature review

The company adopts new accounting policy after going through deep research and its effects when they adopt any new standard it may give positive or negative impact or sometimes it remain unchanged. Around the globe different researcher has done different research on IFRS adoption and its impact. **Sankar Thapa(2012)** in his paper IFRS in Indian banking industry challenges ahead highlighted the challenges faced by the banking industry of India in adoption of IFRS and found that there is a need of change in the existing law, Skilled manpower, Increased cost etc. In another paper by **Santosh V. Rode(2012)** in his paper IFRS

vs. Indian GAAP- Some key differences has stated the similarities and difference between Indian GAAP and IFRS which have significant impact on the financial statement. Another paper **Surajit Das(2017)** in his paper IFRS and its impact on Indian companies: An empirical study has found the need to adopt IFRS in India they had analysed the impact of difference in IFRS and IGAAP which help in devising more suitable rules and regulation towards IFRS compatibility in India.

There are plenty of researches available on the IFRS adoption with mix reviews as IFRS is new to the world and also for India it is in its infant stage. There are many researchers who are in favour of IFRS adoption in India which will grow the economy of the country and there are researcher who had advocated against IFRS and found many challenges in adoption of IFRS in India.

Objectives

This research paper focuses on the following objectives:

1. To examine the benefits of adoption of IFRS in India.
2. To examine the challenges in adoption of IFRS in India.

Benefits of IFRS adoption in India

The IFRS have large number of benefits to the companies and economy. These benefits are classified under the following two heads:

I. General benefits

II. Benefits of IFRS for National Regulatory Bodies

I. General Benefits

1. **It grants grater comparability:** Organizations using similar standards for preparing financial statements can more accurately compare with each other. This is very useful when comparing businesses that are based in different countries, as they may otherwise have different methodologies and rules in preparing these documents. This greater comparability has aided investors to better identify where their investments should go.
2. **It is favourable to new and small investors:** The IFRS can be beneficial for new and small investors by making reporting standards to have better quality and become simpler, putting these investors in a similar position with professional investors, which was not feasible under previous standards. This also entails a reduced risk for these investors when they trade, as the professionals will not be able to take advantage because the nature of financial statements will just be simple to be understood by all.
3. **It leads to greater flexibility:** Use of philosophy which is principles based, instead of rules, this set of standards will have the goal of arriving at a reasonable valuation with various ways to accomplish tasks. This would give businesses the freedom to adopt IFRS to their specific situations, which will result in financial statements that are more easily read and useful.
4. **Improve disclosure:** IFRS improves better disclosure of financial information. The financial accounting information is very important for different users of the business and authentic accounting information is necessary thus IFRS provides improved disclosure practices of the accounting information.
5. **Comparison is made easier with foreign competitors:** In this globalized economy when whole world has become a global village where there is transfer of goods and services, manpower, technology and capital across the boundaries, the companies with different accounting policy gives rise to a conflict of different valuation. So IFRS has

helped in comparison of parent companies accounting information with the foreign companies. Thus helps in creating better business relation.

6. **High quality transparency:** IFRS helps in achieving high quality transparency by adopting a single standard applicable to all the nations. Since all the nation follow same accounting policy which helps in getting accounting information in a better transparent way.
7. **Benefit of raising capital from abroad:** Since there is increase in the foreign direct investment over the past few years, thus IFRS will help the countries to raise the capital from abroad easily. The investing country will not find any difficulty in understanding accounting information of that country since parent company is also following the same accounting policies i.e. IFRS.

II. Benefits Of IFRS For National Regulatory Bodies

1. Indian Accounting standard Board will be vigilant to the top international accounting practice (IFRS) to lead them in the institutionalizing of thoroughly upgraded reporting practices in India.
2. It leads to better and higher standard of financial disclosure.
3. It also leads to improved ability to monitor and attract listings by foreign companies.

Challenges in adoption of IFRS in India

Multiple advantages of adopting IFRS have been listed by various Accounting Professionals all over the world. Despite all its advantages, adoption of IFRS is demanding task and is faced with various challenges.

1. **Not accepted globally:** Fact is, IFRS has not been adopted by US yet, so other countries are also holding on adoption of IFRS. As a result, foreign companies conducting businesses in such countries are having problems in accounting as they have to prepare financial statements in accordance with standards and principles generally accepted in such countries.
2. **Difference in IFRS and GAAP:** Adoption of IFRS requires drastic change in the entire set of financial statements. The differences are very wide and deep rooted. Creating awareness in the users of financial information about IFRS and its impact will be a challenging task. In the recent years, IGAAP has converged with IFRS to a great extent but differences are still there and some of these differences are a significant challenge that should be overcome. Concerns were noted by the participants in the following areas.
 - a. IFRS is based more on principles, and thus it is more 'progressive' than Indian GAAP. Greater choices under IFRS mean that there is increased need of professional judgement, and this requires an elementary change in attitudes of Indian accountants.
 - b. Different measurement and recognition criteria for assets and liabilities will be a challenge in initial transition. This will impact not only earnings, but it is vital to be able to seize those differences through proper information systems.
 - c. Certain accounting areas that will be more complicated included financial instruments and business combinations. Most of the complications related with them are a result of higher use of fair value accounting under IFRS.
3. **Interaction between Accounting and Legislation:** There are doubts about the compatibility of Indian laws with IFRS in certain matters pertaining to accounting, such as formats and presentation requirements. Similarly, there is uncertainty over tax treatments of items arising from convergence such as unrealized gains and losses and the move from a tax basis for depreciation (IGAAP) to one of useful economic life (IFRS).

- 4. Education and Training:** Dearth of academic courses and training facilities on IFRS will also pose challenge in India. A key challenge is to ensure companies, auditors, regulators and the investment community is appropriately skilled to apply and interpret IFRS.
- 5. Orderly Financial Reporting Processes:** Although various Indian companies have still not thought about the impact on their information systems. These will require a fundamental review and initial costs could be significant. At the same time, it is important to have in place sound systems in order to ensure that subsequent generation of reporting information is efficient.
- 6. Regulatory and Legal Considerations:** Presently, the reporting requisites are governed by various regulators in India and their provisions override other laws. IFRS does not recognize such overriding laws. The regulatory and legal requirements in India will pose a challenge unless the same is been addressed by respective regulatory. IFRS convergence would affect most of the items in the financial statements and consequently the tax liabilities would also undergo a change. Thus the taxation laws should address the treatment of tax liabilities arising on convergence from Indian GAAP to IFRS.
- 7. Fair Value Measurement:** Fair value is used by IFRS as a measurement base for valuing most of the items of financial statements. The use of fair value accounting can bring a lot of volatility and subjectivity to the financial statements. It also involves a lot of hard work in arriving at the fair value and valuation experts have to be used.
- 8. Requires high cost:** Whether big or small, all organizations would feel the impact if IFRS is adopted by the country. However, small enterprises would be at a disadvantage as they do not have enough resources to implement changes that adoption of IFRS brings. Training of staff and hiring of consultants and accountants for assistance will be a costly affair. Small enterprises would be more burdened financially in comparison to the large enterprises.

Conclusion

The present study is all about the adoption of IFRS in India and the benefits and challenges in its adoption. Since there is a need of single standard of accounting policies across the world as there is increase in the trade of goods and services, technology and capital across the boundaries. This paper found that there are different benefits that come with the adoption of IFRS, with its adoption the Indian company will be benefited to a great extent as they will be able to compete with the foreign companies. In this globalized economy, IFRS will provide Indian company with a better and improved disclosure practices and better transparency of the accounting information. This will also help in getting cross border investments very easily. But with benefits there are different challenges in its adoption since Indian political system is more complicated as compared to other countries. So there is difference in legislation and accounting. Also the training and education of IFRS is not upto the mark and the cost of adopting IFRS is also very high. This research paper will help in understanding IFRS in India and its benefits and challenges.

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Customers Relationship Management in Allahabad Bank and HDFC Bank: A Case Study

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***Abstract:** Now-a-days, life becomes faster and faster. Lots of competition is there in job, education in India. To survive in this competitive era, Banks need adequate facilities to be provided to the customer. Today, Bank is kind of an integral a part of society. Banks play a measure role in providing the facility of money establishments that deal in financial transactions. There are number of varied banks settled in several elements of our country whereas earlier there have been restricted range of banks with some branches in massive cities and cities in Republic of India, variety of latest banks have opened within the previous couple of decades with branches in each nook and corner of the country. These numbers of banking in India are mainly classified into two parts i.e. Nationalize banks and Private banks. Current study is based on the difference between two banks and their services i.e. Nationalize Bank Allahabad Bank and Private bank HDFC Bank and their relationship with customers. Around 40 customers are selected as a sample size for this study.*

***Key Words:** money, bank, Nationalize Bank, Allahabad Bank, Private bank, HDFC Bank, Customers satisfaction etc.*

Introduction: The cash keeping with ourselves is very hard and it's quite risky. Individual feels to keep this cash in the bank. People are inspired to stay their cash within the banks as a result of it's a secure and secure thanks to store the cash. The cash keep within the bank within the variety of fastened deposits and continual deposits conjointly fetches an honest quantity of interest. Additionally to cash, one also can keep jewellery and vital papers within the bank lockers. "Banking in India, in the modern sense, originated in the last decade of the 18th century. Among the first banks were the Bank of Hindustan, which was established in 1770 and liquidated in 1829–32; and the General Bank of India, established in 1786 but failed in 1791.^[1]" Current Scenario is that there are number of options to the client for banking. The researcher feels to study comparatively on the service provided by Nationalize bank and Private Banks Special concern with Allahabad Bank and HDFC bank with following aims and objectives.

Aims and Objectives of the Study

- a. To study about the facilities of Allahabad Bank and HDFC Bank for customers.
- b. To compare the service quality of Allahabad Bank and HDFC Bank towards customers.

Hypothesis

There is less different between Nationalize bank and Private bank in facilities for customers in respect to facilities but charges are more HDFC Bank in as compare to Allahabad Bank.

Problem of the Statement: There are various options of Banks in India, but yet customers are having problems in the maintenance of account, service of ATM, On-line banking facilities etc. Hence, it is very important to study on the problems of customers regarding to the service provided by banks to maintain healthy relations with customers in Banks.

Methodology of the Study: The current work is data base work. Total 40 customers are selected from Allahabad Bank and HDFC Bank for the study with promising them that their

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names and place where they are having account in bank is kept as secret. Because it may be a cause of their further suffering in banks.

Following parameters are study for the study:

- a. Behaviour of employees with customers in Banks.
- b. Online facilities available by banks.
- c. ATM service provided by bank.
- d. Facilities provided by the banks.

Sample Size

There were 40 customers selected from two Banks i.e. Allahabad Bank and HDFC Bank-20-20 for both. Their oral interviews were conducted and out of 40- the views of ten [25% of the sample size] are mentioned in the current work considering above four parameters the questions were asked to customers.

Source of the Study

- a. **Primary Source:** It is collected via oral interviews customers of Allahabad Bank and HDFC Bank. Total forty samples are selected from these two banks and 10/40's views are mentioned here in the current work.
- b. **The Secondary Source:** Related material in the form of books, journals, article in Printed or published form is used as secondary source of the study.

Literature Review:

Dasgupta Gautama Siddhartha, Paul, Fuloria & Sanjay (2011). The study was conducted to grasp the behavioural intention of mobile banking usage of Indian customers. Analysis strategies just like the correlational analysis and a multivariate analysis were worn out order to see the extent of impact the antecedents have over the behavioural intentions of mobile banking usage. The results of the study showed that aside from the standard variables like Perceived quality and Perceived simple Use, factors like Perceived Image, Perceived worth, Self-affectivity, Perceived quality and Tradition all considerably affects behavioural Intentions towards mobile banking usage.

Palani and Yasodha P. (Apr 2012) The analysis paper is targeted on customer's perceptions on mobile banking offered by Indian Overseas Bank and it conjointly focuses on the varied drivers that drive mobile banking shoppers.. The results of this study showed that gender, education and financial gain of the shoppers play a very important role in usage of mobile banking. Most of the analyses square measure centred on the acceptance of the mobile banking technology thanks to that not a lot of research has been conducted on individuals. The analysis reveals that if skills are upgraded among the shoppers there'll be larger temperament on the part of shoppers toward the utilization of Mobile banking. Some the factors like security trust, gender, education, religion, and worth will have marginal impact on shopper outlook towards Mobile banking compared to the opposite factors.

Thakur, Rakhi; Srivastava, Mala. (2013). The paper studies the factors influencing the adoption intention of mobile commerce. Perceived quality, perceived simple use and social influence square measure found to be important dimensions of technology adoption readiness to use mobile commerce whereas facilitating conditions weren't found to be important. The results of the analysis study conjointly indicate the perceived quality risk outlined by security risk and privacy risk square measure considerably related to behavioural intention in negative relation, that indicates that security and privacy issues square measure necessary in deterring customers from victimization mobile commerce. This analysis study developed AN integrated model for behavioural intention towards money innovations.

sensible implications of this study is one among the few empirical studies that have investigated the adoption of mobile commerce in Bharat, that is taken into account one among the quickest growing countries in terms of mobile usage. The study relates to inclusion of each utilitarian and quality facet of adoption intention. It offers AN empirical basis on that mobile and banking corporations will base their mobile payments promoting strategy.

Kumar, Reji G; Rejikumar, G; Ravindran, D Sudharani. This analysis paper examines the factors influencing the continuance selections of the first adopters of m-banking services in Kerala, India. The study used constructs adopted from Technology Acceptance Model together with constructs of perceived service quality, perceived quality and perceived risk to through empirical observation establish the influence on satisfaction and continuance usage intentions. The study confirmed that once adoption of the technology, the client finds satisfaction within the quality parameters of the service. Perceptions concerning the risks concerned in m-banking had adverse impact on service quality and satisfaction.

Kalaiarasi, H & Srividya, V. three (Jul-Sep 2012). Mobile banking as a brand new channel to the prevailing banking channels provides convenient and price economical banking services anytime anyplace. It's determined that, although Bharat has robust potential for mobile banking solely five-hitter of mobile subscribers square measure registered users of mobile banking. Attracting the new customers might not be simple than holding the prevailing mobile banking customers 2009). Hence the present analysis focuses on the factors influencing actual usage of mobile banking services. The results shows that, Indians mobile banking usage is influenced by simple mobile banking technology, its suitability to the user's fashion and therefore the advantages like quality and mobile transactions. But customer's perception towards security of mobile transactions and privacy fears demotivates actual usage.

Tenkasi Taluk & Devasena, S Valli, (Jan 2012). Banking system is that the backbone of the economy and knowledge Technology (IT) successively has become the backbone of banking activities. Technology, that was enjoying a confirmative role in banking, has come back to the forefront with the ever-increasing challenges and needs. Technology to start out with was a business enabler and currently has become a business driver. The Banks cannot think about introducing a money product while not IT support. Be it client service, transactions, remittances, audit, marketing, valuation or the other activity within the Banks, IT plays a very important role to not complete the activity with high potency however conjointly has the potential to initiate and meet the longer term needs. The Banking Sector was early parent of technology and therein method set an example to the opposite industries the requirement to pick automation for taking full advantage in operational potency.

Through a large range of banks, the system of Indian banking is expressed by means that of combined possession. The world of economic banking consists of thirty three foreign banks, forty personal sector banks, and twenty seven public sector banks wherever majority possession is enclosed by the govt.. In 2003-04, whole assets of bank add up to a tiny low quantity Olympian seventy p.c of GDP (Gross Domestic Product). In 2003-04, whereas the foreign and personal banks apprehend twenty five p.c, the general public sector banks comprise of concerning seventy five of the industry assets.

History of Banks in Republic of India: In India, the banking industry dates back to the religious writing civilization. Loans got to the poor therein era too solely the nitty-gritty's

concerned within the same were totally different. Loans deeds therein amount were notable by the name rnaklekhya or rnapatra.

Big businessmen and landlords gave cash to the tiny traders and farmers on interest within the earlier times. This culture remains current in some villages within the country. The lands or different valuable assets of these United Nations agency were unable to pay the quantity were appropriated even as the banks do currently.

The first bank established in Republic of India was the Bank of geographical area. it had been opened within the year 1770 in Calcutta. Bank of urban centre, Bank of Calcutta and Bank of Madras were come upon later within the early nineteenth century.

Facilities Provided by Banks

Providing loans, that are another primary perform of the banks, is additionally useful for people and businesses in some ways. Salaried folks will build their assets like property, car, etc. simply with the assistance of loans from the bank. Businessmen will expand their businesses with this facility. Varieties of different services also are provided to the businessmen to ease their money transactions and aid within the growth of their business.

Online Banking has additional increased the method of banking. Varied banking services like checking balance, transferring quantity, applying for loan square measure currently provided on the bank's web site. All the shoppers need doing is choosing net banking service.

Current study is based on survey of various customers. Out of 40 customers/samples from both bank, there is the ratio of around fifty-fifty talking in favour or against to banks. Few views are given below:

HDFC:

- a. Here are some views of customers about the service of HHDFC bank. Service is good, Net banking is good, but asks for the security qns every time you do online transaction. So it's quite irritating. This bank Gives overdraft facility. Credit card is good as well (specially during flipkart/Amazon sales. - Withdrawal limits, min balance charges, outstation cheque charges etc. are a little high.
- b. I have had an HDFC account for 11 years. For the past few years, I have been living abroad and visiting only occasionally. During the last few visits I have been disappointed with HDFC.
- c. **Online banking:** The website is just, strange. There is no other way to describe it. The net-banking link on the website opens up in a separate 650px by 1024px popup-window for some reason, and it goes downhill from there. Poor accessibility practices and outdated techniques (1995 called, they want their frame-sets back) abound.
- d. **ATM:** On my latest trip, I have tried to an HDFC ATM 3 times. I have managed to use it only once. Once the machine was out of cash. The next time, it was off (the night watchman told me it doesn't turn on automatically after a power cut).
- e. **In-branch service:** The day the ATM was out of cash, I walked into the branch (because it was daytime and the branch was open). I could not find a withdrawal slip. A bank employee I approached refused to be helpful, or apologetic. Instead, he bluntly told me that I needed a check. Excuse me, checks cost money and I didn't leave home with the cheque-book. And why do I need to write myself a check anyway? Being in a hurry, I left the branch and found myself a PNB ATM to use my HDFC card at (I used the same PNB ATM when the HDFC ATM was off. May be PNB has some highly advanced ATMS that come back on after power cuts?).

Allahabad Bank: Here are some views of customers about Allahabad Bank

- a. Since all my family members have saving account in Allahabad bank, i can surely answer this. Though technologically they are slightly backward and their ATMs are difficult to find but employees are well mannered, polite and get you through all difficulties.
- b. I have never found any employee misbehaving with any customer however many a times their services are slow but that's the story of all the public sector banks of India.
- c. I am using this Savings account for the last six years and the services of them have been quite good so far. Their customer support and the staffs had been helpful and there have not been any sort of extra charges which they had been making so far. Overall it had been a good service.
- d. My saving account was taken with ALLHABAD BANK, my experience is not good with this bank. On one occasion i withdraw 10000 rs but the cash did not came the money got deducted i complaint to customer care about this they said it will get refund within 20 days. I have to do so much of follow up with them
- e. In Allahabad bank minimum balance is Rs. 1000, I have opened the account before 8 years. All services are good but same ATM centres won't function however the customer support is very good. Mobile application is easy and safe infra structured developed.

Finding of Work: The trendy banking services help in easing the method of trade, development of industries and different activities that facilitate within the development of the country's economy. Banks and different money establishments that promote the expansion of companies and safeguard the cash and different valuable assets of people square measure actually play an integral role within the development of a country's economy. It will be hard to answer who is the best as every bank is best at something, some provides best saving account, some provide best current account, some have best FD rates, some are best at this some are best at that and so on. Yet some findings of the study based on customers views are given below:

1. Though Allahabad Bank is nationalize bank and HDFC is Private Bank, it has been rated 27th safest **bank** in the world, according to latest **Bank Safety** Ranking by 'The Banker', a Financial Times publication.
2. HDFC sell you insurance at higher price than Allahabad Bank.
3. HDFC Bank is one of the largest banks in India and has been doing well both on retail and assets side. Their origin is from HDFC limited which was established for giving out loans to both retail and corporates while Allahabad Bank is small bank.

Suggestions: Coin has both sides. It's applicable to banking sectors too. Hence it is suggested that:

- a. Customer should identify his/her needs while selecting the bank and then define for which Bank they have to go.
- b. Sometimes prejudice may be cause of customers lack of satisfactions.
- c. Banks needs to upgrade their technical facilities for the connivance of the customers.

Conclusion: In the system of Indian banking, the degree of competition is calculable. In India, the banking sector was created as a noteworthy case study by many factors. At first, through the target of profitableness, productivity, and enhancing potency, Indian experience alleviation of the banking sector, throughout the Nineteen Nineties. Secondly, the banking sector expertise a big transformation that's being driven by the necessity for creating a competitive economy, productive, and market-driven thus on maintain intensify growth and bigger investment levels. In markets that are rising the studies of competition relate to countries through an ulterior consolidation and history of banking crises. Concentration

enlarged as a result of consolidation, and therefore the tested studies in these countries, whether or not this resulted in increased within the power of establishments or increase within the competition. It's quiet fascinating to watch within the Indian context, whether or not penetration of foreign and personal banks and diversification of public sector banks consists of any impact on competition. Hence, both Private and Nationalize bank must convey customers in a proper manner and provide the adequate facilities to stand in this competitive era of banking sectors too.

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Comparative Analysis Of Volatility Of Indian Stock Market With Emerging And Developed Stock Markets

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Sr. Dr. B J Queensley Jeyanthi**

***Abstract-** This research paper investigates the volatility of five emerging stock markets (India, China, Indonesia, Malaysia, South Korea) and three developed stock markets (Japan, US, UK). The sample period for daily data including open, high, low and closing prices spans from 01-April-2005 to 31-March-2015. This study uses the various volatility estimators PK (Parkinson, 1980), GK (Garman and Klass, 1980), Descriptive statistics. The data set used for the study is the daily closing values of different stock market indices. The empirical result proves that Indian stock market withstands the world financial crises.*

***Key words** - Stock market volatility, market indices, Descriptive Statistics, Kurtosis, Skewness.*

1. Introduction

Volatility plays a vital role in finance. Stock market volatility is a complex subject that many investors do not fully understand. Volatility is up and down movement of the market. It is measured by the standard deviation from the expectation. Stock market volatility measures fluctuations in stock prices. Low volatility means small fluctuations and high volatility means large fluctuations. Volatility measures the risk of security. It is used in option pricing formula to gauge the fluctuations in the returns of the underlying assets. Volatility indicates the pricing behaviour of the security and helps estimate the fluctuations that may happen in a short period of time.

Volatility in the stock price affects the returns of the investors. The globalisation of securities market has brought an increased attention to stock markets throughout the world. When there is co-integration, the market absorbs the shocks of other markets and nullifies the portfolio diversification benefits. The pre-eminent positions of the stock market in the national economy, the growth in the investor base and the globalisation have induced the researcher to study the market efficiency, volatility and co-integration. Studies related to these aspects of stock markets were dated back to 1965, Fama (1965), Grubel (1968), Conard and Juttner (1973), Bruno H. Solnik (1973), Agmon T (1974), James C. Dyer (1976), Paul Barnes (1986), Andrew W. Lo and A.C. Mackinlay (1988), Skinner. D.J.(1989), Taylor and Tonks (1989). But studies from the year 2000 are taken for review.

This chapter concerns with review of important empirical works, concerning stock market volatility and return starting from 2005 to 2015. The review of literature is undertaken related to market volatility and return. But studies from the year 1995 are taken for review.

2. Studies Related to Stock Market Volatility and Return

Prakash G. Apte (2001) investigated the relationship between the volatility of the stock market and that of the nominal exchange rate in India. He used daily closing data on two stock market indices viz. BSE30 (SENSEX), and the NIFTY50 and the daily closing USD/INR exchange rate. The period covered was from January 2 1991 to April

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24,2000.They Used the E-Garch specification proposed by Nelson (1991) He examined whether changes in the volatility of the stock market affecting the volatility in the foreign exchange market and vice versa. Asymmetric effect on positive and negative returns in the incorporating model specification surprises on the volatility both in the market as well as spillovers across the two markets.

Gupta (2002) studied the Performance Evaluation of National Stock Exchange of India. He collected data for the five year period 2006-2010 from Prowess database of CMIE. He found that National Stock Exchange (NSE) has played the catalytic role in bringing about the transformations. The processes and procedures set by National Stock Exchange marked a paradigm shift in the securities market. The relative importance of various stock exchanges in the market has undergone dramatic change during last decade (1990's). National Stock Exchange in October 1995, within the first year of its operations became the largest exchange in terms of volume transacted.

Krishnamurti (2003) stated that there are important differences in ownership structure, geographical reach, internal control systems and institutionalized risk management facilities between the BSE and NSE. They selected 40 sample stocks covering the period 1st January, 1997 to 31st July, 1997 are obtained from NSE and BSE. He used a paired comparison approach and documented significant differences in liquidity and price volatility between the two markets. He found that NSE is superior in its department on many counts. The reputation of surveillance system in NSE is better than BSE. NSE adopts a completely driven system in order while BSE has a system that is a part order driven and another part quote driven. Both exchanges have price stabilization features.

M. Samanta G.P. (2003) analysed the link between stock market volatility, excess returns and future output growth. He applied autoregressive model. The S&P CNX Nifty was chosen from April 1993 to December 2002. The result proved that stock market volatility was strongly influenced by its own past values. The volatility was also quite strongly related (at least contemporaneously) to excess returns in recent years.

Golaka C. Nath (2003) studied the behavior of volatility in cash market after the introduction of derivatives. The S&P CNX Nifty and the CNX Nifty Junior and 20 stocks were selected randomly from the S&P CNX Nifty and the CNX Nifty Junior index for studying the volatility behavior during the period January, 1999 to October, 2003. They classified the entire period into five time buckets, taking into account after the introduction of futures on individual stocks and indices options on individual stocks and indices by considering the last time buckets from November, 2002 to October, 2003. They used 4 different methods GARCH (1, 1), IGARCH with $\lambda = 0.94$, one year rolling window of standard deviation and a 6 month rolling standard deviation. They concluded that the volatility of the market fell in the post derivative period.

George C. Pardee (2003) examined the stock market volatility of 12 developed countries. The monthly returns were calculated for each of those countries from the late 19th or early 20th century to 2002 from their starting date of trading. They established that volatility had not been constant. There was an evidence of 'U'-shaped pattern of volatility in majority of the countries. To explain these 'U'-shaped trends they examined the role of monetary policy and financial internationalization, found a positive association of monetary volatility with stock market volatility and suggested that the conduct of monetary regime was important for stock market volatility. They further found that financial internationalization was also positively associated with stock market volatility.

Raju Anirban Ghosh M.T. (2004) compared the international stock market volatility among six developed markets namely, the USA, the UK, France, Germany, Australia, Hong Kong and the twelve emerging markets namely India, Singapore, Malaysia, China, Indonesia, Chile, Brazil, Mexico, South Africa, Korea and Taiwan using daily closing index price of 24 year period from January 1980 to December 2003. They used Parkinson (1980) model, Garman and Klass (1980) model, open to open volatility model and traditional close-to-close volatility model. They arrived at the conclusion that many of the developed and all emerging markets experienced high volatility from 1997 to 2002 indicating convergence of markets. Volatility was low in 2003 in almost all the countries compared to emerging markets and some of the developed markets. India experienced low intra-day volatility. Extreme value volatility in India touched its peak in 2000 at 3.17 per cent and continuously slid thereafter. Xuejing Xing (2004) analyzed stock market volatility in thirty seven international Markets from 1973 through 2000, using DataStream Country Indexes. This paper found that the education level of investors plays a significant role in explaining cross-country market volatility differences. In addition, there is some evidence indicating that market industry concentration, the relative size of the stock market, and the number of firms listed may also be of significant explanatory power to cross-sectional market volatility differences.

Ajay Pandey (2005) evaluated the extreme value volatility estimators and their empirical performance in Indian capital market. He used the S&P CNX Nifty data from January 1999 to December 2002 and used two traditional estimators (close to close volatility and mean adjusted version of the close to close estimation), four extreme value estimators (Parkinson, Garman and Klass, Rogers Satchell and Yang–Zhang) and two conditional volatility models GARCH (1, 1) model and E GARCH model volatility. According to him, for estimating the volatility, the extreme value estimators perform better on efficiency criteria than the conditional models. Conditional volatility models performed better than the extreme value estimators in respect of bias.

Stefan Gerlach.et.al. (2006) investigated the behaviour of the volatility of returns in bond and stock markets for a sample of eight countries using very long samples of data. The main source of data was the Global Financial Data database. The period under consideration covered the years between 1850 and 2005; depending on availability, the data start between January 1850 (French, German and US bond yields and US equity prices) and January 1919 (Canadian equity prices) and end in all cases in November 2005. The volatilities of inflation and GDP have also been calculated using EWMA but applied to annual changes in the variables of interest. Volatility has been high during episodes of economic and political turbulence, in particular during the interwar period. Moreover, volatility has generally been high since the early 1970s. The volatilities of returns have been computed using exponentially weighted moving averages (EWMA) of squared returns, which follows closely the Risk Metrics methodology. Volatility is normally estimated using daily returns. They concluded that 1. Volatility was dominated by large, temporary increases that appear correlated with episodes of economic weakness, political instability and financial turmoil. 2. Volatility has been much higher from the 1970s. Seeking to explain it would be an important topic for future research. 3. The movements in volatility that have been observed in recent years are small in a historical perspective.

Chukwuogor (2007) examined the general patterns of recent global stock market returns and the volatility of such returns using 40 global stock indexes of countries classified into developed and emerging markets as barometers for the period 1997-2004. He investigated

the presence of the day-of-the-week return in these countries and the correlation of the returns of these global stock indexes to the US market. A set of parametric and non-parametric tests was used to test the significance of the standard deviations and further determine the correlation of the returns of these global stock indexes to the US market. There was evidence of negative and low correlation of returns between the US stock markets and many global stock markets. These findings presented interesting opportunities and dynamics for enhanced return through diversification in global portfolio investments.

Mallikarjunappa T.et.al. (2008) studied the volatility implications of the introduction of derivatives on stock market volatility in India using the S&P CNX Nifty Index as a benchmark. This study uses the daily closing prices of the Spot Nifty Index, the Nifty Index Futures, the Nifty Junior Index and the spot S&P500 Index from October 5, 1995, through June 30, 2006. They found clustering and persistence of volatility before and after derivatives, while listing they seem to have no stabilisation or destabilisation effects on market volatility. The post derivatives period showed that the sensitivity of the index returns to market returns and any day-of-the-week effects have disappeared. That is, the nature of the volatility patterns has altered during the post-derivatives period.

Gregory James (2009) examined the relationship between financial liberalisation and stock market volatility in Indonesia from April 11, 1983 to January 23, 2006. He found that capital market reforms coincided with a dramatic increase in stock market volatility but volatility significantly decreased when the market was opened to foreign investors. There was a significant rise in the volatility during the crisis. Volatility subsequently decreased two years and six years after the crisis and returned to the same level that had prevailed from the opening of the market.

Gupta (2011) analysed whether Indian stock market returns were correlated to the stock market returns of other selected Asian Economies or not and compared the distribution of the stock market returns of India with other selected Asian economies. She included BSE(India), Heng Seng(Hong Kong), JKS(Indonesia), KLSE(Malaysia), Nikkie (Japan), KS11(Korea) in her study and used the descriptive statistics of the six Asian markets for the period between 2005 and 2009. She found that the mean of the weekly returns of India and the Indonesian markets were observed to be the highest around 23%. Japanese markets were flat during the study period. Volatility as measured by standard deviation and its square, the variance was the least observed in the Malaysian markets.

Sankharaj Roy (2013) has measured the volatility of Indian stock market during the period of 2005 to 2012. The data related to the stocks and the index return was collected from the BSE & NSE and he used the volatility models like Parkinson Model, Garman & Klass Model, and Intra and Inter day volatility. It has been observed that returns were mostly negative in both the market indexes during the recession period with the higher volatility when the market was falling and vice versa. He concluded that the volatility during the phase of economic recession i.e. 2008 was high in the Indian market. The two indices taken for the study confirmed that there was relationship between the economic recession and stock market volatility. Whenever there is recession or financial crisis the stock market reacts negatively thus increases the volatility.

Debesh Bhowmik (2013) evaluated the multidimensional framework of stock market volatility. The study witnessed that (a) A country's depression or recession turned into severe volatile stock market which cannot be cured in the short run. (b) Political turmoil or instability or chaos made negative impact on stock market which spurs volatility. (c) The

stock market volatility has the negative nexus with the growth rate of a nation i.e. high volatility reduces growth rate. (d) There is causality between them. (e) Since stock market volatility brings forth economic crisis which has ultimately spill over on growth inversely to other countries as well. The international trade and stock market volatility is negatively related in the sense that volatility reduces the volume of trade and increases current account and capital account deficits.

Kasilingam Lingaraja, et.al. (2014) investigated the efficiency of Stock market and volatility behaviour of eight (India, China, Indonesia, Korea, Malaysia, Philippines, Taiwan, Thailand) Asian emerging market indices. They used the secondary daily time series data for the period of ten years from 1st January 2004 to 31st December 2013. The Econometric models (GARCH, Autocorrelation and Run test) were used to test the volatility and market efficiency of Asian emerging stock markets. They found significant evidences of market efficiency and randomness distribution in these emerging Asian markets.

3. Scope of the Study

This research covers eight emerging and developed countries stock price indices and the analysis will be done for the ten years period from year 2005-2015.

4. Objective of the Study

The main objective of this study is to examine the stock market volatility of emerging and developed countries during the study period and to disseminate knowledge about the stock price behaviour.

5. Data

The empirical work is based on daily closing prices of the stock indices. Only secondary data were used for this study. To analyse the market, daily closing values of S&P CNX Nifty (India), SSE (China), KLSE (Malaysia), JKSE (Indonesia), KS11 (South Korea), NIKKIE 225 (Japan), NASDAQ (US) and FTSE100 (UK) indices were taken from March 2005 April 2015. The daily data on stock market indices were downloaded from yahoo finance website Finance yahoo.com.

6. Methodology

The daily return is calculated by using the following formula. $rt = (\log pt - \log pt-1) * 100$

6.1. Descriptive Statistics:

Descriptive statistics is carried out to analyze the behaviour of the data of returns of the markets. It usually includes mean, median, maximum and minimum statistics of the data. It also provides the level of deviation in each variable.

6.2. Volatility

Volatility measures the risk of security. Volatility has been broadly classified into inter-day volatility and intraday volatility.

6.3. Inter Day volatility

Inter day refers to price movements of a given security between two days of trading. Inter day volatility is further classified into close to close and open to open volatility.

6.4. Close to Close Volatility

For computing close to close volatility, the closing values of the indices.

Close to close volatility is measured with the following formula

$$\sigma = \sqrt{(1/n-1) \sum (r_t - \bar{r})^2}$$

6.5. Open to open Volatility

Open to Open volatility is measured with the following formula:

$$\sigma = \sqrt{(1/n-1) \sum (r_t - \bar{r})^2}$$

6.6. Intra-Day Volatility

This term is often used to refer to the new highs and lows of a security. Intraday refers to price movements of a given security over the course of one day of trading. Intraday volatility is calculated with the help of Parkinson Model and Garman and Klass model.

6.7. Parkinson Model

High–low volatility is calculated with the following formula:

$$\sigma = k\sqrt{1/n \sum \log(H_t / L_t)^2}$$

6.8. Garman and Klass Model

The Garman and Klass model is used to calculate the open–close volatility. The formula for Garman and Klass model (1980) takes the following form.

$$\sigma = \sqrt{1/n \sum (1/2)[\log(H_t / L_t)]^2 - [2\log(2) - 1][\log(C_t / O_t)]^2}$$

7. Summary of Findings

The close to close volatility and open to open volatility in India, China, Indonesia, Malaysia, South Korea, Japan, US and UK moved in tandem. Among all the countries the volatility was very high in US (2.942).

Close to close volatility was very high compared to open to open volatility. The close to close and the open to open volatility in India, China, Indonesia, South Korea, Malaysia, Japan, UK, US were at their peak in 2008-2009 due to global financial crises. The entire financial year of the stock market was in the grip of bears. In India, open to open and close to close volatility appears to be neck to neck. This indicates smooth flow of information during the day as well as over -night. It touched its 3 percentage points in China.

Intra-day volatility also has the similar trend as in the case of inter-day volatility. In the India, China, Indonesia, South Korea, Malaysia, Japan, UK and US both open-close and high-low volatility were high in the year 2008-2009 and very low in 2014-2015 as in the case of inter-day volatility. But in the China both open-close and high-low volatility were low in the year 2012-2013 and in the US and UK both open-close and high-low volatility were high in the year 2013-2014.

It appears that the US scores over other developed markets in terms of intra-day volatility. In the UK, open to open volatility is slightly higher than high-low volatility and open to close volatilities. The volatility is on the rise for the past three year's i.e. from 2006 -2007 to 2008-2009. US scored higher volatility compared to all the developed markets. The open to close volatility, in case of France, is lower than open to open and close to close volatility. In the year 2008-09, in UK and US it almost touched 2 percentage points and peaked at 2.09 per cent in US and it appears to be highest among all the developed markets in that year. Intra-day dispersion is also high.

Emerging markets exhibited higher intra-day volatility compared to developed markets. Owing to economic and socio-political variations, the volatility in the emerging markets was generally on the high side. Among all the emerging countries studied, India experienced very high intra-day volatility followed by Indonesia, South Korea, Kola Lumpur and China. From the year 2005-06 to 2008-09 the volatility was very high in China and India. In India open to open, volatility is always higher than close to close volatility and many a times higher than open to close. Among all the emerging markets the intra-day volatility was very high in India and China in the year 2008-09. Except US all the developed countries volatility was

at its peak in the year 2008-09. In the first quarter of 2008 the market slumped following bad news from the global markets.

The world stock markets suffered loss in this quarter. The loss as well as the volatility was very high in the Indian stock market. The fifth largest US investment bank Bear Stearns' liquidity position deteriorated significantly, and the Federal Reserve's emergency cut in its discount rate created setback in the stock markets. Benchmarks (Sensex) cracked following a sharp setback in global markets, selling by foreign institutional investors. On 22nd January 2008 market wide circuit filters were applied after key benchmark indices fell by 10% within minutes of commencement of trade. The four year boom ended on 21 January 2008. Indian shares were heavily affected by the sell-off on 21 January, Monday. Financial stocks fell sharply, with the ICICI Bank losing 10 per cent and the State Bank of India, the nation's largest, dropping 5.6 per cent. Overseas funds sold \$691 million of Indian stocks. India is also being hit by inflation. Prices of wheat, aluminium, steel and other items had gone up sharply. As a result, investors were taking less interest in stocks and finding safer investment in gold, minerals and oil and the rupee was falling against the US dollar in 2008. In respect of volatility, the Indian market moved in tandem with the US stock market with a slight difference.

8. Conclusion

In India open to open and close to close volatility appears to be neck to neck. In the developed countries except Australia inter-day volatility was very low in the year 2005-2006. It clearly exhibits that developed countries moved in tandem with each other. US scored higher volatility compared to all the developed markets. Among all the emerging markets the intra-day volatility was very high in India and China in the year 2008-09. The developed markets UK, US and Japan and emerging markets Kola Lumpur, Korea, and India moved in tandem. Indian stock market withstands the global financial crisis.

Table.1: Stock Index Daily Close to Close and Open to Open Volatility (Percentage) (Emerging and Developed Countries)

Year	CHINA		JAPAN		INDONESIA		SOUTH KORIA		MALAYSIA		INDIA		UK		US	
	Close-Close	Open-Open														
2005-2006	1.277	1.311	1.084	1.074	1.166	1.213	1.104	1.222	0.462	0.463	1.035	1.038	0.578	0.576	0.865	0.817
2006-2007	1.731	2.019	1.145	1.090	1.348	1.421	1.085	1.138	0.802	0.831	1.775	1.801	0.829	0.831	1.009	0.999
2007-2008	2.349	2.521	1.563	1.311	1.805	1.941	1.629	1.709	1.254	1.143	2.455	2.442	1.346	1.346	1.390	1.462
2008-2009	2.752	3.102	2.942	2.499	2.306	2.717	2.559	2.764	1.124	1.218	2.669	2.649	2.369	2.361	2.806	2.607
2009-2010	1.704	1.821	1.413	1.162	1.439	1.436	1.237	1.265	1.950	2.034	1.892	1.884	1.114	1.115	1.201	1.134
2010-2011	1.413	1.543	1.598	1.432	1.317	1.315	0.941	1.032	0.563	0.600	1.111	1.105	1.090	1.091	1.228	1.204
2011-2012	1.189	1.257	1.143	1.082	1.403	1.399	1.640	1.644	0.693	0.657	1.286	1.410	1.304	1.308	1.461	1.323
2012-2013	1.087	1.039	1.207	1.158	0.848	0.794	0.926	0.923	0.458	0.505	0.835	0.928	0.834	0.841	0.988	1.023
2013-2014	1.095	1.120	1.704	1.654	1.420	1.356	0.795	0.789	0.550	0.565	1.138	1.202	0.759	0.759	0.809	0.801
2014-2015	1.335	1.297	1.112	1.101	0.721	0.703	0.601	0.594	0.516	0.529	0.870	0.912	0.772	0.766	0.897	0.962
2005-2015	1.774	1.928	1.576	1.415	1.434	1.514	1.339	1.410	0.948	0.973	1.575	1.596	1.203	1.203	1.517	1.485

Table.2: Stock Index Daily High-Low and Open -Close Volatility (Percentage) (Emerging and Developed Countries)

Year	CHINA		JAPAN		INDONESIA		SOUTH KORIA		MALAYSIA		INDIA		UK		US	
	High - Low	Open - Close	High - Low	Open - Close	High - Low	Open - Close	High - Low	Open - Close	High - Low	Open - Close	High - Low	Open - Close	High - Low	Open - Close	High - Low	Open - Close
2005-2006	0.011	0.010	0.007	0.006	0.009	0.008	0.009	0.008	0.004	0.004	0.010	0.010	0.005	0.004	0.007	0.007
2006-2007	0.015	0.014	0.008	0.007	0.009	0.008	0.007	0.007	0.0063	0.006	0.017	0.016	0.007	0.006	0.008	0.008
2007-2008	0.019	0.019	0.009	0.009	0.011	0.010	0.0117	0.011	0.008	0.007	0.019	0.018	0.011	0.011	0.011	0.010
2008-2009	0.022	0.020	0.018	0.016	0.015	0.014	0.019	0.019	0.008	0.008	0.024	0.023	0.020	0.018	0.021	0.020
2009-2010	0.014	0.013	0.008	0.008	0.012	0.012	0.010	0.010	0.006	0.005	0.016	0.015	0.010	0.010	0.010	0.010
2010-2011	0.011	0.011	0.009	0.009	0.011	0.010	0.007	0.007	0.004	0.004	0.009	0.009	0.009	0.009	0.010	0.010
2011-2012	0.009	0.009	0.006	0.006	0.011	0.010	0.010	0.010	0.005	0.005	0.010	0.010	0.011	0.011	0.010	0.010
2012-2013	0.008	0.008	0.007	0.006	0.006	0.006	0.006	0.006	0.003	0.003	0.009	0.010	0.007	0.006	0.007	0.007
2013-2014	0.009	0.009	0.011	0.010	0.009	0.009	0.005	0.005	0.004	0.004	0.009	0.008	0.006	0.006	0.006	0.006
2014-2015	0.011	0.011	0.006	0.006	0.005	0.005	0.004	0.004	0.003	0.003	0.007	0.007	0.006	0.006	0.007	0.007
2005-2015	0.014	0.013	0.010	0.009	0.010	0.009	0.010	0.010	0.005	0.005	0.014	0.013	0.010	0.009	0.011	0.011

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Case Study: Discovering a Blue Ocean Opportunity in the Convenience Food Sector- A Case of iD Fresh Food

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Case Abstract

This case intends to understand the market growth strategy of Blue Ocean evolved by W. Chan Kim and Renée Mauborgne based on the success story of iD Fresh Foods. Unlike the traditional marketing strategy based on 4 Ps (product, pricing, promotion, distribution,) which are used by firms to establish a strong hold in the market, Kim and Mouborgne's classification categorizes strategies on the basis of overlap between consumer needs, competitor offerings, and the brands' competencies. iD Fresh food has experienced remarkable success in a very short span of time. The strategy adopted by iD is a valuable example to understand the Blue Ocean principle of making the competition irrelevant by creating an uncontested market space. This case provides valuable learning for management students on the importance of effective strategies that help firms' manoeuvre competition and establish market dominance.

Key Words: First mover, RTC, innovation, Growth strategy

“In Blue Oceans, Competition is irrelevant because the rules of the game are waiting to be set”

..... W. Chan Kim and

Renée Mauborgne

About iD Fresh Food

The Humble Beginnings of iD Fresh Food – A Reflection of the Growth Story

Back in 2006, the brand iD was just a small store selling idly and dosa batter. However, over the years the company has created a unique space for itself in the competitive food market, optimistically aiming at becoming a Rs.1000 crore company in the coming years.

The entrepreneurial journey of PC Mustafa is really intriguing as it unfolds the story of how the son of a daily wage laborer, who had almost dropped out of school in his 6th grade, is today the owner 100 million dollar brand iD .After completing his engineering, PC Mustafa's' career included stint with Motorola and later Citi Bank. With a strong desire to pursue his higher education, he joined IIM Bangalore and it was during this period the seeds of entrepreneurship were sown in his mind. On one occasion while he was managing his cousin's kirana store he noticed there was a high demand for idli and dosa batters among consumers. He realized there was an untapped need in the market. The unbranded batter which was sold was of poor quality and not adequately available to meet the customer requirements at the right time. The need of the hour was to trigger a shift in consumer buying from unbranded batter to iD brand which meant assurance of hygiene and quality. With this his nominal savings he decided to embark on his entrepreneurial expedition and entered the packaged food business. iD Fresh Food founded by Mustafa and his four cousins - Abdul

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Nazer, Shamsudeen TK, Jafar TK and Noushad TA came in to existence in the 2005. The first batter production unit of the company was set up at Hoskote in the year 2007, ensuring quality and hygiene in every process in the year 2007. The company increased its product range and included Malabar Parotas which was instantly accepted in the market by 2010. The expanded its production base in the next 2 years by starting operations in Mumbai and Hyderabad. Experiencing encouraging success for its products in indigenous markets, iD Fresh Foods internationalized its operations by setting up its first unit in Dubai in 2014. (iD Fresh Food). What started out as a small family business has grown manifold with 50,000 kg of batter being manufactured daily from their units across India country and one in Dubai, which converts into a million idlis. Today iD success is a remarkable inspiration for many young minds who want to take the plunge in the world of entrepreneurship. (Babu, A Million Idlis a Day, 2015)

A Snap shot of RTC Food Sector and Strategic Moves of iD Fresh

Since the adoption of economic reforms, India has not only witnessed a landmark shift in the growth rate of its economy, but also a significant change in its traditional social system. Growing urbanization, increase in the proportion of women entering workforce, hectic work schedules that restrict the time available for household chores have contributed to a dynamic change in Indian food consumption patterns. Cooking Indian food has always been intimidating due to the time involved in preparing masalas and batters, which some time ago was completely prepared in the kitchen to ensure quality and authentic taste. However in recent times with more and more dual income families juggling with hectic work schedules and discharging family responsibilities, there is a growing rise in convenience food among Indian consumers. The Indian convenience food business includes both packaged Ready to Eat (RTE) and Ready to Cook (RTC) food. An RTE meal needs to be heated before eating while RTC meal means food that has been seasoned and prepared but still needs to be cooked. Some of the choices in the RTE category range from gravies, dals, biryanis, sweets, and desserts while the RTC group includes breakfast-mixes, idli and dosa batter, masala mixes and dessert mixes. (Chandran, 2016).

The established players in the Indian RTC market include MTR Foods (Bengaluru), ITC Limited (Kolkata), Desai Brothers Ltd (Pune) and Gits Food Products Pvt Ltd (Pune). ABT Foods Limited (Coimbatore) is one of the emerging brands in the RTC food market. These popular brands have always gained attention from the consumers, mainly because they keep involving innovations in their product line. (Food and Beverage News.Com, 2018).

According to Market Research Future (MRFR), the Indian RTC food market was worth \$233.40 million in 2013, and is projected to reach \$754.82 million by the end of 2022, registering a substantial compounded annual growth rate (CAGR) of 14.59 per cent. Cashing in on the opportunity, iD Fresh Food

With growing dual income families were couples race against time and find it hard to balance between work and personal life, the Read – to –Cook product range seemed a blessing. With the market showing signs of high growth potential, players like iD have left no stone unturned in responding to the expanding demand for its food products.

Although iD started with batters, the company has expanded its product range of ready-to-eat products by adding parota, chapati, paneer, curd, and a healthier option of ragi batter. iD has a total network of 20,000 stores spread across Karnataka, Tamil Nadu and other states. The revenue generation for iD has been highest from its outlets in UAE market. The company has been successful in attracting funding from Helion Ventures which invested

around 23 crores and also raised 150 crores from Premjiinvest, the private investment office of Azim Premji for an equity stake of 25% in the company. The funding would be used for up gradation of its existing manufacturing facilities, establishing new distribution networks and R & D that would in turn help iD expand into international markets such as US, UK and Singapore. (Balasubramanyam, 2017)

Fig -2: Region and Product Category wise contribution to iD Fresh revenues

(Chitra, 2018)

Over a span of 3 years the company's endeavors to constantly innovate has paid off with the its new product development - vada maker, which promises "perfectly shaped vadas with a hole in the middle,"

It allows users to squeeze vadas directly into hot oil and avoid the messy, time-consuming process of shaping them by hand. The vada maker has a unique umbrella nozzle for creating the round fluffy sphere with a cutter to ensure even sizes and a hole. The company has filed a patent for the vada maker in India and 140 countries under the PCT Patent Cooperation Treaty.

iD's entry and growth strategy in the food sector provides it the first mover advantage of entering the dosa/idli batter segment. Rather than competing in the highly crowded space such as fast food chains and ready to eat products, iD has chosen to enter an undeveloped market which is idli and dosa batter. Although, dosa batter did exist in the market, it was offered by local manufacturers without brand name or assurance of quality and hygiene. iD has responded to the market opportunity for RTC products by positioning the brand as a professional assistant to a home maker by replacing the cumbersome backend job of preparing food for the family thereby entering into an untapped space in the market. What makes iD brand unique is while the rest of the players in this segment try to increase the shelf life of their products, iD is working to reduce shelf life of its products. It achieves this by following a 0 inventory business model. Since they deal with perishable products, daily distribution to outlets and ensuring quality is restored throughout the supply chain is the secret sauce for the success of iD Fresh Food. Appropriate demand planning is done to ensure that regulation of production according to the market demand and use of mobile app to integrate it into its Enterprise Resource Processing system also helps in tracking everyday sales. As iD promises consumers who are strapped for time an option for easier food options, the company will tread on new innovations that will continue its phase of profitability in the competitive food business.

Methodology

1. Students can be introduced to the Blue Ocean Strategy Framework
2. Comparison can be made between Red Ocean and Blue Ocean and students can be asked to list out those firms operating in the Red Ocean in the Indian Food business
3. Identification of the strategies adopted by iD Fresh Foods that has helped the company discover a Blue Ocean is a subject of interest
4. Keeping in mind iD Fresh Foods, Students can be asked to draw a value innovation which is the corner stone of BOS.
5. Using the BOS tools, students can be asked to prepare Strategy Canvas by capturing the range of factors that the food business competes on and invests in.
6. Prepare an ERRC Grid having 4 factors: Eliminate Reduce, Raise and Create with respect to iD Foods.
7. The business environment is very competitive and iD has to proactively think and plan its strategies for the sustaining in the market in the long run. Students can trace the future growth path that iD can follow to continue its success phase in the market.

Teaching Objectives

Companies today operate in a very competitive market place where there is limited room to outperform competitors and stand out above all the rest. The approach of designing the product, price, promotion and distribution distinctly does not seem adequate to position the firm desirably before customers. Therefore companies are trying to find new avenues in business where they can enjoy uncontested market share or the Blue Ocean to overcome competition and sustain in the long run.

The case would provide and understanding to students about:

1. When most companies face head to head competition by making small incremental improvements in cost and quality, innovative companies break free from the pack by creating a Blue Ocean or **uncontested market**.
2. Instead of searching within the conventional boundaries of the food industry competition, iD Fresh Food has looked across those boundaries to find an unoccupied territory that represents real **value innovation**, which simultaneously pursues differentiation and low cost.
3. When a company finds and creates a new market space (**Blue Ocean**), it must gradually find a **new uncontested space**. This is because after each year the Blue Ocean tends to become a Red Ocean as competitors follow suit.
4. How to apply Blue Ocean Strategy to real business situations in order to help the business **break away from the competition** and achieve strong profitable growth
5. Start exploring **and searching for Blue Oceans** that could be incorporated **for their own start up or business idea** that renders rivals obsolete and unleashes new demand.

Teaching Methods

1. After the teacher has explained the theoretical concept of Blue Ocean Strategy, the class can be divided into teams of 5 – 6 students and the case study can be distributed to the students. They can be asked to understand and relate the case with the principles of blue ocean strategy.
2. Each team can provide inputs or make presentations on the practical usage of the BOS with specific reference to iD Fresh Foods.

3. Innovative thinking on how iDs future strategy can help it sustain its well established position in the food sector in the coming years could solicit interesting responses from the students.

4. The teams can creatively think about discovering new blue oceans in other sectors that can be converted into a profitable business venture.

5. After student presentations and discussions with the teams, the teacher can summarize and highlight the valuable, noteworthy inputs given by each team. The teacher could finally present his or her fresh perspective of the case analysis which could be a value addition for the class.

Discussion Questions

1. How has iD fresh food been successful in creating a Blue Ocean in the competitive food sector?
2. Create a ERRC Grid with respect to iD Fresh Food to understand their BOS Strategy
3. To sustain its position as an established player in the food sector, how can iD discover new blue oceans

Discussion Questions And Answers

1. How has iD fresh food been successful in creating a Blue Ocean in the competitive food sector?

The Indian food services market in India(organized and unorganized) is estimated at Rs. 3,37,500 crore in 2017 and is projected to grow at a CAGR of 10 percent over the next five years to reach Rs. 5,52,000 crore by 2022. (Indian food industry poised for huge growth: FICCI, 2017).It is not surprising that attracted by profits, new players are going to enter, leading to excess competition and need for innovative strategies to survive in the food business. iD fresh food has discovered a blue ocean by entering into a product category that was provided by the unorganized sector. Instead of competing in the red ocean which comprises of restaurants, fast food chains and Ready to Eat food options where the critical factors to succeed are menu, price and quick service ,iD has chosen an uncontested market in the food sector that is providing Ready to Cook food solutions with a promise of health, hygiene and quality.

2. Create an ERRC Grid with respect to iD Fresh Food to understand their BOS Strategy

ERRC Grid which forms a part of the Blue Ocean Strategy is a great tool for discovering opportunities to identify the key features that are used to compete in the market place and design a new buyer value curve. The below table provides the ERRC grid with respect to iD Foods that help if simultaneously pursue differentiation and low cost.

Eliminate

Factors that the industry has long competed on must be eliminated

- Batter business has long been a part of unorganized sector. iDs branded batter has eliminated consumer dependence on unbranded options.
- Converted the art of Vada making into a science. Eliminating the mess involved in vada making. Came up with the umbrella nozzle for creating the round fluffy sphere with a cutter to ensure even sizes and a hole. Allows users to squeeze vadas directly into hot oil and avoid the messy, time-consuming process of shaping them by hand.

Raise

Factors that should be raised above industry standards

- The mindset of consumers is that anything which is packed is not healthy. iD has raised its products above industry standards ensuring the product is "**fresh and 100% natural**" with no preservatives, soda or flavors.
- Provide consumers with a hygienic, branded, yet home-like taste

Reduce

Factors that should be reduced below

- Reduce the shelf life of their products -Food tastes better when it is natural and fresh. So when the rest of the market is busy trying to increase the shelf life of their products, iD is working to reduce shelf life.
- It achieves this by following a 0 inventory business model. Since they deal with perishable products, daily distribution to outlets and ensuring quality is restored throughout the supply chain is the secret sauce for the success of iD Fresh Food.
- Appropriate demand planning is done to ensure that regulation of production according to the market demand and adequately meet the requirement of suppliers so consumer need for the product is met at all times.
- Solving the perishable foods puzzle - Uses a mobile app to track everyday sales and integrates it into its Enterprise Resource Processing system. This enables it to gauge demand live and improve delivery.

Create

Factors that should be created that the industry has never offered

- Create a professional assistant to the home maker who can use smart food tools that allow convenient, faster, better and cheaper meal preparation without taking away the credit from the home maker of preparing delicious food for family.
- Created a market for Ready to Cook food products (RTC)
- Creating a space to enter households that never buy batter and still continue to prefer preparing the batter through conventional, time consuming process.
- Created a new channel of distribution Unmanned iD Trust shops where money is incidental and the real currency is trust.It reflects on the strongly rooted ethical values of the company and creates a sense of trust for its products and brand.

3. In the face of growing competition, what strategies would you like to suggest to iD Fresh to sustain its market position and discover a new Blue Ocean

In the face of growing competition, what strategies would you like to suggest to iD Fresh to sustain its market position with the existing marketing efforts.

iD fresh food can work towards deeper market penetration as currently they have strong presence focused on metropolitan cities. With the company's growth attracting new investors the additional funds raised can be directed towards market expansion especially catering to Indian Diaspora settled in international markets.

The company's innovation the vada maker can be further improvised to make similar products such as doughnuts and other Indian snack food that requires cylindrical shape and a hole.

They could explore possibilities of increase in its product portfolio – in segments like health mix powders, coffee and using online marketplaces like Amazon and Fliplart to make the products available to the right segment.

The company's innovation the vada maker can be further improvised to make similar products such as doughnuts and other Indian snack food that requires cylindrical shape and a hole.

Note: These suggestions are restricted to a few options based on the current strategic moves made by company. However the students can brainstorm for fresh ideas that could enhance and strengthen iD Fresh Foods position in the market.

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Is Sustainable Development A Utopian Idea?

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Abstract

Many of the earth's resources are non-renewable and thus care has to be taken in its usage. The CSR (Corporate Social Responsibility) which has gained wide popularity during 1950's, acknowledged that discretion has to be practiced when it comes to using the non-renewable resources of the earth and every business concern, as the product of the society has a mutual responsibility towards the larger society. The horizon of CSR has been widened to include the sustainable development in the wake numerous ecological issues, emerging from business activities. This paper examines the sustainability of sustainable development in the context of fierce competitive business environment. It examines a few examples of corporates. Taking clue from these successful corporates, this paper proves that sustainable development is possible. The researcher concludes that sustainability coupled with innovation is the only way forward. And that too it is not another utopian idea but rather a Win-Win situation.

Keywords: Corporate Social Responsibility, Sustainable Development, Ecology, Renewable Resources, Innovation

Introduction

Given the environmental degradation and ecological crisis, there seems to no alternative option to sustainable development. All things being equal, numerous organizations are induced that the turning green or sustainable friendly, could bring about greater and more exertion on them monetarily and this could lead to less competitiveness in relation to their rivals. They perceive that it will add extra burden on them and won't convey quick monetary advantages. Take any example of CEOs, especially more in developed countries and perhaps less in under or developing countries, and their worries will spill out without hesitation: It's no joke going "green" and becoming sustainable friendly concerns. They believe that turning their activities sustainable and creating "Eco-friendly" products places them off guard opposite to their opponents; going green will require new machines and processing procedures; and the consumers won't pay more for products amid an economic recession. *It is a Utopian Idea.*

As anyone might expect, the battle to spare the planet has transformed into a pitched fight amongst governments and organizations, amongst organizations and consumer activists, and once in a while between customer activists and governments. It looks like a three-legged race, in which you push ahead with the two loosened legs, however the tied third leg keeps you down. One argument, mooted by strategy specialists and ecological activists, is progressively harder control. They contend that laissez-faire sort of approach is probably not going to be sufficient. Another gathering argument recommends instructing and organizing

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consumers in a way that they will arm-twist the organizations to turn eco-friendly. Albeit both enforcement and education are essential, they will be unable to sufficiently take care of the issue rapidly or comprehensively. The surprising fact is that CEOs carry on as if they need to pick between the generally social advantages of creating economical products or forms and the budgetary expenses of doing as such. Be that as it may, that is just not just true.

The current paper examines sustainable development activities of a few conglomerates and large corporate. This paper demonstrates that contrary to the belief that going “green” or sustainable friendly is doomsday for concerns and impractical in all sense, it is rather a jackpot of organizational and technological innovations that could bring forth both product-line and top-line returns. May be the short term financial burden weigh a bit heavily on companies but in the long run, producing green products and going the sustainable way would bring down expenses and this would lead to reducing inputs that are used in production. It is in fact a win-win situation.

In reality, the journey for sustainability is now beginning to change the market scenario, which will compel organizations to change the way they consider items, advancements, procedures, and plans of action. The way to progress, especially in the midst of monetary emergency, is development. Similarly as some web organizations survived the bust in 2000 to challenge incumbent, along these lines, as well, will sustainability too become a way forward for companies to combat the present situation of environmental crisis. By regarding sustainability as an objective today, early movers will create capabilities that adversaries will be unable to stand against. This would give them an upper hand, since sustainability is going to be an indispensable segment in development. The experiences of those companies which have gone green and adapted Sustainable Development, show that even though it wouldn't be all that rosy yet that is only temporary darkness in the tunnel. The following pages would examine the fundamental stages or phases, based the experiences of such companies, each company may go through in its journey of sustainable development and becoming an eco-friendly organization.

Creation of Eco-friendly Products and Services

First and foremost realization a company should have, is to awaken to the way that a sizable number of consumers favour eco-accommodating offerings, and that their organizations can score over adversaries by being the first to update existing items or grow new ones. With a specific end goal to distinguish product innovation initiatives, ventures need to utilize abilities and apparatuses they gained during the initial stages of their existence.

More often than not the discoveries of those products, causing environmental devastations are not to the liking of the Organizations. For instance. When Procter and Gamble directed life-cycle evaluations to compute the quantum of energy expected to utilize its product, it found that detergents can heighten the usage of electricity to an intense level. They burn through 3% of their yearly power spending to warm water washing. Had they changed to cool water washing, P&G figured, they would have spent 80 billion less kilowatt-hours of power and release 34 million less carbon dioxide in to the atmosphere. That is the reason P&G innovated cold-water detergent. In 2005 P&G introduced Tide Coldwater in the United States and Ariel Cool Clean in Europe. The pattern has gotten on more in Europe than in the United States. By 2008, 21% of British family units were washing in cold water, up from 2% in 2002; in Holland the number shot up from 5% to 52% of families. If this trend continues, P&G will have the unique chance to take advantage of this new development.

To create sustainable products, organizations need to comprehend customer concerns and deliberately inspect the product life cycles. They should figure out how to bring together their marketing expertise in scaling up raw-materials supplies and distribution. As they move into business sectors that lie beyond their traditional marketing areas, they need to collaborate with nongovernmental associations. Keen organizations like P&G, which has kept on putting resources into eco-friendly products in spite of the subsidence, look past the advertising advantages to sharpen capabilities that will empower them to overwhelm markets tomorrow.

Innovation of Business Models

Most administrators accept that making a sustainable plan of action involves basically reevaluating the client offer and making sense of how to convey another one. Not with standing, fruitful models incorporate novel methods for increasing incomes and fulfilling promises. In 2008 FedEx thought of a novel plan of action by coordinating the Kinko's chain of print shops that it had gained in 2004 with its documentary delivery business. Rather than physical delivery of document, say, Manhattan to Florida, FedEx now inquires its customers as to whether they might want to electronically transport the same. It prints and ties the documents at an outlet there and can deliver duplicates anyplace in the city the following morning. The client gets more opportunity to set up the material, accesses better-quality printing, and can browse an extensive variety of report. The document moves almost the entire way electronically and the last few miles in a truck. FedEx's costs shrink and its services become extremely eco-friendly.

A few organizations have grown new models just by asking at various circumstances what their business ought to be. That is the thing that Waste Management, the \$14 billion market pioneer in thrash transfer, did. Two years back it evaluated that some \$9 billion worth of reusable materials may be found in the waste it transported to landfills every year. At about a similar time, its clients, as well, started to understand that they were discarding cash. Waste Management set up a unit, Green Squad, to produce an incentive from thrash. For example, Green Squad has cooperated with Sony in the United States to gather electronic waste that used to wind up in landfills. Rather than being only a waste-trucking organization, Waste Management is demonstrating to clients both generally accepted methods to recoup an incentive from waste and how to lessen squander.

Building up alternative plan of action requires investigating other options to conventional methods of doing business and also seeing how organizations can address clients' issues in an innovative yet fulfilling way. CEOs must figure out how to address loopholes in the existing models and to act entrepreneurially to grow new delivery mechanisms.

Building GenX-Practice Platforms

GenX-practices change existing ideal models. Administrators must critically evaluate the certain presumptions behind current practices in order to usher new practices. This is precisely what prompted the present industrial and services economy. As the proverb goes, "Curiosity is the wick in the candle of learning." By scrutinizing the present state of affairs, individuals and organizations have transformed it into something never seen before. In like vein, we should make inquiries about rare assets: Can we create waterless cleansers? Would we be able to breed rice that grows without water? Can biodegradable bundling help seed the earth with plants and trees? It may indeed sound crazy! But that is how it works.

The quest for sustainability and going green can prompt intriguing and all new GenX practices. One example for such instance is the merging of the web and energy management.

Known as the brilliant matrix, it utilizes advanced innovation to oversee power generation, transmission, and dissemination from a wide range of sources alongside customer request. This matrix will prompt lower costs and in addition the more effective utilization of energy. The idea had been around for quite a long time, but its actualization is considered as giant step in conserving the earth in a big way. The framework has enabled organizations to advance the energy utilization of PCs, arrange gadgets, apparatus, phones, and building hardware, through meters, sensors, and applications. It will likewise empower the improvement of cross-industry stages to deal with the energy needs of urban areas, organizations, structures, and families. Innovation sellers, for example, Cisco, HP, Dell, and IBM are as of now contributing to build up these stages, as are utilities like Duke Energy, SoCal Edison, and Florida Power and Light.

Organizations can be helped to become eco-friendly or pro-sustainability by following the tow pronged strategies. One: When an organization's best administration group chooses to center around the issue, change happens rapidly. For example, in 2005 General Electric's CEO, Jeff Immelt, proclaimed that the organization would center around handling ecological issues. From that point forward each GE business has attempted to climb up the sustainability ladder, which has helped this giant corporate lead the pack from front in a few ventures. Two: Recruiting and holding the correct sort of individuals is imperative. Late research proposes that three-fourths of workforce participants in the United States respect social duty and ecological responsibility as imperative criterion in choosing managers. Individuals who are upbeat about their managers' attitude on those issues additionally appreciate working for them. Accordingly organizations that strive to project themselves sustainable and eco-friendly may well find it lot easier to hire and retain employees. As concerns turn out to be more adroit at this, the experience will lead them to the last phase of sustainable advancement, where the effect of another item or process stretches out past a solitary market.

Establishing the sustainable value Chain

Launching a sustainable value chains is too an important cog in the wheel of sustainable development and going green. To create an environmental friendly business, the concerned organization should put in place an effective value chain. At this stage, organizations should look forward to work with providers and retailers to create eco-accommodating crude materials and segments and diminish waste. Organizations create eco-friendly activities by examining each link in the value chain. To start with they bring out improvements in most evident areas, for example, supply chains, and after that they move to more subtle suspects like returned items.

Supply chains

Most large concerns persuade providers to turn environmentally conscious by offering them impetuses. For example, while reaching out to individuals' worries about the deterioration of environment, multinational companies, for example, HP and Unilever have put resources into innovation advancement to create economical practices in the development of recycled materials for laptops, palm oil, cacao, and other horticultural products. Unilever has declared that by 2015 it will be purchasing palm oil and tea only from sustainable sources, and Staples intends that most of its paper-based products will come from sustainable-yield forests by 2010

Tools, for example, carbon administration, carbon and energy footprint analysis, and life-cycle evaluation enable organizations to distinguish the causes of waste in supply chains. Life-cycle evaluation is especially helpful: It catches ecological related sources of inputs and

yields of whole value chains, from raw materials supply through finished products to returns from consumers. This has helped organizations find, that suppliers consume as much as 80% of the energy, water, and different resources utilized. Hence the supply chain becomes an important aspect in establishing sustainable activities and eco-friendly organization.

Logistics

Key to building an ecological inventory network are operational advancements that prompt more prominent energy proficiency and increase organizations' ability to optimize energy efficiency. Take the instance of FedEx, which sends an army of 650 aircrafts and 44,000 mechanized vehicles that consume 4 million gallons of fuel a day. The organization is substituting old aircrafts with Boeing 757s as a feature of its Fuel Sense program, this will lessen the organization's fuel utilization by 36% while expanding capacity by 20%. It is additionally presenting Boeing 777s, which will diminish fuel utilization by a further 18%. FedEx has built up an arrangement of 30 software programs that assist upgrade aircraft schedule, flight courses, the measure of additional fuel on load up, etcetera.

Work environments.

In light of concerns for the nature, a few companies make room for telecommunication for its employees. These pro-environmental action diminishments in movement time, travel expenses, and energy efficiency. Of IBM's 320,000 workers, 25% work from home, which saves a yearly investment funds of \$700 million in land costs alone. AT&T says that it spares \$550 million every year because of working from home. Efficiency goes up by 10% to 20%, and work fulfilment additionally increments when individuals work from home up to three days seven days. For instance, at the social insurance administrations supplier McKesson reported the most noteworthy activity fulfilment in 2007 comprised of 1,000 attendants who telecommuted.

Returns.

Worries about cutting waste constantly start organizations' enthusiasm for product returns. In the United States, returns lessen corporate viability by a normal of around 4% a year. Rather than rejecting returned items, organizations at this stage attempt to recover a portion of the lost an incentive by reusing them. Not exclusively would this be able to transform a cost focus into a productive business, yet the adjustment in demeanour flags that the organization is more worried about avoiding ecological harm and decreasing waste than it is tied in with ripping apart deals.

Cisco, for instance, had customarily respected the utilized gear it got as scrap and reused it at a cost of about \$8 million a year. Four years prior it attempted to discover utilizes for the gear, for the most part in light of the fact that 80% of the profits were in working condition. An esteem recuperation group at Cisco distinguished inside clients that incorporated its client benefit association, which underpins guarantee claims and administration contracts, and the labs that give specialized help, preparing, and item exhibits. In 2005 Cisco assigned the reusing bunch as a specialty unit, set clear destinations for it, and drew up a notional P&L account. Accordingly, the reuse of gear ascended from 5% in 2004 to 45% in 2008, and Cisco's reusing costs fell by 40%. The unit has turned into a viable that contributed \$100 million to Cisco's primary concern in 2008.

When they establish eco-friendly value chain, organizations unearth the monetary advantages that are associated with energy efficiency and waster reduction. They likewise figure out how to recreate systems that associates sustainability oriented activities to

business operations, as the Cisco illustration proves. Thus, ecological concerns flourish within business concerns, enabling administrators to handle the following huge test.

Conclusion

Administration and ability are basic for building up a low-carbon economy. The current consumerist and marketing framework have brought out massive weight on the planet, while serving the current general population on it. The pressure would be much more than one could ever imagine by next decade. Conventional ways to deal with business will fall, and organizations should create imaginative solutions in the face of fast degrading ecology. That will happen just when administrators perceive a basic truth: Sustainability coupled with innovation is the only way forward. And that too it is not another utopian idea but rather a Win-Win situation.

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Analysis Of In-Store Promotion And Its Impact On Patronage Intention Towards Apparel Stores In Chennai

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Abstract

The Apparels and Textiles Industry in India is one of the oldest industries dating back many centuries. The Apparels Stores have grown swiftly in India in recent years and they replaced the traditional distribution centers of India. In spite of various apparels stores are in India, still planning growth, how those stores plan to attract, retain and gain the customers is a very important subject of study today. With the drop in consumer spending due to the demonetization and competition, the retail stores especially textile/apparel stores have had to work harder to bring customers into their store and to get consumers to spend. One of the many ways which retail stores attract customers into their stores is by way of promotions. When shoppers enter the store, there are multiple sources of information that may change their shopping behavior. Specifically, how promotion strategies influence customers' psychological perception and attitude that would in turn affect not only their purchase intention of apparels but also their patronage intention is an important issue. By focusing on the major Apparel Stores in Chennai, this study intends to analyze which of the in-store promotional aspects mostly affects the consumers' perception and patronage intention towards Apparels and Apparels Stores/Shops in Chennai. An exploratory and analytical study was conducted based on a sample of 125 consumers who bought apparels in Chennai district. Descriptive and Inferential statistical tools like Independent Sample "t" Test, One-way ANOVA, Correlation and Multiple Regression are applied to test the hypotheses and analyze the consumers' perception on the various In-store Promotional strategies and their impact on Patronage Intention towards Apparels Stores in Chennai. The study revealed that demographic variables of the customers have strong influence on the various In-store Promotional strategies and Patronage Intention towards Apparels Stores. It is also found that there is a strong positive relationship between Perception on In-Store Promotional Strategies and Patronage Intention towards Apparel Stores. Out of four in-store promotional strategies, 'Buy One Get One Offer' was the strongest influencing factor in predicting Patronage Intention towards Apparels Stores.

Keywords: Apparels Stores, Shopping behavior, Patronage intention, buy One Get One Offer, Textiles Industry, in-store promotions.

Introduction

The Apparels Stores have grown swiftly in India in recent years and they replaced the traditional distribution centers of India. In spite of various apparels stores are in India, still planning growth, how those stores plan to attract, retain and gain the customers is a very

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important subject of study today. With the drop in consumer spending due to the demonetization and competition, the retail stores especially textile/apparel stores have had to work harder to bring customers into their store and to get consumers to spend. One of the many ways which retail stores attract customers into their stores is by way of promotions. Promotion has a wider scope which includes sales promotion as well as the other promotional strategies. Apparel Stores/Shops typically promote the products they have for sale but stores will also promote themselves. Within the retail marketing mix, In-Store Sales promotions have the strongest impact on consumer behavior that affects their purchase and patronage intention. The different promotions, which stores are adopting, certainly influence the consumers in many ways and to varying degrees. The present study is an attempt to analyze the consumers' perception on the various aspects of In-store Promotion and their impact on Patronage Intention towards Apparels Stores/Shops in Chennai.

Profile Of Apparels And Textiles Industry In India

The Apparels and Textiles Industry in India is one of the oldest industries dating back many centuries. The industry is also basically labour intensive and is one of the largest employers. This industry has two broad segments. First, the unorganized sector which consists of handloom, handicrafts and sericulture, which are operated on a small scale and through traditional tools and methods. The second is the organized sector consisting of spinning, apparel and garments segment which apply modern machinery and techniques such as economies of scale. The Indian textile and apparel industry has the capacity to manufacture a varied variety of products fit to different market segments, both within India and outside the India. At present, the Apparels and Textiles Industry in India is projected nearly 150 Billion USD and is anticipated to achieve 250 billion USD by the year 2019. The industry presently (2017-18) contributes 7 percent of the industrial output of India and also contributes 2 percent to the GDP of India. The industry had more than 45 million employees in the year 2017-18. This industry contributed 15 per cent to the export earnings of India in the year 2017-18.

Textile and apparel exports of India are estimated to increase to 82 billion USD by the year 2021. The Indian Exports of textiles and Apparels has reached Rs.1.30 trillion (provisional) in the financial year 2019. The Man-made garments continue the largest contributor to total the textile and apparel exports of India which is contributing more than 24 percent to total textile and apparels. The rising income level of consumers, favorable demographics, increased penetration of organized retail, etc. are probable reasons for the increase in the demands of textiles and apparels in India.

Statement Of Research Problem

Worldwide, nearly 30 percent of shoppers make buying decisions when they are in-store. In-store marketing/promotion creates a special atmosphere and adds to the better shopping experience. There are many ways of sales promotion. In-store promotion, one of the important sale promotion techniques, plays a vital role in inducing the consumers to buy. Mostly these ways of in-store promotion used are coupons, Windows display, contests, discounts, buy one get one free, Demonstrations, premiums, redemption points, samples, cash back offers, etc. The In-store sales promotions speed up the number of shopping trips to the store. The purchasing and shopping behavior of consumers with respect to the apparels is more useful for understanding the various influences on the consumer purchase decision-making process. However, purchasing decisions made in-store are part of a complicated process made up of many factors that most consumers may not be aware. When shoppers

enter the store, there are multiple sources of information that may change their shopping behavior. Specifically, how promotion strategies influence customers' psychological perception and attitude that would in turn affect not only their purchase intention of apparels but also their patronage intention is an important issue.

Therefore, it is the intent of this study to examine how the stores have used promotions and what affect those in-store promotions have had on consumers and their buying behavior. While the concepts of this research study should be applicable to retail businesses in general, but this research is conducted on the Apparel Stores in Chennai. By focusing on the major Apparel Stores in Chennai, this study intends to analyze which of the in-store promotional aspects mostly affects the consumers' perception and patronage intention towards Apparels and Apparels Stores/Shops.

Objectives Of The Research

The Objectives refer to the questions to be answered through the study. They indicate what researcher trying to get from the study. The objectives of this research are as follows:

- ❖ To study and analyse the perception of consumers on the various In-Store Promotions of the Apparel Stores in Chennai.
- ❖ To evaluate the impact of various In-Store Promotions on Patronage Intention of consumers towards Apparel Stores in Chennai.

Significance Of The Research

Retail market is growing in a high velocity environment all over the world. Retailers currently use all types of promotional activities in order to be differentiated in the market. At the same time, competitiveness among retailers is booming. With the recent and ongoing economic downturn due to demonetization, it is even more imperative that retail stores entice consumers into retail stores and get them to make purchases. Therefore, it is more important now that retail stores are able to deduce what affect promotional activities have on consumer purchasing behavior and how consumers rank promotions relative to each other.

This research is significant in informing the management of Apparel Stores, on the adoption of In-store promotions in order to attract the customers and increase their patronage intention towards apparels and apparels stores. The research is also important for apparel stores to capture the market and also to identify a promotional way that attracts customers as compared to others for greater sales and market share. The findings of the research also provide valuable information on the challenges faced by managers in the adoption of various in-store promotions formulated and provide recommendations on possible measures applicable in overcoming such challenges. Consumers would benefit by understanding that apparel stores adopt various in-store sales promotions and this would help them to associate themselves with apparel stores having strategies that gave the positive attitude and improved purchase intention and patronage intention towards apparels stores. In addition, consumers are in a position to evaluate whether the in-store promotions have an impact on their knowledge, beliefs and attitude which makes them to purchase the products.

Scope Of The Research

Scope of study is a general outline of what the study will cover. The focal point of the study is to analyze the perception of consumer on various In-store Promotion like Price Discount, Coupon Discount, Buy-One-Get-One offer, Window Display, etc. and examine their impact on consumers' patronage Intention towards Apparel Stores in Chennai. This study is limited to the perception of consumers who are buying Apparels (Dress materials) through stores/shops in Chennai. The scope of the research is confined to the apparels consumers of

Chennai district. This study is conducted in selected consumers belong to the selected apparel stores in Chennai district, which may be inappropriate for the apparel stores in other part of the country. The study, analysis, findings, suggestions and conclusion proposed by the researcher, would be of immense use for future research in the area of apparel retailing.

Theoretical Framework

In-Store Promotion

In-store promotion is a marketing strategy that is meant to bring people into the store and to purchase specific items that are part of the in-store promotion. These strategies most often come directly from manufacturers, or they may be offered by the store itself. The idea is to generate additional revenue due to the extra sales of the products involved, or even to induce a brand switch when offered by the manufacturer. Stores most often use such strategies to drive traffic into the store, to eliminate too much stock, or to create additional revenues when sales are slumping. Often, however, the main emphasis comes from brand manufacturers attempting to create brand awareness, while building brand equity in-store.

Patronage Intention

Grewal et al. (1998, p. 48) defined willingness to buy as the “likelihood that the consumer intends to purchase products”, whereas, patronage intention is an overall measure capturing likelihood and willingness to shop, buy, and willingness to recommend to others(Grewal et al., 2003). Therefore, Patronage intention toward a store includes the willingness to buy from that store and similarly patronage intention toward a retail apparels store includes the willingness to buy from that retail apparels store.

Research Methodology

The detailed methodology of the research has been described on the basis of research design, sampling design, data collection method and analysis. From the view point of function, it is a descriptive as well as analytical research because here we discuss the Consumers' perception on the various In-store Promotional aspects and Patronage Intention towards Apparel Stores. From the view point of data nature, it is both qualitative and quantitative research.

TABLE 1: RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Research type	Descriptive and Analytical Research
Population	Customers of Apparels
Sample size	125 Customers
Sampling Area	Chennai
Sampling Method	Non - Probability Sampling – Convenient Sampling
Research Method	Survey
Data type	Primary (Majority of the data) and Secondary Data
Sources of Primary Data	Questionnaire and Personal Interview
Sources of Secondary Data	Newspapers, Journals, Magazines, Reports, Books, Research Articles, Internet, etc.
Research instrument	Structured Questionnaire
Period of data collection	September 2018 to October 2018
Software used for data analysis	MS Excel (2013) &SPSS (Version 20)

Data Analysis And Results

1. Demographic Profile

TABLE 2: DEMOGRAPHIC PROFILE

(Sample Size = 125)

VARIABLES	OPTIONS	FREQUENCIES	(%)
Gender	Male	73	58.40
	Female	52	41.60
Age	19 – 40 Years	Open ended Question (Scale Variable)	68.80
	41 – 62 Years		31.20
Marital Status	Married	77	61.60
	Unmarried	48	38.40
Qualification	School / Diploma	29	23.20
	UG / PG	76	60.80
	Professional / Ph.D.	20	16.00
Monthly Family Income (INR)	Upto Rs.50,000	39	31.20
	Rs.50,001 – Rs.1,00,000	46	36.80
	Rs.1,00,001 – Rs.2,00,000	26	20.80
	Above Rs.2,00,000	14	11.20
Occupation	Salaried	50	40.00
	Business / Professional	15	12.00
	Student	24	19.20
	Home maker	36	28.80

Source: Primary Data

From the Demographic Profile table, it is found that male respondents (73, 58.40%) are more than female respondents (52, 41.60%). Most of the respondents (68.80%) related to the age group of 19 – 40 years. More than 61% of the respondents are married. 60.80% (76) of the respondents are Under and Post Graduates. With respect to the Monthly Family Income, 36.80% (46) of the respondents are belong to the monthly income from Rs.50,001 to Rs.1,00,000. 40% (50) of the respondents are salaried employees followed by Home maker (36, 28.80%), Student (24, 19.20%) and rest of them (15, 12%) belong to Business/Professional occupation.

2. Apparel Store Data

TABLE 3: APPAREL STORE DATA

(Sample Size = 125)

VARIABLES	OPTIONS	FREQUENCIES	(%)
Average Shopping Expenditure per purchase	Upto Rs.5,000	73	58.40
	Rs.5,001 – Rs.10,000	33	26.40
	Above Rs.10,000	19	15.20
Occasion of Purchase of Apparels	Festival Times	55	44.00
	Functions	44	35.20
	Offer for Sales	26	20.80

Source: Primary Data

The Apparel Store Data table provides the information Average Shopping Expenditure per purchase and Occasion of Purchase of Apparels by the respondents. It is inferred that most of the respondents (58.40%, 73) spend upto Rs.5,000 towards Shopping Expenditure. 44% of the respondents purchase their Apparels during the occasion of “Festival Times”. 35.20% (44) purchased the same for functions and rest of the respondents (20.80%, 26) bought the apparels when there is an Offer for sales.

3. Perception On In-Store Promotion Of Apparel Stores

Independent Sample ‘t’ Test – Analysis

H₀: There is no significant difference between the Male and Female respondents with respect to the perception on In-Store Promotion of Apparel Store.

An independent-samples t-test was conducted to compare the difference between the Male and Female respondents with respect to the perception on In-Store Promotion of Apparel Store.

TABLE 4: GENDER – PERCEPTION ON IN-STORE PROMOTION OF APPAREL STORES

VARIABLES	GENDER						t - value	p - value
	MALE			FEMALE				
	N	Mean	SD	N	Mean	SD		
Price Discount	73	9.23	3.422	52	10.58	3.268	2.222	0.028*
Buy One Get One Offer	73	8.78	3.237	52	10.73	3.062	3.426	0.001*
Window Display	73	9.90	2.814	52	10.65	2.841	1.460	0.147
Promotional Signage	73	9.60	2.686	52	10.88	2.587	2.687	0.008*
PERCEPTION ON IN-STORE PROMOTION OF APPAREL STORE	73	37.52	9.768	52	42.85	10.374	2.898	0.005*

Source: Primary Data (**1% Level of Significance) (*5%Level of Significance)

As the P values are lesser than Sig. Value (0.01 and 0.05) in three out of four aspects and also in the Perception on In-Store Promotion of Apparel Store Score (0.005), the Null Hypotheses are rejected. The Null Hypothesis is accepted in one aspect - “Window Display” (0.147) since the P value is greater than Sig. Value (0.05). Based on the overall mean Score, we can say that the mean score of Female respondents (M = 42.85) is more than the Male respondents (M = 37.52). This indicates that the Female respondents have more perception on In-Store Promotion of Apparel Store than Male respondents. Hence, there is a significant difference between the Male and Female respondents with respect to the perception on In-Store Promotion of Apparel Store.

One -Way Anova

H₀: There is no significant difference among the Occasion of Purchase of the respondents with respect to the Perception on In-Store Promotion of Apparel Store.

A one-way between-groups analysis of variance (ANOVA) was conducted to explore the significant difference among the Occasion of Purchase of the respondents with respect to the Perception on In-Store Promotion of Apparel Store.

TABLE 5: OCCASION OF PURCHASE – PERCEPTION ON IN-STORE PROMOTION OF APPAREL STORE

VARIABLES	OCCASION OF PURCHASE			F – value	p – value
	Festival times (55)	Functions (44)	Offer for Sales (26)		
Price Discount	9.18	9.27	11.96	7.328	0.001**
	3.186	3.598	2.705		
Buy One Get One Offer	9.16	9.05	11.42	5.441	0.005**
	3.573	3.065	2.403		
Window Display	9.85	10.18	11.04	1.554	0.216
	3.112	2.839	2.049		
Promotional Signage	9.67	9.73	11.81	6.839	0.002**
	2.742	2.823	1.674		
PERCEPTION ON IN-STORE PROMOTION OF APPAREL STORE	37.87	38.23	46.23	7.155	0.001**
	10.396	10.811	6.231		

Source: Primary Data (No. of respondents are shown in brackets)

(**1% Level of Significance) (5% Level of Significance)

As the *P* values are lesser than Sig. Value (0.01 and 0.05) in three out of four aspects and also in the Perception on In-Store Promotion of Apparel Score, the Null Hypotheses are rejected. The Null Hypothesis is accepted in one aspect - “Window Display” (0.216) since the *P* value is greater than Sig. Value (0.05). Apart from reaching statistical significance, the actual difference in the mean score of the Perception on In-Store Promotion of Apparel Store among the Occasion of Purchase groups is also large ((*M* = 37.87 to 46.23). The Mean score of the Perception on In-Store Promotion towards Apparel Store in case of Offer for Sales (*M* = 46.23) is more than others. This indicates that the respondents who have purchased the apparels when ‘Offer for Sales’ have perceived more on In-Store Promotion towards Apparel Store than others. Hence, there is significant difference among the Occasion of Purchase of the respondents with respect to the Perception on In-Store Promotion of Apparel Store.

4. Patronage Intention towards Apparel Stores

Independent Sample ‘t’ Test

H₀: There is no significant difference among the Male and Female with respect to the Patronage Intention towards Apparel Stores.

An independent-samples t-test was conducted to compare the difference between the Male and Female respondents with respect to the Patronage Intention towards Apparel Stores.

TABLE 6: GENDER – PATRONAGE INTENTION TOWARDS APPAREL STORES

VARIABLE	GENDER						t - value	p - value
	MALE			FEMALE				
	N	Mean	SD	N	Mean	SD		
Patronage Intention towards Apparel Stores	73	16.79	3.180	52	18.44	3.102	2.897	0.005*

Source: Primary Data (**1% Level of Significance)

As the *P* value is lesser than Sig. Value (0.01) in the above case (0.005), the Null Hypothesis is rejected. From the above table, we can say that the Mean score of the Patronage Intention towards Apparel Stores is more for Female respondents (M = 18.44) than the Male respondents (M = 16.79). This indicates that the Female respondents have more Patronage Intention towards Apparel Stores than the male respondents. Therefore, there is a significant difference among the Male and Female with respect to the Patronage Intention towards Apparel Stores.

Occasion Of Purchase – Patronage Intention Towards Apparel Stores

ONE -WAY ANOVA

H₀: There is no significant difference among the Occasion of Purchase of the respondents with respect to the Patronage Intention towards Apparel Stores.

A one-way between-groups analysis of variance (ANOVA) was conducted to explore the significant difference among the Occasion of Purchase of the respondents with respect to the Patronage Intention towards Apparel Stores.

TABLE 7: OCCASION OF PURCHASE – PATRONAGE INTENTION TOWARDS APPAREL STORES

VARIABLE	OCCASION OF PURCHASE			F - value	p - value
	Festival times (55)	Functions (44)	Offer for Sales (26)		
Patronage Intention towards Apparel Stores	16.65	17.61	19.00	4.987	0.008**
	3.301	3.356	2.280		

Source: Primary Data (No. of respondents are shown in brackets)

(**1% Level of Significance)

As the *P* value is lesser than Sig. Value (0.01) in the Patronage Intention towards Apparel Stores Score, the Null Hypothesis is rejected. Apart from reaching statistical significance, the actual difference in the mean score of the Patronage Intention towards Apparel Stores among the Occasion of Purchase groups is also large (M = 16.65 to 19.00). The Mean score of the Patronage Intention towards Apparel Stores in case of the Occasion of Purchase - "Offer for Sales" (M = 19.00) is more than others. Hence, it is inferred that the respondents who purchase apparels during 'Offer for Sales' have more Patronage Intention towards Apparel Stores than others. Therefore, there is a significant difference among the Occasion of Purchase of the respondents with respect to the Patronage Intention towards Apparel Stores.

5. Perception On In-Store Promotion And Patronage Intention Towards Apparel Stores

CORRELATION ANALYSIS

H₀: There is no significant relationship between the Perception on various aspects of In-Store Promotion and Patronage Intention towards Apparel Stores.

A Pearson product-moment correlation was run to determine the relationship between the Perception on various aspects of In-Store Promotion and Patronage Intention towards Apparel Stores.

TABLE 8: PERCEPTION ON IN-STORE PROMOTION AND PATRONAGE INTENTION TOWARDS APPAREL STORES

VARIABLES	N	'r' VALUE	P-VALUE	RELATIONSHIP	REMARKS	
					SIGNIFICANT	RESULT
Price Discount – Patronage Intention towards Apparel Stores	125	0.727**	0.000	Positive	Significant	REJECTED
Buy One Get One offer – Patronage Intention towards Apparel Stores	125	0.731**	0.000	Positive	Significant	REJECTED
Window Display – Patronage Intention towards Apparel Stores	125	0.540**	0.000	Positive	Significant	REJECTED
Promotional Signage – Patronage Intention towards Apparel Stores	125	0.716**	0.000	Positive	Significant	REJECTED

(Source: Primary Data) **. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

As the P values are lesser than Sig. Value (0.01) in all the above aspects, the Null Hypotheses are rejected. There are high positive and significant correlation between the Perception on the various aspects of In-Store Promotion and Patronage Intention towards Apparel Stores. Out of four aspects relating to the Perception on In-Store Promotion of Apparel Store, “Buy One Get One Offer” (r = 0.731) has more relationship with Patronage Intention towards Apparel Stores than others. “Window Display” (r = 0.540) has less relationship with Patronage Intention towards Apparel Stores when compared with others. Therefore, there is a significant relationship between the Perception on various aspects of In-Store Promotion and Patronage Intention towards Apparel Stores.

Multiple Regression Analysis

Multiple Regression was conducted to determine the best linear combination of the Perception on the various aspects of In-Store Promotion of Apparel Stores and Patronage Intention towards Apparel Stores.

TABLE 9: PERCEPTION ON IN-STORE PROMOTION STORE APPAREL AND PATRONAGE INTENTION TOWARDS APPAREL STORES REGRESSION COEFFICIENT

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	7.781	.739		10.526	.000
Price Discount	.284	.080	.299	3.568	.001
Buy One Get One Offer	.324	.080	.330	4.067	.000
Window Display	.155	.073	.136	2.123	.036
Promotional Signage	.220	.108	.184	2.036	.044

Dependent Variable: PATRONAGE INTENTION TOWARDS APPAREL STORES

The combination of all the independent variables (In-Store Promotional aspects) significantly predicts the dependent variable i.e., Patronage Intention towards Apparel Stores, $F(2, 122) = 4.987$, p values are lesser than .001 (Sig. Value 2-tailed) and Adjusted R Square is 0.652 or 65% which is large effect according to Cohen. Out of four independent variables relating to In-Store Promotion of Apparel Store, “Buy One Get One Offer” (0.330) is the strongest influencing factor which predicting the dependent variable i.e., Patronage Intention towards Apparel Stores. From the unstandardized coefficient, it is found that the one unit increase in the “Buy One Get One Offer” would increase the Patronage Intention towards Apparel Stores by 0.324 units. Price Discount (0.299), promotional Signage (0.184) and Window Display (0.136) also contribute to Patronage Intention towards Apparel Stores but lesser than “Buy One Get One Offer”.

Limitations Of The Research

The outcome of this research has given valuable feedbacks to researchers. However, these outcomes were accompanied with some limitations. The biggest limitation of the study was to collect the information from the respondents. Because of the limited time and financial resources available, the survey is of limited scale and scope, such that the survey results may not be fully representative of the views of the consumers in the city (Chennai) studied. The study is also limited to apparel stores products only and this study considers only In-store promotions of apparel stores. This study has gathered the data during September to October 2018. Therefore, similar research on some other time period, in same geographical location may produce some different result.

Suggestions And Conclusion

India has seen very few research studies on the impact of in-store promotion, making it difficult for promoters to understand whether their investments in in-store promotion are vindicated. Promotions can be a very effective means of affecting consumer behavior and helping to push consumers to the final step of making a purchase. The research reveals that the demographic profile of Consumers have direct influence over the perception and patronage intention towards Apparel Stores. It is also found from the study that the male consumers have less perception and patronage intention towards Apparels Stores than their counter parts do. It is found from the study that out of various In-Store Promotions of Apparel Stores, the respondents have less perception on ‘Window Display’ promotion when compared with others. So, the Management of Apparel Stores should enhance the attractiveness of Window Display Promotion by adding more impressive contents and creativity.

Therefore, Apparel Stores should devise the policies and strategies to improve the level of perception, attitude and patronage intention of the male customers in future. The Apparel Stores must endeavor to design their products and promotional activities in such a way to attract the most promising segment, based on the demographic profile of consumers as well as to find out the ways and means to reach the non-promising segments too. Out of four In-Store Promotion of Apparel Store, "Buy One Get One Offer" is the strongest influencing factor which predicting the Patronage Intention towards Apparel Stores. Offering customers more flexible prices and promotions or offering a one-stop shopping service are some examples that stores can use to make their business succeed. The sustainability and acceleration of growth pace of Apparel Stores depends on how far they design, alter or modify their policies and marketing strategies especially promotional strategies, according to the consumer behavior towards shopping of apparels.

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Applications of Neural Networking Model in Statistics

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Abstract

Neural networks have received a great deal of attention over the last few years. They are being used in the areas of prediction and classification, areas where regression models and other related statistical techniques have traditionally been used. An Artificial Neural Network (ANN) is an information processing paradigm that is inspired by the way biological nervous systems, such as the brain, process information. A Neural Network is a series of algorithms that endeavours to recognise underlying relationships in a set of data through a process that mimics the way the human brain operates.

Keywords: Regression models, Feed-Forward Networks, Feed - back ward Networks

Introduction

The practice or science of collection and analysing numerical data in large quantities, especially for the purpose of inferring proportions in whole from those in a representative sample. A Neural Network is a series of algorithms that endeavours to recognise underlying relationships in a set of data through a process that mimics the way the human brain operates.

Why neural networks

Adaptive learning

Self-Organization

Real Time Operation

Fault Tolerance via Redundant Information Coding

Architecture of neural networks

Feed-Forward Networks

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Feed- backward Networks

The Learning Process

The memorization of patterns and the subsequent response of the network can be categorized into two general paradigms

1. Associative Mapping : in which the network learns to produce a particular pattern on the set of input units whenever another particular pattern is applied on the set of input units
2. Regularity Detection :in which units learn to respond to particular properties of the input patterns. Whereas in associative mapping the network stores the relationships among patterns, in regularity detection the response of each unit has a particular 'meaning'

Every neural network posses knowledge which is contained in the values of the connections weights.

Two major categories of neural networks

1. Fixed networks
2. Adaptive networks

All learning methods used for adaptive neural networks can be classified into two major categories:

- Supervised learning
- Unsupervised learning

Advantages of Neural Network

When we have large amount of complex data Neural Network saves us a lot of time by combining and figuring out which one are important.

Neural Network can adapt to changing input so the network generates the best possible result without needing to redesign the output criteria.

As data gets bigger and bigger Neural Network will likely play an increasingly important role in helping us make sense of all that data .

Neural Network allow us to make use of data that might seem to overwhelming for us to try to use on it's own. They can find patterns that humans might never be able to see.

Applications of neural networks

- Neural Networks in Practice
- Neural Networks in Medicine
- Neural Networks in Business

Statistics and Neural Network applicable in

Linear and Nonlinear Regression

Multiple Regression

Classifical Networks

Historical and Bibliographical remarks

Understanding Neural Network as Statistical tools

Neural Network have been used for a wide variety of applications where statistical methods are traditionally employed They have been used in classification of problems such as identifying underwater sonar contacts, predicting heart problems in patients, diagnosing hypertension, playing backgammon and recognising speech. In time series applications they have been used in predicting stock market ,predicting protein secondary structures. As statisticians we would normally solve these problems through classical statistical model such as Discriminate analysis, logistics analysis, Baye's Multiple regression and time series models such as ARIMA ,forecasting methods. It is therefore time to recognise Neural Network as a potential tool for data analysis.

Conclusions

The Computing World has a lot to gain from neural networks

Their ability to learn by example makes them very flexible and powerful

They are also very well suited for real time systems because of their fast response and computational times

Neural networks also contribute to other areas of research such as neurology and psychology.

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A Study on Structured Analysis and Design Tools

Raj Sinha*

Abstract

Structured Analysis is a set of techniques and graphical tools such as ER Model, Data Flow Diagrams, Flowchart, Data Dictionary, Decision Trees, Decision Tables, Structured English and Pseudocode that allow the analyst to develop a new kind of system specification that are easily understandable to the developer. From the DFD, the next step is the definition of the modules and their relationships to one another in a form called a structure chart, using a data dictionary and other structured tools.

Keywords: *Data Flow Diagram, Data Dictionary, Decision Tree, Decision table.*

Introduction: Structured Analysis is a logical tool to understand and describe the information system in a logical way which uses graphical tools in an organized manner that makes use of graphical diagrams to develop and present system specifications to users in a way that makes them clear and easy to understand. The diagrams explain the steps that need to occur and the data that is needed to meet the design requirements of the system. Some of the important steps involved in structured analysis are as below:

- Studying the current system and evaluating all of its issues
- Modelling this system
- Modelling the new system around these issues, in order to fix them
- Modelling the new physical environment
- Evaluating any alternatives
- Choosing the best system approach
- Creating the graphical specifications

It defines

Fig 1.0 Structured Analysis

Objectives

- To determine if the current System is in trouble.
- To determine appropriate alternatives
- To make recommendation

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Tools of Structured Analysis: Following are the various tools and techniques which are used for system development. They are –

- ER Model
- Flowchart
- Data Flow Diagrams
- Decision Trees
- Decision Tables
- Structured English
- Data Dictionary

E-R Model: Entity-relationship model is database analysis and design tool which lists real-life application entities and defines the relationship between real life entities that are to be mapped to database. E-R model forms basis for database design.

Example:

Entity	Primary Key	Attribute
Student	Student_ID	StudentName
Professor	Employee_ID	ProfessorName
Course	Course_ID	CourseName
Entity	Primary Key	Attribute

Fig 1.1 Example of ER Model

Flowchart: A flow chart which was introduced by Frank Gilberth in 1921, is a graphical or symbolic representation of a process. Earlier they were called “Process Flow Charts”. Here, each step in the process is represented by a different symbol and contains a short description of the process step. The flow chart symbols are linked together with arrows showing the process flow direction.

Notation of Flowchart

Symbol Name	Purpose	Symbol
Start/Stop	Used at the beginning and end of the algorithm to show start and end of the program.	
Process	Indicates processes like mathematical operations.	
Input/ Output	Used for denoting program inputs and outputs.	
Decision	Stands for decision statements in a program, where answer is usually Yes or No	
Arrow	Shows relationships between different shapes.	
On-page Connector	Connects two or more parts of a flowchart, which are on the same page.	
Off-page Connector	Connects two parts of a flowchart which are spread over different pages.	

Fig 1.2 Example of Flowchart of SDLC Process

Data Flow Diagram: DFD are graphical representation to depict the flow of data and the transformation that takes place. DFD don't supply detail description of modules but graphically describe a system data and how the data interacts with the system.

Purpose of DFD

- Provides a graphical tool which can be used by the analyst to explain his understanding of the system to the user
- Can be easily converted into a structure chart which is used in design.

Context diagram: An overview of an organizational system that shows the system boundaries, external entities that interact with the system and the major information flows between the entities and the system. In this diagram, a single process represents the whole system. When we explore the context Analysis diagram then only it is called as DFD.

Fig 1.3 Example of Context Diagram College Management System

First level DFD: A data flow diagram that represents a system’s major processes, data flows, and data stores at a high level of detail.

Fig 1.4 Example of First Level DFD of College Management System

Second Level DFD: Certain elements of any data-flow diagram can be decomposed (“exploded”) into a more detailed model a level lower in the hierarchy.

Fig 1.5 Example of Second Level DFD of College Management System
Various components of a Data Flow Diagram

Components	Description	Symbol
Process	Any transformation of data from one form to another. People, procedures or devices can be used as processes that use or produce (transform) data.	
Data Flow	Path of data as it flows through a system. Data moves in a specific direction from a point of origin to point of destination in the form of a document, letter, telephone call or virtually any other medium	
Source or sink of data or External Entity	origin and destination of data. Lies outside the content of the system.	
Data store	Data at rest. Repository of data.	

Rules for drawing a data flow diagram:

- For process:
 - No process can have only outputs and inputs.
 - A process has a verb phrase label.
- For Data Store:
 - Data cannot move directly from one data store to another data store. Data must be moved through a process.
 - Data cannot move directly from an outside source to data store. Data must be moved through a process that receives data from the source and places it into the data store.
 - Data cannot move directly to an outside sink from a data store. Data must be moved through a process.
 - A data store has a noun phrase label.
- External Entity:
 - Fix the scope of system and identify all external entity.
 - It has a noun phrase label
- For data flow:
 - It cannot connect:
 - Two External Entities
 - An external Entity and a data store.
 - Can Connect:
 - Two Processes
 - An External entity and a process
 - A process and a data store.
 - Label all data flows
 - A data flow to a data store means update (delete or change).
 - A data flow from a data store means retrieve or use.
 - A data flow has a noun phrase label.

Leveling of DFD

- A Context diagram gives an overview.
- It should be split into major processes which gives greater details
- Each major process is further split to give more details

Balancing DFD: The data that flow into or out of a bubble on a parent diagram are equivalent to net inputs and output to and from a child diagram. This equivalence is called balancing.

An example showing balanced decomposition

In the next level, bubble 0.1 is decomposed.

(a) Level 1 DFD

In the level 1, data item (d1, d3) flow out of the bubble 0.1. and the data item(d2) flow into the bubble 0.1.

(b) Level 2 DFD

The decomposition is balanced. As (d1, d3) flow out of the level2 diagram and d2 flows in.

Fig 1.6 Example of Balanced Decomposition

Types of DFD

Design Feature	Logical	Physical
What the model depicts?	How the business operates?	How the System will be implemented? Or, How the current system operates?
What the processes represent?	Business activities	Program, Program modules and manual procedures.
What the data stores represent?	Collection of data regardless of how the data are stored?	Physical Files and databases, manual files
Type of data store	Show data store representing permanent data collection.	Master files, Transaction Files. Any processes that operate at two different times must be connected by a data store.

System Controls	Show Business Controls.	Show control for validating input data. For obtaining a record, ensuring successful completion of a process and for system security.
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Difference between Flowchart and DFD

Criteria	Flowchart	DFD
Flow of	Control	Data
Process Execute	one at a time	Parallel
Flow of data through	an Information Processing System	Business Processes
Action	Physical	Logical
View of the System	High Level	Lower Level
Input form or output to external Source	Does not have any	Describes the path of data from external source to internal store or vice versa
Timing and Sequence	Aptly Shown by flow chart	Particular order or simultaneously is not described
Show	How to make a System Function	Define the functionality of the system
Used	Designing a Process	Describes the path of data that will complete that process
Types	System Flow chart, Data Flow chart, Document Flow Chart and Program Flow Chart	Physical DFD Logical DFD

With the help of a **Question** let us understand different Structured Analysis tool

If Customer is individual and purchases 10 or more than 10 books, discount of 20% is given.
 If Customer is individual and purchases less than 10 books but more than 5 books, discount of 15% is given.
 If Customer is individual and purchases 5 or less than 5 books, discount of 10% is given
 If Customer is librarian and purchases 25 or more books, discount of 15% is given
 If Customer is librarian and purchases more than 10 but less than 25 books, discount of 10% is given

Decision Tree: Provides a graphical representation of decision logic that non-technical people find easy to understand. It's an easy mapping of a computer design which shows branch points but not the details of the user dialogues. It helps to show the path that is possible in a design following an action or decision by the user. Thus, it helps the designer to visualize how the user will move through the design to reach a desired location.

In Simple words, a decision tree provides an over view of the flow of control to be built into the computer program.

Fig 1.7 Example of Decision Tree

Solution for the above mentioned Question

Decision Table: They are non-procedural specification of decision rules. They have been used extensively in the systematic design of information system. They have also been used for communication and documenting complex decision procedures.

A decision table defines a logical procedure by means of a set of condition and related actions. Thus, it is a tool to represent complex processing decision in a compact form.

Components of decision table:

- Condition Stub – lists all the condition to be checked
- Action Stub – outlines all the action to be carried out to meet such condition.
- Condition Entry – provides answers to questions asked in condition stub quadrant.
- Action Entry – appropriate action resulting from the answers to the conditions in the condition entry quadrant.

Fig 1.8 Decision Table

Rules

- (Y)- existence of a condition.
- (N)– condition which is not satisfied.
- (blank or a hyphen) - states it is to be ignored.
- X (or a check mark will do) - action states it is to be carried out.

INPUT CONDITION	Condition Entry (Rule 1)	Condition Entry(Rule 2)	Condition Entry (Rule 3)
ACTION	SubsequentAction Entry	SubsequentAction Entry	SubsequentAction Entry

ID	CONDITIONS/ACTIONS	TEST CASE 1	TEST CASE 2	TEST CASE 3	TEST CASE 4	TEST CASE 5
Condition 1	Account Already Approved	T	T	T	T	F
Condition 2	OTP (One Time Password) Matched	T	T	F	F	X
Condition 3	Sufficient Money in the Account	T	F	T	F	X
Action 1	Transfer Money	Execute				
Action 2	Show a Message as 'Insufficient Amount'		Execute			
Action 3	Block The Transaction Incase of Suspicious Transaction			Execute	Execute	X

Fig 1.9 Example of Decision Table

Decision table is of 3 types

- LEDT- Limited Entry Decision Table
 - The question asked have only 'YES' or 'NO' as answer and the action can be denotes only by 'X' (Cross) or '-' (Hyphen). No other symbol or code is allowed. The numbers of condition are thus more in this type of decision table.
 - Here, the Question is written in the condition stub and their answer in the condition entry part of the decision table.

Solution for the above mentioned Question

Conditions	Rule 1	Rule 2	Rule 3	Rule 4	Rule 5
Customer is an Individual	Y	Y	Y		
Customer is a Librarian				Y	Y
Purchased 5 or less Books			Y		
Purchased more than 5 Books		Y			
Purchased 10 or more Books	Y	N			Y
Purchased 25 or more Books				Y	N
Actions					
10% Discount given			X		Y
15% Discount given		X		X	
20% Discount given	X				

- EEDT- Extended Entry Decision Table
 - It can have multiple answer based on the various type of Question asked which is extended into the condition entry part of the decision table. It should be observed that each question is formulated by combining the statement in the condition stub with that in the condition entry of the decision table which is commonly known as EEDT.

Solution for the above mentioned Question:

Conditions	Rule 1	Rule 2	Rule 3	Rule 4	Rule 5
C1: Customer?	Individual	Individual	Individual	Librarian	Librarian
C2: Number of Books	>=10	>5 and <10	<=5	>10 &<25	>=25
Actions					
A1: Discount =	20%	15%	10%	10%	15%

- MEDT - Mixed Entry Decision Table
- The Question dealt in LEDT and EEDT can also be shown in another form with same question extending to the entry part and other being limited to the condition stub. This table can have 'YES' or 'NO' in the condition entry as well as different answer of the question in condition stub.
- It is compromise between LEDT and EEDT. Thus the choice of the form in which a decision table is formulated depends on the problem, available software system, etc.

Solution for the above mentioned Question

Conditions	Rule 1	Rule 2	Rule 3	Rule 4	Rule 5
C1: Individual Customer?	Y	Y	Y	N	N
C2: Number of Books	>=10	>5 and <10	<=5	>10 &<25	>=25
Actions					
A1: 10% Discount given			X	X	
A2: 15% Discount given		X			Y
A3: 20% Discount given	X				

Structured English: Structured English is similar to a programming language such as Pascal, which does not have strict syntax rules in comparison to other programming languages. The intention is only to give precise description of a process in a simple English language which should be understandable to the user. In case of structured English, the following conventions are used in writing structured English process description:

- Imperative Statements: Keywords
 - Arithmetic and relational operation: (+, *, -, /)(LT means less than, LE means less than equal To, GT means Greater than, GE means Greater than equal To, EQ means Equal To ,NE means Not Equal To)
 - Decision Structures: (If..then..Else) (Case) Statements
 - Repetition: Looping (For, While, Do while)
- The point to remember is to make individual procedures simple, so that a non-computer specialist can easily read and understand the procedure.

Notation	Meaning
LT	Less than
LE	Less than Equal to
GT	Greater than
GE	Greater than Equal to
EQ	Equal To
NE	Not Equal To

Solution for the above mentioned Question

```
If Customer EQ Individual
Then
    If Book_Purchase GE 10
        Then
            20% Discount
        End If
    End If
    If Book_Purchase GE 5 AND LE 10
        Then
            15% Discount
        End If
    End If
    If Book_Purchase LE 5
        Then
            20% Discount
        End If
Else
    If Customer EQ Librarian
        Then
            If Book_Purchase GE 25
                Then
                    15% Discount
                End If
            End If
            If Book_Purchase LT 10 AND LT 25
                Then
                    10% Discount
                End If
            End If
            If Book_Purchase LE 10
                Then
                    Discount EQ NIL
                End If
            End If
End IF
```

Data Dictionary: Defines each term (element) encountered during the analysis and design of a new system. It is a special kind of dictionary which contains all the information about the data of a system. It forms an integral part of structured specification. It is only a documentation of data. The important components of data dictionary are:

- Data Element: Smallest unit of data that is meaningful or pieces of data which can't be meaningfully decomposed are known as data elements. For each data element the data dictionary should hold the following description:
 - Name
 - Description
 - Name of the relative data element
 - Length and type of data element
 - Codification Structure
 - Range of value and their meaning
- Data Structure: They are made up data element or a combination of both data element and data structure. They should contain the following information:
 - Name

- Description
 - Included data elements and data structure with brief description
- Data Flow: Contains the volume of flow (Start, End) point with the description of data.
 - Data Store: Additional information on the volume and data flows to and from it is also usually recorded.
 - Process: Documenting the processes include documenting name and brief description of the process followed by a process description. The entry for each and every process forms a part of data dictionary.

Apart from a name and number the Entry contains the process description

What the process has to do?

Process Specification should be specified in such a way that they are both logically correct and easy to understand.

Fig 1.10 Example of Data Dictionary

Data Structure Notation: They are expressed in terms of a related set of components. Convention used in depicting data structures are:

{ } Any one option can be selected. For Eg:

(n-m) Specifies number of occurrence from n to m times. Lower limit is must whereas upper limit is optional. For Eg: Item-details(1-3)

[] Enclosed Component is optional. For Eg: If the purchase order need not be present then it will be represented as [Person Sign]

For Eg: A table that contains employee details

Field Name	Data Type	Field Size for display	Description	Example
Employee Number	Integer	10	Unique ID of each employee	1645000001
Name	Text	20	Name of the employee	David Heston
Date of Birth	Date/Time	10	DOB of Employee	08/03/1995
Phone Number	Integer	10	Phone number of employee	6583648648

Structured Design: It is a data-flow based methodology which approach begins with a system specification that identifies I/O and describes the functional aspects of the system. Structured design partitions a program into small, independent modules. It's an attempt to

minimize complexity and make a problem manageable by subdividing it into smaller segments., which is called modularization or decomposition which is discussed in next section in detail.

Fig 1.11 Structured Design Method

Structured Chart: A top-down modular design tool which shows the breakdown of a system to its lowest manageable levels with the help of graphical representation of:

- Squares represent different modules in the system
- Lines that connect modules which shows the relationship between modules.

The documentation tool for structured design is the hierarchy or structure chart. The use of only two graphical elements forces the chart designer to provide only the essential information. A structure chart is a tree of sub-routines in a program which indicates the interconnections among the sub-routines. The sub-routines should be labeled with the same name used in the pseudo code.

Fig 1.12 Example of Structured Chart in Programming

A structure chart depicts:

- the size and complexity of the system, and
- number of readily identifiable functions and modules within each function and
- Whether each identifiable function is a manageable entity or should be broken down into smaller components.

Solution for the above mentioned Question

Module Specification: Any system in its entirety (as a whole) performs a number of functions. A system has to be divided into programs containing one or more modules. A great care has to be taken while dividing the system into programs or module. A software system cannot be modular by simply breaking it into a set of module, for modularity each module needs to support a well-defined abstraction and have a clear interface through which it can interact with other modules.

To segment the system, the designer examines the entire system to decide the program and module boundaries. The main concepts here are the:

Coupling is between the modules and Cohesion within the module

Coupling is the measure of or degree of interdependence between modules. Two modules with high coupling are strongly inter-connected and thus depend on each other. Modules should be **loosely coupled** which means that modules should have little dependence on other modules in a system.

Fig 1.13 Coupling

Types of Coupling	Description	Example
Data	communicate by passing only data components are independent to each other and communicating through data. Therefore, it doesn't contain tramp data.	customer billing system parameter passing
Stamp	complete data structure is passed from one module to another module. Therefore, it involves tramp data.	.
Control	modules communicate by passing control information	Sort() that takes comparison function as an argument
External	the modules depend on other modules	protocol, external file, device format, etc
Common	modules have shared data	global data structures
Content	one module can modify the data of another module or control flow is passed from one module to the other module. Worst form of module	

Cohesion is the property that specifies how tightly bound the elements of a module are. Thus, it is a measure of the degree to which elements of the module are functionally related. A cohesive module performs a single task within software procedure requiring little interaction with procedure being performed in other part of the program. Modules should be **highly cohesive** which means that modules should carry out a single processing function.

Fig 1.14 Cohesion

Types of Cohesion	Description	Example
Functional	Ideal Situation. Degree of cohesion- HIGHEST The elements of a module are functionally grouped into a logical unit and they work together as a logical unit.	Sort an array..sort() Search()
Sequential	An output of some data becomes the input for other element. Occurs naturally in programming language.	Search array for a certain name. Place the name in another array and sort the array. Change the name from last-first to first-last. Print first-last name.
Communicational	Two elements operate on the same input data or contribute towards the same output data	update record in the database and send it to the printer Transaction File
Procedural	Ensure the order of execution	calculate student GPA, print student record,
Temporal	Statements are grouped into a procedure and executed together during the same time-frame	Init() Component that is used to initialize a set of objects.
Logical	elements are logically related and not functionally..AVOIDED	
Coincidental	The elements are not related. breaking a module into smaller modules Accidental and the worst form of cohesion.	print next line reverse the characters of a string in a single component

The designer aims at minimizing coupling and maximizing cohesion to get a modular design. Such a design ensures that each module perform a specific function and can be developed relatively independently by programmers. Thus, a good design is characterized by low coupling that is low interdependence between the modules and high cohesion that is high inter- relationship within the elements of a single module.

Conclusion: System analysis is the detailed evaluation of a particular system to identify areas for improvements and make any further changes if necessary which includes: gathering the company requirements and to research the path that is to be taken to effect these requirements. The ultimate target is to have a fully operational system in place which provides efficiency and reliability to the company. When a system analysis is properly performed, it ensures that the correct path is taken with regards to applications which help

to minimize errors thereby reducing future IT requirements for fixing problems. System analysis allows for better management policy through changing the software to suit any business changes which indicate that the final product will be totally controllable. The quality of the systems is ensured through the checking of the system on regular basis through system analysis. A risk assessment is carried out to evaluate all the negative effects on the processes. It can also be used to improve procedures in handling accounts receivable, in preparing and implementing a budget and in scheduling regular or one-time projects. The benefits of an integrated system include higher levels of quality control and lower production costs by streamlining data processing and production processes. The main objectives of business are to make money. An obvious advantage of using system analysis and design is to improve business quality thereby increasing profits.

Although System analysis offers a wide range of benefits it might also have some limitation. One of the main drawbacks which are mostly overlooked is the risk of too much analyzing which may be costly and time consuming. It is therefore part of the analyst's job to find the right balance.

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Payments Banks In India – A Study Of National Electronic Fund Transfer (NEFT)

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Abstract

Payments banks are latest addition in financial inclusion. Payments bank is like any other banks which are established for low income group of people and it is use for payments of utility bills, mobile recharge, small savings, retail payments, third party fund transfer and all remittance services, all other services like issue of Debit Card/ATM etc. There is restriction on lending service. Aim of the research paper is to study the concept and framework of Payments bank and National Electronic Fund Transfer services provided by Payments banks. This study based on the period of 23 Months that is from November, 2016 to September, 2018. Under this period six Payments banks are established and started their operations. This study based on secondary source of data. Study concludes that during the study period debit/outward and credit /inward transactions are rapidly increased except in case of Airtel payments Bank. Growth rate of NEFT transactions in payments banks are highly appreciated.

Keywords: Financial inclusion, NEFT and Payments Bank

1.0 Introduction

There are two kinds of banking licenses granted by the Reserve Bank of India, Universal Bank License and Differentiated Bank License. Main aim of Differentiated Banks (niche banks) is fulfill the needs of a certain demographic segment of the population which is not covered by other banks. Payments Banks and Small Finance Banks are examples of differentiated banks in India. Banks are working as the backbone of modern business. Development of any economy depends upon the banking system. In present scenario business models are changing therefore up gradation in banking services and new digital modes of payment system is very important. Most of the transactions are made with the help of internet banking. Generally Most of the people prefer NEFT as mode of payment for retail payments and fund transfer purpose. Payments Bank is also known as Mobile Bank. All transactions can be made with help of mobile phone and no need to go bank branch.

1.1 Payments Bank

A payments bank operating in small scale it is also a Bank like any other bank, but without involving any credit risk. In simple words, Payments bank can offer most of the banking operations except credit card & loans. Payments banks can accept up to Rs. 1 lac as demand deposits, they can offer remittance services, transfers / mobile payments / purchases and other banking services like ATM / Debit cards, net banking and third party fund transfers.

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1.2 Definition

The Reserve Bank of India Issues licenses to entities to carry on the business of banking and other business in which banking companies may engage, as defined and described in section 5 (b) and 6 (1) (a) to (o) of the Banking Regulation Act, 1949, respectively.

1.3 Description

Reserve Bank of India formed a committee to study, Comprehensive financial services for small businesses and low income households, headed by Dr. Nachiket Mor on September 2013. Objectives of the committee were to achieving financial inclusion and increased access to financial services. The committee submitted its report to RBI in January 2014. One of the key suggestions of the committee was to introduce specialized banks or 'payments bank' to cater to the lower income groups and small businesses so that by 1st January 2016, each and every resident of India can have a global bank account.

- Reserve Bank of India, in 2015, gave licenses to eleven (11) companies to open payments bank.
- The aimed of the banks were to reach out to the unbanked population of the country, many of which live in very small towns and villages.

1.4 Characteristics of Payment Banks

1. Mobile banks: in fact payment banks will be mobile only bank, but they will not have full-fledged branches like any other banks. The account holders will be able to operate their accounts using the mobile applications.
2. Small Savings: In Payment Banks account you can deposits Up to Rs 1 lakh.
3. ATM and debit cards: Payment Banks can issue the ATM and Debit card to their account holders they can withdraw amount from any ATM across the India.
4. Mobile Services: customer of payment bank can make a payment of bills and it allows transfers and remittance of money through the mobile, it offers services such as cashless and chequeless purchases. Transactions through a phone, and money transfer directly to bank accounts at nearly no cost being a part of the gateway that connects banks.
5. Saving account and interest: Payments bank account holders will earn interest on the balance in their savings account like any normal bank account, For example, Airtel offers rate of interest 7.25% to its savings account holder. The interest rates are expected to be higher as the bank has less infrastructure cost.

1.5 Payments Banks in India

1) Airtel Payments Banks Limited 2) Paytm Payments Bank Limited 3) Fino Payments Bank Limited 4) Aditya Birla Idea Payments Bank Limited 5) Jio Payments Bank Limited 6) India Post Payments Bank Limited 7) National Securities Depository Limited 8) Vodafone M-Pesa 9) Tech Mahindra 10) Cholamandalam Finance 11) Dilip Shanghvi. Out of 11 three applicants cancelled their license. 1) Tech Mahindra 2) Cholamandalam Finance 3) Dilip Shanghvi. IDFC Bank and Telenor JV, have already dropped out. At presently Airtel M-Commerce Services Limited and Kotak Mahindra Bank Limited collaborated and start a Airtel Bank Limited. Payments banks do not have the full-fledged services of a regular bank. Their services are limited as following.

1.6 Payments Banks can offer Services

- They can accept deposits up to Rs 1,00,000 per account
- Establish Remittances and Bill payments like utility bills
- Payments banks can issue Debit Cards / ATM Cards
- Mobile Banking is possible through payments banks

➤ E-commerce – Online Shopping payments

1.7 Payments Banks commenced their Operations

1. Airtel Payments Banks Limited 2) Paytm Payments Bank Limited 3) Fino Payments Bank Limited 4) Aditya Birla Idea Payments Bank Limited 5) Jio Payments Bank Limited 6) India Post Payments Bank Limited. Services offering by these Payments Banks are Saving Account, Current Account, Debit & ATM Card, Payments (Utility bill payments, Mobile Recharge), NEFT, IMPS, UPI, USSD, AEPS, POS, BHIM, Wallets & Insurance etc.

1.8 NEFT

National Electronic Fund Transfer is used for retail payments. It is nation-wide payment system. Under this individual can electronically transfer funds from any bank branch to any individual having an account with any other bank branch in the country participating in the scheme.

2.0 Objectives Of The Study

1. To know the concept of Payments Bank in India & growth trend of NEFT transactions in Payments Banks.

3.0 Methodology

This study is analytical in nature. In this study all payments banks are selected for study except those banks that are not yet start operations. This study is based on secondary source of data and data was collected from RBI & NCPI websites and other sources that are journals and magazines etc. Data was analyzed with the help of statistical techniques i.e. Mean, Standard deviation, Co-efficient of variation and Annual compound growth rate.

3.1 Period of the study: this study is based on period of 23 Months i.e. November 2016 to Sept 2018. In these meantime payments banks started their operations in different time period.

3.2 Scope of the study: This study covers only NEFT transactions of the Payments banks across the India during the period of Nov. 2016 to Sept. 2018. This study covers the transactions of Airtel Payments Bank Limited, Paytm Payments Bank Limited, Fino Payments Bank Limited, Aditya Birla Idea Payments Bank Limited and Jio Payments Bank Limited.

3.3 Limitations of the study: This study is confined with NEFT transaction of the Payments Banks of India. This study is based on published data. India Post Payments banks not considered for study due late starts of operations. This bank commenced the operations in the month of September, 2018.

4.0 Data Analysis

Table -1: NEFT Transaction of Airtel Payments Bank Limited

Month	OUTWARD / DEBIT		INWARD / CREDIT	
	No. of Transactions	Rs. (Million)	No. of Transactions	Rs. (Million)
Nov -2016	19	0.88	36	0.01
Dec	494	131.72	109	0.79
Jan- 2017	7669	670.65	1301	4.95
Feb	21447	623.61	7367	11.9
Mar	27561	652.57	10806	22.06
Apr	12334	389.56	6905	15.98

May	6306	264.51	5340	13.31
Jun	3493	255.22	6363	16.97
Jul	1870	153.14	6441	23.24
Aug	1702	780.78	6671	25.42
Sept	2119	1216.67	10026	37.86
Oct	2251	920.02	12374	35.89
Nov	61965	4559.88	27507	79.04
Dec	202545	10429.66	114748	74.49
Jan-2018	311997	19956.49	227928	78.55
Feb	123187	18687.0	70406	63.2
Mar	48102	20145.52	25185	43.51
Apr	33342	17436.59	17304	2007.34
May	36798	22475.67	21442	3312.74
Jun	52597	19889.65	29769	10304.88
Jul	75378	20931.40	46198	8838.30
Aug	62778	22262.01	30170	7941.89
Sept	106861	19995.88	65602	10315.97
Average	52296.30	8818.65	32608.61	1881.23
S.D	75246.69	9622.58	50736.55	3614.58
CV	143.89%	109.12%	155.59%	192.14%
CAGR	0.02%	0.04%	0.04%	0.42%

(Source: Reserve Bank of India)

Chart -1: NEFT Transactions in Airtel Payments Bank Limited

Table -1 shows the NEFT transactions of Airtel Payments Bank Limited in terms of volume and value of transactions during the month of Nov.2016 to Sept.2018. Airtel Payments Bank is a first bank who commenced the operations in the month of November 2016. During the study period it was found that average numbers of Outward / Debit transactions were 52296.30 and in terms of value Rs. 8818.61 million. In case of Inward / Credit numbers of transactions were 32608.61 and in terms of value Rs. 1881.23. Compound annual growth rate in transactions were 0.02% and 0.04% in terms volume and value respectively. It implies that growth rate was slow during the study period. During the study period co-efficient of

variation is more in case of Inward/ Credit transactions. Highest transactions were recorded in the month of December January, 2018 then after transactions were declined.

Table -2: NEFT Transactions of Paytm Payments Bank Limited

Month	OUTWARD / DEBIT		INWARD / CREDIT	
	No. of Transactions	Rs. (Million)	No. Of Transactions	Rs. (Million)
2017-Jun	1	0.00	6	450.01
Jul	44	16424.93	50	23533.41
Aug	48	18942.81	232	33740.70
Sep	505	19777.59	8635	35373.31
Oct	537	25393.78	9987	39325.10
Nov	878	23768.09	18618	38611.58
Dec	1595	26925.68	29545	43275.82
2018-Jan	5758	33691.60	172897	54629.60
Feb	4832	32266.3	121559	49669.0
Mar	6401	37511.62	138732	54345.98
Apr	8391	38995.75	155349	60287.62
May	15195	49377.90	246146	72787.48
Jun	20750	54309.91	284901	71519.90
Jul	26231	62985.30	331681	79711.80
Aug	30158	62936.93	347560	79968.81
Sep	59816	62611.63	323872	78960.30
Average	11321.25	35369.98	136860.62	51011.89
S.D	16243.95	18758.35	133469.14	22590.16
CV	143.48%	53.03%	97.52%	44.28%
CAGR	108.19%	285.87%	106.77%	41.13%

(Source: Reserve Bank of India)

Chart -2: NEFT Transactions in Paytm Payments Bank Limited

Table 2 reveals NEFT transactions of Paytm Payments Banks Limited. Paytm Payments Bank is second Payments Bank after Airtel. Paytm commenced the operations in June, 2017. During the study period it was found that average numbers of Outward/Debit transactions

were 11321.25 and in terms of value it was Rs. 35369.98 Millions and Compound annual growth rate was 108.19% and 285.87% respectively. In case of Inward/Credit, average numbers of transactions were 136861 and in terms of value it was Rs.51011.89 Millions and Compound annual growth rate was 106.77% and 41.13% respectively. Coefficient of variation of Debit transactions were 143.48% and 53.03% for volume and value respectively. Paytm's transactions were growing continuously and significantly. Paytm inward/ Credit transactions were more than outward/Debit transactions.

Table -3: NEFT Transactions of Fino Payments Bank Limited

Month	OUTWARD / DEBIT		INWARD / CREDIT	
	No. of Transactions	Rs. (Million)	No. of Transactions	Rs. (Million)
2017-Jul	17	0.01	22	0.04
Aug	10803	55.06	455	2.32
Sep	63477	363.22	5210	46.99
Oct	62076	391.02	6855	101.32
Nov	112347	689.75	11111	259.62
Dec	151917	854.87	21001	1067.42
2018-Jan	154879	939.99	31709	1125.81
Feb	132507	904.3	60747	2499.7
Mar	156953	1132.74	80931	2791.89
Apr	258393	1578.37	102755	2441.36
May	295719	1977.21	107126	3404.53
Jun	309664	2123.80	89506	3955.96
Jul	309452	2011.52	79461	4588.44
Aug	283646	2178.50	74434	5014.22
Sep	275868	2088.50	67700	4635.11
Average	171847.867	1152.59	49268.2	2128.98
S.D	109977.85	784.53	39603.07	1878.87
CV	64.00%	68.07%	80.38%	88.25%
CAGR	99.86%	134.80%	77.48%	130.33%

(Source: Reserve Bank of India)

Chart -3: NEFT Transactions in Fino Payments Bank Limited

Table3 reveals NEFT transactions of Fino Payments Bank Limited it commenced the operations in the July, 2017. It is a third Payments Bank incorporated as Payments Bank. During the study period it was found that Average numbers of Debit / Outward transactions were 171848 and in terms of value Rs. 1152.59. Compound annual growth rate was 99.86% and 134.80% in volume and value respectively. It implies that during the study period every month NEFT transactions were increased by 100%. Coefficient of variation is 64.00% and 68.07% respectively. In case of Credit / Inward transactions average was 49268 in volume and Rs. 2128.98 in value. Compound annual growth rate was 77.48% and 134.80% in volume and value and coefficient of variations were 80.38% and 88.25% respectively.

Table -4: NEFT Transactions of Aditya Birla Idea Payments Bank Limited

Month	OUTWARD / DEBIT		INWARD / CREDIT	
	No. of Transactions	Rs. (Million)	No. of Transactions	Rs. (Million)
2018-Feb	2	0.0	2	0.0
Mar	35	0.04	138	3.23
Apr	110	0.42	394	13.83
May	2264	26.47	2673	156.03
Jun	4231	49.61	4886	335.32
Jul	4371	78.16	7010	625.26
Aug	3638	92.72	8233	740.04
Sep	4308	44.16	8989	845.94
Average	2369.87	36.44	4040.62	339.96
S.D	2035.73	36.23	3747.44	351.86
CV	85.90%	99.41%	92.74%	103.50%
CAGR	199.35%	478.37%	232.52%	860.70%

(Source: Reserve Bank of India)

Chart - 4: NEFT Transactions in Aditya Birla Idea Payments Bank Limited

Table 4 represents NEFT transactions of Aditya Birla Idea Payments Bank Limited it is fourth Payments Bank and commenced operations in February, 2018. During the period from commencement of operations NEFT average numbers of Outward/ Debit transactions were 2370 and in terms of money Rs. 36.44 Millions. CAGR were 199.35% or 200% and 478.37% in volume and value respectively that is very significant figures. Coefficient of variation of Debit transactions volume and values were 85.90% and 99.41% respectively in different months its shows big variation. In case of Credit / Inward transactions Average volume and values were 4041 and Rs. 339.96 respectively. CAGR of Debit transactions in terms of volume and value were 232.52% and 860.70% respectively. It means that growth of Credit / Inward transactions were more compare to Outward/ Debit transactions and rate of growth also significant. Coefficient of variation in Credit / Inward transactions in volume and values were 92.74% and 103.50% respectively.

Table -5: NEFT Transactions of Jio Payments Bank Limited

Month	OUTWARD / DEBIT		INWARD / CREDIT	
	No. of Transactions	Rs. (Million)	No. of Transactions	Rs. (Million)
2018-Apr	4756	0.11	140	7.18
May	3479	0.22	171	57.82
Jun	3576	8.69	237	87.95
July	1472	2.81	199	34.25
August	372	0.28	197	30.06
Sept	252	0.21	190	25.64
Average	2317.83	2.05	189	40.48
S.D	1878.58	3.41	32.23	28.39
CV	81.05%	166.39%	17.05%	70.14%
CAGR	-44.43%	14.30%	6.30%	28.99%

(Source: Reserve Bank of India)

Chart -5: NEFT Transactions of Jio Payments Bank Limited

Table 5 represents the NEFT transactions of Jio Payments Bank Limited. Jio Payments Bank commenced the operations in April, 2018. It is fifth Payments bank in India. During the period from commencement of operations Average Outward / Debit numbers of transactions were 2318 and in terms of value it was Rs. 2.05 millions. CAGR of Debit transactions in volume and values were -44.43% and 14.30% respectively. It implies that numbers of transactions were decreased every month whereas value was increased compare to base period but it is not satisfactory level of growth. Coefficient of variation in volume and value were 81.05% and 166.39% respectively. In case of Inward / Credit transactions average numbers were 189 and value is Rs. 40.48 millions. CAGR in volume and value were 6.30% and 28.99% respectively. CAGR is not significantly increased. CV was 17.05% and 70.14% it implies that it is small variation.

5.0 Conclusion

This study conclude that Payment banks are providing services like payments and remittance services and small savings accounts to especially low-income households, migrant labors, small businesses, unorganized sector entities and other users. They will not lend to customers. These banks focus and serve the needs of a certain demographic segment of the population. NEFT transactions in volume and value are growing continuously in Paytm Payments Bank, Fino Patyments Bank and Aditya Birla Idea Payments Bank. In case of Airtel Payments bank it is noticed that growth rate is very slow and it is first Payments Bank of India. Transactions of Jio Payments bank decreased during the study period it shows the negative growth. It is observed that Credit / Inward transactions in value are more than the Debit / Outward transaction of all Payments Banks except Airtel Payments bank.

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Application of Hadamard Matrices in Coding Theory

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Abstract

Hadamard matrices are a special class of square matrices with entries 1 and -1 only. They have many applications in Coding theory, Physical Sciences, Neuron networks and Computer Science. Therefore, the concentration of this paper is on the applications in Coding theory; in particular, the way of construction of binary codes and optimal codes is discussed. A code of with 2 symbols is called a binary code. If in a sequence, all code words have same length, then it is called a block code. In general, all codes will be considered over the field F_2 containing 2 elements. A code with a set of S code words of length m with r symbols and Hamming distance d is denoted by $(m, S, d; r)$. This code is called optimal if S is as large as possible for given m, d and r . For optimizing a code, the help of Hadamard matrices is required. Therefore, the link between the existence of Hadamard matrices and the construction of optimal codes is studied.

Keywords: Hadamard Matrix; Binary code; Optimal code; Hamming Distance;

1. Introduction

To transmit information secretly from one place to another place, it is sent in a sequences of symbols. This process is known as 'coding'. The symbols which are used in this process are called 'coding symbols. A sequence of these symbols is known as 'code word'. A code word of two symbols is called a 'binary code'. Though there exist many types of codes, we are interested in 'binary codes' only because it corresponds to two states of a switch which are 'on' and 'off'. In a sequence, if all code words are of the same length, then it is called a 'block code'. In general, a finite field of order q will be considered as a set of symbols, where q is some integral power a prime number p . Throughout this work, we consider the field F_2 of order 2 containing the elements 0, 1. We form n -tuples by using the symbols 0, 1 as blocks, and we say that the length of these blocks is n . The Hamming distance between two code words is defined as the number components in which the words differ. The minimum Hamming distance d between all the words of a code is called the d -code.

2. Main Results

Definition 1: A code with a set of S code words of length m with r symbols and Hamming distance d is denoted by $(m, S, d; r)$.

Definition 2: A code is called 'optimal' if S is as large as possible for a given m, d and r .

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In view of optimizing codes, Plotkin [2] found the bounds for binary codes which are given in the following Lemma.

Lemma 3: If S is the number of code words, m is the length of code word and d is the Hamming distance, then the bounds for S are given by

(i) $S \leq 2 \left\lfloor \frac{d}{2d - m} \right\rfloor$ if d is even and $d \leq m < 2d$;

(ii) $S \leq 2m$ if d is even and $m = 2d$;

(iii) $S \leq 2 \left\lfloor \frac{d+1}{2d+1-m} \right\rfloor$ if d is odd and $d \leq m < 2d+1$;

$S \leq 2m+2$ if d is odd and $m = 2d+1$;

Proof: Refer to [2].

Lemma 4: If $C_1(m_1, S_1, d_1; 2)$, $C_2(m_2, S_2, d_2; 2)$ be two codes such that $S_2 \geq S_1$, then a code $C(m, S_1, d; 2)$ with $m = a_1 m_1 + a_2 m_2$ and $d \geq a_1 d_1 + a_2 d_2$ can be constructed from C_1 and C_2 for any values of a_1 and a_2

Proof: To construct the code C , paste a_1 copies of C_1 side by side, followed by a_2 copies of C_2 side by side, and omit the last $S_2 - S_1$ rows of C_2 to obtain the code C .

Definition 5: The code obtained in the Lemma 4 is called the composition of two codes and it is denoted by $a_1 C_1 \oplus a_2 C_2$.

Towards the construction of optimal binary codes which meet the Plotkin bounds, we have

Theorem 4: If H is a normalized Hadamard matrix of order $4k$, then the following binary codes $(4k, 8k, 2k; 2)$; $(4k-1, 4k, 2k; 2)$; $(4k-1, 8k, 2k-1; 2)$; $(4k-2, 2k, 2k; 2)$ are optimal.

Proof: Let H be a normalized Hadamard matrix of order $4k$. Then the $8k$ rows of the two matrices H and $\frac{1}{2}(J-H)$, where J is the matrix obtained from H by replacing 0 by 2 as $0 \equiv 2 \pmod{2}$ in the field F_2 , form the code $(4k, 8k, 2k; 2)$. For second and third codes, consider the matrix K by deleting the first column of H . Then, the $4k$ rows of the matrix $\frac{1}{2}(J+K)$, where J is the matrix obtained from H by deleting the first column, and the $8k$ rows of the matrix $\frac{1}{2}(J-K)$, where J is the matrix obtained from H by deleting first column and replacing 0 by 2 as $0 \equiv 2 \pmod{2}$ in the field F_2 , form the codes $(4k-1, 4k, 2k; 2)$ and $(4k-1, 8k, 2k-1; 2)$. For the last code, consider the matrix L by deleting all rows of K which start with 1 and delete the first column from the resultant matrix. Then the $2k$ rows of the matrix $\frac{1}{2}(J+L)$ form the code $(4k-2, 2k, 2k; 2)$.

Example 5: If we take $k=3$, the order of the Hadamard matrix is $4k=12$.

Then the following two matrices give the code $(4k, 8k, 2k; 2) = (12, 24, 6; 2)$

```

1 1 1 1 1 1 1 1 1 1 1 1 1 1 1 1 1 1 1 1 1
1 0 1 0 1 1 1 0 0 0 1 0 0 1 0 1 1 1 0 0 0 1 0
1 0 0 1 0 1 1 1 0 0 0 1 0 0 1 0 1 1 1 0 0 0 1
1 1 0 0 1 0 1 1 1 0 0 0 1 0 0 1 0 1 1 1 0 0 0
1 0 1 0 0 1 0 1 1 1 0 0 0 1 0 0 1 0 1 1 1 0 0
1 0 0 1 0 0 1 0 1 1 1 0 0 0 1 0 0 1 0 1 1 1 0
1 0 0 0 1 0 0 1 0 1 1 1 0 0 0 1 0 0 1 0 1 1 1
1 1 0 0 0 1 0 0 1 0 1 1 1 0 0 0 1 0 0 1 0 1 1
1 1 1 0 0 0 1 0 0 1 0 1 1 1 0 0 0 1 0 0 1 0 1
1 1 1 1 0 0 0 1 0 0 1 0 1 1 1 0 0 0 1 0 0 1 0
1 0 1 1 1 0 0 0 1 0 0 1 0 1 1 1 0 0 0 1 0 0 1
1 1 0 1 1 1 0 0 0 1 0 0 1 0 1 1 1 0 0 0 1 0 0

```

The following two matrices give the code $(4k-1, 8k, 2k-1; 2) = (11, 24, 5; 2)$

```

1 1 1 1 1 1 1 1 1 1 1 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0
0 1 0 1 1 1 0 0 0 1 0 1 0 1 0 0 0 1 1 1 0 1
0 0 1 0 1 1 1 0 0 0 1 1 1 0 1 0 0 0 1 1 1 0
1 0 0 1 0 1 1 1 0 0 0 0 1 1 0 1 0 0 0 1 1 1
0 1 0 0 1 0 1 1 1 0 0 1 0 1 1 0 1 0 0 0 1 1
0 0 1 0 0 1 0 1 1 1 0 1 1 0 1 1 0 1 0 0 0 1
0 0 0 1 0 0 1 0 1 1 1 1 1 1 0 1 1 0 1 0 0 0
1 0 0 0 1 0 0 1 0 1 1 0 1 1 1 0 1 1 0 1 0 0
1 1 0 0 0 1 0 0 1 0 1 0 0 1 1 1 0 1 1 0 1 0
1 1 1 0 0 0 1 0 0 1 0 0 0 0 1 1 1 0 1 1 0 1
0 1 1 1 0 0 0 1 0 0 1 1 0 0 0 1 1 1 0 1 1 0
1 0 1 1 1 0 0 0 1 0 0 0 1 0 0 0 1 1 1 0 1 1

```

The following matrix gives the code $(4k-1, 4k, 2k; 2) = (11, 12, 6; 2)$

```

0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0
0 1 0 1 0 0 0 1 1 1 0 1
0 1 1 0 1 0 0 0 1 1 1 0
0 0 1 1 0 1 0 0 0 1 1 1
0 1 0 1 1 0 1 0 0 0 1 1
0 1 1 0 1 1 0 1 0 0 0 1
0 1 1 1 0 1 1 0 1 0 0 0
0 0 1 1 1 0 1 1 0 1 0 0
0 0 0 1 1 1 0 1 1 0 1 0
0 0 0 0 1 1 1 0 1 1 0 1
0 1 0 0 0 1 1 1 0 1 1 0
0 0 1 0 0 0 1 1 1 0 1 1

```

The following matrix gives the code $(4k - 2, 2k, 2k; 2) = (10, 6, 6; 2)$

```
1 0 1 1 1 0 0 0 1 0
0 1 0 1 1 1 0 0 0 1
1 0 0 1 0 1 1 1 0 0
0 1 0 0 1 0 1 1 1 0
0 0 1 0 0 1 0 1 1 1
1 1 1 0 0 0 1 0 0 1
```

3. Conclusion

In a similar manner, other codes can also be constructed by using Hadamard matrices. It is possible by making the code words to be the vectors in the linear span of the code over the field F_2 . The code $(32, 64, 16; 2)$ derived from the Hadamard matrix of order 32 is used in the Mariner telemetry system.

4. Acknowledgement

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A Study On Customer Relationship Management Practices In Banking Sector; With Special Reference To Service Co-Operative Banks In Malappuram Districts

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Abstract

Customer relationship management is a comprehensive strategy and process of acquiring, retaining and partnering with selective customers to create to superior value for the company and customers, it involves the integration of marketing , sales ,customer service, and the supply chain functions of the organization to achieve greater efficiencies and effectiveness in delivering customer value.

CRM has been one of the most talked subjects recently in corporate circles. It is a strategy used to learn more about customer's needs and behaviors in order to develop stronger relationship with them. Over all good customer relationship are at the heart of business success. The concept of CRM has been a core concept which has attracted all facets of business. CRM has relevant and demanding application in service marketing. Retail banking and financial services have also not been an exception to this phenomenon. CRM in the field of retail banking has attracted much of researchers and practitioners. There has been continuous research in the field of CRM and its application in banking and financial services. But in india , research in the field of relationship marketing has not taken off to the expectation and is still in the infant stage when compared to other countries in the west. The main objective of the study is to study the customer relationship Management practice that is implemented at customer level and to know the satisfaction level of the customers towards CRM practices. For this purpose a sample of 100 respondents were collected from the respondents and the conclusion is that the study report can be used as a supplementary factor to know about the perception of customers about banking services

Keywords: CRM, DEPOSITS,SERVICES,E-BANKING ,FINANCIAL PRODUCTS

Introduction

CRM, or Customer relationship management, is a number of strategies and technologies that are used to build stronger relationships between companies and their customers.

There are a number of reasons why CRM has become so important in the last 10 years. The competition in the global market has become highly competitive, and it has become easier for customers to switch companies if they are not happy with the service they receive. One of the primary goals of CRM is to maintain clients. When it is used effectively, a company will be able to build a relationship with their customers that can last a lifetime.

Today, customers have more power in deciding their bank of choice. Consequently, keeping existing customers, as well as attracting new ones, is a critical concern for banks. Customer satisfaction is an important variable in evaluation and control in a bank marketing management. Poor customer satisfaction will lead to a decline in customer loyalty, and given the extended offerings from the competitors, customers can easily switch banks. Banks need

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to leverage effectively on their customer relationships and make better use of customer information across the institution.

Customer support is directly connected to CRM. If a company fails to provide quality customer support, they have also failed with their CRM system. When a customer makes complaints they must be handled quickly and efficiently

Statement Of Problem

Today many businesses such as banks, insurance companies, and other service providers realized the importance of customer relationship management (CRM) and its potential to help them to acquire new customers, retain existing customers and maximize their life time value.

People generally approach private bank and public bank for banking services. The customers in cooperative banks are less than that of other banks. Private and public bank provide comparatively better services than cooperative bank. The customers may not be satisfied with the services provided by the cooperative bank. The reason for less number of customers in cooperative bank may be the poor customer relationship management

Objectives Of The Study

- To analyze the CRM process in service cooperative banks
- To identify the role of CRM in customer retention
- To study the perception of bank officials /management towards the implementation of CRM in the bank.
- To examine the role of IT system/ technological infrastructure in effective CRM in bank
- To make few suggestions for improving customer relationship.

Scope And Significance Of Study

Customers support is an important factor in the success of any bank. This customer support is directly related to CRM. If a company fails to provide quality customer support, they have also failed with their CRM system. Managing customer relationship is important for the bank. CRM is a business strategy in banks to create good culture among society and markets. CRM helps to build internal and external relationship that increases profit margin and productivity. The CRM in the bank stores all customer transaction. Customer did not want to maintain the records. By implementing CRM , it will close the gap between banking organization and customer acquisition, growth and retention

CRM provides convenient and speedy process of transaction between banks and its customers. It can easily maintain its existing customers and to create new customers with the help of CRM. Customer satisfaction is one of the growing challenges to build up a successful business. Banking organization facing problems like global competition. Banking organization facing problems like global competition for deposit, loan and underwriting fees. In order to meet these obstacles strong CRM is required.

Variable Of The Study

- Income
- Occupation
- Facilities and services
- Benefits
- Customer dealings
- Rate of interest
- Security requirements
- Employees attitude

- Transaction time
- Transaction cost
- Amenities provided
- E-banking facilities

Research Methodology

Research design

This study is designed as a descriptive research using primary data and secondary data

Sample survey

Sample survey has conducted among bank and customers, who are selected randomly.

Sample size

Samples of 100 customers were selected randomly on convenient basis.

Collection of data

Both primary and secondary data were used for the study. Primary data were collected through questionnaires from customers and employees of the bank. Secondary data were collected from published records and websites

Tool for analysis and presentation

Statistical tool used for analyzing data is percentage. Various tools used for presentation of data are tables, Graphs and diagrams.

Tools for data collection

The data required for the study is collected by using questionnaire

Limitations Of The Study

- Time constraints – the time duration for doing the study is very limited
- The sample size may not be adequate to represent the total population concerned
- Illiteracy of respondents
- Difficulty in getting reliable data.

Review of Literature

Bergenfield (2010) Businesses are in a constant race to increase profits, keep current customers and gain or poach new ones, competing for customers on a globalised market like never before. One of the many sets of tools aimed at aiding the interaction between supplier and customer is customer relationship management (CRM).

Morgan and Hunt (1994) defined Relationship marketing as the marketing activities directed toward establishing, developing, and maintaining successful relational exchanges. The separation of the producers from the users was a natural outcome of the industrial era. On the one hand, mass production enforced producers to sell their product & services through middlemen, and on the other, industrial organizations, due to specialization of corporate functions, created specialist purchasing departments and buyer professionals, thus separating the users from the producers.

As Nevin (1995) points out, these terms have been used to reflect a variety of themes and perspective. Some of these themes offer a narrow functional marketing perspective while others offer a perspective that is broad and somewhat paradigmatic in approach and orientation. A narrow perspective of customer relationship management is database marketing emphasizing the promotional aspects of marketing linked to data base efforts(Bickert,1992)

Analysis And Interpretation

CRM or customer relationship management is a number of strategies and technologies that are used to build stronger relationship between the companies and their customers. Through

customer relationship management customer satisfaction can be improved in banking sector. By establishing CRM in banks it can resist the customer switch over

Gender wise classification of respondents

Table 1: Gender wise classification of respondent

Gender	No of respondents	Percentage
Male	50	50
Female	50	50
Total	100	100

Age wise classification of respondents

Table 2: Age wise classification of respondents

Age group	No of respondents	Percentage
Under 20	6	6
20-40	48	48
40-60	38	38
Above 60	8	8
Total	100	100

Educational wise classification of respondents

This classification is based on the educational qualification of the customers. The result of the analysis is given below

Table 3: Educational wise classification of respondents

Education	Respondents	Percentages
SSLC	36	36
Plus 2	24	24
Bachelor degree	30	30
Master degree	4	4
Others	6	6
Total	100	100

Source – primary data

Occupation wise classification of respondents

Occupation is one of the factor influencing the customers for selecting type of bank. The result of the analysis is given below

Table 4: Occupation wise classification of respondents

Occupation	No of respondents	Percentages
Agriculturist	42	42
Business man	22	22
Professionals	12	12
Students	10	10
Others	14	14
Total	100	100

Source

Customer loyalty towards bank

This classification measure the customers loyalty towards their bank in terms of the number of years

Table 5: Customer loyalty towards bank

Years	no of respondents	Percentage
Under 5 years	26	26
5-10 years	24	24
10-15 years	16	16
Above 15 years	34	34
Total	100	100

Source-primary data

Diagram-1: Customer loyalty towards bank

The table no 5 indicate that out of 50 samples, 34% of respondents have been the customer of the bank for more than 15 years. 24% Of respondents are the customers of service cooperative bank for 5-10 years. Only 16% of customers are belonging to the category of 10-15 years

Reason for preferring service cooperative bank

There are many reason for preferring the service cooperative by the customers for their banking transactions. Table no 6 shows the customer's reason for preferring cooperative bank.

Table 6: Reason for preferring service cooperative bank

Reasons	No of respondents	Percentage
Low rate of interest	12	12
Customer friendly	40	40
Nearness	30	30
Speedy transaction	18	18
Others	2	2
total	100	100

Diagram-2: Reason for preferring service cooperative bank

Table 6 shows that reason for preferring service cooperative bank by most of the customers. 40% is the bank's customer friendly approach. 30% of respondents preferring cooperative bank because of nearness factor. Due to speedy transaction of bank only 18% of customers preferring cooperative bank.

Seeking customer comments and complaints

Through seeking customer comments and complaints the bank can establish good relationship with their customers and can access the satisfaction of customer towards the service provided by the bank

Table7: Seeking of customer comments and complaints

Response	No of respondents	Percentage
Never	8	8
Sometimes	24	24
Rarely	12	12
Frequently	16	16
Always	40	40
total	100	100

Source- primary data

It can be understood that 40% of customers opined that cooperative bank always seek their comments and complaints for improving service provided by bank. 8% of customers opined that bank never seek their comments and complaints. At the same time 16% of customers are saying that the bank seek their comments and complaints

Solving complaints of customer immediately

Customers feel satisfaction while solving their complaints immediately by bank. How often the banks solve the customer complaints is given in the following table.

Table 8: Frequency of solving customer complaints of customers immediately

frequency	No of respondents	Percentage
Always	50	50
Very often	8	8
Sometimes	38	38
Rarely	-	-
Never	4	4
total	100	100

Source- primary data

Diagram 4: Frequency of seeking customer comments and complaints

The study shows that out of 50 customers 50% of customers opined that , their complaints are always solved by their bank immediately. Only 4% of customers are against this opinion that the bank never solves their problem immediately

Means of communication channel

There are different means of communication channel used by the bank to establish good relationship with the customers like e-mail, phone, printed letter etc. using an appropriate channel is very important in maintaining good relationship with the customer. The following table gives details about their aspects

Table 9: Means of communication channel

channel	No of respondents	Percentage
e-mail	-	-
Phone	52	52
Printed letters	16	16
Face to face	32	32
Any other means	-	-
total	100	100

Source-primary data

Feedback on banking service

Many banks are seeking feedback regarding their services from their customers. Table no 10 will show the frequency of feedback on banking service

Table 10: Frequency of feedback on banking services

frequency	No of respondents	Percentage
Always	20	20
Frequently	28	28
Often	20	20
Very often	14	14
Never	18	18
total	100	100

Source-primary data

Concession or benefit to the regular customers

As a regular customer of the bank, he may get some benefit or concession. The following table shows the frequency of getting some concession or benefits to the regular customers

Table 11: Concession or benefit to the customers

response	No of respondents	Percentage
Yes	62	62
No	38	38
total	100	100

Source- primary data

Response of customers towards communication of bank's new scheme

The bank should communicate with their customers regarding their new scheme to establish a good relationship with them. How often banks follow their rule in the opinion of customers is exhibited in table no 12

Table 12: Response of customers towards communication of bank's new scheme

response	No of respondents	Percentage
Always	8	8
Regularly	32	32
Some time	38	38
Rarely	10	10
Never	12	12
total	100	100

Source –primary data

Attitude of employees towards customers

Based on the attitude of employees, a bank can establish a better relationship with the customers and can increase the number of customers. The following table shows the opinion on different attitude of employees .

Table 13: Attitude of employees towards customers

Attitude	No of respondents	Percentage
Very good	36	36
Good	64	64
Average	-	-
Poor	-	-
Very poor	-	-
Total	100	100

Opening procedure of an account in the service cooperative bank

To become a customer of a bank one should open an account in his name. To open an account there are many procedure to be followed. The table below shows how far it is easy to open an account in service cooperative bank.

Table 14: Opening procedure of an account in service cooperative bank

process	No of respondents	Percentage
Very easy	60	60
Easy	40	40
Neither easy nor difficult	-	-
Difficult	-	-
Very difficult	-	-
total	100	100

Source –primary data

Overall satisfaction level of services provided by service cooperative bank

Satisfaction of customers is one of the important factor to retain a customer in service cooperative bank for a longer period. So it is very important to access the satisfaction level of customer. The following table presents the satisfaction level of a customer regarding the service provided by their bank

Table15: Satisfaction level of customers on services provided by service cooperative bank

Response	no of respondents	Percentage
Very satisfied	34	34
Satisfied	66	66
Neutral	-	-
Dissatisfied	-	-
Very dissatisfied	-	-
total	100	100

Source –primary data

Agency services provided by service cooperative bank

There are banks which provide agency services like payment of telephone bill, booking tickets, rent received etc. the following table shows the frequency of agency services by the bank.

Table 16: Agency services provided by service cooperative bank

Particulars	No of respondents	Percentage
Always	8	8
Regularly	14	14
Sometimes	28	28
Rarely	-	-
Never	50	50
Total	100	100

Source- primary data

Loan taken from the bank

Providing loan is a primary function of a bank. It is a common services provided to its customers. The following table shows how many customers have taken loan from the bank.

Table 17: Loan from the bank

response	No of respondents	Percentage
Yes	52	52
No	48	48
total	100	100

Consumer's preference in taking loan

Banks provides different type of loan like agricultural loan, vehicle loan, etc. details of the type of loan taken by customers is given in table 18

Table 18: Types of loan

types	No of respondents	Percentage
Education loan	5	5
Marriage loan	5	5
Agricultural loan	19	19
Vehicle loan	23	23
Others	48	48
Total	100	100

Source – primary data

Percentage of loan written off by the bank

Generally banks write off the loan which are taken by the customers. When customers become insolvent and if there is no any legal heirs to repay the loan taken by the customers. The following table shows the percentage of customers whose loan has been written off by the bank.

Table 19: Loan written off by the bank

response	No of respondents	Percentage
Yes	5	5
No	95	95
total	100	100

Source – primary data

Default in repayment of loan

There are many customers who do not repay their loan in time. The following table shows the frequency of default in payment of loan

Table 20: Default in payment of loan

response	No of respondents	Percentage
Yes	5	5
No	95	95
Total	100	100

Source-primary data

Majority of customer does not make any default in repayment of loan (95%).

Securities required for taking loan.

To take loan from the bank some securities should be provided by the customers. There are different types of securities like personal security, pledge etc

Table 21: Securities required for taking loan

Securities	No of respondents	Percentage
Personal security	43	43
Pledge	29	29
Mortgage	9	9
Hypothecation	-	-
Others	19	19
Total	100	100

Source – primary data

Is depositing in cooperative bank more beneficial than other bank

All banks are providing a certain percentage of interest on their deposit. The following table shows the customers response about the benefit of depositing in cooperative bank.

Table 22: Opinion on benefits of depositing in cooperative bank

Response	No of respondents	Percentage
Strongly agree	18	18
Agree	56	56
Neutral	22	22
Disagree	10	10
Strongly disagree	-	-
Total	100	100

Source- primary data

Problem faced by a customer as a customer of cooperative bank

Sometimes a person faces some problem as a customer of the cooperative bank while making transaction with the bank. This table shows the details of some of the problem faced by the customer.

Table 24: Problem faced by a customer as a customer of cooperative bank

response	No of respondents	Percentage
Lack of ATM facility	80	80
More transaction time	16	16
Non availability of core banking	4	4
Total	100	100

Source- primary data

CHI – SQUARE Analysis

Several test of significance was developed by statistician. Chi – square is a statistical measure used in the context of sampling analysis for comparing a variance to a theoretical variance. As a non- parametric test, it can be used to determine if categorical data shows dependency or two classifications are independency, it can also be used to make comparison between theoretical population and actual data. The objective of chi-square is to find out how well the distribution of observed frequencies ‘O’ fit the distribution of expected frequencies ‘E’. Hence this test is called goodness of fit test.

The formula used for chi-square is,

$$\text{Chi-square} = \sum \frac{(O-E)^2}{E}$$

Where,

O=Observed frequencies

E=Expected frequencies

$$\text{Expected frequencies} = \frac{(\text{column total} * \text{row total})}{\text{grand total}}$$

H0 ; there is no significance difference between quality of banking service and customer satisfaction

H1 ; there is significant difference between quality of banking service and customer satisfaction

Quality of services provided by bank	Customer level of satisfaction with service					Total
	Highly satisfied	satisfied	neutral	dissatisfied	Highly dissatisfied	
Quick and fast services	2	1	1	1	0	5
Handling of a/c without mistake	9	7	2	1	0	19
Level of privacy offered	6	6	1	2	1	16
Way complaints are handled	2	1	0	0	1	4
Time taken to process transaction	4	1	1	0	0	6
	23	16	5	4	2	50

❖ Significant level = 0.05 (5%)

❖ Degree of freedom = (r-1)(c-1)

= (5-1)(5-1)

= 4*4

= **16**

❖ Critical value = **26.296**

❖ Decision value = accept the null hypothesis when chi-square value < 26.296

Table no computation of chi-square

O	E	$(O - E)^2$	$\frac{(O - E)^2}{E}$
2	2.3	0.09	0.0391
1	1.6	0.36	0.225
1	0.5	0.25	1
1	0.4	0.36	0.9
0	0.2	0.04	0.2
9	8.73	0.0729	0.0083
7	6.08	0.8464	0.1392
2	1.9	0.01	0.0052
1	1.52	0.2704	0.1778
0	0.76	0.5776	0.76
6	7.36	1.8496	0.2513
6	5.12	0.7744	0.1512
1	1.6	0.36	0.225
2	1.28	0.5184	0.405
1	0.64	0.1296	0.2025
2	1.84	0.0256	0.0139
1	1.28	0.0784	0.0612
0	0.4	0.16	0.4
0	0.32	0.1024	0.32
1	0.16	0.7056	4.41
4	2.76	1.5376	0.5571
1	1.92	0.8464	0.4408
1	0.6	0.16	0.2666
0	0.48	0.2304	0.48
0	0.24	0.0576	0.24
			11.8792

Chi-square = $\sum \frac{(O-E)^2}{E}$ = **11.8792**

Since calculated value is less than the table value, we accept the null hypothesis.

Findings And Suggestions

- 43% of customers taking loan against personal security and 29% of customers take loan against pledge. Some customers take loan against mortgage and on other securities (9% & 19% respectively). Out of the sample no one take loan against hypothecation
- 56% of customers agree that depositing in cooperative bank is more beneficial than depositing in other bank. Out of the sample 22% of the respondent neither agree nor disagree with this.
- Majority of customer does not make any default in repayment of loan (95%).
- 95% of customers are expressed that their loan has been never written off by the bank. Only 5% of customers loan have been written off by the bank
- out of 100samples 48% of customers take other type of loan like gold loan. 23% of them take vehicle loan. Only 19% of them take agricultural loan. 5% of customers take marriage loan as well as education loan.

- 66% of respondents think that the service provided by service cooperative bank are satisfied. At the same time 30% of respondents feel very much satisfaction.
- majority of customers feel very easy to open an account in a service cooperative bank (60%). While 40% of customers feel it 'easy'. But no customer feel any difficult to open an account in service cooperative bank.
- Out of 100 customers most of the customers (64%) feel good in behavior of employees .while 36% of respondents feel very good in the behavior of bank employees. No one feel 'poor' in the employees behavior.
- 12% Of customers are not informed about the new scheme of bank. Only 8% of customers get informed about new scheme of bank 'always'.
- majority of customers get concession or benefits (62%). But 35% of customers didn't have such opinion
- Out of 100 samples, 28% of customers are opined that , they frequently given their feedback on banking service to the bank. 20% Of customers are giving feedback to their bank often
- majority of customers (52%) are contacting their bank through phone.16% and 32% of customers respectively made relationship with their bank by using face to face and printed letters respectively. No respondents made contact with their bank by using e-mail or by any other means.
- 50% of customers opined that , their complaints are always solved by their bank immediately. Only 4% of customers are against this opinion that the bank never solves their problem immediately
- It can be understood that 40% of customers opined that cooperative bank always seek their comments and complaints for improving service provided by bank. 8% of customers opined that bank never seek their comments and complaints. At the same time 16% of customers are saying that the bank seek their comments and complaints
- 40% is the bank's customer friendly approach.30% of respondents preferring cooperative bank because of nearness factor. Due to speedy transaction of bank only 18% of customers preferring cooperative bank.
- , 34% of respondents have been the customer of the bank for more than 15 years. 24% Of respondents are the customers of service cooperative bank for 5-10 years. Only 16% of customers are belonging to the category of 10-15 years
- most of the customers of service cooperative bank are agriculturist and business man

Conclusion

Customer relationship management is based on customer because survive was made in the global market and focused on the customer and the customer is becoming a key factor for any business . The banks know that its cost is more to acquire a new customers than to get an existing customer for a making a purchase. Another aspect of survival of CRM is that knowing the customer better and also his/her preferences will allow the banks to acquire new customers more easily and facilitates targets services The conclusion is that the study report can be used as a supplementary factor to know about the perception of customers about software and many of the customers are not aware of the software if the company arranges for a work shop on software usage then it can used by every customers where the client database can be maintained easily

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A Study On Human Resource Management Practices Of Small And Medium Enterprises In Coimbatore District Of Tamilnadu State

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Abstract

This study presents an opportunity to study the possible effects of human resource management practices on small and medium enterprises. Such a study also helps to identify the influence of Human Resource Management practices on the performance of small and medium enterprises. A total of 12,873 small and medium enterprises in Coimbatore district, convenience sampling technique was used to select the respondents. In order to collect data from the employees of small and medium enterprises, the researcher contacted employees working in those small and medium enterprises. Accordingly, 200 employees of small and medium enterprises had been selected for the study. It is concluded that the overall human resource practices in small and medium enterprises are satisfactory, which is an appreciable factor in small and medium enterprises. The conclusions of this research pave the way for several research areas and have the potential of becoming a base for auxiliary research. Since the study is empirical in nature, the conclusions have been drawn on the basis of personal views and perceptions of employees in small and medium enterprises.

Keywords: Human Resource Practices, Small and Medium Enterprises and Performance

Introduction

The term human resource management (HRM) has been relatively adopted in business organizations in place of personnel management. HRM can be defined as the management of activities undertaken to attract, develop, motivate, and maintain a high performing workforce within the organization.

Statement of the Problem

To be successful in small and medium enterprises, they must be able to employ people who will stay with the business and perform at high levels. Employees working in any enterprise regardless of the size are committed to the organization are more likely to stay in their positions and perform well. HRM practices are one way that organizations can build organizational performance. This study presents an opportunity to study the possible effects of human resource management practices on small and medium enterprises. Such a study also helps to identify the influence of HRM practices on the performance of small and medium enterprises.

Significance of the Study

Identifying the HRM practices that tend to enhance performance would be a significant benefit for small and medium enterprises. The application of HRM practices that tend to enhance performance of small and medium enterprises could lead to other significant positive outcomes in small and medium enterprises. Enhanced performance should, lead to

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more vibrant and successful economy. The results of this research may be useful for many small and medium enterprises, not just in Coimbatore district, but in other districts of Tamilnadu.

Objectives of the Study

- 1) To study the Human Resources practices of small and medium enterprises in Coimbatore District
- 2) To identify the relationship between gender group of employees and Human Resources practices of small and medium enterprises in Coimbatore District.

Methodology

A total of 12,873 small and medium enterprises in Coimbatore district, convenience sampling technique was used to select the respondents. In order to collect data from the employees of small and medium enterprises, the researcher contacted employees working in those small and medium enterprises. Accordingly, 200 employees of small and medium enterprises had been selected for the study.

Limitations of the Study

Many small and medium enterprises did not have a designated HR position and hence, the data was collected from designations such as Supervisors and Managers. Many of them were taking care of the technical side of the small and medium enterprises apart from the HR function and hence emphasis on HR is lopsided. Hence, the perception on the HR practices and small and medium enterprises performance might not have been adequate.

Analysis and Interpretation

Talent Management among the employees of different gender group

In order to find out the significant difference among the mean scores regarding the talent management on the nine statements, data relating thereto were collected and the 't' test was administered with the null hypothesis as, **there is no significant difference in talent management among different gender group of employees in Small and medium enterprises in Coimbatore district.** The resulted mean scores on the talent management and the respective 't' statistics are presented in Table 1.

Table 1: Talent Management among employees of different gender group

Sl. No	Talent Management	Gender (Mean Score)		T Statistics
		Male	Female	
1.	Talent management procedures predict extra ordinary talents	3.7697	3.4889	3.007*
2.	Employees' participation in management encouraged	3.7879	3.5259	2.551*
3.	Organization provides sense of recognition and social status	3.6727	3.4148	2.441*
4.	Good motivation system emphasized	3.7152	3.6000	1.058
5.	Small and medium enterprises helps to improve motivation and morale of employees	3.6745	3.3333	2.884*
6.	Employees' capabilities are broadened through goal setting experiences	3.6364	3.4741	1.503

7.	Delegation of authority followed as an integral part of the Small and medium enterprises	3.8364	3.4296	3.449*
8.	Good mechanisms to identify potential leaders are followed	3.4727	3.3852	1.048
9.	Small and medium enterprises helps for the employees personal growth	3.7394	3.4296	2.481*

Source: Derived Data

*-Significant at 5 per cent level

From the above table, it is understood that the important talent management among male employees are delegation of authority followed as an integral part of the organization and employees' participation in management encouraged as the mean scores are 3.8364 and 3.7879 respectively. It is found that the important talent management among female employees are good motivation system emphasised and employees' participation in management encouraged as the mean scores are 3.6000 and 3.5259 respectively. A significant difference for the different gender group of employees were identified regarding the different talent management such as talent management procedures predict extra ordinary talents, employees' participation in management encouraged, organization provides sense of recognition and social status, organization helps to improve motivation and morale of employees, delegation of authority followed as an integral part of the organization and organization helps for the employees personal growth since the respective "T" statistics were significant at 5 per cent level.

Performance Management among the employees of different gender group

In order to find out the significant difference among the mean scores regarding the performance management on the ten statements, data relating thereto were collected and the 't' test was administered with the null hypothesis as, **there is no significant difference in performance management among different gender group of employees in Small and medium enterprises in Coimbatore district.** The resulted mean scores on the performance management and the respective 't' statistics are presented in Table 2.

Table 2: Performance Management among employees of different gender group

Sl. No	Performance Management	Gender (Mean Score)		T Statistics
		Male	Female	
1.	Performance plans are made for every year	4.0149	3.7475	2.597*
2.	Key performance areas are identified	3.9701	3.8182	1.856
3.	Performance management issues and plans are discussed explicitly	4.0299	3.6768	3.414*
4.	Employee's autonomy to plan and to do work is empowered	4.0547	3.7475	2.973*
5.	Performance management procedure wins co-operation and team work	4.1294	3.8081	3.873*
6.	Performance Appraisal system and ratings done and reviewed periodically	4.0597	3.7576	2.978*
7.	Performance Appraisal system identifies strength and weakness of employees.	3.9801	3.7896	2.007

8.	Performance Appraisal procedure improves individual skills	4.0299	3.7374	2.878*
9.	Performance linked compensation provided are adequate	4.0149	3.7879	2.646*
10.	Promotion, Transfer, Wage structure, Benefits and counselling are based on performance appraisal ratings	4.1244	3.7778	3.403*

Source: Derived Data

*-Significant at 5 per cent level

From the above table, it is understood that the important performance management among male employees are performance management procedure wins co-operation and team work and promotion, transfer, wage structure, benefits and counseling are based on performance appraisal ratings as the mean scores are 4.1294 and 4.1244 respectively. It is found that the important performance management among female employees are key performance area are identified and performance management procedure wins co-operation and team work as the mean scores are 3.8182 and 3.8081 respectively. A significant difference for the different gender group of employees were identified regarding the different performance management such as performance plans are made for every year, performance management issues and plans are discussed explicitly, employee's autonomy to plan and to do work is empowered, performance management procedure wins co-operation and team work, performance appraisal system and ratings done and reviewed periodically, performance appraisal procedure improves individual skills, performance linked compensation provided are adequate and promotion, transfer, wage structure, benefits and counseling are based on performance appraisal ratings since the respective "t" statistics were significant at 5 per cent level.

Compensation Management among the employees of different gender group

In order to find out the significant difference among the mean scores regarding the compensation management on the eight statements, data relating thereto were collected and the 't' test was administered with the null hypothesis as, **there is no significant difference in compensation management among different gender group of employees in Small and medium enterprises in Coimbatore district.** The resulted mean scores on the compensation management and the respective 't' statistics are presented in Table 3.

Table 3: Compensation Management among employees of different types of family

Sl. No	Compensation Management	Gender (Mean Score)		T Statistics
		Male	Female	
1.	Wage and salary structures are meeting with the legal requirements	3.8242	3.4815	3.189*
2.	Incentive plans are designed	3.9333	3.5333	3.779*
3.	Compensation plans are well designed (To attract talented & hard working people)	3.6303	3.5630	0.747
4.	Compensation and incentive plans minimise absenteeism, labour turnover, etc	3.7515	3.4725	2.646*
5.	Compensation plan improves goodwill and public image of the small and medium enterprises	3.5939	3.2889	2.485*

6.	Compensation plans consistent with business plans	3.4061	3.2148	1.865
7.	Employee compensation plan influence Small and medium enterprises profitability and growth	3.3576	3.1037	2.164*
8.	Compensation plans encourages motivation, morale and productivity	3.4424	3.2519	1.625
9.	Compensation provided in accordance with compensation	3.3576	3.1778	1.530
10.	Compensation plans reviewed and revised periodically.	3.4606	3.2593	1.672
11.	Risk coverage plans are designed	3.4545	3.3481	0.957

Source: Primary Data

*-Significant at 5 per cent level

From the above table, it is understood that the important compensation management among male employees are incentive plans are designed and wage and salary structures are meeting with the legal requirements as the mean scores are 3.9333 and 3.8242 respectively. It is found that the important compensation management among female employees are compensation plan are well designed (To attract talented & hard working people) and incentive plans are designed as the mean scores are 3.5630 and 3.5333 respectively. A significant difference for the different gender group of employees were identified regarding the different compensation management such as wage and salary structures are meeting with the legal requirements, incentive plans are designed, compensation and incentive plans minimize absenteeism, labour turnover, etc., compensation plan improves good will and public image of the firm and employee compensation plan influence organization profitability and growth since the respective “t” statistics were significant at 5 per cent level.

Gender and Promotional Policies of Small and medium enterprises

To test the promotional policies of Small and medium enterprises based on gender, the following null hypothesis was proposed.

H₀: There is no significant difference between mean rank for gender of the respondents and promotional policies of Small and medium enterprises.

The details of the result of Mann-Whitney test is reported in table 4.

Table 4: Mann-Whitney U Test for Gender and Promotional Policies

Promotional Policies	U-value	Z-value	p-value	Mean rank	
				Male	Female
Plenty of opportunity for promotion in small and medium enterprises	9235.000	2.600	0.009	162.03	136.41
Providing fair and equitable job promotions	10043.00	1.500	0.134	157.13	142.39
Existing policy of promotion is good	10018.50	1.540	0.124	157.28	142.21
Promotion policies are well defined	9874.000	1.745	0.081	142.84	159.86
Promotion policies are shared with all employees	9572.500	2.144	0.032	159.98	138.91

Promotions at small and medium enterprises are timely	9045.500	2.870	0.004	163.18	135.00
Promotion priority is given for merit	9910.500	1.689	0.091	157.94	141.41
Promotion priority is given for seniority	10574.00	0.776	0.237	153.92	146.33
Timely recognition	11027.00	0.152	0.379	151.17	149.68
Reward and remuneration system is very effective	10401.00	1.011	0.312	154.96	145.04

Source: Computed data

It is inferred that gender of the respondents affect the promotional policies of small and medium enterprises namely plenty of opportunity for promotion in your company (C.V 9235.000, p value 0.009, p<0.05), promotion policies are shared with all employees (C.V 9572.500, p value 0.032, p<0.05) and promotions at your company are timely (C.V 9045.500, p value 0.004, p<0.05).

Reward Management among the employees of different gender group

In order to find out the significant difference among the mean scores regarding the reward management on the seven statements, data relating thereto were collected and the ‘t’ test was administered with the null hypothesis as, **there is no significant difference in reward management among different gender group of employees in Small and medium enterprises in Coimbatore district.** The resulted mean scores on the reward management and the respective ‘T’ statistics are presented in Table 5.

Table 5: Reward Management among employees of different gender group

Sl. No	Reward Management	Gender (Mean Score)		T Statistics
		Male	Female	
1.	Reward systems are determined objectively	3.6606	3.3259	2.666*
2.	Both the monetary and non-monetary benefits are well defined	3.4909	3.1407	3.020*
3.	Reward mechanisms are adequate.	3.4303	3.0963	2.958*
4.	Awards & Rewards techniques motivate the personnel	3.4708	3.3926	0.860
5.	Effective reward system ensures higher productivity	3.5697	3.3185	1.948
6.	Reward system encourages Industrial Peace	3.5212	3.2889	1.834
7.	Appreciating words and complements encouraged are adequate	3.4606	3.3852	0.658

Source: Primary data

*-Significant at 5 per cent level

From the above table, it is understood that the important reward management among male employees are reward systems are determined objectively and effective reward system ensures higher productivity as the mean scores are 3.6606 and 3.5697 respectively. It is found that the important reward management among female employees are award & reward

technique motivate the personnel and appreciating words and complements encouraged are adequate as the mean scores are 3.3926 and 3.3852 respectively. A significant difference for the different gender group of employees were identified regarding the different reward management such as reward systems are determined objectively, both the monetary and non-monetary benefits are well defined and reward mechanisms are adequate since the respective “t” statistics were significant at 5 per cent level.

Health and Safety Management among the employees of different gender group

In order to find out the significant difference among the mean scores regarding the health and safety management on the nine statements, data relating thereto were collected and the ‘t’ test was administered with the null hypothesis as, **there is no significant difference in health and safety management among different gender group of employees in Small and medium enterprises in Coimbatore district.** The resulted mean scores on the health and safety management and the respective ‘t’ statistics are presented in Table 6.

Table 6: Health and Safety Management among employees of different gender group

Sl. No	Health and Safety Management	Gender (Mean Score)		T Statistics
		Male	Female	
1.	Employees’ safety is an important consideration in every decision and plan	3.8909	3.2296	4.509*
2.	Small and medium enterprises create safe work environment	3.9636	3.4963	3.729*
3.	Health and safety policies maintain and improve productivity and quality of work life	3.8364	3.6593	1.712
4.	Health and safety policies reduce and minimize industrial unrest, accidents and absenteeism and labour turnover	3.8182	3.6667	1.424
5.	Safety education and training to employees are provided	3.7818	3.4148	2.992*
6.	Health and safety policies preserve both physical and mental health of employees	3.5212	2.9407	3.866*
7.	Safety consciousness and safe working habits are effectively developed	3.6444	3.5333	1.913
8.	Breach of health and safety regulations are strictly punished	3.3333	3.1407	1.491
9.	Safe working climate ensures job satisfaction	3.6242	3.8074	1.606

Source: Primary data

*-Significant at 5 per cent level

From the above table, it is understood that the important health and safety management among male employees are small and medium enterprises create safe work environment and employees’ safety is an important consideration in every decision and plan as the mean scores are 3.9636 and 3.8909 respectively. It is found that the important health and safety management among female employees are safe working climate ensures job satisfaction and health and safety policies reduce and minimize industrial unrest, accidents and absenteeism and labour turnover as the mean scores are 3.8074 and 3.6667 respectively. A significant

difference for the different gender group of employees were identified regarding the different health and safety management such as employees' safety is an important consideration in every decision and plan, small and medium enterprises create safe work environment, safety education and training to employees are provided and health and safety policies preserve both physical and mental health of employees since the respective "t" statistics were significant at 5 per cent level.

Grievances Handling System of Small and medium enterprises Vs Gender of employees

An attempt was made to know the grievances handling system of Small and medium enterprises based on gender. To test the grievances handling system of Small and medium enterprises based on gender, the following hypothesis was proposed.

H₀: There is no significant difference between mean rank for gender of the employees and grievances handling system of Small and medium enterprises.

The details of the result of Mann-Whitney test is reported in table 7.

Table 7: Mann-Whitney U Test for Gender and Grievances Handling System

Grievances Handling System	U-value	Z-value	p-value	Mean rank	
				Male	Female
There is formal procedure for handling grievances	8551.500	-3.826	0.000	166.17	131.34
Superiors handles work-related issues satisfactorily	8453.500	-3.958	0.000	166.97	130.62
Supervisors is available for my queries and doubt	8773.500	-3.405	0.001	164.83	132.99
Supervisor delegates work effectively	9251.000	-2.730	0.006	161.93	136.53

Source: Computed data

Table 7 discloses that the null hypothesis (H₀) is rejected at the 5% level of significance with regard to the grievances handling system of Small and medium enterprises such as there is formal procedure for handling grievances, superiors handles work-related issues satisfactorily, supervisors is available for my queries and doubt and supervisor delegates work effectively due to the p value is less than 0.05. It shows that gender wise there is a significant difference in grievances handling system of Small and medium enterprises such as there is formal procedure for handling grievances, superiors handles work-related issues satisfactorily, supervisors is available for my queries and doubt and supervisor delegates work effectively.

Conflict Management among the employees of different gender group

In order to find out the significant difference among the mean scores regarding the conflict management on the nine statements, data relating thereto were collected and the 't' test was administered with the null hypothesis as, **there is no significant difference in conflict management among different gender group of employees in Small and medium enterprises in Coimbatore district.** The resulted mean scores on the conflict management and the respective 't' statistics are presented in Table 8.

Table 8: Conflict Management among employees of different gender group

Sl. No	Conflict Management	Gender (Mean Score)		T Statistics
		Male	Female	
1.	Good industrial relation system followed	3.6970	3.8963	2.320*
2.	Small and medium enterprises maintains harmonious relationship (between management and employees and unions)	3.7515	3.8815	1.301
3.	Conflicts managed by fair and transparent and procedures.	3.7212	3.7630	1.401
4.	Collective bargaining system provided.	3.4909	3.5852	1.109
5.	Small and medium enterprises consults workers associations and trade union while formulating policies, procedures and plans	3.4182	3.5111	0.959
6.	Disciplinary code and procedure formulated	3.3636	3.4963	1.258
7.	Grievance handling mechanisms are adequate	3.2970	3.3926	0.925
8.	Redressal systems for employees' grievance handling are well established	3.3818	3.6000	2.162*
9.	Small and medium enterprises ensures industrial peace	3.3333	3.4444	1.119

Source: Primary data

*-Significant at 5 per cent level

From the above table, it is understood that the important conflict management among male employees are small and medium enterprises maintains harmonious relationship (between management and employees and unions) and conflicts managed by fair and transparent and procedures as the mean scores are 3.7515 and 3.7212 respectively. It is found that the important conflict management among female employees are good industrial relation system followed and small and medium enterprises maintains harmonious relationship (between management and employees and unions) as the mean scores are 3.8963 and 3.8815 respectively. A significant difference for the different gender group of employees were identified regarding the different conflict management such as good industrial relation system followed and redressal systems for employees' grievance handling are well established since the respective "T" statistics were significant at 5 per cent level.

Suggestions

- The small and medium enterprises should have systematic recruitment and selection policy for employing best qualified persons. The recruitment and selection policy should be flexible and integrate organizational and employee needs.
- The small and medium enterprises need to adopt a strategy that could improve the employee's quality of work life to satisfy both the enterprises objectives and employee needs. Each employee should provide with freedom and opportunity to utilize and develop their knowledge and skill to the maximum extend.

- The small and medium enterprises may conduct orientation programme to the new entrants. The employees need to be treated more humanely and in a friendly manner which could inculcate in them a sense of responsibility and trust.

Conclusion

It is concluded that the overall human resource practices in small and medium enterprises are satisfactory, which is an appreciable factor in small and medium enterprises. The conclusions of this research pave the way for several research areas and have the potential of becoming a base for auxiliary research. Since the study is empirical in nature, the conclusions have been drawn on the basis of personal views and perceptions of employees in small and medium enterprises.

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Stochastic Models For Time To Recruitment In A Manpower System With Correlated Wastage Of Manpower When The Breakdown Threshold Has Two Components Using Univariate Cum Policy Of Recruitment

A. DEVI*

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Abstract

In this paper, the problem of time to recruitment is analyzed for a single grade manpower system in which attrition takes place due to two types of policy decisions. Assuming (i) policy decisions and exits occur at different epochs (ii) wastage of manpower due to exits are exchangeable and constantly correlated exponential random variables and (iii) breakdown threshold for the cumulative wastage of manpower in the system has two components which are independent exponential random variables, three stochastic models are constructed using different assumptions on inter-decision times and variance of the time to recruitment is obtained for these models using an univariate CUM policy of recruitment and a different probabilistic analysis.

Keywords

Single grade manpower system, non-instantaneous exits, intensity of attrition, correlated wastage of manpower, ordinary renewal process, geometric process, order statistics, breakdown threshold with two components, univariate CUM policy of recruitment and variance of time to recruitment.

Introduction

Authors in [1] and [2] are the pioneers in the study on manpower models for a system with one or more grades. In [14] the authors have initiated the study on the problem of time to recruitment for the single grade manpower system which is subject to attrition with **instantaneous exits**, using the univariate policy of recruitment based on shock model approach for replacement of systems in reliability theory. In [8], the author has obtained the system characteristics when the loss of manpower process and inter-decision time process form a correlated pair of renewal sequences. For the study of this problem corresponding to correlated inter-decision times under different policies of recruitment, one can refer to [10], [11], [12] and [13]. In [9] the author has studied this problem assuming geometric process and order statistics for inter-decision times. In [7] the authors have studied the problem of time to recruitment by assuming that the attrition is generated by a geometric process of inter-decision times using a different probabilistic analysis. In [3] the authors have considered the single grade manpower system with **non-instantaneous exits** and obtained variance of the time to recruitment when the wastage of manpower, inter-decision times and

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exit times are independent and identically distributed continuous random variables and breakdown threshold is an exponential random variable. While in [4] the models in [3] are studied when the policy decisions are classified into two types, in [5], the models in [4] are studied when breakdown threshold for the cumulative wastage of manpower in the system has two components. The present paper extends the research work in [4], wastage of manpower due to exits are exchangeable and constantly correlated exponential random variables.

MODEL DESCRIPTION AND ANALYSIS FOR MODEL-I

Consider an organization with one grade in which policy decisions taken at random epochs in $(0, \infty)$ produce depletion in manpower (wastage) due to exits of personnel. It is assumed that the exits are not instantaneous. Policy decisions are classified into two types according to the intensity of attrition. While the first type of policy decisions has high attrition rate $\lambda_1 > 0$, the second type is associated with decisions which has low attrition rate $\lambda_2 > 0$. Let a_1 and $(1-a_1)$ be the proportion of decisions with high and low attrition rate respectively. Let $\{A_n\}$ be a sequence of independent inter-decision times following hyper-exponential distribution with parameters a_1, λ_1 and λ_2 . For $i=1,2,3, \dots$, let S_i be the cumulative wastage of manpower in the first i exit epochs and m_i be its probability density function, where the summands of S_i are exchangeable and constantly correlated exponential random variables with mean u ($u > 0$) and correlation R . Let B_i be a sequence of independent and identically distributed inter-exit times. Let D_{i+1} be the time at which $(i+1)^{th}$ exit occurs. Let Y be the breakdown threshold for the cumulative wastage of manpower in the organization with probability density function $h(\cdot)$. It is assumed that Y is the sum of the exponential breakdown threshold level Y_1 for cumulative wastage due to exits with mean $\frac{1}{\theta_1}$ ($\theta_1 > 0$) and

exponential threshold Y_2 for cumulative wastage due to frequent breaks of existing workers with mean $\frac{1}{\theta_2}$ ($\theta_2 > 0$). Let $\chi(I)$ be the indicator function of the event I . Let T be the random

variable denoting the time to recruitment with mean $E(T)$ and variance $V(T)$.

As in [3] we get,

$$T = \sum_{i=0}^{\infty} D_{i+1} \chi(S_i \leq Y < S_{i+1}) \tag{1}$$

$$E(T) = \sum_{i=0}^{\infty} (i+1) E(B) P(S_i \leq Y < S_{i+1}) \tag{2}$$

and

$$E(T^2) = \sum_{i=0}^{\infty} (i+1) [V(B) + (i+1)E^2(B)] P(S_i \leq Y < S_{i+1}) \tag{3}$$

$$\text{where } P(S_i \leq Y < S_{i+1}) = \int_0^{\infty} \int_0^t \tilde{M}(t-x) m_i(x) h(t) dx dt \tag{4}$$

Proceeding as in [4], from (2), (3) and (4) and [6] we get on simplification

$$E(T) = (K_{17} - K_{18}) \left(\frac{a_1 \lambda_2 + a_2 \lambda_1}{\lambda_1 \lambda_2 q} \right) \tag{5}$$

and

$$V(T) = (K_{17} - K_{18}) \left(\frac{2q[a_1\lambda_2^2 + a_2\lambda_1^2] + 2(1-q)[a_1\lambda_2 + a_2\lambda_1]^2}{(\lambda_1\lambda_2q)^2} \right) - (K_{17}(1 + K_{17}) - K_{18}(1 - K_{18}) - K_{19} + K_{20} - 2K_{17}K_{18}) \left(\frac{a_1\lambda_2 + a_2\lambda_1}{\lambda_1\lambda_2q} \right)^2 \tag{6}$$

where

$$K_{17} = \sum_{i=0}^{\infty} (i+1) \left(\frac{\theta_1\theta_2(1-R)}{(\theta_1 - \theta_2)(\alpha + \theta_2)v^{i-2} (1 + \theta_2v)^{i-1} [(1-R + iR)(v + \theta_2v) - iR]} \right),$$

$$K_{18} = \sum_{i=0}^{\infty} (i+1) \left(\frac{\theta_1\theta_2(1-R)}{(\theta_1 - \theta_2)(\alpha + \theta_1)v^{i-2} (1 + \theta_1v)^{i-1} [(1-R + iR)(v + \theta_1v) - iR]} \right), \tag{7}$$

$$K_{19} = \sum_{i=0}^{\infty} (i+1)^2 \left(\frac{\theta_1\theta_2(1-R)}{(\theta_1 - \theta_2)(\alpha + \theta_2)v^{i-2} (1 + \theta_2v)^{i-1} [(1-R + iR)(v + \theta_2v) - iR]} \right) \text{ and}$$

$$K_{20} = \sum_{i=0}^{\infty} (i+1)^2 \left(\frac{\theta_1\theta_2(1-R)}{(\theta_1 - \theta_2)(\alpha + \theta_1)v^{i-2} (1 + \theta_1v)^{i-1} [(1-R + iR)(v + \theta_1v) - iR]} \right).$$

(5) and (6) give mean and variance of time to recruitment for the present model.

MODEL DESCRIPTION AND ANALYSIS FOR MODEL-II

In this model, the inter-policy decision times form a geometric process with rate $c, c > 0$, where the distribution of A_1 is hyper-exponential with parameters a_1, λ_1 and λ_2 . All other assumptions are as in Model-I.

In this case from (2), (3), (4) and [4], on simplification we get

$$E(T) = (K_{17} - K_{18}) \left[\frac{c(a_1\lambda_2 + a_2\lambda_1)}{\lambda_1\lambda_2(c-1+q)} \right]. \tag{8}$$

$$V(T) = (K_{17} - K_{18}) \left[\frac{2c^2(a_1\lambda_2^2 + a_2\lambda_1^2)}{(c^2 - 1 + q)(\lambda_1\lambda_2)^2} \right] - (K_{17}(1 + K_{17}) - K_{18}(1 - K_{18}) - K_{19} + K_{20} - 2K_{17}K_{18}) \left[\frac{c(a_1\lambda_2 + a_2\lambda_1)}{\lambda_1\lambda_2(c-1+q)} \right]^2 \tag{9}$$

where K_{17}, K_{18}, K_{19} and K_{20} are given by (7).

(8) and (9) give mean and variance of time to recruitment for the present model.

MODEL DESCRIPTION AND ANALYSIS FOR MODEL-III

Description of this model is similar to that of Model-I except the assumption on inter-decision times. In this model it is assumed that the inter-policy decision times form an order statistics. More specifically, let $\{U_{(l)}\}_{l=1}^r$ be a set of order statistics associated with a sample of size r taken from the population $\{U_n\}_{n=1}^{\infty}$ of independent and identically distributed hyper-exponential random variables with the population mean $E(U_n) = E(U) = \frac{a_1}{\lambda_1} + \frac{(1-a_1)}{\lambda_2}$, $n=1,2,\dots$. In this case, the cumulative distribution function $S(t)$ of the population and the probability density function $s_{(l)}(t)$ of the l^{th} order statistics are given by

$$S(t) = a_1(1 - e^{-\lambda_1 t}) + (1 - a_1)(1 - e^{-\lambda_2 t}), \quad a_1 > 0, \lambda_1 > 0 \text{ and } \lambda_2 > 0.$$

From the theory of order statistics [15], it is known that

$$s_{(l)}(t) = l \binom{r}{l} (S(t))^{l-1} s(t) [1 - S(t)]^{r-l}, \quad l = 1, 2, \dots, r.$$

In this Model the inter - policy decision times $A_n, n=1,2,\dots$ form a sequence of independent and identically distributed random variable with cumulative distribution $F(t)$ and probability density function $f(t)$. By the assumption that the inter-policy decision times form an order statistics we mean that the probability density function $f(t)$ is identified with that of the order statistics $\{U_{(l)}\}_{l=1}^r$. Thus $f(t)$ can be any one of the $s_{(l)}(t), l = 1,2,\dots,r$.

We now determine $E(T)$ and $V(T)$ under two cases.

Case(i): $f(t) = s_{(1)}(t)$.

The probability density function of the first order statistics is

$$s_{(1)}(t) = r[1 - S(t)]^{r-1}s(t)$$

From (2),(3),(4) and [4], on simplification it is found that

$$E(T) = \frac{K_3(K_{17} - K_{18})}{q} \tag{10}$$

and

$$V(T) = \left(\frac{1}{q^2}\right) \left[(K_{17} - K_{18}) \left(qK_4 + 2(1-q)(K_3)^2 \right) - (K_3)^2 (K_{17}(1 + K_{17}) - K_{18}(1 - K_{18}) - K_{19} + K_{20} - 2K_{17}K_{18}) \right] \tag{11}$$

where $K_3, K_4, K_{17}, K_{18}, K_{19}$ and K_{20} are given by [4] and (7) respectively.

(10) and (11) give the mean and variance of time to recruitment for case (i) of the present model.

Case (ii): $f(t) = s_{(r)}(t)$

The probability density function of the r^{th} order statistics is

$$s_{(r)}(t) = r[S(t)]^{r-1}s(t)$$

From (2), (3),(4) and [4], on simplification it is found that

$$E(T) = \frac{K_5(K_{17} - K_{18})}{q} \tag{12}$$

and

$$V(T) = \left(\frac{1}{q^2}\right) \left[(K_{17} - K_{18}) \left(qK_6 + 2(1-q)(K_5)^2 \right) - (K_5)^2 (K_{17}(1 + K_{17}) - K_{18}(1 - K_{18}) - K_{19} + K_{20} - 2K_{17}K_{18}) \right] \tag{13}$$

where $K_5, K_6, K_{17}, K_{18}, K_{19}$ and K_{20} are given by [4] and (7) respectively.

(12) and (13) give the mean and variance of time to recruitment for case (ii) of the present model.

CONCLUSION

The present work improves the earlier relevant research work in the context of admitting non-instantaneous exits with correlated wastage in the system. They will be useful in the process of planning recruitment when the system has the above cited provision. Testing of distribution used in the present work can be done by analysing the data collected from a primary or secondary source.

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Carbon Trading – Related Issues And Position In India

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Abstract

Increase in the population levels over a period of time will lead to serious environmental hazards such as droughts, floods and spread of diseases and most dangerous that is global warming. The impact of these hazards I already being felt in many parts of the world. However it is difficult to motivate countries to reduce pollution, as the process of industrialization has to go on. The present study gives a solution to global warming that is carbon trading. Carbon trading provides economic incentives to developing countries to reduce emissions of greenhouse gases .India is also a developing country. So, India also take advantages of carbon trading. But only a little portion of Indian society aware about what is carbon trading. ? This study is a little efforts to provide a general understanding about very recent and emerging issue. This study explains the term carbon trading and some related concepts. This paper also explains the position of India in carbon trading as a developing country.

Keywords: Environmental hazards, carbon trading.

introduction

Sometimes, some ideas are like devils, such one is global warming. And sometimes some ideas are like sweat dreams and such one is carbon trading. Global warming is not a problem of any specific country. But it is now a worldwide problem that is very dangerous for human life all over the world. Global and national level decisions at present and in the next few years are crucial to determine how effectively we will be able to meet this challenge.

Carbon trading provides a solution to global warming. Carbon trading means trading of carbon. It is unbelievable that CO₂ is also traded among countries just like other commodities. “Carbon trading or emission trading is an administrative approach used to control pollution by providing incentives for achieving reduction in emission of pollutants from environment.”(1)

In simple words, carbon trading is a business between developing and developed countries. Kyoto Protocol set some specific targets for emission of greenhouse gas in the environment. If they fail to achieve those targets, then they have heavy fines. So ,if any developed country fails to achieve the required reduction in the emission of greenhouse gases, then it may purchase CER's(certified emission reductions) from developing countries and meet their tarfets.it is not important that someone is doing more to reduce carbon emission and someone else is just buying the right to pollute the air. More important is overall reduction in the emission of greenhouse gases that Kyoto Protocol set out to achieve.

There is one another aspect of carbon trading that the developed countries implement s cleaner technologies in developing countries for reduction of greenhouse gases. Because developed countries are required to spend approximately \$300 to \$500 to reduce a ton of co₂ emission as compared to just \$10-25\$ required by a developing country. With the help of these cleaner technologies ,developing country reduce their emission levels, generates CER's and sold them to developed country and earn huge money. This is the process of

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carbon trading. The idea behind carbon trading was to make developed countries for their wild ways with emission and same time monetarily rewarding to countries for the good behavior in this regard.

Objectives Of Study

The main aim of the present study is to achieve the following objectives:

- To examine the term carbon trading in detail.
- To examine various aspect related to carbon trading.
- To study the position of carbon trading in India.

Research Methodology

This study is only a descriptive study to analyses the carbon trading and related issues. Only few quantitative data used to analyze the position of carbon trading in India .only secondary data is used which is collected from annual reports published by companies, economic survey by Indian government and various websites searched for the collection of secondary data.

Carbon Trading And Some Related Issues

The process of buying and selling of carbon credits is called carbo trading. In this process of buying and selling there are two parties-one is developed country and another is developing country.

1. CER's - Currency for trade: Certified emission reduction as defined by Kyoto Protocol, is one of carbon emitted by burning of fossil fuels. CER's is a measuring devise by the Kyoto protocol to reduce world greenhouse gas emissions and hence fight climate change. Each CER's represents one metric ton of carbon dioxide either remove from the atmosphere or saved from being emitted.
2. CO₂(e) - CARBON EQUIVALENTS: Carbon dioxide equivalents provide a universal standard of measurement against which the impact of releasing different greenhouse gas can be evaluated .every greenhouse gas has a Global Warming Potential (GWP). The global warming potential of a given gas describe its effect on climate change relative to a similar amount of carbon dioxide. this allow the regulation of greenhouse gases under the Kyoto Protocol to be converted to the common unit of CO₂(e)
3. CARBON MARKET: Like other commodities market, this market also have two sides and one price factor. Emerging carbon credit markets offer golden opportunities for the developing countries to star energy saving devices to reduce GHG emissions and earn carbon credits. So, developing country like China, India and Brazil are the major source of supply in carbon market. And in demand side all developed countries are included.
4. PRICE FACTOR IN CARBON MARKET: price for one CER is decided in the carbon market. In developing countries across the world, CER prices are influenced by various factors include electricity, coal, oil prices etc. there is no stability in carbon credit prices. The price of carbon trading normally ranges between \$70 - 140\$, depending on the stage of approval process of the projects. For those projects which are in process of registration, the price is lower. But those which already registered get higher carbon credit prices in the market.

Position Of Carbon Trading In India

India is a party to the United Nations framework convention on climate change and its Kyoto protocol. Many companies in India are now doing a new form of business known as carbon trading. This trading of carbon is possible in India with the help of clean development mechanism (CDM). In CDM projects, cleaner technology installed by developed countries

in India. This is because cutting down emissions in developed countries demands very high cost of reduction of greenhouse gases.

Table 1: cost of reducing 1 tone of co2

Classification of countries	Cost of reduction per tone
Developed countries	\$300-\$500
Developing countries	\$10-\$15

Source: A report of World Bank

It is clearly shown from the above table why developed countries want to install cleaner technologies in developing countries rather than install in their own countries.

Clean development mechanism is a base for carbon trading business in India. It is necessary to overview of current status of clean development projects in India.

Table 2: An overview of CDM projects in India.

Project status	No. of projects Aug. 2008	No. of projects Nov.2008
CDM projects registered at CDM executive board UNFCC	355	360
CDM projects at or after validation stage	1021	1426

Source: CDM country fact sheet: India (IGES)

Table 2 shows a brief overview of clean development projects in India during aug-nov 2008 as there is an interesting trend in total projects(registered or un registered).

Carbon Trading By Indian Companies

As explained in previous section-A, with the help of clean development mechanism, Indian companies can switch to cleaner technologies and generate more CER through cutting down CO2 emission in the environment.as industrialization goes on, big companies are increasing are increasing their manufacturing process and thus increased their turnover. And, while doing so they are adding greenhouse gasses in the atmosphere like never before.

The good news is that they are also making bucket full of money simply by putting so called “clean development” tag to some of their dirtiest projects.

Table 3: CER’s issued till 2016, status of Indian companies

Name of the company	CER’s received in millions tones	Company’s share in%
SRF Ltd.	3.8	50
Gujarat fluorochemicals Ltd.	3.0	39.47
Others	0.8	10.53
Total	7.6	100

Source <http://www.unfccc.int/unfccc> 2016

Table 3 shows that out of total 7.6 million tones CER’s 3.8 mt. received by SRF Ltd that is 50% of total. And another 3 million tones CER’s received by Gujarat fluoro chemicals Ltd., whose share is approximately 40% of total. So, SRF Ltd. and Gujarat aurochemicals Ltd. are the top most companies in carbon trading.

Finding

It has been found that India has grown tremendously in the field of carbon trading and Indian companies earn big profits from carbon trading. It is observed in the study that India is the second most potential country to implement the clean development projects. There is mainly two reasons. First, low cost of reducing greenhouses from the environment as compared to developed countries. Second one is, India's high level emission of greenhouse gasses. On the basis of study, it is found that till July, 2008, there were total 1109 clean development registered projects world-wide. Out of these 1109 clean development projects, India stands for the first 360 registered projects (i.e. about 32% of total) but interesting factor to be observed here is that in spite of its first position in the case of no. of registered projects, India holds the second position in the case of receipts of certified emission reductions (CERIS) from UNFCCC. While at the same time china holds the first position with its 51.51% share in receipts of CER's. It is also analyzed that even though India is a big beneficiary in carbon trading, but still there is a lack of proper regulations for trading of carbon in this market. so, it is suggested that center government has been asked by international treaty as NCDEX (National Commodity and Derivatives Exchange Limited) to put a proper policy framework for supplier of CER's. As India is huge supplier of CER's, it will get benefit with a right policy in this trading.

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Assessment & fulfillment of training needs of various organizations with reference to Nagpur region

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Abstract

The Training need analysis is basically a data gathering process used to identify and compare an organizations actual level of performance to the projected (Desired) level of performance. Thus a TNA is quite simply a way of identifying the existing gaps in the knowledge & the strengths & weaknesses in the processes that enable or hinder effective training programs being delivered. From the research carried out the statistical data represents that the assumption of hypothesis is true in nature. The attitude towards training to be expenditure than investment is observed more in organizations in Nagpur region.

Keywords: TNA, Discrepancies, Behavioural modification, Scorecard

Introduction

The Training need analysis is basically a data gathering process used to identify and compare an organizations actual level of performance to the projected (Desired) level of performance. The difference (Discrepancy) will identify the immediate and/or long range training need. An employee's talent cannot be fully productive without a systematic training program. In absence of formal training program an employee would train himself by trial & error by observing others but this would be costly, hazardous apart from time consuming and inefficient results. Training is also beneficial for employees in terms of better job security and opportunity for advancement.

Training Need Analysis

A TNA is a review of learning & development needs within an organization. It considers the skills, knowledge & behaviours that people need and how to develop them effectively. A TNA is considered to be the foundation of all training activities. In order to deliver appropriate & effective training which meets the need of individuals and the organization & represents value for money, a TNA is essential.

Role of needs assessment

Effective training must be reinforced by reliable & continuous self-examination. For human settlements organizations, this self-examination is nothing more than the collection and analysis of existing organizational data to extract meaningful conclusions about the need for training. When a manager collects data about an organization and studies it with training in mind, he or she is engaging in "needs assessment".

Literature Review

Arshad, Yusof, Mahmood, Ahmed & Akhtar "A Study on TNA Process among Manufacturing Companies Registered with Pembangunan Sumber Manusia Berhad (PSMB) at Bayan Lepas Area, Penang, Malaysia" found that out of six, five organization contextual variable has a relationship with TNA factors. Even though it is not really an in-depth study, it is significant enough to agree upon that the recommendation made by TNA researchers is followed by organization in this study. The right adoption of TNA process will increase on

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its effectiveness without wasting time, energy and money in order to achieve the desired performance. Johnson (1993) clearly pointed out that performance improvement is achieved through skilled, knowledgeable and committed workers who want to make their organization successful. Training needs analysis is considered to be the foundation of all training activities.

In order to deliver appropriate, effective training which meets the needs of individuals and the organisation and represents value for money a training needs analysis is essential (Boydell and Leary 1996, Reid and Barrington 1999). There is general agreement in the literature that a training needs analysis is a best practice first step in the systematic approach to training (Wills 1998, Boydell and Leary 1996, Reid and Barrington 1999, Garavan et al., 1995, Bartram and Gibson 1997, 1999, Reay 1994).

Objectives

- 1) To identify & bridge the gap between existing performance ability and training assessment and desired performance & training assessments.
- 2) To observe & study the organizational growth affected by TNA in Nagpur region.
- 3) To observe how the new entrants are imparted the basic knowledge and skill they need for an intelligent performance of different task.
- 4) To find how they assist the employee to function more effectively in their present jobs while exposing them to the latest concepts, information & techniques.
- 5) To reduce supervision, wastage & accidents. Development of effective work habits & methods of work should contribute towards reduction in the accident rate, less supervision & wastage of material.

Hypothesis

There is a gap between ‘assessment & fulfillment of training needs’ and the ‘Training imparted’ to the employee in organizations in Nagpur region.

Sampling method is the way the sample units are to be selected. Random sampling method is used for the research. Sample size is 35 organizations in and around Nagpur.

Data Analysis & Interpretation

1) Is training conducted in your organization?	
• Yes	66 %
• No	33 %
2) Which training format your organization uses?	
• No training	34 %
• Inhouse	49 %
• Outhouse	17 %
3) Which type of training is conducted in your organization?	
• Behavioural Modification training	20 %
• Technical training	24 %
• Operational Training	10 %
• Health & safety measurement training	22%
• Functional Training	14 %
• Organizational Development training	7 %
• Leadership training	3%

4) What is the size of employees that undergo training program	
• 1 – 5	45 %
• 6 – 10	35 %
• 10 – 20	9 %
• < 20	9 %
5) For what duration training programs are conducted generally?	
• 1 day	40%
• 3 days	37 %
• 1 week	17 %
• 2 weeks	6 %
• 4 weeks or more	0
6) How many times training is conducted annually?	
• Never	35%
• Once	17%
• Twice	11%
• Thrice	31%
• Five times	0
• As per Need analysis	6%
7) What is annual investment on an individual training?	
• Nil	34%
• Upto 10 K	29%
• Up to 20 K	26%
• Up to 25 K	11%
8) Do you conduct training need assessment periodically?	
• Never	49%
• Rarely	17 %
• Occasionally	23%
• Often	11%
• Regularly	0
9) Do you implement training after assessment as per the needs of organization?	
• Yes	17%
• Sometimes	29%
• Never	54%
10) Do you use TNA scorecard for training need identification?	
• Yes	6%
• No	94%
11) Do you believe TNA helps in improving employee effectiveness & increased employee output	
• Yes	20%
• May be/Not sure	37%
• No	43%
12) Reason for TNA in organization is due to	

• Growing competition	61 %
• Fast changing environment	17%
• To be leaders in the market	22%
13) You believe training is actually	
• Not necessary for organization	29%
• Expenditure for organization	51%
• Investment for organization	20%
14) Do you find training programs conducted after assessing the training needs is fulfilling the requirements of organization?	
• Effectively	33%
• Satisfactory	50%
• Neutral	17%
• Unsatisfactory	0
15) Do you think there is a gap in training needs assessment & fulfillment & actual training practices followed in the organization?	
• Strongly agree	17 %
• Agree	50 %
• Somewhat agree/Disagree	11%
• Disagree	11%
• Strongly Disagree	11%

66 % of companies conduct the training program as compared to 33 % of them lacking in it. Inhouse training format is more prevalent in companies with 49 % as compared to outhouse training with 17 % . 34 % of the companies don't impart any form of training. Technical, Health & safety measurement & Behavioural modification training programs are given preference whereas Organizational Development training Leadership training programs are least considered. Out of 23 companies that conduct the training program maximum of them go with 1-5 employees for training i.e. 47 % then 35 % of them impart training to 6-10 employees & only 9 % of them think of facilitating 10-20 & more than 20 employees with training in a company. Nearly all companies i.e. 22 & 20 of them that conduct training program get along well with single day & 3 day training respectively. 9 companies facilitate a week long training program & only 3 companies provide 2 weeks training, whereas no company is interested in conducting training for a 4 week long period.31 % of the companies conduct training program three times a year whereas no companies go for 5 times training program annually.17 % of them conduct at least one program annually & 11 % opt for 2 programs each year. Only 6 % companies conduct the training program as per need analysis. Not a single company conducts Training need assessment regularly. 49 % companies never conduct training need assessment periodically. Occasionally conducting Training need assessment companies are 23 % with 17 % rarely 11% of them very often conduct Training need assessment periodically.

Majority of the companies 54 % overlook the factor of implementing training after assessment as per the needs of organization. Only 6 % of the companies use TNA scorecard for training need identification as compared to 94 % of them who ignore it.20 % of the companies think that the TNA helps in improving employee effectiveness & increased employee output where as 43 % of this disagree with it. Maximum numbers of companies

i.e. 61 % think that the reason for TNA in organizations is due to the growing competition in the industry. 51 % of the companies think that training is actually expenditure for the organization. 50 % of the companies are satisfied that after assessment the training is fulfilling the requirement of organization.

Conclusion

TNA is only the first critical stage in any training cycle. Thus a TNA is quite simply a way of identifying the existing gaps in the knowledge & the strengths & weaknesses in the processes that enable or hinder effective training programs being delivered. From the research carried out the statistical data represents that the assumption of hypothesis is true in nature. Only 34 % conduct training needs assessment more often compared to the others. Only 17 % actually implement the needs identified to fulfill the organizational needs among them. The growing competition and business environment is accelerating the importance of identifying the way to become more strategically effective and therefore the organization recognizes the value of training needs assessment. The major differences in approach to TNA have been observed is due to the difference of organizations structure i.e. local business unit or National business Unit or multinational business unit. Thus the research verifies that there is a gap between assessment & fulfillment of training needs & training imparted to the employees in organizations situated in Nagpur region. As a result of which the organizations located in Nagpur region are unable to gain optimal output from employees as few impart training in disorganized manner. The attitude towards training to be expenditure than investment is observed more in organization in Nagpur region.

Managerial Implications

The rationale for developing a training program relies heavily on identifying training needs and justifying the cost & benefits to the organization. Without a clear understanding of needs, training efforts are best randomly useful and worst, useless. The trainer will only be successful and perceived as such to the extent that needs are carefully accessed, and programs developed and carried out that meet those needs. The end result is the more precise picture of training needs, which can lead to a performance improvement, oriented training program and better results from training.

The organization needs to change their perception of training for real & effective development of organization. Training should be seen as an investment for medium & long term return. There should be a periodic assessment of training needs in the organization which can vary depending on the size of organization from small scale to large scale organization present in Nagpur. The TNA will act as a source for achieving the organizational goals, if organizational design contains the TNA facility. For which the companies should set the process and should include in their HR policies. Organizations also need to confirm the quality assurance of the training for their needed employee and organizational development.

Training priorities will also be ranked against set up criteria including relevance to immediate local government, organizational needs, timeliness, training format & target group. Organizations can effectively implement training through using systematic needs assessments models. To ensure the effective training need assessment & fulfillment the organization can adopt the reviewing technique of TNA scorecard.

Implications for future research

The assessment begins with a need which can be identified in several ways but is generally described as a gap between what is currently in place and what is needed , now and in the future.

Gaps can include differences/Discrepancies between:

- 1) What the organization expects to happen and what actually happens.
- 2) Current & desired job performance.
- 3) Existing & desired competencies & skills.
- 4) Competencies & performance of work teams.
- 5) Problem solving or productivity issues.
- 6) The need to prepare for and respond to future changes in the organization or job duties.

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Influential Relationship Among The Stocks Of Top Thirty Bse Companies

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Abstract

Top thirty listed BSE companies were selected for analyzing the influential relationship among the stock prices and to identify future price movement & investment opportunity in these companies. Daily stock prices of the last ten years were arranged from BSE-100, making them stationary, the influential relationship of the stock prices was analyzed using correlation and regression tests. The result informs that Bharti Airtel, Coal India Ltd, Yes Bank Ltd and Infosys have perfect correlation and regression among the stocks selected and influences the other stocks giving an indication to investors for framing investment strategy.

Keywords: Influential relationship, linear relationship, BSE-50, investment opportunity.

JEL Classification: G-11, G-12, G-14, G-17,

Background

Prices of stocks are highly volatile in nature, most of the time investors invest their savings in stocks without analyzing the behavior of stock prices in the market with the changing market conditions, which result in higher probability of profits or losses to investors. Most investors and financial analysts are concerned about the uncertainty of the returns on their investment assets, caused by the variability in speculative market prices (and market risk) and the instability of business performance. Volatility has become a very important concept in different areas in financial theory and practice, such as risk management, portfolio selection, derivative pricing. In stock market, volatility is the key systematic risk faced by investors who hold a market portfolio and investors want a premium for investing in these risky assets. Stock prices are dependent upon the stock prices of different other companies' stock's even though companies are in different sectors, different activities, services and earning revenues from different sources but still their stocks are correlated to each other, they influence and being influenced by the fluctuations in the stocks of companies at a particular point of time. Investor need to consider the performance of their selected stock in the market, growth opportunities, investment opportunities in relation to understand the importance of relationship of stock of one company with other companies' stock and up to what extent the prices of other companies would influence the stock of their selected company. To analyze the interdependence of top thirty companies of Bombay stock exchange of India, correlation and regression of top thirty companies would play a vital role in interpreting the performance of their stock in relation to find the movement of other stocks in the market and provide knowledge as how to react in the market whether to invest or divest in the existing market and how that fluctuation would provide gain or loss to the investor.

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We have chosen top thirty companies of Bombay stock exchange and analyze the behavior of their stock in connection with the movement of their stocks along with the fluctuations in the other companies of the stock exchange which would help in analyzing the significance of dependent and independent stocks and up to what extent they may affected and being affected with the fluctuations in other stocks. Different variables are taken into consideration along with the price fluctuation and interdependency factor for determination of market scenario.

Literature Review

(Divya, 2017) in her study *A study on determinants of equity share prices of companies listed in BSE SENSEX*, observed that only one variable Dividend Payout ratio (DPR) can be used to determine the impact of all these variables on the market price of a share. A linear relationship is detected between the dependent and independent variables with the help of Scatter Plot.

The standardized Residual for the tests namely the Shapiro-Wilk Test and Jarque–Bera Test is found to be normally distributed which is indicated by Significance level which is higher than 0.05 where the data is considered to be normally distributed. (Bumtariya-2016) in their study *A research report on empirical investigation on CAPM model for performance of BSE 30 companies of stock market*, investigated the mobilizing resources for investment, directly from the investors, providing liquidity for the investors and monitoring and disciplining company managements are the principal functions of the stock markets. During the research specific findings involves, HDFC Ltd. having 5.51 % average cost of debt during the study period.it was also analyze that ICICI Bank Ltd, Hindalco industries Ltd., Tata Steel Ltd., Jindal Steel & Power Ltd., Tata Motors Ltd., Larsen & Toubro Ltd., Reliance industries Ltd., SBI Ltd., HDFC Ltd. and BHE Ltd. are the riskier securities among sampled companies during the study period. So far as concern to average Ke DLF Ltd. it shows that high risky security having high expected rate of return. Furthermore, it was also analyze that there is a high correlation between Beta & Ke during the study period. (J-2016) in their work *Financial performance analysis of selected BSE 30 companies an application DuPont model and ratio analysis techniques* found that Maruti Suzuki having highest ROS among selected BSE 30 companies during the study period. So far as concern to ROA it was found that TCS having highest ROA amongst selected BSE 30 companies during the study period. It shows that company has good managerial efficiency with concern to profit earning. Furthermore, it was also concluded that IT Sector got first position with concern to ROA as compare to other sectors of selected BSE –30 companies during the study period. It shows that company's earning capacity for its shareholders are high during the study period. Furthermore, it was also found that Tata Motors having lowest ROE during the study period. (BISWAL, p. c.-2011) conducted a research on, *An analysis of stock prices in India: wavelets and spectral applications*, with the objective to analyze stock price behavior in India in spectral domain, to show the wavelets as an alternative approach in analyzing stock price behavior in India, to carry out certain applications of wavelet analysis in Indian stock market, viz. long memory pattern and spillover effect. The findings include the time-scale decompositions or multi-scale nature clearly indicates the usefulness of the wavelets. In the stock market, there are traders who take a very long-term view and consequently concentrate on what are termed as market fundamentals. Their decisions have a time horizon of a few months to a year; so they may be interested in middle level wavelet decompositions of the return series. And yet other traders are in the market for whom a day is a long time and consequently concentrate on day-

by-day fluctuations. Given these observations, our study makes an important contribution to the existing literature, which would certainly provide a broad based framework to study and analyze the stock price behavior.

Objectives

- To analyze the inter stock relationship among top thirty companies of BSE-50;
- To identify the investment opportunity in selected companies.

Methodology

This research paper covers the stocks of the 30 companies which are listed in the Bombay Stock Exchange(BSE). In this research paper the study is conducted where it is seen how the stock price movement of one company can affect the stock of other company(s).

The BSE-30 companies were selected for the analysis based on their market capitalization. The companies are Adani Port, Bhartia Airtel, Axis Bank, Bajaj Auto, Coal India Ltd, HDFC Bank Ltd., Dr. Reddy Laboratory, HDFC, Hero Motors, Hindustan Unilever Ltd., ICICI Bank Ltd., IndusInd Ltd., Infosys, ITC, Kotak Mahindra, Larsen and Toubro, Mahindra and Mahindra, Maruti Suzuki, NTPC, Oil and Natural Gas, Power Grid Corp Ltd., Reliance Industries Ltd., SBI, Sun Pharma, Tata Consultancy, Tata Motors, Tata Steels, Wipro Ltd., Yes Bank.

Data set uses daily closing prices of selected companies for last eleven years ranging from 1/1/2007 to 31/12/2018.

The tools used for analysis are Microsoft Excel 2016, IBM SPSS (Regression and Co-relation). **Augmented Dickey Fuller (ADF)** test was used to check stationarity of data. The regression assumption test like **Breusch-Godfrey serial correlation LM test** to check the serial correlation of the residuals and **Heteroskedasticity test** and **ARCH LM test** were also used before finding the influential relationship. The regression model used in the study is $y = a + b_1x_1 + b_2x_2 + b_3x_3 + b_4x_4 + \dots + b_{29}x_{29} + e$.

Results And Discussion

Correlation

<Insert table- 1 >

The result of two tailed correlation test and interdependency of stocks:

We observed that there is negative correlation of Asian paints with Adani port, Axis bank, Airtel, Power Grid stock prices. There is weak downhill negative correlation among the prices of both the companies i.e -0.298. which states that with the fluctuations in the stock of Asian paints impact the prices of Adani port by 23.8% as prices would rises with the decrease in the prices of Asian paints. There is monotonous 57% effect of change in stock prices of Asian paints on the prices of axis bank which states that when the stock prices of Asian paints become double gradually than the prices of axis bank move in the same direction by one time increases whereas there is weak downhill linear relationship of Asian paints and Bajaj auto ltd of 0.151 which states that prices of Asian paints affect the prices of Bajaj auto ltd by 15% as with the increases in the prices of Asian paints the prices of Bajaj auto would increase by 15%.

HDFC bank and Asian paints have weak negative correlation -0.094. as prices of Asian paints would have minute impact of 9% on the prices of HDFC bank as the prices of HDFC bank would increases by 10% with the downfall in the prices of Asian paints but Asian paints impact the prices of Dr. Reddy laboratories by 20% having slightly impact on the fluctuations of stock prices. Asian paints would have strong uphill impact on the stock prices

of state bank of India of 52% whereas ICICI bank have 34.3% impact of changes in the stock prices of Asian paints.

The Stock prices of Adani port have the high downhill correlation with the stocks of reliance industries ltd, oil & natural gas corporation ltd, Larsen & Toubro ltd, Housing development finance corp. ltd , coal India ltd and Bharti Airtel. companies like HDFC, sun pharmaceuticals pvt ltd changed drastically with the change in the stock prices of Adani port by 85% as price movements are negatively correlated even though the service market of both the companies are not related to each other. Stocks of SBI, ICICI bank, Infosys have strong uphill correlation with the prices of axis bank of India which states that prices of SBI, ICICI bank and Infosys would move in the same direction and fluctuates with the movements the prices of axis bank of India by 75% whereas Stock prices of Asian paints have moderate positive correlation with prices of state bank of India, as stock prices moves in the same direction because they are strongly influenced with changes in the prices of axis bank fluctuations would be more than 50% with the changes due to internal and external fluctuations.

Stock prices of Bajaj auto ltd have weak uphill correlation with the prices of top thirty companies of Bombay stock exchange of India. As Bajaj auto will positively impact the prices of other twenty companies of stock but doesn't have high or moderate correlation with any other companies as variables are independent in nature they doesn't affect each other monotonously with the market changes. Bharti Ariel have perfect uphill correlation with prices of coal India i.e 1. prices of both the companies would impact the price movement of each other stock at the high pace which states that prices are strongly correlated to each other, increases or decrease in the prices of Ariel would drastically impact the prices movement of coal India ltd.

There is strong uphill correlation of stock prices of HDFC bank ltd with Tata motors, Tata steels, NTPC, oil and natural gas, Adani port which states that prices of above listed stock would move in the same direction due to positive correlation of stock prices with stocks of HDFC bank ltd as slight movement in the prices of HDFC bank would create drastic impact on the prices of tata motors, Tata steels, NTPC, oil and natural gas, Adani port. Stock prices of Dr. Reddy laboratories have very weak positive correlation with the stocks of other top twenty – nine companies of Bombay stock exchange of India. There is no strong relationship among the stocks for their movement which means that fluctuations in the stocks of Dr. Reddy laboratories would not impact majorly on the prices of other stocks. There is moderate positive correlation of stock prices of hero motors with Maruti Suzuki India ltd, Bajaj auto ltd, IndusInd ltd, Tata steels which states that fluctuations in stock prices of hero motors would not drastically impact the prices of these stocks but it would impact approximately create 25% positive impact on the stock prices. Major relationship of Hindustan Uniliver ltd would be with Maruti Suzuki of positive 21.5% and least with ITC of 2.05% which shows that both the companies have no linear relationship. . Major relationship of ICICI would be with Larsen and Turbro of positive 27.8% and least with Bajaj auto of 1.05% which shows that both the companies have no linear relationship.

Major relationship of IndusInd ltd would be with Maruti Suzuki of positive 37.8% and least with Asian paints of 0.7% which shows that both the companies have no linear relationship. Major relationship of Infosys would be with Tata consultancy of positive 31.2% and negative with sun pharma of 1.2% which shows that both the companies have inverse relationship.

Major correlation of ITC would be with HUL of positive 20.5% and least with Asian Paints of 0.53% which shows that both the companies have less linear relationship and Kotak Mahindra would be with Tata steel of positive correlation of 32.4% and least with Asian paints of 0.9% which shows that both the companies have no linear relationship. There is moderate positive correlation of Larsen and Turbo with stocks of Maruti Suzuki, IndusInd ltd, Dr. Reddy laboratories, HDFC, ITC, kotak Mahindra bank, reliance communication, Tata steels and sun pharmaceuticals research ltd. Major relationship of Mahindra and Mahindra would be with Maruti Suzuki of positive 27.2% and least with Asian paints of 0.3% which shows that both the companies have no linear relationship.

There is moderate positive correlation of stock prices of NTPC with Maruti Suzuki India ltd, Bajaj auto ltd, IndusInd ltd, Tata steels which states that fluctuations in stock prices of NTPC would not drastically impact the prices of these stocks but it would impact approximately create 25% positive impact on the stock prices whereas there is weak positive correlation of stock prices of hero motors ltd and Adani port, Airtel, Coal India ltd, HDFC bank, Hindustan Unilever ltd, ICICI bank, ITC, NTPC, state bank of India, Tata consultancy, Tata motors, Wipro, yes bank, axis bank. Major relationship of Oil and Natural gas would be with NTPC of positive 30.8% and least with Asian paints of 0.3% which shows that both the companies have no linear relationship. NTPC would be with Maruti Suzuki of positive 55.8% and least with Asian paints of 0.5% which shows that both the companies have no linear relationship. SBI have moderate positive correlation with stocks of Maruti Suzuki, IndusInd ltd, Dr. Reddy laboratories, HDFC, ITC, Kotak Mahindra bank, reliance communication, Tata steels and sun pharmaceuticals research ltd which states that stock prices of SBI would impact the stock prices of other top thirty-nine companies of Bombay stock exchange of India. Wipro would be with Tata Consultancy of positive 38.3% and no relationship with Asian paints which shows that both the companies have no linear relationship and Yes Bank would be with Tata Consultancy of positive 38.3% and least with Asian paints of 0.006% which shows that both the companies have no linear relationship.

Regression

< Table 2 >

Influential relationship:

Yes bank ltd, Infosys , Bharti airtel, Coal India ltd and Asian paints have perfect regression at the significance level which rejects the null hypothesis that there is no relationship between the stock prices of top thirty companies of Bombay stock exchange of India which states that there is perfect relationship among these stocks. stock analysis through regression states that stocks of listed four companies would drastically change with the fluctuation in the other stocks in the market. Bajaj Auto, Adani port, HDFC are the least affected stocks in align with other twenty-seven stocks.

Findings & Conclusion

The findings made on the interrelationship between the determinants in the study by analyzing the impact of stock prices of independent variables and states the existence of relationship among different companies' stock's. stocks of Bharti Airtel ltd, coal India ltd, Yes Bank ltd and Wipro ltd have perfect correlation and regression i.e 1, which symbolize that stocks are highly influenced with the movement in the prices of one company on the another. Investor should monitor the fluctuations in these stocks prices because any changes in any one stock price would drastically impact the price of other competitive stocks. If investor would analyze the price movement and decide accordingly whether they have to

invest or divest in the stock, then it would help investors to earn huge returns in the short span of time with much knowledge. Whereas other companies' stocks are influencing the stock prices but due to weak correlation and regression among those companies like Bajaj auto ltd, HDFC bank ltd have moderate or slight impact on the prices which states that their stock prices are influenced from independent stocks but having minimal impact on their movement.

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Appendix

TABLE 1: The result of two tailed correlation test and interdependency of stocks:

	Astana	Adani	azixbank	bajijAuto	bbartisAirtel	coolin disLT	HDF Cban LTD	Dr.RE DDYI abo	HDFC	Hero Motor	HindustanUniliver LTD	ICICIbank LTD	INDUSIndlTD	INFOSYS	ITC	KOTA Kmahindra	AIRTEL	LARS ENR broLT	MshindrsAndM Suzuki	maruti Suzuki	NTPC	OilAndNat Gas	Power GridCo rpltd	RelianceIndustries LTD	SBI	SunPharmaAdv.R esearch	tataCo nsultancy	tataMot ors	tataSte elz	wipro Ltd	YczB ank				
Adani Pearson	-.238	1																																	
Sig (2-N)	.000																																		
2439	2439	2439	2379	2439	2439	2439	2439	2439	2439	2439	2439	2439	2439	2439	2439	2439	2439	2439	2439	2439	2439	2439	2439	2439	2439	2439	2439	2439	2439	2439	2439	2439	2439	2439	
azixbank Pearson	.575	-.119	1																																
Sig (2-N)	.000	.000																																	
2724	2439	2725	2379	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	
bajijAuto Pearson	-.187	-.045	-.217	1																															
Sig (2-N)	.000	.023	.000																																
2379	2379	2379	2379	2379	2379	2379	2379	2379	2379	2379	2379	2379	2379	2379	2379	2379	2379	2379	2379	2379	2379	2379	2379	2379	2379	2379	2379	2379	2379	2379	2379	2379	2379	2379	
bbartisAirtel Pearson	-.353	.573	-.306	-.565	1																														
Sig (2-N)	.000	.000	.000	.000																															
2724	2439	2725	2379	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	
coolin disLT Pearson	-.353	.573	-.306	-.565	1.000																														
Sig (2-N)	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000																														
2724	2439	2725	2379	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	
HDF Cban LTD Pearson	-.094	.479	.063	.034	.036	.036	1																												
Sig (2-N)	.000	.000	.001	.000	.000	.000	.000																												
2724	2439	2725	2379	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	
Dr.R EDD Ylab Pearson	-.182	-.414	-.203	.776	-.622	-.622	-.179	1																											
Sig (2-N)	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000																											
2724	2439	2725	2379	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	
HDF C Pearson	-.351	.836	-.221	-.058	.548	.548	.432	-.457	1																										
Sig (2-N)	.000	.000	.000	.005	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000																										
2724	2439	2725	2379	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	
Hero Motor Pearson	-.123	-.293	-.224	.319	-.641	-.641	.039	.820	-.309	1																									
Sig (2-N)	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.041	.000	.000	.000																									
2724	2439	2725	2379	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	
HindustanUniliver LTD Pearson	-.238	-.285	-.336	.825	-.443	-.443	-.031	.837	-.286	.306	1																								
Sig (2-N)	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000																								
2724	2439	2725	2379	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	
ICICI bank LTD Pearson	.343	-.029	.701	-.264	.048	.048	-.042	-.343	-.032	-.430	-.532	1																							
Sig (2-N)	.000	.151	.000	.000	.012	.012	.030	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000																							
2724	2439	2725	2379	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	
INDUSIndlTD Pearson	-.224	-.200	-.402	.848	-.410	-.410	.062	.712	-.203	.318	.365	-.580	1																						
Sig (2-N)	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.001	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000																						
2724	2439	2725	2379	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	
INFO SYS Pearson	.322	-.242	.687	-.223	-.301	-.301	-.111	-.031	-.335	-.213	-.382	.829	-.475	1																					
Sig (2-N)	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000																					
2724	2439	2725	2379	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	
ITC Pearson	-.114	-.234	-.015	.536	-.566	-.566	-.321	.775	-.239	.623	.673	-.082	.542	.106	1																				
Sig (2-N)	.000	.000	.420	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000																				
2724	2439	2725	2379	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	2725	
KOTA Kmahindra Pearson	-.325	.314	-.183	.648	-.041	-.041	.086	.466	.256	.453	.542	-.095	.435	-.108	.566	1																			
Sig (2-N)	.000	.000																																	

TABLE 2: Influential relationship:

Dependent variables	R	Adjusted R Squ	F	significanc
adani port	0.273	0.075	7.032	0.00
asian paints	1	0.97		0.00
axis bank	0.387	0.15	15.324	0.00
bajaj auto	0.141	0.132	14.344	0.00
bharti airtel	1	1		0.00
coal india ltd	1	1		0.00
Dr. reddy laboratories	0.302	0.081	8.751	0.00
HDFC bank ltd	0.293	0.076	8.199	0.00
HDFC	0.365	0.123	13.341	0.00
Hero motor cop.	0.475	0.217	25.403	0.00
hindustan uniliver	0.36	0.119	12.922	0.00
icici bank ltd	0.377	0.133	14.46	0.00
indus Ind ltd	0.497	0.239	28.612	0.00
infosys	0.352	0.114	12.319	0.00
ITC	0.312	0.087	9.357	0.00
Kotak mahindra	0.419	0.166	18.522	0.00
Larsen and Toubro	0.468	0.21	24.433	0.00
Mahindra and Mahindra	0.38	0.134	14.651	0.00
Maruti and Suzuki	0.53	0.273	34.054	0.00
NTPC	0.595	0.346	47.587	0.00
Oil and Natural Gas Ltd.	0.332	0.1	10.797	0.00
Power and Grid Corp of India	0.561	0.307	39.913	0.00
Reliances Industries	0.474	0.216	25.282	0.00
State Bank of India	0.374	0.13	14.149	0.00
SunPharma	0.306	0.083	8.974	0.00
Tata Consultancy	0.441	0.186	21.064	0.00
Tata Motors	0.431	0.176	19.816	0.00
Tata Steels	0.614	0.37	52.626	0.00
WiproLtd	1	1		0.00
Yes Bank	1	1		0.00

Sources: Author compilation.

Proposed Countermeasure For Side Channel Attack To Protect Detection Of Encryption Key And Algorithm From Power Consumption Signature

PADMAVATHI K

DR. PRASENJIT CHOWDHURY

Abstract

Cryptographic algorithms are generally designed to cost thousands of years of crypto analysis computation time [196, 201, 202] to break the code, but when they are actualized as a technology, software implementation or hardware details are easier to glean, allowing leakage of information that can help crack them in days, not centuries. Knowledge of execution time, power dissipation pattern or even magnetic radiation and its spectral content can help infer key parameters, narrowing the options to guide the search for hacking successfully. This information is not the main information like key, password etc. So, it is called side channel, and the modus operandi is called *side channel attack* (SCA). Counter measure approach to cover-up details of software implementations by emulating hardware implementations are discussed in this chapter. Such counter measures maintain the generality of secure circuits, but do not succumb to the limitations of specific algorithm, thereby increasing the flexibility of the approach. A closer look at implementation options reveals embedded systems are common in many low ends as well as high end systems, and they play an essential role in our society. The attacks against these systems are achieving higher levels of sophistication and critical mass. Latest technologies are having difficulty coping with dual requirement of higher performance and enhanced security, thereby necessitating new solutions that enable a clear definition of 'secure embedded system'.

Keywords: Cryptographic, Reconfigurable, Algorithms, Advanced Encryption Standard

1.1 Introduction

Cryptographic algorithms are generally designed to cost thousands of years of crypto analysis computation time [196, 201, 202] to break the code, but when they are actualized as a technology, software implementation or hardware details are easier to glean, allowing leakage of information that can help crack them in days, not centuries. Knowledge of execution time, power dissipation pattern or even magnetic radiation and its spectral content can help infer key parameters, narrowing the options to guide the search for hacking successfully. This information is not the main information like key, password etc. So, it is called side channel, and the modus operandi is called *side channel attack* (SCA). Counter measure approach to cover-up details of software implementations by emulating hardware implementations are discussed in this chapter. Such counter measures maintain the generality of secure circuits, but do not succumb to the limitations of specific algorithm, thereby increasing the flexibility of the approach. A closer look at implementation options reveals embedded systems are common in many low ends as well as high end systems, and they play an essential role in our society. The attacks against these systems are achieving higher levels of sophistication and critical mass. Latest technologies are having difficulty coping with dual requirement of higher performance and enhanced security, thereby

necessitating new solutions that enable a clear definition of ‘secure embedded system’. In such systems, architectures are not only tamper resistant and reliable, but also enable high performance and energy efficient requirements. Such secure embedded systems prevent attacks or react when an attack has been detected while guaranteeing the energy and computational efficiency of the system. FPGAs can address these requirements and provide efficient security primitives [198]. But before delving into the solution space, we highlight current vulnerabilities of FPGA at all levels of the security pyramid (in Figure 4.1). While studying and designing solutions, it is best to identify the weakest point in the whole security pyramid, as there is no additional value of newer solutions, without addressing the weakest link in the security chain. Severe attacks can be mounted by exploiting simple weaknesses in a system, and make massive brute force computational attacks unnecessary.

Figure 1.1 Security Pyramid: Toward A Defense-In-Depth [198]

Any information that gives hints or details about a cryptographic device can be useful to mount and attack, and over the years it has become necessary to guard against quite a few types of threat patterns. For example, it does not take high competency to extract power consumption or electromagnetic emissions, and careful study of spectral content can indicate the size of the encryption key, and other inference on class of algorithm used. In other cases, errors can be induced during encryption or decryption process. Thus, it is necessary to protect cryptographic devices against fault injection or leakage of information. Counter measures for ASICs are well established over the years, but this is not the case for FPGA devices. Studies in the areas of academics and Industry have been conducted so far for investigating the integrity and confidentiality of FPGA devices.

Security in Reconfigurable Hardware Devices

Many design criteria have to be considered while selecting an implementation platform in a digital system. There is need to look beyond obvious criteria like system performance, speed and area cost of a system, to additional security criteria like physical security (against key recovery and algorithm manipulation) flexibility of security algorithm, power consumption that could end up effecting design selection. The theory and research publications on cryptographic implementation on FPGA devices are extensive, but few papers have anything to say about the convenience levels of using FPGA devices as a target device for security applications from a system point of view. There are some reports of resilience of FPGA against physical or system attacks, which too are quite dangerous compared to brainy algorithm attacks [144-146]. A detail analysis of FPGA security [146-147] reflects that FPGA technology can provide security levels quite reasonable when used properly.

The fourth-generation design security of Xilinx Virtex-4 family is equipped with bitstream encryption/decryption technology based on 256-bit Advanced Encryption Standard [AES]. The user generates the encryption key and encrypted bit-stream using Xilinx ISE software. In the second step, during configuration, the Virtex-4 device decrypts the incoming bit-stream using a decryption logic module with dedicated memory for storing the 256-bit encryption key [148].

The major threat for cryptographic applications is disclosure of the confidential cryptographic key, either a symmetric key or the private key of an asymmetric algorithm. As per the outcome, FPGA implementations are also vulnerable to side-channel attacks [142,146], in which information is gained directly from the physical implementation. As mentioned earlier, extraction from power consumption, timing behavior, and electromagnetic radiation are discussed extensively [136-140, 143]. The concept of Power analysis attacks was introduced in 1998 by Kocher et al. [150], where power consumption of the FPGA device is measured closely during the execution of a cryptographic operation. Thereafter, that power consumption can be analyzed in an effort for finding regions in the power consumption trace of a device that are correlated with algorithm's secret key.

The first experimental setup in a lab, and the results of a power analysis attack [142] showed a methodical approach to glean side band information from elliptical curve cryptosystem implementation. Later, RSA, AES and DES based FPGA implementations were also shown to be vulnerable [144-145]. They showed that SCA can crack a crypto implementation much faster than a brute force crypto-analysis approach. The main advantage of crypto implementation is exorbitant computational cost imposed due to exponential complexity. But SCA based methodology brought unexpected parameters to aid cracking, thereby reducing the complexity quite drastically. It showed the crypto key could be methodically inferred bit by bit, or piece by piece.

Let's take a more detailed look at the working of an SCA approach with a graphical description of the concept in figure 4.2. Let's label the cryptographic algorithm as f , which responds to input *plaintext* (PT), and the *key* (K) to generate an *Encryption Response* [ER .] Thus $ER=f(PT,K)$, and the goal of the SCA is to infer the key K , that is otherwise not directly observable through the ports of the FPGA device.

Figure: 1.2 An Example Of Side Channel Attack On Crypto-Device And Uncovers The Key Enclosed [198]

We already know that each bit of ER is related to the individual bit combinations of PT and K . In the case that K has 128 bits; a brute force attack needs to consider 2^{128} possible values of the key that would cost an exorbitant computational resource for a traditional brute force attack, hence aiding the security of the cryptographic algorithm. But an SCA attack breaks the 128 bit monolithic key into smaller pieces, even as small as 1 bit each.

Hence the search space of the key is reduced from 2^{128} to smaller $16 \cdot 2^k = 2^{16}$, which can be seen as a drastic reduction in complexity. The simplest way to understand this is that not only the full correct key value correlates with the power consumption signal traces, but correlations can be found to infer *intermediate values* of key also. This the breaking of the key K , into *intermediate values* $[IV]$, allows for partitioning of key, hence complexity of breaking the crypto algorithm. Although every single bit of the output ER is guaranteed to be related to every bit of K , this is not true for the intermediate values. It can always find intermediate values that are only related to a small part of K , e.g. one byte of K . For example, assume that it can find an intermediate value IV which depends on a single key byte $K[7 : 0]$ and the plaintext PT . It can be written as

$$IV = g(PT, K[7 : 0]).$$

Then $K[7 : 0]$ can be discovered with only 2^8 guesses. To test which guess is correct, wit is required to observe IV . This variable is inside the implementation, but it is indirectly observable through its power dissipation. Indeed, the power dissipated by IV is a part of the power dissipated by the entire device, which can be measured by the attackers. Hence, by measurement of the chip power dissipation, there is a way to test the guesses the attacker makes on a single key byte. Through proper correlation techniques, the chip's overall power dissipation can be used in place of the power dissipation from IV , while the power dissipated by unrelated components can be treated as noise. Power SCA techniques have emerged in recent years, and a Unified Framework for the Analysis of Side-Channel Key Recovery Attacks: extended version is shown in Figure 4.3.

Figure: 1.3 Unified Framework for the Analysis of Side-Channel Key Recovery Attacks [200]

1.2 Problem Statement

Published literature has already demonstrated need to protect against Side Channel Attacks to protect detection of encryption key and algorithm from power consumption signature. Countermeasures proposed to overcome Simple Power Analysis (SPA) and Differential Power Analysis (DPA), are data masking, table masking, current flattening, circuitry level solutions, dummy instruction insertions and balancing bit-flips. All these techniques are either susceptible to multi-order side channel attacks, not sufficiently generic to cover all encryption algorithms, or burden the system with high area cost, runtime or energy consumption.

Methods like RIJID have demonstrated ability to mask these through inserting dummy instructions as discussed. But these solutions require compiler support, knowledge of specific algorithm, and an assumption that the system can be contained in the chip memory. This approach violates the earlier goal for a unified solution space independent of application and platform specifics.

1.3 Method Of Solution

For mission critical applications, Countermeasures for SCA are one of the most important requirements.

To overcome the pitfalls of previous countermeasures, a Hardware/Software based randomized module injection technique is proposed in this study. To protect the system from both SPA and DPA, proposed technique injects random hardware modules at random places during the execution of an application. After that, it is design systematic method to measure the security level of a power analysis attack.

In this thesis, research presents a SCA modules that are inserted at random interval of time. This is done at run time using partial reconfiguration feature of FPGAs. The hardware modules are pre-generated and stored in external memory. These modules are dynamically loaded during run time while cryptographic algorithms are running on the system. In addition to being application independent implementation, it shows more than 50X more difficult in key decidability.

This chapter concludes with the discussion on the implementation with respect to area overhead, power consumption of the device. It also emphasizes that the proposed approach is cryptographic algorithm independent.

1.4 Power Analysis Attacks

In these attacks the power consumption of devices, especially cryptographic modules, is studied by the attackers [196,199]. Close proximity to a sensor node to measure the power consumption of the sensor node is required to mount a power analysis attack. There are two types of power analysis [200]: simple power analysis (SPA) and differential power analysis (DPA).

1.4.1 SPA

The attacker directly observes the device's power consumption. The working principle is that power consumed by the device varies depending on the data processed on and the instructions performed during different parts of an execution. A power trace is a set of power consumption measurements during a cryptographic operation. By closely studying power traces, it is possible to determine the characteristic details of a cryptographic device and the algorithm being used.

1.4.2DPA

It exploits characteristic behavior using statistical analysis to extract hidden information from a large sample of power traces obtained during controlled cryptographic computations [149]. In a dynamic power analysis based attack, the attacker does not need to know so many details about how the algorithm is implemented like in a SPA. Secret key is obtained bit by bit. It is based on the different amount of power consumption that the algorithm needs to manipulate a certain bit (if it is zero or one) during a **specific time**.

1.5 SCA Counter measures

There are generally two kinds of macro strategies to counter sorts of SCAs, by physical tactics or by structural improvements on the functional level [153].

1.5.1PHYSICAL PROTECTION

Encapsulate the sensor node with some special casing could avoid or at least reduce the strength of certain kinds of SCAs. A tamper-proof casing, on the other hand, could also prevent wear and tear due to brutal environment factors. In allusion to different scenarios, a variety of casings are deployed.

1.5.2FUNCTIONAL PROTECTION

Another macro category of SCA-countermeasures is based on the functional protection. Functional protection is the generic term which refers to all the SCA-countermeasures except for the physical methods (i.e. Casing). In this kind of protection, various techniques are used to counter different sorts of SCAs, commonly or respectively.

1.6 Importance Of Counter Measuring Differential Power Analysis

Among all of these SCAs, the attack towards power characteristics is particularly devastating for cryptographic implementations. SPA (Simple Power Analysis) was firstly introduced by Paul Kocher et al in 1998 [150]. SPA exploits the facts that different operations and different data values processed by a component must have different power consumption characteristics. In the SPA attacks, the attacker only focuses on single power trace to look for such power characteristics and was proved to be successful in attacks to SMART cards [151]. DPA (Differential Power Analysis), on the other hand, depends on a large number of power traces to analyze the intermediate value of the cryptographic algorithm and then guess and verify the secret key of the cryptographic algorithm by means of statistical methods [150]. DPA attack looks at (multiple) specific intermediate values of the implementation, thus it's especially hard to be defeated. The current countermeasures are generally based on normalizing the power difference or randomizing the power characteristics. Reconfigurable device, to some extent, offers a preferable implementation platform to meet the requirements of the balance between high-security insurance and low-power control.

Side Channel Attack (SCA) can be applied to unprotected implementations of any algorithm. It works because an attacker can confirm an intermediate value of the secret key which correlates with a small part of the secret key that occurs during the execution of decryption – encryption algorithm. Since the processed data produces a strong signature in the power consumption of the implementation, there is a strong correlation between the power consumption and the intermediate values. So an attacker can quickly check the quality of correctness of their partial prediction by calculating this correlation. This observation also hints at a way to counteract SCA is to randomize the intermediate values that occur during the execution of the algorithm by adding another secret value, which is called mask. When this mask value is changed for every execution of the algorithm, the power dissipation signature becomes difficult to correlate for intermediate values, and the attacker is thus

unable to predict intermediate values. In this work, experimental setup for power analysis on FPGA is developed as shown in Figure 3-4. Different case studies have been described here.

Figure: 1.4 DPA Attack Flow For Our AES Circuit

1.7 Novel Approach To Counter Measure Using Partial Reconfiguration

- Published literature already extensively discussed in chapter one and it is demonstrating the need to protect against Side Channel Attacks to protect detection of encryption key and algorithm from power consumption signature. Methods like RIJID have demonstrated ability to mask these through inserting dummy instructions as discussed. But these solutions require compiler support, knowledge of specific algorithm and an assumption that the system can be contained in the chip memory. This approach violates the earlier goal for a unified solution space independent of application encryption algorithm and architectural specifics.
- The research in this thesis presents SCA modules that are inserted at random interval of time. This is done at run time using partial reconfiguration feature of FPGAs. The hardware modules are pre-generated and stored in external memory. These modules are dynamically loaded during run time while cryptographic algorithms are running on the system. In addition to being application independent implementation, it shows more than 50X more difficult in key decode ability.
- The proposed technique inserts random hardware modules at random places in FPGAs at the time of application execution, which protects the system from power analysis attacks, both SPA and DPA. Further, systematic method is devised to measure the security level of a power trace.

1.7.1 GENERAL OVERVIEW OF PROPOSED APPROACH

A PR design platform using Microblaze embedded processor is designed as shown in Figure 4.5. The FPGA is configured with Static region and partial region. The static region has local logic as well as softcore processor Microblaze. The Cryptographic algorithm written in C/C++ is executed in Microblaze. The code is stored in External memory. This is base system without the countermeasure. This we refer as software version. The power is measured for the given algorithm as per the experimental setup shown in Figure 3.10.

SCA countermeasure is made active by injecting Hardware module in the Partial Reconfiguration region identified in the system as shown in Figure 3.6 and 3.9.

Figure: 1.5 PR Design Using Embedded Microcontroller In FPGA

The hardware modules to be configured are of different size, in terms of area and power consumption signature. The hardware modules are composed of free running counters. The counters are of 4 bit, 8 bit, 16 bit and 32 bit. Depending on the size of counters, the area and power of hardware modules varies. So, their configuration bit file size and configuration time varies with reference to their size. The configuration bit files of these are pre-generated for partial reconfiguration region defined in FPGA. This configuration bit files are stored in Compact FLASH or BRAM of the FPGAs as shown in Figure 3.9. The Hardware modules are changed during runtime as shown in Figure 3.7, As per the software design flow in Figure 3.8 and the algorithm is implemented. The cryptographic software [200] is to be modified as per software design flow. Critical points of software are to be identified, which leaks significant information for power analysis. Here software code is to be added as shown in the algorithm flow below, which randomly chooses the hardware module and insert it in the FPGA. The pre-designed hardware modules of various sizes are kept in memory as bit files. This hardware module have different sizes in terms of configuration bit file size as well as different /varying power signatures It actually now decides the power signature of the FPGA device. These modules are randomly selected and inserted at run time. The seed of the selections is left to the software written in C. It actually uses the random function of C library and chooses the hardware module number. The Crypto algorithms are iterative process, so in each round, it will have come across another hardware module in the runtime. This is how the power consumption of device is varied and power analysis is masked. The proposed method of hardware module insertion is independent of algorithm as it is to be updated in the software part of the crypto algorithm. This helps in improving the mechanism against RIJID where we require the knowledge of Crypto algorithm to find location for instruction injection and special compiler support.

Algorithm To Implement Hardware Module

Execution of Cryptographic Algorithm.

Insert the following at critical points of cryptographic algorithm.

SET FLAG: Insert hardware module.

Choose hardware module randomly form given list.

Read configuration bit file of chosen hardware module. Load the configuration bit file into the FPGA partial reconfiguration module position.

RESET FLAG:

Figure: 1.6 Block Diagram of System with Multiple PRRs (Courtesy: Xilinx) PRR – Partially Reconfigurable Regions

e.g. Initially a basic system is loaded, where only Microprocessor and basic I/O are available. After some time two hardware modules A and B are loaded. After certain amount of time the Hardware module B is stopped and another module C is loaded in place of module B as shown in Figure 4.7.

Figure: 1.7 Run Time Reconfiguration of Hardware Module Injection (courtesy: Xilinx)

This is how the power consumption of system is varied.

The Power measurements are carried out using simple cryptographic algorithms executed in Microblaze with no hardware modules and with random insertion of hardware modules of same size or different size, at fixed and random intervals. The software design flow is as shown in Figure 4.8.

SOFTWARE DESIGN FLOW

Figure: 1.8 Software Design Flow

Figure: 1.9 Hardware Module Configuration with File with PRRs

1.7.2 EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

Xilinx soft core processor Microblaze (MB) is used to build a PR based SoC Platform. Xilinx Virtex5 LX110T FPGA based board is used for prototype implementation. The MB processor is clocked at 100 MHz. The software application is written with the use of SDK and stored on-board DDR2 SRAM memory. The DDR memory also stores an AES encryption key which cannot be read out of the board. The experimental setup consists of FPGA board hooked, Tektronix Oscilloscope (Tektronix 2014) and a PC, as shown in Figure 4.10. For the data transfer between FPGA board and PC UART is used via RS232 cable. The current measurement is carried out by measurement through 1-ohm resistor mechanism. The current flowing into the FPGA core is measured by the current probe (Tektronix CT-2) hooked to an oscilloscope. Power consumption signature of the FPGA is rated through current. JTAG cable is used for on chip data transfer between FPGA board and PC through Chip Scope for online debugging. The data transfer across the PC and oscilloscope is through USB cable communication between the oscilloscope and the PC. The PC is thus able to send command to the oscilloscope; for example - to require the oscilloscope to sample current traces with the current probe. After one sampling is finished, the PC is also able to obtain the current sample trace also through the USB cable.

Figure: 4. 10 Experimental Setup of Countermeasure of SCA on FPGA

Power measurement for SCA: For every measurement, the following steps of operations are performed:

- The PC sends a random Plain Text message (16 bytes) (PT) to the FPGA board through the RS-232 cable. The PT is also recorded in the PC.
- The Microblaze receives PT from the RS-232 cable, calculates the cryptographic program with PT; and PT as per the software implementation. Cipher is the cryptographic application under attack.
- After sending out PT, the PC sends command to the oscilloscope to sample the current trace when the Microblaze is running cryptographic algorithm and also inserting Hardware module run time in the FPGA when it is performing encryption.
- When sampling is done, the oscilloscope sends the current trace TR [999:0] (1000 sampling points) back to PC for further analysis.

1.7.3 CORRELATION POWER ATTACK

As the name suggests, a SCA called Correlation Power Attack (CPA) [153] is mounted with the above measurement results. In the experiments, CPA focuses on the SubBytes step (16 bytes) outputs in the first round of the AES algorithm. CPA is a searching process and every output is only related to one byte of the key. To attack one key byte, it goes through every possible value of that key byte ($2^8 = 256$ possible values). Different outputs of the Sub Bytes operation are used for different key guesses, which leads to different power dissipation expectations, called *power hypothesis*. A decision function calculates the correlation coefficient of the power hypothesis and the actual current measurement traces, to identify the correct key value that is used by the encryption, where the correct key guess results in larger correlation coefficient than any other incorrect key guess. Every sample trace has 1000 sample points that cover a certain range of time (500 us in experiments) which includes the calculation of the first round of the AES. Although the attackers do not know which points correspond to the instruction execution related to the Sub Bytes's outputs, brute forcing

through every point is still possible by increasing the analysis complexity, but the analysis time is still acceptable.

The key point (Table 4.1) shows that the protected AES (with hardware module insertion) is much harder to attack. Experiments are first compared with the unprotected AES (AES) and then to the protected AES (referring to Random Hardware module insertion) implementations. The attack results on one of AES's key bytes with 5120 measurements as an example are shown in Figure 4.11, where the time that each measurement covers is represented on the x-axis. The first-round execution of AES occurs within this time range. The correlation coefficient between the power hypothesis and the actual current measurement is represented on the y-axis. The CPA analysis is mounted at each sampling point (1000 in total), which results in 256 correlation coefficients for 256 possible key values. Figure 4.11 is thus obtained after finishing SCA analysis at 1000 different sampling points.

Figure: 1.11 Attack Result on Unprotected AES

Attack result on unprotected AES: Correlation between the sampled current and the power expectations with 5120 measurements is shown. Correct key's trace is plotted in black here, while all other key's traces are plotted in gray. The emerged black trace represents successful attack.

Figure: 1.12 Attack Result on Protected AES System

Attack result on protected AES system: Correlation between the sampled current and the power estimations with 5120 measurements is shown again. Correct key's trace is plotted in

black here, while all other key's traces are plotted in gray. The buried black trace represents unsuccessful attack.

Correlation coefficient values of AES for different keys

Figure: 1.13 Correlation Coefficient Values of AES for Different Keys. There Are More Than One Significant Peaks.

Figure 4.13 is the plot of correlation coefficient values of AES for different keys. The correlation peaks indicate in this time frame the presence of key. These correlation peaks are further analyzed for identification of key numbers. Figure 4.14 shows the correlation coefficient of key “43” identified from the analyzed data. It is observed that key no. “43” out of 256 keys of AES has highest value of correlation; it implies that key “43” is identified. Figure 4.15 shows the output of correlation coefficient of different keys for masked power traces with our proposed SCA-CM mechanism. It is clearly seen that no significant peak is observed in any of the 256 keys. It is obvious from the plots and analysis that our proposed scheme offers Side channel attack Counter Measure.

Figure: 4.14 Correlation Coefficient Values Of AES For Different Keys. There Is A Significant Peak Corresponding To Correct Key 43

Figure: 4.15 Correlation Coefficient Values Of Masked AES For Different Keys.

There Is No Such Significant Peak So That Correct Key Can Be Guessed

The black trace corresponds to the correlation coefficients at 1000 different time points when correct key byte value is used to calculate the power hypothesis. The gray traces correspond to other incorrect key byte values. It turns out that the black trace differentiates itself from all the other gray traces (around 200 μ s). This means that the correct key byte value can be identified and the attack is successful. The experiment also mounted the same CPA attack with hardware module insertion of random size and also at random time with fixed size implementation. The example of the attack on the same key byte is shown in Figure 4.11. The black trace is totally buried into the gray traces. So the correct key byte value is not identifiable. Therefore, the attack is not successful. Figure 4.11 and 4.12 give two visualized attack examples when the sampling trace number is 5120. To quantify the security improvement, researchers usually use *Measurement to Disclosure* (MTD). MTD gives the number of measurements required for a successful attack. Larger MTD indicates better security. Here, we define the successful attack to be uncovering all 16 bytes of the AES key. Table 4.1 presents more detailed attack results. For AES, 1280 measurements are sufficient to uncover all 16 key bytes. For AES with hardware module insertion, the number of measurements for full attack increases to 25600. The improvement is as high as 20. All these designs could be broken with a similar effort to break AES, as shown in Table 4.1. Table 4.1 also shows that AES with hardware module (random size) insertion, pays 10.7 times decrease of throughput and 1.1 times increase of footprint for higher capability of resisting CPA. The Power consumption increases by almost 90- 100 %. Since the implementation is having larger power but it has flexibility of using a platform for any encryption algorithm without modifying any hardware details of designed system. Just by changing the cryptographic algorithm to be implemented in the software is to be modified by inserting code of Hardware module injection at the critical point of cryptographic algorithm. It is also tested on DES and 3DES cryptographic algorithm.

Table: 4.1 Attack Results Summary for AES Algorithm

Parameter	AES	AES with Hardware Module insertion of random size	AES with Hardware Module insertion of Fixed size at random interval
Throughput (kb/s)	1100	103	144
Footprint of software (kB)	45.7	48.3	48.3
Key bytes not found ¹			
@ 512	4	16	16
@1280	0	15	15
@5120	0	10	10
@12800	0	5	4
@25600	0	3	1

1 Number of measurements

Table: 4.2 Synthesis Results –Device Utilization Summary: Xilinx Virtex - 5LX110T1ff1136 for AES

Resources	Original: Without Random Hardware insertion			Random Hardware insertion		Overhead OH
	Available	Used	Utilization	Used	Utilization	
Slice Registers	69120	2599	3.76 %	3400	4.91 %	1.15 %
Number of LUTs	69120	2220	3.76 %	3400	4.91 %	1.15 %
Number of Bonded IOBs	640	48	7.5 %	48	7.5 %	0 %
Number of Block RAMs/FIFO	148	66	0.62 %	148	0.62 %	0 %
Number of BufG/BufGCTRLS	32	4	12.5 %	4	12.5 %	0 %
Number of ICAPs	2	0	0 %	1	50 %	50 %

Table: 4.3 Details about the Random Hardware Module Sizes and Their Configuration Bit Size with Configuration Time

Hardware modules for Partial Reconfiguration	Size in terms of CLBs	Configuration File size	Configuration time
Size 1 x	5 × 5	14 KB	0.14 ms
2 x	10 × 5	29 KB	0.29 ms
3 x	10 × 10	56 KB	0.56 ms
4 x	15 × 10	80 KB	0.80 ms

Full Configuration of FPGA:

3799KB (Configuration Bit File size) so configuration time is 37.99 ms at clock frequency of 100 MHz.

Table 4.4 Power consumption report for various Cryptographic algorithms

Strategy / Cryptographic Algorithm	Average Power _W [mW]		
	AES	DES	3DES
No Countermeasure	1231	1020	1365
Software Counter measure	1274	1042	1402
With random size of Hardware module with regular interval	1822	1657	2033
With random Time insertion of Hardware module with fixed size (10 × 10)	1820	1650	2010

Figure: 4.16 Power Consumption Comparison for Various Crypto Algorithms with Proposed Approach

It can be noticed from the graph shown in Figure 4.16 that there is no significant difference between no countermeasure and software counter measure. But Hardware counter measure power consumption is increased by 56 % or so. But it gives the safety almost 20 times as discussed earlier.

RIJJD [95] framework is using Random Code injection to Mask power analysis but it requires special hardware changes in the processor architecture along with compiler support. We are comparing our proposal with it in terms of energy overhead, hardware overhead and run time overhead for various encryption algorithms in the following table 4.5.

Table 4.5 Comparison With RIJID

Types of Overheads	SCA Counter Measure methods	Types of Encryption Algorithm			
		AES	DES	3DES	RSA
Hardware Overhead in %	RIJID	1.98	1.98	1.98	1.98
	Our proposal	1.15	1.15	1.15	1.15
Run Time Overhead in %	RIJID	24.67	--	--	32.97
	Our Proposal	21.24	21.24	21.24	21.24
Energy Overhead in %	RIJID	38.2	18.9	19.1	12.5
	Our Proposal	67	61	67	67

1.8 Conclusion

To overcome the drawbacks of previous countermeasures, a Hardware/Software based randomized hardware module injection technique is proposed here. The Proposed technique injects random hardware modules at random places in FPGAs during the execution of an application which protects the system from both SPA and DPA. For AES with hardware module insertion, the number of measurements for full attack increases to 25600. The improvement is as high as 20 time compare to no countermeasure. It also shows that AES with hardware module (random size) insertion, pays 10.7 times decrease of throughput and 1.1 times increase of footprint for higher capability of resisting CPA. The Power consumption increases by almost 60 %. The hardware overhead is 5-10 % depends on number of hardware modules used. The proposed implementation is having larger power but it has flexibility of using platform for any encryption algorithm without modifying any hardware details of designed system. Here modification is required in software by inserting code for Hardware module injection at the critical point of cryptographic algorithm.

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A Study Of Induction Motor Protection System

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Abstract

In the current era of automation, an induction motor is the most significant drive as this motor is applicable in a number of industrial applications. A protection mechanism is needed in order to protect these motors from all kinds of faults either electrical or mechanical. There are a lot of electrical faults which can be occurred in an induction motor. Some of these faults are high voltage, lower voltage, earth fault and overload etc. It is observed that the lives of these motors tend to shorten due to electrical faults as these motors get heated. The reason for the fault in an induction motor can be due to fault in the driven plant due to higher supply of power externally. The current paper highlights the mechanism for the protection of an induction motor.

Keywords: Induction Motor, Fault, Power

Introduction

An induction motor is also known as asynchronous motor which can be used for many applications. The speed of these motors is lesser than that of synchronous speed where the synchronous speed is considered as the magnetic field speed which is used to rotate the stator.

According to the sorts of supply of input, there are basically two types of induction motor i.e. single phase and three phase induction motors. Wound type and slip ring motor are the further classification of three phase induction motor.

Induction Motor

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Supply is essential in DC motor in order to aid the rotor and stator winding. But, in case of induction motor, only AC supply is provided related with the stator winding. As a result of AC supply, a flux is adjusted in the stator winding.

A rotating magnetic field is formed when this flux is allowed to rotate with normal speed i.e. synchronous speed. Due to alternative speeds in conductors and magnetic field, an induced magnetic field is generated. Short circuits are found in rotor conductors as mentioned in the Faraday's law.

This induction in electronic magnetic field thus leads to the generation of rotor current. Hence, these motors are known as induction motors.

Induction Motor Working Principle

An alternating flux also tends to generate around the rotor as the induction of current takes place in the rotor.

Induction Motor Protection System

Induction motor is used in many industries. The load and the standard temperature are kept at normal conditions and three phase supply is used for these motors. A fault can be seen in an induction motor due to loss of any phase or increase in the winding's temperature.

The proposed protection system for the induction motor offers the process for the elimination of power supply to the motor suddenly if any fault is observed in any phase or the motor gets over heated.

In the proposed system, there are three phase power supply. In these phases, there are three transformers of single phase which are attached to it. A group of working amplifiers is also used for the purpose of input voltage.

The temperature of induction motor is measured with the help of a thermistor while keeping alongside of the body of the motor. The main relay is switched to operate the motor and single phasing is detected with the help of a group of relays.

Also, current sensors and phase sensors can be used here in order to protect the induction motor from overloading and wrong phase sequence. Due to the usage of the protection system for the induction motor, the life cycle of these motors enhances as the faults arising due to voltage and heating are avoided and the performance of the motor also improves effectively.

Protection System for Induction Motor

The problem in the supply system is the major cause of occurrence of faults in induction motors. These faults can be avoided by running the motor at specific voltage, load and current.

The supply voltage is also responsible for the proper working of an induction motor provided with a specific range and load should come under the stated limit so that the performance of the induction motors can be improved. When one phase out of three phase supply is open then single phasing is occurred. This kind of phasing is observed due to imbalance in the voltage. If single phasing is observed in three-phase induction motor then it tends to deliver the load with full efficiency.

The load is continuously driven by the motor until the motor gets heated or motor gets turn off due to some internal or external disturbances. In some cases, ground fault is regarded as the basic reason for the fault in the induction motors. Insulation conditions are raised due to imbalancing of phase current. This insulation failure is also responsible in some cases for the occurrence of fault in the induction motors.

In some cases, overload condition is occurred due to increase in the mechanical torque. Increase in phase current and overheating are some general issues causing overloading in the induction motors which are needed to be avoided. On minimizing the voltage, under voltage fault is occurred in induction motors. On the other hand, higher limit of voltage results into over-voltage in induction motors. Hence, the efficiency of the voltage should be moderated so that no fault can be occurred in the motor as any fault may degrade the performance of the motor.

Discussion

Over-current protection is the basic type of protection used against overloads and short circuits in stator windings of motors. Inverse time and instantaneous phase and ground overcurrent relays can be employed for motors above 1200 W. For small/medium size motors where cost of CT's and protective relays is not economically justified, thermal relays and HRC fuses are employed, thermal relays used for overload protection and HRC fuses for short-circuit protection.

Transformers are provided with over-current protection against faults, only, when the cost of differential relaying cannot be justified. However, over-current relays are provided in addition to differential relays to take care of through faults. Temperature indicators and

alarms are always provided for large transformers. Small transformers below 500 kVA installed in distribution system are generally protected by drop-out fuses, as the cost of relays plus circuit-breakers is not generally justified Line Protection.

The temperature of a motor winding is measured or monitored by measuring the resistance of the winding. This is done by introducing a small direct current component into the motor current, which can be done by connecting an asymmetric resistance device in the motor circuit. The resistance of the motor winding can then be determined from measurements of the direct current component and the corresponding voltage. This can also be done by using a magnetic amplifier with a bias winding excited in response to the voltage of the asymmetric resistance and a control winding excited by the motor current.

Thermal relay - the most common type of motor protection. The principle of its operation is based on the possibility of an electric current to heat a conductor through which it flows. The main part of the thermal relay is a bimetallic plate. Which, when heated, curves and thus breaks the contact. Heating plate occurs when the current exceeds its permissible value.

Fuses are the simplest and most common protection device. The purpose of the fuses is to disconnect the consumer (part of the lighting system, engine, etc.) from the mains with an unacceptably high overload or short circuit. At the same time, a large amount of heat melts the fusible insert of the fuse and thus breaks the electrical circuit. Being the most common protective devices, fuses at the same time are very imperfect. Fuses have a relatively small limiting breaking capacity.

Phase reversal problem occurs in motor when the supply phase is reversed due to wrong connection (except than ryb) due to phase reversal motor starts running in anticlockwise (opposite direction from normal) would cause operation and safety problem. Most of three phases motor run opposite phases. This type of protection is used in application like elevators where it would be damaging or dangerous for the motor to run in reverse. Generally when motor is connected with the important application then type of protection being much more important .when the load is connected with motor then reversal of phase means direction of rotation is changed. It could cause serious problem therefore much more care is required to protect the motor form such type of fault.

Conclusion

The induction motor have now become very popular as compared to other motor for many of the industries because it is low cost simple and extremely rugged construction, high reliability high efficiency and good power factor, low maintenance cost.

Induction motors are utilized as a part of different industry, for example, paper process, sugar industry, for driving the mechanical frameworks. The maintenance of an induction motor is very essential. The observing of induction motor through wired correspondence is costly as well as the information correspondence may influence because of physical conditions like human hazards. Hence wireless communication becomes price worthy turns on excellent substitute for observing as well as the control of induction motor. It upgrades the execution of the motor.

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Estimation Of Expected Time To Recruitment In A Manpower System With Wastage As A Geometric Process Using Univariate Cum Policy Of Recruitment

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Abstract

In this paper, the problem of time to recruitment is analyzed for a single grade manpower system in which attrition takes place due to two types of policy decisions where this classification is done according to intensity of attrition. Assuming (i) policy decisions and exits occur at different epochs (ii) wastage of manpower due to exits form a geometric process and (iii) breakdown threshold for the cumulative wastage of manpower follows exponential random variables. Three stochastic models are constructed and the variance of the time to recruitment is obtained using an univariate CUM policy of recruitment. While in Model I the inter-decision times form an ordinary renewal process, in Models II and III, they form a geometric process and order statistics respectively. Employing a different probabilistic analysis, analytical results in closed form for system characteristics are derived.

Keywords

Single grade manpower system, non-instantaneous exits, intensity of attrition, independent wastage of manpower, ordinary renewal process, geometric process, order statistics, breakdown threshold, univariate CUM policy of recruitment and variance of time to recruitment.

2010 Mathematics Subject Classification– 90B70, 91B40, 91D35, 60H30.

Introduction

Attrition is a common phenomenon in many marketing organizations. This leads to the depletion of manpower. Recruitment on every occasion of depletion is not advisable since every recruitment involves cost. Hence the cumulative depletion of manpower is permitted till it reaches a level, called the breakdown threshold. If the total loss of manpower exceeds this threshold, the activities in the organization will be affected and hence recruitment becomes necessary. Many researchers have studied several problems in manpower planning using different methods. In [1] and [2] the authors have discussed some manpower planning models for a single and multi-grade manpower system using Markovian and renewal theoretic approach. In [18] the authors have initiated the study on the problem of time to recruitment for the single grade manpower system which is subject to attrition, using the univariate policy of recruitment based on shock model approach for replacement of systems in reliability theory. In [15], the author has obtained the system characteristics when the loss of manpower process and inter-decision time process form a correlated pair of renewal sequences. In [17] the author has studied this problem assuming geometric process and order

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statistics for inter-decision times. In [14] the authors have studied the problem of time to recruitment by assuming that the attrition is generated by a geometric process of inter-decision times using a different probabilistic analysis. In [12] the author has initiated the study of the problem of time to recruitment by incorporating alertness in the event of cumulative loss of manpower due to attrition crossing the threshold, by considering optional and mandatory thresholds for the cumulative loss of manpower in this manpower system. While in one stochastic model described in [12] the author has obtained the variance of time to recruitment when the inter-decision times form a geometric process, in [20] the authors have studied the problem when the inter-decision times form an order statistics. Assuming that the decision epochs and the exit points at which the actual attrition takes place are different, the authors in [3], [5], [9] and [10] have respectively obtained the variance of the time to recruitment using Laplace transform technique according as the inter-decision times form an ordinary renewal process or a sequence of exchangeable and constantly correlated exponential random variables or a geometric process or an order statistics. In [4], [6], [16] and [7] the authors have studied the research work in [3], [5], [9] and [10] using a different probabilistic analysis. In [8] the authors have studied the results of [4], [6], [16], and [7] using univariate Max policy of recruitment. Recently, in [11] the authors have studied the work in [8] when the breakdown threshold level for the maximum loss of manpower is the sum of the exponential breakdown threshold levels of wastage and frequent breaks of existing workers. The present paper extends the research work in [4], [16] and [7] when the policy decisions are of two types, one with low attrition rate and the other with high rate of attrition.

Model Description and Analysis

Consider an organization taking policy decisions at random epochs in $(0, \infty)$ and at every decision making epoch a random number of persons quit the organization. There is an associated loss of manpower, if a person quits. It is assumed that the loss of manpower is linear and cumulative. For $i=1,2,3,\dots$, let X_i be a geometric process with rate d , $d>0$, it is assumed that X_1 is a exponential random variable with probability distribution function $M(\cdot)$, probability density function $m(\cdot)$. The policy decisions which produce depletion of manpower are classified into two types depending upon the intensity of attrition. It is assumed that the first type of policy decisions has high attrition rate λ_1 ($\lambda_1>0$) and the second type has low attrition rate λ_2 ($\lambda_2>0$). Let a_1 and a_2 be the proportion of decisions with high and low attrition rate respectively. Let A_i be the time between $(i-1)^{\text{th}}$ and i^{th} policy decisions, forming a sequence of independent random variables. Let B_i be the time between $(i-1)^{\text{th}}$ and i^{th} exit times, forming a sequence of independent and identically distributed random variables with probability distribution function $G(\cdot)$ and density function $g(\cdot)$. Let D_{i+1} be the waiting time upto $(i+1)$ exits. Let Y be the independent exponential threshold level for the depletion of manpower in the organization with probability distribution function $H(\cdot)$ and density function $h(\cdot)$. Let q be the probability that every policy decision has exit of personnel. As $q=0$ corresponds to the case where exits are impossible, it is assumed that $q \neq 0$. Let $\chi(I)$ be the indicator function of the event I . Let T be the random variable denoting the time to recruitment with mean $E(T)$ and variance $V(T)$. The univariate cum policy of recruitment employed in this paper is stated as follows: *Recruitment is done whenever the cumulative loss of man hours in the organization exceeds the threshold for the loss of man hours in this organization.*

Proceeding with the arguments discussed in [4], it is clear that

$$T = \sum_{i=0}^{\infty} D_{i+1} \chi (S_i \leq Y < S_{i+1}) \tag{1}$$

From (1) and from the definition of D_{i+1} , we get

$$E(T) = \sum_{i=0}^{\infty} (i+1) E(B) P (S_i \leq Y < S_{i+1}) \tag{2}$$

and

$$E(T^2) = \sum_{i=0}^{\infty} (i+1) [V(B) + (i+1)E^2(B)] P (S_i \leq Y < S_{i+1}) \tag{3}$$

By using law of total probability we get

$$P (S_i \leq Y < S_{i+1}) = \int_0^{\infty} \int_0^t \overline{M} (t-x) m_i(x) h(t) dx dt \tag{4}$$

Proceeding as in [4], from (2), (3) and (4), on simplification it can be shown that

$$E(T) = K_{21} \left(\frac{a_1 \lambda_2 + a_2 \lambda_1}{\lambda_1 \lambda_2 q} \right). \tag{5}$$

and

$$V(T) = (K_{21}) \left(\frac{2q [a_1 \lambda_2^2 + a_2 \lambda_1^2] + 2(1-q) [a_1 \lambda_2 + a_2 \lambda_1]^2}{(\lambda_1 \lambda_2 q)^2} \right) - (K_{21}^2 + K_{21} - K_{22}) \left(\frac{a_1 \lambda_2 + a_2 \lambda_1}{\lambda_1 \lambda_2 q} \right)^2 \tag{6}$$

where

$$K_{21} = \sum_{i=0}^{\infty} \left[\frac{(i+1)(\theta_1 \alpha d^{i-1})}{(\alpha d^i + \theta_1)(\alpha d^{i-1} + \theta_1)} \right] \text{ and } K_{22} = \sum_{i=0}^{\infty} \left[\frac{(i+1)^2 (\theta_1 \alpha d^{i-1})}{(\alpha d^i + \theta_1)(\alpha d^{i-1} + \theta_1)} \right] \tag{7}$$

(5) and (6) give mean and variance of time to recruitment for the present model.

MODEL DESCRIPTION AND ANALYSIS FOR MODEL-II

In this model, the problem of time to recruitment for a single grade manpower system is analyzed by assuming that the inter-policy decision times form a geometric process with rate $c, c > 0$. It is assumed that distribution of A_1 is hyper-exponential with parameters a_1, λ_1 and λ_2 .

In this case from (2), (3), (4) and [4], on simplification we get

$$E(T) = K_{21} \left[\frac{c(a_1 \lambda_2 + a_2 \lambda_1)}{\lambda_1 \lambda_2 (c-1+q)} \right]. \tag{8}$$

and

$$V(T) = K_{21} \left[\frac{2c^2 (a_1 \lambda_2^2 + a_2 \lambda_1^2)}{(c^2 - 1 + q)(\lambda_1 \lambda_2)^2} \right] - (K_{21}^2 + K_{21} - K_{22}) \left[\frac{c(a_1 \lambda_2 + a_2 \lambda_1)}{\lambda_1 \lambda_2 (c-1+q)} \right]^2 \tag{9}$$

where K_{21} and K_{22} given by (7).

(8) and (9) give mean and variance of time to recruitment for the present model.

MODEL DESCRIPTION AND ANALYSIS FOR MODEL-III

Description of this model is similar to that of Model-I except the assumption on inter-decision times. In this model it is assumed that the inter-policy decision times form an order

statistics. More specifically, let $\{U_{(l)}\}_{l=1}^r$ be a set of order statistics associated with a sample of size r taken from the population $\{U_n\}_{n=1}^\infty$ of independent and identically distributed hyper-exponential random variables with the population mean $E(U_n) = E(U) = \frac{a_1}{\lambda_1} + \frac{(1-a_1)}{\lambda_2}$, $n=1,2,\dots$. In this case, the cumulative distribution function $S(t)$ of the population and the probability density function $s_{(l)}(t)$ of the l^{th} order statistics are given by

$$S(t) = a_1(1 - e^{-\lambda_1 t}) + (1 - a_1)(1 - e^{-\lambda_2 t}), \quad a_1 > 0, \lambda_1 > 0 \text{ and } \lambda_2 > 0.$$

From the theory of order statistics, it is known that

$$s_{(l)}(t) = l \binom{r}{l} (S(t))^{l-1} s(t) [1 - S(t)]^{r-l}, \quad l = 1, 2, \dots, r.$$

In this Model the inter - policy decision times $A_n, n=1,2,\dots$ form a sequence of independent and identically distributed random variable with cumulative distribution $F(t)$ and probability density function $f(t)$. By the assumption that the inter-policy decision times form an order statistics we mean that the probability density function $f(t)$ is identified with that of the order statistics $\{U_{(l)}\}_{l=1}^r$. Thus $f(t)$ can be any one of the $s_{(l)}(t), l = 1, 2, \dots, r$.

We now determine $E(T)$ and $V(T)$ under two cases.

Case(i): $f(t) = s_{(1)}(t)$.

The probability density function of the first order statistics is

$$s_{(1)}(t) = r[1 - S(t)]^{r-1} s(t)$$

From (2),(3),(4) and [4], on simplification it is found that

$$E(T) = \frac{K_3 K_{21}}{q} \tag{10}$$

and

$$V(T) = \left(\frac{1}{q^2}\right) \left[K_{21} \left(qK_4 + 2(1-q)(K_3)^2 \right) - (K_3)^2 (K_{21}^2 + K_{21} - K_{22}) \right] \tag{11}$$

where K_{21} and K_{22} are given by (7) respectively.

(10) and (11) give the mean and variance of time to recruitment for case (i) of the present model.

Case (ii): $f(t) = s_{(r)}(t)$

The probability density function of the r^{th} order statistics is

$$s_{(r)}(t) = r[S(t)]^{r-1} s(t)$$

From (2), (3),(4) and [4], on simplification it is found that

$$E(T) = \frac{K_5 K_{21}}{q} \tag{12}$$

and

$$V(T) = \left(\frac{1}{q^2}\right) \left[K_{21} \left(qK_6 + 2(1-q)(K_5)^2 \right) - (K_5)^2 (K_{21}^2 + K_{21} - K_{22}) \right] \tag{13}$$

where K_{21} and K_{22} are given by (7) respectively.

(12) and (13) give the mean and variance of time to recruitment for case (ii) of the present model.

Conclusion

The models discussed in this paper improve the earlier relevant research work in the context of admitting the realistic assumption of non-instantaneous exits in the system and taking into account wastage due to frequent breaks for this system. They will be useful in the process of planning recruitment when the system has the above cited provision. The suitability of distributions assumed in the present work can be tested by data analysis.

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Expected Time To Recruitment In A Manpower System With Wastage As A Geometric Process When The Breakdown Threshold Has Two Components Using Univariate Cum Policy Of Recruitment

A. DEVI*

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Abstract

In this paper, the problem of time to recruitment is analyzed for a single grade manpower system in which attrition takes place due to two types of policy decisions where this classification is done according to intensity of attrition. Assuming (i) policy decisions and exits occur at different epochs (ii) wastage of manpower due to exits form a geometric process and (iii) breakdown threshold for the cumulative wastage of manpower in the system has two components which are independent exponential random variables. Three stochastic models are constructed and the variance of the time to recruitment is obtained using an univariate CUM policy of recruitment. While in Model I the inter-decision times form an ordinary renewal process, in Models II and III, they form a geometric process and order statistics respectively. Employing a different probabilistic analysis, analytical results in closed form for system characteristics are derived.

Keywords

Single grade manpower system, non-instantaneous exits, intensity of attrition, independent wastage of manpower, ordinary renewal process, geometric process, order statistics, breakdown threshold with two components, univariate CUM policy of recruitment and variance of time to recruitment.

2010 Mathematics Subject Classification– 90B70, 91B40, 91D35, 60H30.

Introduction

Wastage of personnel due to retirement, death and resignation is a common phenomenon in administrative as well as production oriented organizations. There are certain special problems associated with the organization engaged in sales and marketing. Frequent exits and recruitments are very common in such organizations. Whenever the organization announces revised policies regarding sales target, revision of wages, incentives and perquisites the exodus is possible. Reduction in the total strength of marketing personnel adversely affects the sales turnover of the organization. Frequent recruitments may also be expensive due to the cost of recruitments and training. As the wastage of manpower is unpredictable, a suitable recruitment policy has to be designed to overcome this wastage. The univariate recruitment policy, usually known as CUM policy of recruitment in the literature, is based on the replacement policy associated with the shock model approach in

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reliability theory and is stated as follows: *Recruitment is made whenever the cumulative wastage of man hours exceeds its breakdown threshold*. Several researchers have studied the problem of time to recruitment for a single grade manpower system using shock model approach. In [1] and [2] the authors have discussed some manpower planning models for a single and multi-grade manpower system using Markovian and renewal theoretic approach. In [12] the authors have analyzed the problem of time to recruitment for the single grade manpower system which is subject to attrition with **instantaneous exits**, using CUM policy of recruitment when the wastage of manpower process and inter-decision time process are independent. In [11], the author has studied the problem by associating geometric process and order statistics for inter-decision times. In [8], the authors have analyzed the work in [11] with (i) exponential breakdown threshold and (ii) extended exponential threshold having shape parameter 2 using a bivariate CUM policy of recruitment when the inter-decision times form a geometric process. In [9], the authors have studied the problem of time recruitment by assuming that the attrition is generated by a geometric process of inter-decision times. Variance of the time to recruitment for a single grade manpower system with optional and mandatory thresholds is obtained in [15] when inter-decision times form an order statistics. In [16], the authors have obtained variance of time to recruitment when the breakdown threshold level for the cumulative wastage of manpower is the sum of the exponential breakdown threshold levels of wastage and backup resource for manpower using Laplace transform technique. Recently, in [14], the authors have studied the work in [16] when the inter-decision times form a geometric process using a different method employed in [9]. In [3] the authors have considered the single grade manpower system with **non-instantaneous exits** and obtained variance of the time to recruitment when the wastage of manpower, inter-decision times and exit times are independent and identically distributed continuous random variables according as the mandatory breakdown threshold is an exponential random variable or extended exponential random variable with shape parameter 2 or a continuous random variable with SCBZ property. In [6] and [7] the authors have extended the research work in [3] when the inter-decision times form (i) a geometric process and (ii) an order statistics respectively. In [4], [10] and [5] the authors have studied the work in [3], [6] and [7] using the method of [9]. The present paper extends the research work in [10] and [5] when the breakdown threshold level for the cumulative wastage in the manpower system is the sum of two components namely an exponential threshold for cumulative wastages due to exits and an exponential threshold for cumulative wastage due to frequent breaks of existing workers.

MODEL DESCRIPTION AND ANALYSIS FOR MODEL-I

Consider an organization taking policy decisions at random epochs in $(0, \infty)$ and at every decision making epoch a random number of persons quit the organization. There is an associated wastage of manpower, if a person quits. It is assumed that the loss of manpower is linear and cumulative. For $i=1,2,3,\dots$, let X_i be a geometric process with rate d , $d>0$, it is assumed that X_1 is a exponential random variable with probability distribution function $M(\cdot)$, probability density function $m(\cdot)$. The policy decisions which produce depletion of manpower are classified into two types depending upon the intensity of attrition. It is assumed that the first type of policy decisions has high attrition rate λ_1 ($\lambda_1>0$) and the second type has low attrition rate λ_2 ($\lambda_2>0$). Let a_1 and $(1-a_1)$ be the proportion of decisions with high and low attrition rate respectively. Let A_n be the time between $(n-1)^{\text{th}}$ and n^{th} policy decisions, forming a sequence of independent random variables. Let B_i be the time between

(i-1)th and ith exit epochs, forming a sequence of independent and identically distributed random variables with probability distribution function G(.) and density function g(.). Let D_{i+1} be the waiting time upto (i+1)th exit epoch. Let Y be the breakdown threshold for the cumulative wastage of manpower in the organization with probability density function h(.). It is assumed that Y is the sum of the exponential breakdown threshold level Y_1 for cumulative wastage due to exits with mean $\frac{1}{\theta_1}$ ($\theta_1 > 0$) and exponential threshold Y_2 for

cumulative wastage due to frequent breaks of existing workers with mean $\frac{1}{\theta_2}$ ($\theta_2 > 0$). Let q

($q \neq 0$) be the probability that every policy decision has exit of personnel. Let $\chi(I)$ be the indicator function of the event I. Let T be the random variable denoting the time to recruitment with mean E(T) and variance V(T).

As in [4] we get,

$$T = \sum_{i=0}^{\infty} D_{i+1} \chi(S_i \leq (Y_1 + Y_2) < S_{i+1}) \tag{1}$$

$$E(T) = \sum_{i=0}^{\infty} (i+1) E(B) P(S_i \leq (Y_1 + Y_2) < S_{i+1}) \tag{2}$$

And

$$E(T^2) = \sum_{i=0}^{\infty} (i+1) [V(B) + (i+1)E^2(B)] P(S_i \leq (Y_1 + Y_2) < S_{i+1}) \tag{3}$$

where $P(S_i \leq (Y_1 + Y_2) < S_{i+1}) = \int_0^{\infty} \int_0^t \tilde{M}(t-x) m_i(x) h(t) dx dt$ (4)

It can be shown from the hypothesis on Y that

$$h(t) = \frac{\theta_1 \theta_2}{\theta_1 - \theta_2} (e^{-\theta_2 t} - e^{-\theta_1 t}), \theta_1 > 0, \theta_2 > 0. \tag{5}$$

Proceeding as in [4], from (2), (3), (4) and (5) and on simplification it can be shown that

$$E(T) = (K_{23} - K_{24}) \left(\frac{a_1 \lambda_2 + a_2 \lambda_1}{\lambda_1 \lambda_2 q} \right). \tag{6}$$

and

$$V(T) = (K_{23} - K_{24}) \left(\frac{2q [a_1 \lambda_2^2 + a_2 \lambda_1^2] + 2(1-q) [a_1 \lambda_2 + a_2 \lambda_1]^2}{(\lambda_1 \lambda_2 q)^2} \right) - (K_{23}(1 + K_{23}) - K_{24}(1 - K_{24}) - K_{25} + K_{26} - 2K_{23}K_{24}) \left(\frac{a_1 \lambda_2 + a_2 \lambda_1}{\lambda_1 \lambda_2 q} \right)^2 \tag{7}$$

where

$$K_{23} = \sum_{i=0}^{\infty} (i+1) \left(\frac{\theta_1 \theta_2 \alpha d^{i-1}}{(\theta_1 - \theta_2)(\alpha d^i + \theta_2)(\alpha d^{i-1} + \theta_2)} \right), K_{24} = \sum_{i=0}^{\infty} (i+1) \left(\frac{\theta_1 \theta_2 \alpha d^{i-1}}{(\theta_1 - \theta_2)(\alpha d^i + \theta_1)(\alpha d^{i-1} + \theta_1)} \right), \tag{8}$$

$$K_{25} = \sum_{i=0}^{\infty} (i+1)^2 \left(\frac{\theta_1 \theta_2 \alpha d^{i-1}}{(\theta_1 - \theta_2)(\alpha d^i + \theta_2)(\alpha d^{i-1} + \theta_2)} \right) \text{ and } K_{26} = \sum_{i=0}^{\infty} (i+1)^2 \left(\frac{\theta_1 \theta_2 \alpha d^{i-1}}{(\theta_1 - \theta_2)(\alpha d^i + \theta_1)(\alpha d^{i-1} + \theta_1)} \right).$$

(6) and (7) give mean and variance of time to recruitment for the present model.

Note:

- Our results subsume the work of Vijayasankar (2016) when $q=d=1$, who have assumed that exits are instantaneous.

MODEL DESCRIPTION AND ANALYSIS FOR MODEL-II

In this model, the problem of time to recruitment for a single grade manpower system is analyzed by assuming that the inter-policy decision times form a geometric process with rate $c, c>0$. It is assumed that distribution of A_1 is hyper-exponential with parameters a_1, λ_1 and λ_2 .

In this case from (2), (3), (4) and [4], on simplification we get

$$E(T) = (K_{23} - K_{24}) \left[\frac{c(a_1\lambda_2 + a_2\lambda_1)}{\lambda_1\lambda_2(c-1+q)} \right] \tag{9}$$

and

$$V(T) = (K_{23} - K_{24}) \left[\frac{2c^2(a_1\lambda_2^2 + a_2\lambda_1^2)}{(c^2 - 1 + q)(\lambda_1\lambda_2)^2} \right] - (K_{23}(1 + K_{23}) - K_{24}(1 - K_{24}) - K_{25} + K_{26} - 2K_{23}K_{24}) \left[\frac{c(a_1\lambda_2 + a_2\lambda_1)}{\lambda_1\lambda_2(c-1+q)} \right]^2 \tag{10}$$

where K_{23}, K_{24}, K_{25} and K_{26} are given by (8).

(9) and (10) give mean and variance of time to recruitment for the present model.

Note:

- When $q = d = a_1 = 1$, our results agree with Jayalakshmi et.al (2015(a)), who have assumed that exits are instantaneous.

MODEL DESCRIPTION AND ANALYSIS FOR MODEL-III

Description of this model is similar to that of Model-I except the assumption on inter-decision times. In this model it is assumed that the inter-policy decision times form an order statistics. More specifically, let $\{U_{(l)}\}_{l=1}^r$ be a set of order statistics associated with a sample of size r taken from the population $\{U_n\}_{n=1}^\infty$ of independent and identically distributed hyper-exponential random variables with the population mean $E(U_n) = E(U) = \frac{a_1}{\lambda_1} + \frac{(1-a_1)}{\lambda_2}$, $n=1,2,\dots$. In this case, the cumulative distribution function $S(t)$ of the population and the probability density function $s_{(l)}(t)$ of the l^{th} order statistics are given by

$$S(t) = a_1(1 - e^{-\lambda_1 t}) + (1 - a_1)(1 - e^{-\lambda_2 t}), \quad a_1 > 0, \lambda_1 > 0 \text{ and } \lambda_2 > 0.$$

From the theory of order statistics [13], it is known that

$$s_{(l)}(t) = l \binom{r}{l} (S(t))^{l-1} s(t) [1 - S(t)]^{r-l}, \quad l = 1, 2, \dots, r.$$

In this Model the inter - policy decision times $A_n, n=1,2,\dots$ form a sequence of independent and identically distributed random variable with cumulative distribution $F(t)$ and probability density function $f(t)$. By the assumption that the inter-policy decision times form an order statistics we mean that the probability density function $f(t)$ is identified with that of the order statistics $\{U_{(l)}\}_{l=1}^r$. Thus $f(t)$ can be any one of the $s_{(l)}(t), l = 1, 2, \dots, r$.

We now determine $E(T)$ and $V(T)$ under two cases.

Case(i): $f(t) = s_{(1)}(t)$.

The probability density function of the first order statistics is

$$s_{(1)}(t) = r[1 - S(t)]^{r-1}s(t)$$

From (2),(3),(4) and [4], on simplification it is found that

$$E(T) = \frac{K_3(K_{23} - K_{24})}{q} \tag{11}$$

and

$$V(T) = \left(\frac{1}{q^2}\right) \left[(K_{23} - K_{24}) (qK_4 + 2(1-q)(K_3)^2) - (K_3)^2 (K_{23}(1 + K_{23}) - K_{24}(1 - K_{24}) - K_{25} + K_{26} - 2K_{23}K_{24}) \right] \tag{12}$$

where $K_3, K_4, K_{23}, K_{24}, K_{25}$ and K_{26} are given by [4] and (8) respectively.

(11) and (12) give the mean and variance of time to recruitment for case (i) of the present model.

Case (ii): $f(t) = s_{(r)}(t)$

The probability density function of the r^{th} order statistics is

$$s_{(r)}(t) = r[S(t)]^{r-1}s(t)$$

From (2), (3),(4) and [4], on simplification it is found that

$$E(T) = \frac{K_5(K_{23} - K_{24})}{q} \tag{13}$$

and

$$V(T) = \left(\frac{1}{q^2}\right) \left[(K_{23} - K_{24}) (qK_6 + 2(1-q)(K_5)^2) - (K_5)^2 (K_{23}(1 + K_{23}) - K_{24}(1 - K_{24}) - K_{25} + K_{26} - 2K_{23}K_{24}) \right] \tag{14}$$

where $K_5, K_6, K_{23}, K_{24}, K_{25}$ and K_{26} are given by [4] and (8) respectively.

(13) and (14) give the mean and variance of time to recruitment for case (ii) of the present model.

Note:

- When $q = a_1 = d=1$ and the breakdown threshold has only the normal component, our results agree with the results of Muthaiyan (2010), where it was assumed that policy decisions have the same intensity of attrition and exits are instantaneous.

CONCLUSION

The models discussed in this paper improve the earlier relevant research work in the context of admitting the realistic assumption of non-instantaneous exits in the system and taking into account wastage due to frequent breaks for this system. They will be useful in the process of planning recruitment when the system has the above cited provision. The suitability of distributions assumed in the present work can be tested by data analysis.

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A Study on Impact of Usage of Plastic Money in India

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Abstract: The term innovation means that „to create one thing new“ banks no longer restricted themselves to traditional banking activities , however explored newer avenues to extend business and capture new market. Today, we are having a reasonably well developed banking industry with totally different categories of banks. A number of them have engaged within the areas of consumer credit, master cards, merchant banking, net and phone banking, leasing, mutual funds etc. Some banks have already started subsidiaries for merchant banking; leasing and mutual funds are within the method of doing. This study presents an outline of the event of banking in India from time to time specifically centered on the plastic cards usage trends since these are introduced in Indian banking sector. Varied types of plastic cards provided by banks in India like ATM cards, Debit Cards, Credit Cards and smart cards are mentioned. The study additionally highlights the role of those cards as electronic payment tool to be utilized by customers and discusses clearing and settlement method of those cards. Some future plans made by various banks and institutions are also summarized in a way that it depicts the image of its future growth and prospects in India.

Research methodology: in this study primary data is compiled using structured questionnaire method along with reference of secondary information from various research articles and certified journal publications

Keywords: Plastic money, Electronic Banking, credit card, debit card

I. Introduction

Indian economy has flourished with the advent of liberalization, Privatization and globalisation

.Banking sector isn't an exception too. These reforms have presented a challenge before Indian banking sector to shake hands with the pace of latest technology. Without a sound and effective banking system in India it cannot have a healthy economy. The banking system of India should not only be problem free but it should be able to meet new challenges posed by the technology and the other external and internal factors but, mere technology up gradation or introduction of innovative products cannot improve the state of affairs till customers don't respond to it positively. Hence, it becomes very necessary for the banks to offer the services or products while taking into consideration the customers' wants, preferences, perceptions and convenience. The banks' services are not simply confined to their particular branch customers only. Customer is now treated as customer of banks as a whole, which implies that he is currently capable of enjoying facilities such as anywhere, anytime banking (Kamesam, 2003). This concept as enabled the bankers to ascertain long term connection with their customers. Hence, Electronic banking is the new trend significantly adopted by banking sector worldwide because of its wider scope for the customers as well as banks at large. Various sophisticated products have been launched by the banks which facilitate them to satisfy the basic necessities of their customers. With entry of tech savvy private sector banks and foreign banks, the competitive environment has

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started prevailing in banking sector too. No doubt, Public-sector banks have large network of ancient branches to approach their customers as compared to the private and foreign players. However, with the assistance of information technology, it has now become possible for banks to deliver products and services with efficiency and to improve customer base without opening new branches. Hence, these new private and foreign players are trying to compete with them on the basis of adoption of new technological services like plastic cards, PC banking, Electronic Funds Transfer(EFT), net banking etc. to approach the maximum customers in spite of having less physical branches (Venkatesan and Kumar,2007). Attributable to this reason, public sector banks also are likely to move towards electronic banking, which ultimately leads the entire banking sector to the remarkable improvement with respect to its efficiency, client services, productivity, profitability etc. Thus, Banks are now reengineering the way in which their services can be reached to their customers by bringing in flexibility in their “distribution channels”. the information technology has replaced the brick or traditional banking with the wide range of e-banking products and services like ATM(Automated Teller Machine), net Banking, Credit Cards, PC banking, EFTs, Debit Cards, smart Cards etc. With the effect of this dynamic environment, Indian banking has witnessed exceptional growth since 2006 as banking sector is growing by 18%and it is six times over the last decade growth.

II. Literature Review

The literature relating to the topic as under: ManideepKaur and KamalpreetKaur (2008), in their article,“Development of Plastic Cards Market: Past, Present and Future Scenario in Indian Banks” conclude that Indian banking sector is accepting the challenge of information technology as all the groups of bankers have now recognized it as essential requirement for their survivaland growth in future Despite the strong advances in e-payments, an estimated 90 percent of personal consumption expenditure in India is still made with cash which indicates the tremendous growth potential of this business. So this can be considered as mere beginning which indicates the bright future prospects of plastic card market in India .P Manivannan (2013) in his research paper “Plastic Money a way for cash Less Payment System” examined that Plastic Money i.e. usage of Credit card was measured a luxury, and has become needed. These plastic money and electronic payments was and used by only higher income group. This facility extended not only to customers in urban areas or cities, but also to customers residing in rural area. However, today, with development of banking and trading activity, the fixed income group or salaried classes are also start using the plastic money and electronic payment systems and particularly Credit cards.

In this research paper an attempt has been made to study an overview of the development of banking in the plastic cards usage trends since these have been introduced in Indian banking sector. The study also highlights the role of these cards as electronic payment tool to be used by customers and discusses the penetration of these cards in replacement of cash and paper money. The factors for adoption of plastic money in replacement of cash and paper money have been identified which shows the preference of the customers for plastic cards over the cash and paper money

KEY BARRIERS TO DIGITAL PAYMENTS

Source: The Economic Times Blog

Objectives

- To understand the impact of plastic money in the economy.
- To know the privileges enjoyed by the customers with the plastic money facility given by the banker.
- To show the result of plastic cash on day to day basis with a primary study of an unbiased sample

Theoretical insights Plastic Money-Types Charge Card

A charge card carries all the features of credit cards. However, after using a charge card you'll need to pay off the whole amount billed, by the due date. If you fail to do so, you're possible to be considered a defaulter and can sometimes have to pay up a steep late payment charge.

Amex Card

Amex stands for American express and is one of the well-known charge cards. This card has its own merchant establishment tie-ups and does not rely upon the network of MasterCard or Visa.

MasterCard and Visa

MasterCard and Visa are international non-profit organizations dedicated to promote the growth of the card business across the globe. They have designed a vast network of merchant institutions so that customer's world- wide might use their respective credit cards to make various purchases.

Debit Cards

Debit card is a magnetically encoded plastic card issued by banks which has replaced money and cheques. It permits the customers to pay for goods and services without carrying cash with them. In some cases, debit card is multipurpose which can even be used as ATM for withdrawing money and to check account balances. It is issued free of cost with the savings or current account. Debit card is one of the best online-payment tool through which the amount purchase is immediately subtracted from customer account and credited to merchant's account provided if that much amount is available in customers account. It has overcome the delayed payment process of cheques, due to which sometimes merchants have to suffer. There are presently 2 ways in which debit cards transactions are processed

1. Online debit (also known as PIN)
2. Offline debit (also known as signature debit)

ATM Cards

These cards are typically used at ATM machines (ATMs) to withdraw money, make deposits, or transfer funds between accounts. ATM card is used by inserting the card into an ATM machine and enter a personal number, or PIN, for security. The system checks the account for adequate funds before allowing any transaction

Advantages Of Plastic Money

- **Purchasing Power:**

Credit or Debit cards made it easier to buy things. Now we don't have any need to carry money in a large amount. Plastic money is accepted everywhere, anytime.

- **Time Saving:**

Through a credit card or debit card you can purchase anything from anyplace without spending money on fare or cash transition. Just provide your card details to seller store or corporations and settle your order. Now you don't have to worry about time wastes. Use internet for minimum time reduction.

- **Extra Safety:**

While you are not carrying money, how can it be lost? But if your card has lost, simply contact to your bank or financial institution, which provide you cards. It will block the account and no-one can draw one coin without your permission. Therefore it's 100 percent safe without any tension.

Disadvantages Of Plastic Money

- **Shops using other Vendors:**

There are numerous shops that accept credit cards of a specific company only. In this situation the money is the only manner of payment for those who use a credit card of another company.

- **Less global Availability:**

There are numerous cases where various firms do not let their cards to be utilized in areas wherever they have a regional dispute with.

- **Worn out Magnetic Strip:**

The magnetic strip of a credit card can get worn out due to large use. If such a condition happens while travelling, and this is the only way of cash that the consumer has, then he or she must wait until the time they receive a new card, which can take a minimum of forty eighth.

- **Increased Debt and High Interest Rates:**

Credit Card from financial institutions and corporations charge high interest rates (May be 10% to 25%) on more money if you fail to pay off up to the fix date of the month. This interests their earning, for which they provide you additional shopping for limits then your money. This is not a good idea that you owe loan on high interest rates and spend it in unnecessary things or purchasing. This is complete money wastages.

- **Fraud:**

Credit cards are often stolen. A thief may use them directly or to get their information (which is needed in cash exchange). In today's technical intelligence it is also possible to get a clone of any credit card or debit card, which works like original and they can give you a heavy loss. Thus be aware from credit cards fraud as they are like stolen your cash from your pocket without your information.

III. Findings and Conclusion

The below are the questions posed to the respondents for the purpose of primary data collection and analysis with ---

Sample size-80 respondents

Mode of data collection-Structured Questionnaire

Theoretical data representation with supportive quantitative percentages obtained from the primary source of data collected through questionnaires portraying the results there off.

Theoretical Analysis

From the data obtained, it is observed that

- More than 84% of the respondents belonged to the age group of 18-25 years who are career beginners and portrays that they have a higher interest towards usage of plastic money of all means. Followed by the age group of 25-35 years and 35-45 years amounting to about 10% of the respondents who are in their career growth and mid-career? Finally a very small percentage of 5% belonged to 50 years and above who were at their career decline or retirement stage and are not very comfortable with usage of plastic money. Hence it is observed that there exists relation between career stage and usage of plastic money as it encompasses their earnings and job security for repayment.
- The female group of 51.5% is slightly more inclined towards usage of plastic money for all means followed by the male group of 48.5%. According to the survey conducted it is inferred that the women are comfortable in using plastic money in comparison with the men. Also it can be inferred that banks and financial institutions are in a pace to capture the female population higher than the male population for avoidance of credit default which is observed to be less among the female population.(in case of credit cards only)
- 68.3% of the sample group prefers credit cards followed by ATM card and debit cards (31.7%). By this result we inferred that most of them are flexible with the usage of credit cards to debit cards because of various reasons being ease of post-paid credit, immediate availability of purchasing power, increased credit limits and installment credit clearance facility.
- The crux of the survey i.e.; 48.5% of respondents are interested in using both cash and card for different kinds of payments as per the requirement and feasibility of purchase location and situation, followed by only card with 27.3% and only cash with 24.2%. Hence, it is inferred that both the means are important for payment purposes. But when card and cash are compared card is given much preference to cash as it is easy to handle and fear of loss is minimized due to its PIN protection encrypts that do not enable malpractice or usage of cards by others. .
- 78.8% of the respondents find that usage of plastic money is safer and secured where 21.2% of them find that usage of plastic money is unsecured for the reasons being primarily lack of trust in plastic money, malware and software issues in payment gateways and point of service mechanism, malpractices by payment gateways, banks negligence and retail outlets and lack of sufficient knowledge and literacy about usage of plastic money as portrayed in the response graph below.

Figure-2 Graph showing respondents views on why plastic money is unsecured

- For the respondents who have a positive approach towards usage of plastic money, the reason for them not preferring paper cash were that 34.8% of the respondents do not prefer paper money because of the increasing duplicity and fear of theft and 30.4% do not prefer paper money because of wear and tear of paper money as portrayed as given in the below graph.

Figure-3 Graph showing respondents reasons for not preferring paper cash

- 90.9% of the respondents think plastic money will penetrate into society more in future with increasing literacy and awareness about its usage and benefits but the remaining 9.1% think that plastic money will not penetrate in to society any more due to increasing insecurity, excessive transactional costs and excessive transparency of transactions not in favor of the population mindset.
- 54.5% of the respondents think more of plastic money transactions over cash transactions will help to curb black money circulation in economy and money laundering effect can be minimized with excessive transparency of transactions whereas the rest 45.5% neither agreed nor disagreed but responded neutral on the possibility discussed.
- Maximum usage of plastic money was for utilities listed as under-----
 - Utility bills-(51.6%)
 - Online shopping-(80.6%)
 - Mobile app purchases-(32.3%)
 - Application fee payments-(29%)

Figure-4 Graph showing listed top utilities of plastic money usage

- 62.5% perceive that biometric identity is the best security measure to protect from misuse of plastic money followed by pin number and password with 21.9% and 15.6% as the security measures to be adopted for a better and safer usage of plastic money.

IV. Conclusion and Suggestive measures

As observed in the study, it is inferred that the changing phase of technology has taken a step towards the transformation of transactional framework in the economy. This change has proposed people to initiate the usage of plastic money instead of the conventional hard cash for carrying out transactions on a daily basis which also enables them the advantage of credit purchases and post-repayment option for the amount of credit utilized on these cards. It has become the best, easiest and more comfortable way to handle money with the advent of this plastic money. Like every coin has two sides, this initiation also has its own advantages and disadvantages as mentioned in the theoretical framework above. Security of transactions is a major concern for people which is hindering to get more inclined towards plastic money and also repayable capacity which plays a vital role.

Thus government needs to take steps to build better and safer payment gateways with high security programmed software which does not give a lead to data theft or hacking of monetary details of the users.

Banks should educate people through awareness programs briefing about the uses of plastic and the usage directions to the financially illiterate population as well as the existing customers. To encourage more and more people to use plastic money.

Government needs to adopt this as a mass initiative and make plastic money usage facility available to the untapped population of the economy to make plastic money more in usage in our country.

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On Concurrent Vector Fields In Finsler Spaces With Randers' Metric

By

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Abstract. Concurrent vector fields in a Finsler space were first of all defined and studied by Tachibana [2]. and latter on by Matsumoto and Eguchi [6] and others. Recently Rastogi and Dwivedi [12] proved that this definition of concurrent vector fields in its present form is not suitable and hence they modified the definition of concurrent vector fields in a Finsler space as follows:

Definition1. A vector field $X^i(x)$ in a Finsler space F^n is said to be a concurrent vector field, if it satisfies $X^i A_{ijk} = \alpha h_{jk}$ and $X^i |_{j} = -\delta^i_j$.

The purpose of the present paper is to study concurrent vector fields in a Finsler space with Randers' metric [1].

Keywords: Concurrent Vector field, Finsler space, Randers' metric, n fundamental forms.

1. Introduction. Let F^n be an n-dimensional Finsler space equipped with an n-dimensional differentiable manifold M^n and a fundamental function $L(x, y)$ on M^n . If $\beta(x, y) = b_i(x) dx^i$ is a 1-form on M^n , we have for Finsler space $*F^n$ Matsumoto [8]

$$*L(x, y) = L(x, y) + \beta(x, y). \tag{1.1}$$

Prasad & Singh [9] considered the function $*L^3 = L^3 + \beta^3$ and studied the relation between V-fundamental form of hyper surfaces of Tangent Riemannian spaces. C Shibata [7] have studied the properties of Finsler spaces whose metric function $L(x, y) = f(L, \beta)$, where f is positively homogenous of degree one in L & β . This change of metric is called a β change. Further particular case of β charge of metric given by

$*L^2 = L.\beta$. have been studied by Prasad, Pandey & Dwivedi [11], also Singh and Dwivedi [13] worked on the existence of concurrent vector fields in a Finsler space.

If $L(x, y)$ is a Riemannian metric, then $*F^n$, is a Randers space [1]. Here we shall be considering the case in which $L(x, y)$ is a general Finsler metric. Now following equations due to Matsumoto [8] are important for the study of $*F^n$

$$*l_i = l_i + b_i, *h_{ij} = \tau h_{ij}, (\tau = *L/L), \tag{1.2}$$

$$*g^{ij} = \tau h^{ij} + *l_i *l_j, *g^{ij} = \tau^{-1} g^{ij} + \mu l^i l^j - \tau^{-2} (l^i b^j + l^j b^i), \tag{1.3}$$

where $\mu = (Lb^2 + \beta)/(*L \tau^2)$, $b^2 = b_i b^i$ and $b^i = g^{ij} b_j$. Also we have $*l^i = *g^{ij} *l_j = \tau^{-1} l^i$.

If we have $m_i = b_i - (\beta/L) l_i$, then $m_i l^i = 0$ and

$$*C_{ijk} = \tau C_{ijk} + (h_{ij} m_k + h_{jk} m_i + h_{ki} m_j)/(2L). \tag{1.4}$$

such that $*C_{ijk} *l^i = 0$.

The connection parameters in F^n are denoted by $(F^i_{jk}, N^i_k, C^i_{jk})$ where $N^r_j = F^r_{oj} = y^k F^r_{kj}$, $C^r_{ij} = g^{rk} C_{ikj}$ and h- and v- covariant derivatives are denoted by Matsumoto [8]:

$$X_i |_{j} = \partial_j X_i - N^r_j \Delta_r X_i - X_r F^r_{ij}, \tag{1.5}$$

and

$$X_i |_{j} = \Delta_j X_i - X_r C^r_{ij}, \tag{1.6}$$

If $*F_{jk}^i$ is the coefficient of connection in $*F^n$, then it can be expressed as $*F_{jk}^i = F_{jk}^i + D_{jk}^i$, where D_{jk}^i is a tensor defined by Matsumoto [8]

$$D_{jk}^i = L g^{ti} H_{ijk} + l^i \tau^{-1}(H_{jk} - L H_{tjk} b^t), \tag{1.7}$$

such that

$$H_{ijk} = 2^{-1}(L_{jkr} D^{r_{0i}} - L_{kir} D^{r_{0j}} - L_{ijr} D^{r_{0k}}) \tag{1.8}$$

and

$$H_{jk} = 2^{-1}\{(b_{j|k} + b_{k|j}) - L_{jr} D^{r_{0k}} - L_{kr} D^{r_{0j}}\}, \tag{1.9}$$

where

$$L_{ij} = h_{ij}L^{-1}, L_{ijk} = 2L^{-1}C_{ijk} - L^{-2}(h_{ij} l_k + h_{jk} l_i + h_{ki} l_j). \tag{1.10}$$

From equation (1.9) we can observe that H_{jk} is symmetric in j and k and H_{ijk} satisfies following identities:

$$H_{ijk} = H_{ikj}, H_{ijk} - H_{jik} = L_{jkr} D^{r_{0i}} - L_{ikr} D^{r_{0j}}, H_{ijk} - H_{kji} = L_{jkr} D^{r_{0i}} - L_{ijr} D^{r_{0k}} \tag{1.11}$$

$$H_{ijk} + H_{jik} + L_{ijr} D^{r_{0k}} = 0, H_{ijk} + H_{kji} + L_{kir} D^{r_{0j}} = 0 \tag{1.12}$$

and

$$\Sigma_{(i,j,k)} \{H_{ijk} + 2^{-1} L_{ijr} D^{r_{0k}}\} = 0. \tag{1.13}$$

Differentiating L_{ijk} co-variantly with respect to x^m , we get $L_{ijk|m} = 2L^{-1}C_{ijk|m}$, which gives

$$H_{ijk|m} = L^{-1}(C_{jkr|m} D^{r_{0i}} - C_{kir|m} D^{r_{0j}} - C_{ijr|m} D^{r_{0k}}) + 2^{-1}(L_{jkr} D^{r_{0i|m}} - L_{kir} D^{r_{0j|m}} - L_{ijr} D^{r_{0k|m}}). \tag{1.14}$$

2. CONCURRENT VECTOR FIELDS AND v-COVARIANT DERIVATIVES.

Let X^i be a concurrent vector field with magnitude X and let $X^i l_i = f(x,y)$, then we can get $X^i h_{ij} = Y_j = X_j - f(x,y)l_j = Y^i h_{ij}$, $X^i L_{ij} = Y^i L_{ij} = L^{-1} Y_j$.

Taking v-covariant derivative of $X^m X_m = X^2$, we can obtain on simplification

$X X_{|j} = 0$. As X is non zero, we get $X_{|j} = 0$. Similarly taking v-covariant derivative of $X_i l^i = f(x,y)$, we get on simplification $f(x,y)_{|j} = L^{-1} Y_j$, which on multiplication by l^j and the use of $Y_j l^j = 0$, gives $f(x,y)_{|0} = 0$. Hence we have:

Theorem 2.1- In a Finsler space F^n , a concurrent vector field $X^i(x)$ with magnitude X , satisfies $X_{|j} = 0$ and also $f(x,y)_{|0} = 0$, i.e., $f(x,y)$ is homogeneous of degree zero in y .

As $X_{j|k} = -X_r C_{rjk}$, equation $Y_{j|k} = X_{j|k} - f(x,y)_{|k} l_j - f(x,y) L^{-1} h_{jk}$ gives, $Y_{j|k} - Y_{k|j} = f_j l_k - f_k l_j = L^{-1}(Y_j l_k - Y_k l_j)$, where $f_j = f_{|j}$. Hence we have:

Theorem 2.2- In a Finsler space F^n , having a concurrent vector field $X^i(x)$, $Y_{j|k}$ will be symmetric in j and k if and only if $f_j l_k = f_k l_j$.

Taking v-covariant derivative of $X^i C_i = L^{-1} \alpha (n-1)$, we get $X^i C_{i|j} = L^{-1}\{(n-1)(\alpha_{|j} - L^{-1}\alpha l_j) - \alpha C_j\}$, which leads to $X^i C_{i|0} = L^{-1}(n-1)(\alpha_{|0} - L^{-1}\alpha)$. Hence we have:

Theorem 2.3- In a Finsler space F^n , having a concurrent vector field $X^i(x)$, the necessary and sufficient condition for $X^i C_{i|0}$ to vanish, is given by $\alpha_{|0} = L^{-1}\alpha$.

From $X^i C_i = L^{-1} \alpha (n-1)$, we can also obtain

$$X^i X^j C_{i|j} = L^{-1}(n-1) \{\alpha_{|j} X^j - L^{-1}\alpha^2\} \tag{2.1}$$

and

$$\alpha_{|j} C^j = - (n-1)^{-1}(L X^i C_{i|j} C^j + \alpha C^2) \tag{2.2}$$

From equation (1.10), we can obtain

$$X^i L_{ijk} = L^{-2} T_{jk}, \tag{2.3}$$

where

$$T_{kr} = \{2\alpha - f(x,y)\} h_{kr} - Y_k l_r - Y_r l_k \tag{2.4}$$

From equation (2.4), we can obtain

$$\begin{aligned} T_{kr} l^k &= -Y_r, T_{kr} X^k = 2\{\alpha - f(x,y)\} Y_r - (X^2 - f^2(x,y)) l_r, \\ T_{kr} l^k l^r &= 0, T_{kr} X^k X^r = \{2\alpha - 3f(x,y)\} (X^2 - f^2), \end{aligned} \quad (2.5)$$

Taking v-covariant derivative of T_{kr} we can obtain

$$T_{kr|m} = 2\alpha_{|m} h_{kr} - L^{-1} \{3\alpha (l_r h_{km} + l_k h_{rm}) - 2Y_m l_k l_r + (h_{mk} Y_r + h_{rm} Y_k + Y_m h_{kr})\} \quad (2.6)$$

From equation (2.6), we can obtain

$$\begin{aligned} T_{kr|m} l^m &= 2\alpha_{|0} h_{kr}, T_{kr|m} l^k = 2Y_m l_r - 3\alpha L^{-1} h_{rm}, \\ T_{kr|m} l^m l^k &= 0, T_{kr|m} l^k l^r = 2Y_m \\ T_{kr|m} X^m &= \{2\alpha_{|m} X^m - L^{-1}(X^2 - f^2)\} h_{kr} - L^{-1} \{Y_r(Y_k + 3\alpha l_k) \\ &\quad + Y_k(Y_r + 3\alpha l_r) - 2(f^2 - X^2) l_k l_r\} \\ T_{kr|m} X^m l^k &= -L^{-1} [3\alpha X_r + l_r(2X^2 - 2f^2 - 3\alpha f)] \end{aligned}$$

and

$$T_{kr|m} X^m X^k = 2\alpha_{|m} X^m Y_r - L^{-1} [(X^2 - f^2) \{3Y_r - (2f - 3\alpha) l_r\} + 3f\alpha Y_r] \quad (2.7)$$

Hence we have:

Theorem 2.4- The v-covariant derivative of the tensor T_{kr} based on concurrent vector field X_i satisfies equations (2.6) and (2.7).

Furthermore for a concurrent vector field we have $X^i A_{ijk} = \alpha h_{jk}$, which implies

$$X^i A_{ijk|m} = \alpha_{|m} h_{jk} - L^{-1} \alpha (h_{jm} l_k + h_{km} l_j - A_{mjk}) \quad (2.8)$$

$$X^i A_{ijk|0} = \alpha_{|0} h_{jk} \quad (2.9)$$

By writing $A_{ijk|0} = M_{ijk}$, equation (2.9) helps us to give following:

Definition 2- A vector field $X^i(x)$ in a Finsler space F^n shall be called M-concurrent vector field, if it satisfies $X^i_{|j} = -\delta^i_j$ and (2.9).

From definition 1 and 2, we can easily establish

Theorem 2.5- Every concurrent vector field shall be a M-concurrent vector field but the converse is not true in general.

Remark. In case tensor M_{ijk} is proportional to A_{ijk} , i.e., $M_{ijk} = \mu A_{ijk}$, M-concurrent vector field with $\alpha_{|0} = \mu\alpha$, shall be a concurrent vector field.

Taking v-covariant derivative of $A_{ijk} = L C_{ijk}$, we can write $A_{ijk|0} = C_{ijk} + L C_{ijk|0}$, which leads to

$$X^i A_{ijk} + X^i L^2 C_{ijk|0} = \alpha h_{jk} + L^2 X^i C_{i|0} h_{jk} (n-1)^{-1} \quad (2.10)$$

Hence we have:

Theorem 2.6- The M-concurrent vector field X^i shall be a concurrent vector field, if and only if $X^i C_{ijk|0} = X^i C_{i|0} h_{jk} (n-1)^{-1}$.

From equation $X^i A_{ijk} = \alpha h_{jk}$, we can write

$$X^i X^j A_{ijk} = \alpha Y_k, \quad (2.11)$$

Taking v-covariant derivative of equation (2.11), we obtain on simplification

$$X^i X^j A_{ijk|m} = \alpha_{|m} Y_k - 3L^{-1} \alpha^2 h_{km} - \alpha X L^{-1} h_{km} \quad (2.12)$$

which gives

$$X^i X^j A_{ijk|m} l^k = 0, X^i X^j A_{ijk|m} l^m = \alpha_{|0} X_k, \quad (2.13)$$

$$C_{(k,m)} \{X^i X^j A_{ijk|m} - \alpha_{|m} Y_k\} = 0 \quad (2.14)$$

Hence we have:

Theorem 2.7- In a Finsler space F^n , a concurrent vector field X^i satisfies equations (2.13) and (2.14).

3. CONCURRENT VECTOR FIELDS AND h-COVARIANT DERIVATIVES.

From $X_m X^m = X^2$, we can obtain on applying h-covariant derivative $X_{|k} = -X^{-1} X_k$, $X_{|0} = 0$ and $X^k X_{|k} = -X$. Taking h-covariant derivative of $X^i C_i = L^{-1}(n-1)\alpha$, we can obtain $X^i P_i =$

$L^{-1}(n-1)\alpha_{|0}$ and $X^i X^m C_{ij|m} = L^{-1}(n-1)(\alpha_{|m} X^m - \alpha)$. We can further obtain $Y_{j|k} = -h_{jk} = -g_{jk} - f_{jk} l_j$, which implies $f_{|k} = -l_k$, $f_{|0} = -1$, $f_{|k|j} = -L^{-1} h_{jk}$ and $f_{|k|0} = 0$.

If we take h-covariant derivative of equation (2.4), we can obtain on simplification

$$T_{kr|m} = 2 \alpha_{|m} h_{kr} + h_{kr} l_m + h_{rm} l_k + h_{mk} l_r \tag{3.1}$$

which leads to

$$\zeta_{(r,m)} \{T_{kr|m} - 2 h_{kr} \alpha_{|m}\} = 0 \tag{3.2}$$

$$T_{kr|m} l^m = (1 + 2 \alpha_{|0}) h_{kr}, \tag{3.3}$$

$$T_{kr|m} X^k = (2 \alpha_{|m} + l_m) Y_r + l_r Y_m + f h_{rm} \tag{3.4}$$

$$T_{kr|m} X^m = (2 \alpha_{|m} X^m + f) h_{kr} + Y_k l_r + Y_r l_k \tag{3.5}$$

Hence we have:

Theorem 3.1- If X^i is a concurrent vector field, in F^n , the tensor T_{kr} satisfies equations (3.1) to (3.5).

If we multiply equation (1.8) by l^i , X^j and Y^j respectively we get on simplification

$$l^j H_{ijk} = -2^{-1} [L^{-2}(h_{kj} D^j_{0i} - h_{ji} D^j_{0k}) + L_{ijk} D^j_{00}] \tag{3.6}$$

$$X^j H_{ijk} = 2^{-1} [L^{-2}(D^r_{0i} T_{kr} - D^r_{0k} T_{ir}) - D^r_{0j} X^j L_{kir}], \tag{3.7}$$

and

$$Y^j H_{ijk} = X^j H_{ijk} + 2^{-1} f [L^{-2}(D^j_{0i} h_{kj} - D^j_{0k} h_{ij}) + L_{ijk} D^j_{00}] \tag{3.8}$$

Theorem 3.2- If X^i is a concurrent vector field, in F^n , the tensor H_{ijk} satisfies equations (3.7) and (3.8).

Furthermore from equation (2.11) we can obtain

$$X^i X^j A_{ijk|m} = \alpha_{|m} Y_k + \alpha h_{km} \tag{3.9}$$

and

$$X^i X^j (A_{ijk|m} - A_{ijm|k}) = \alpha_{|m} Y_k - \alpha_{|k} Y_m, \tag{3.10}$$

Hence we have:

Theorem 3.3- In a Finsler space F^n , concurrent vector field X^i , satisfies equations (3.9) and (3.10).

Further since we can obtain

$$X^i X^j L_{ijk} = L^{-2} \{2(\alpha - f) Y_k - (X^2 - f^2) l_k\} \tag{3.11}$$

therefore we can also obtain

$$X^i L_{ijk|m} = L_{mjk} + L^{-2} \{2 \alpha_{|m} h_{jk} + h_{jm} l_k + h_{km} l_j + h_{jk} l_m\} \tag{3.12}$$

$$X^i X^j L_{ijk|m} = L^{-2} (T_{mk} + 2 \alpha_{|m} Y_k + Y_k l_m + Y_m l_k + f h_{km}) \tag{3.13}$$

and

$$\zeta_{(k,m)} \{X^i X^j L_{ijk|m} - 2L^{-2} Y_k \alpha_{|m}\} = 0 \tag{3.14}$$

Hence we have:

Theorem 3.4- In a Finsler space F^n , concurrent vector field X^i , satisfies equations (3.11) to (3.14).

4. CONCURRENT VECTOR FIELDS IN $*F^n$.

Let $*X^i$ be a vector field in $*F^n$, which is given by $*X^i = \theta(x,y) X^i$, then by virtue of (1.3), we can obtain $*X_i = \tau \theta(x,y) Y_i + *f *l_i$, where $*f = *X^i *l_i$. We can also obtain

$$*f = \theta(x,y)(f + X^i b_i) \tag{4.1}$$

If we write $*X^2 = *g_{ij} *X^i *X^j$, by virtue of (1.2) and (1.3), we can obtain

$$\theta^2(x,y) = \tau^{-1} (*X^2 - *f^2)(X^2 - f^2)^{-1} \tag{4.2}$$

From equation (4.2), we can obtain

Theorem 4.1- If two vector fields X^i and $*X^i$ of F^n and $*F^n$ respectively are related by the relation $*X^i = \theta(x,y) X^i$, the scalar $\theta(x,y)$ satisfies equation (4.2).

Comparing (4.1) and (4.2), we can obtain

$$X^i b_i = [*f \{L(X^2-f^2)\}^{1/2} - f \{*L(*X^2 -*f^2)\}^{1/2}] \{*L(*X^2 -*f^2)\}^{1/2} \quad (4.3)$$

Hence we have:

Theorem 4.2- If X^i is a concurrent vector field in F^n and $*F^n$ is a Finsler space defined by the law of transformation (1.1), the inner product of X^i and b_i is given by the equation (4.3).

In a Finsler space $*F^n$, the vector field $*X^i(x)$, will be a concurrent vector field, if it satisfies

$$i) *X^i *A_{ijk} = *\alpha *h_{jk}, \quad ii) *X^i_{||j} = -\delta^i_j, \quad (4.4)$$

where $*X^i_{||j}$ represents covariant derivative based on coefficient of connection $*F^i_{jk}$ in $*F^n$.

From equation (1.4), we can obtain by virtue of definition of concurrent vector field in F^n

$$*X^i *A_{ijk} = (1/2)\theta \tau [Y_j m_k + Y_k m_j + h_{jk}(2 \tau \alpha + X^i m_i)] \quad (4.5)$$

If we substituting $[(n+1)(n-1)^{-1}X^i m_i + 2 \tau \alpha] \theta = 2*\alpha$, in equation (4.5) we get

$$*X^i *A_{ijk} = *\alpha *h_{jk} + (1/2)\theta \tau (Y_j m_k + Y_k m_j) - \tau (n-1)^{-1}h_{jk} X^i m_i \quad (4.6)$$

which by virtue of (4.4) leads to

Theorem 4.3- The necessary and sufficient condition for a concurrent vector field X^i in F^n to transform to a concurrent vector field $*X^i$ in $*F^n$ is that it satisfies $\theta (Y_j m_k + Y_k m_j) - 2(n-1)^{-1}h_{jk} X^i m_i = 0$.

If we take $\theta (Y_j m_k + Y_k m_j) - 2(n-1)^{-1}h_{jk} X^i m_i = 0$ and multiply it by g^{jk} , we obtain on simplification $X^j m_j = 0$ and $X^j b_j = f \beta L^{-1}$. Hence we have:

Theorem 4.4- If vector fields X^i in F^n and $*X^i$ in $*F^n$, are concurrent vector fields, then X^i satisfies $X^j m_j = 0$ and $X^j b_j = f \beta L^{-1}$.

If we assume $X^j b_j = f \beta L^{-1}$ and $Y_j m_k + Y_k m_j = 0$, equation (4.6) gives $*X^i *A_{ijk} = *\alpha *h_{jk}$. Hence we have:

Theorem 4.5- The necessary and sufficient condition for $*X^i$ to be a concurrent vector field in $*F^n$ is given by $X^j b_j = f \beta L^{-1}$ and $(Y_j m_k + Y_k m_j) = 0$.

In case $*F^n$ is a Randers' space equation (1.4) reduces to

$$*C_{ijk} = (h_{ij} m_k + h_{jk} m_i + h_{ki} m_j)/(2L). \quad (4.7)$$

which leads to

$$*X^i *A_{ijk} = (1/2)\theta \tau (Y_j m_k + Y_k m_j + X^i m_i h_{jk}) \quad (4.8)$$

If vector field $*X^i$ is concurrent in $*F^n$, by virtue of equation (4.4) and (4.8) we get

$$X^i m_i = 2(n-1) (n+1)^{-1} *\alpha \quad (4.9)$$

Hence we have:

Theorem 4.6- A vector field $*X^i(x)$, which is concurrent in a Randers' space $*F^n$ satisfies equation (4.9).

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Analysis of contribution of three sectors in Ethiopian Economic Growth

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Abstract

The economic growth of a country is mostly based on three sectors agriculture, industry (manufacturing) and service sectors. The purpose of this document is to determine concerned of the three economic sectors in economic growth in Ethiopian before in the past 14years (from 2004 – 2017 G.C). This paper has been prepared by using secondary data from National bank of Ethiopian growth and transformation plan (GTP II). This paper formulates the regression equation using economic growth as dependent variable and three independent variables that are the economic sectors (agriculture, industry and service) sector.

The study uses both descriptive and inferential statistics to analysis the relationship between the dependent variable and explanatory variables. The result find in this paper indicates that there is a positive relationship between economic growth and each economic sector.

Generally, in order to increase the agricultural economic growth the contribution of industry and service sector is significant. In the same way, all three sectors are related to each other. In conclusion, this study finds that agriculture, manufacturing and services sectors have positive relationship with economic growth.

Keywords: Economic growth, economic sectors, industry, market, service sector etc.

1. Introduction

1.1. Background of the Study

Ethiopia's location gives it strategic dominance as a jumping off point in the Horn of Africa, close to the Middle East and its markets. Bordering Eritrea, Somalia, Kenya, South Sudan, and Sudan, Ethiopia is landlocked. Addis Ababa is the capital of Ethiopia which found in the center of the country. With about 102 million people (2016), with over 83 different languages and the second most populous nation in Africa after Nigeria, and it is one of the fastest growing non-oil dependent economies in Africa .However, it is also one of the poorest, with a per capita income of \$783. Ethiopia aims to reach lower-middle-income status by 2025. /World Bank 2018.

Most of the land in Ethiopia is highlands, grasslands, deserts with only a few rivers, and Et hiopia is a landlocked country.The Ethiopia economy is primarily based on agriculture accounting for 41% of gross domestic product (GDP).

Ineffective cultivation practices and inadequate rainfall are the major deterrents to the agricultural sector. But after 1990's joint efforts by the Ethiopia Government and aid agencies are helping to upgrade the traditional agricultural practices especially after the introduction of the Structural adjustment program (SAP) in 1992 to the Ethiopian economy. Since recent years the Ethiopian economy which had exhibited 9.9 percent average annual growth during 2012/13- 2016/17, registered 10.9 percent growth in 2016/17, depicting recovery from challenging macroeconomic and weather conditions of the previous year. The registered growth rate in real GDP was 0.2 percentage point lower than base case scenario GTPII target set for the fiscal year although it was significantly higher than 2.6 percent

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average growth estimated for Sub-Saharan Africa (World Economic Outlook Update, October 2017).

The growth in real GDP was mainly attributed to 10.3 percent growth in services, 6.7 percent in agriculture and 18.7 percent in industrial sectors respectively. And nominal GDP per capita rose to USD 863 depicting 7.8 percent improvement over the previous year. In 2017/18 the economy projected to grow 11.1 % in contrast to IMF's forecast of 3.7 % growth for the world and 3.4 % for Sub-Saharan Africa (SSA), (WEO, and October 2017). When we see contribution of each sector to country's GDP, all sectors have their own contributions progressing. For instance, in 2016/17, the agricultural sector exhibited 6.7 percent growth rate which showed recovery from El-Nino effect of the previous year which merely saw 2.3 percent expansion. Yet, it was 1.3 percentage point lower than the 8 percent target for the year. During the same years/2016/17 the share of agriculture in GDP went down to 36.3 %, more or less equivalent with GTPII target of 36.4 percent for the fiscal year. The lion's share of agricultural sector was crop production, comprising 65.3 %, followed by animal farming & hunting 25.3 % and forestry 8.9 %.

Industrial sector showed 18.7 percent annual growth and accounted for 25.6 percent of GDP. The sector contributed 40.4 percent to the overall economic growth during the fiscal year and its performance was more or less in line with GTPII target of 20.8 percent growth though its share was higher than 18 percent share targeted for the same period. That of manufacturing increased by 17.4 % and constituted about 25 % of. Construction industry, expanded by 20.7 % in terms of roads, railways, dams and residential houses expansion and electricity & water and mining & quarrying had 3 and 1.1 % contribution to industrial production, respectively Service sector continued to dominate the economy as its share in GDP was about 39.3 percent and its contribution to GDP growth reached 36.7 %. The 10.3 % growth in service sector was largely attributed to the expansion of wholesale & retail trade 7.6 % public administration & defense 22.1 % and transport & communication. (**NBE Annual Report 2011/2011-2016/2017**)

More purposely we will present sectors contributions to Ethiopian economic growth and GDP growth in Ethiopia using analytically and specifically. This paper examines the sectors contributions and the country's real GDP, growth real GDP, Per capita/Nominal/, growth rate in per capita ,sectors share to GDP in Ethiopian economic growth since 2011/2011-2016/2017 those roles played by the agriculture sector, industry sector and service sector. The paper starts with an overview of economic growth and the progress in the GDP and economic structure. Attention is given to the agriculture sector (crop production and animal farming and hunting), industry sector (construction and manufacturing) and service sector (whole sale and retails trade etc) as the success of Ethiopia's GTP I and II is strongly tied to the performance of this sector. Finally the paper addresses the conclusion and suggestion/recommendation of the study.

1.2. Significance of the study

Ethiopian economy was dependent on agriculture for long period of time. In this case the growth of this country was slow. But after few years it starts to adopt the service sector and manufacturing sector from time to time. So this document assesses the significance of these economic sectors to growth. It will use as initial idea for detail analysis regarding to this issue. It also shows the progress of Ethiopian economic growth for the last 14 years.

2. Literature Review

Libanio (2006) investigates the relation between manufacturing output growth and economic performance from a Kaldorian perspective by estimating Kaldor's first and second growth laws for a sample of seven Latin American economies during the period 1985-2001. The relation between industrial growth and GDP growth can be explained by the effects of manufacturing on productivity levels in the whole economy. The results of this study confirm manufacturing as the engine of growth, and suggest the existence of significant increasing returns in the manufacturing sector in the largest Latin American economies.

To determine the relationship between the services industry and economic growth in China, Wang and Li (2010) use an empirical analysis involving unit-roots, co-integration and Granger causality tests based on time series data from 1990 to 2008. The results indicate Granger causality and long-term stable equilibrium relationship between the services industry and economic growth. In other words, the development of the services industry plays an important role in economic growth in China. Wu (2007) examines and compares services sector development in two Asia giant economies namely China and India. The study investigates the determinants of demand for services and sheds light on the outlook for services sector growth in the two countries. The study reveals that growth in the services sector has mainly been driven by increasing specialization of production, rising standards of living and accelerated urbanization in both societies. There are also some non-economic factors which are difficult to be quantified in the empirical analysis but have played important roles in services development in the two countries. India's services sector is seen as a dominant contributor to GDP growth but China's services sector seems to lag behind.

In addition, Linden and Mahmood (2007) analyze the long run dynamic relationship between sector shares (agriculture, manufacturing and services) and economic growth for 15 Schengen countries in the period 1970 to 2004. Using panel co-integration techniques, there is evidence that the relationship between services-share growth and the growth rate of real per capita GDP is bi-directional. Hence, their study confirms that feedback impact exists between the services sector and the growth rate of real per capita GDP.

Economic performance in Ethiopia is highly correlated with the political process. Ethiopia's history is full of conflicts, drastic policy changes and reversals. Before 1974, the macroeconomic policy was largely informed by a market oriented economic system. The period 1974 -1991 witnessed a centralized economic system ('socialism'), where the state is given a significant role in all spheres of economic activity. The post-Dergu period is again taking us back to the market oriented system of the imperial regime. Such cyclical political process and regime shifts are not only unpredictable but also violent. As a predominantly agriculture based economy (where agriculture employs more than 85 percent of the population and contributing nearly half to GDP), the economic performance in Ethiopia is largely determined by what happens in the agricultural sector. The performance can be seen along three distinctive periods. During the 'Imperial regime' (before 1974) growth was satisfactory. The GDP at constant factor cost has grown by 4.6, 3.8 and 1.9 percent during 1953-59, 1960-65 and 1966-73 periods, respectively. Clearly a downward trend is observed. This growth rate further decelerated in the subsequent period of the Dergue (1974-1990) to a mere 1.9 per cent - a growth rate far below the estimated population growth of 2.9%. Various factors can be cited for this poor performance. This can easily be seen if we disaggregate this period in rather short time intervals. During the period 1974-1978 the growth rate was 0.4%. Among other things the civil war, the instability induced by the

emerging new policy (following the 1974 revolution) as well as the war with Somalia could explain a good part of this growth performance. In 1979-83 growth rate rose to 4.2% - a period characterized by relatively stable and good weather conditions. In 1984-85 growth plummeted to -5.3%. These were periods of severe drought. This rate picked up to 7.9% in 1986-87, only to decline back to 1% in 1988-8 this is basically the structure inherited by the government in Addis in 1991. During the post-Dergue period (1992-1998) the real GDP has grown by an average of 6.1 percent (if the abnormal year of 1991 is included the figure drops to 4.7%).

GDP registers the highest figure when there is good rain and the lowest (sometimes negative) when it is not. The sharp decline in the level of rainfall in 1984/85, in 1991/92 and also 1993/94 and now 1999-2000 is accompanied by a sharp decline in output. This dependence on rain-feed agriculture has a direct implication on agricultural policy. Unless a fundamental action is taken against it, the sustainability of good macro performance is not warranted. The GDP growth rate in the year 1997/98 brightly illustrates the change. In this particular year the industrial sector grew by 10%, the distributive sector (trade, transport etc.) by 8.2 percent and other services (bank, insurance, public administration and social service) grew by 7.9 percent. This is an impressive record. However, total GDP grew only by 0.5 percent owing to the poor performance in the agricultural sector that has registered -7.6 percent growth rates/ (Alemayehu 1999d) Recent Macroeconomic Development Ethiopia **Alemayehu Geda** August, 2001/ Macroeconomic Performance in Post-Reform Ethiopia.

The Ethiopian economy continued its strong expansion in FY14 with real GDP growing by 10.3 percent. At the same time, inflation has remained in single digits for the last two years. On the fiscal side the budgetary stance at the general government level has been cautious. In an effort to adjust for the rising cost of living, the FY15 budget incorporated an increase in public sector salaries through a supplementary budget in the middle of the fiscal year. Goods exports showed positive growth in 2013/14 but rates remained far below their historical growth; furthermore, export growth fell into negative territory again—after an earlier dip in 2013/14—in the last quarter of 2014 and first quarter of 2015

The Ethiopian economy continued its strong expansion in FY14.1 Real GDP grew by 10.3 percent compared with 9.8 percent in FY2013. Economic growth was driven mainly by the services sector, which accounted for about half (5.3 percentage points) of the growth contribution, followed by industry (2.8 percentage points) due to an ongoing construction boom. Agriculture, in turn, contributed 2.3 percentage points. The manufacturing sub-sector contributed only 0.5 percentage points to the GDP growth, less than the 0.7 percentage point's contribution of the preceding year. Real GDP per capita grew by 7.2 percent in FY14, which is close to the necessary 8.0 percent annual per capita growth rate needed for Ethiopia to reach middle-income status by 2025. On the demand side, public investment growth accounted for more than half of GDP growth. Public investment contributed 56 percent to total GDP growth in 2013/14 (Figure 1.1.2). Private investment growth contributed 24 percent to overall GDP growth followed by private consumption with 14 percent in 2013/14. Public investment, which is largely driven by public enterprises, showed an average annual growth of 14 percent in the last three years (2010/11–2013/14). Such investment is fueled by domestic and external credits to public enterprises, which grew on average by 21 percent during the same three-year period. On the contrary, the net exports contribution to GDP is – 4.3 percent as a result of large capital import of capital goods associated with public infrastructure investment which has a positive long-term contribution to growth. Three-

fourths of the GDP growth in 2013/14 can be explained by the developments in three sub-sectors: agriculture, construction, and services.

In the agriculture sector, the crop production value-added increased by 8.2 percent and was higher than the 6.6 percent increase in 2012/13. Within the crops category, oilseed showed a declining trend for now two consecutive years due to a decline in the production of linseed (decreased by 2.1 percent in 2013/14); and a combined drop of 24 percent in safflower and rapeseed. At the same time, sesame—one of the major export items of Ethiopia—increased production by 21 percent. Construction value-added increased by 36 percent and was the major driver of the industry sector in 2013/14. With this, construction contributed 2.2 percentage points to GDP growth and accounted for 81 percent of the total growth contribution of the industry sector.

Ethiopia has continued to register relatively high economic growth over the past decade, with annual average real GDP growth rate of 10.8% since 2004/05, one of the highest in Africa. This has expanded real GDP from ETB 248.3 billion to ETB 691 billion and nominal GDP per capita from ETB 1,475 to ETB 13,883 in the same period. The public sector led development strategy, with its focus on heavy investment in infrastructure, has underpinned this strong economic growth.

Growth has been generally broad-based, as all sectors grew significantly. On average, agriculture has grown by 8.0%, industry by 12.9%, and services by 12.9% since 2004/05. This growth, particularly the boom in the construction sector, has created jobs.

However, the high economic growth has not been accompanied by structural transformation. The manufacturing sector continues to contribute a small share of GDP, while the full potential of the private sector remains restricted by various business climate constraints. The high public investments have tended to crowd out the private sector, and led to the widening of the investment-saving gap (17.5% of GDP in 2014/15) and the external sector gap. These macroeconomic imbalances have in turn led to an increase in external borrowing, which is behind the International Monetary Fund's (IMF) recent downward rating of moderate risk of external debt distress. In addition to these adverse macroeconomic effects, sustainability of growth in future will be constrained by the low human capital base, low institutional capacity and low agricultural sector productivity 5. On agricultural productivity, the high dependency on traditional, rain-fed farming in small and fragmented landholdings needs to be addressed. Climate change is also a major threat to the sustainability of growth, especially due to its negative impact on agricultural output as well as the additional cost of climate resilient infrastructure.

Initially, agriculture was the predominant sector contributing to GDP growth, accounting for 54.9% of GDP growth in 2004/05. However, in subsequent periods, its contribution to GDP growth has consistently declined, reaching 24.9% in 2014/15. The contribution of the services sector to GDP growth, on the other hand, rose from 37.5% to 46.1% over the same period. The contribution of the industrial sector to GDP in terms of both growth and share has been increasing, albeit from a low base. The sector's growth rate and its share to GDP were 21.7% and 15.2% in 2014/15, respectively. This low level signals that economic transformation has yet to take shape. To transform the economy, the GoE needs to promote greater private investment, particularly in the strategic priority area of agro based light manufacturing. Ethiopia is one of the two African countries piloting the UNIDO led Inclusive and Sustainable Industrial Development Initiative. The GoE has selected the leather and leather products, textiles and garment and agro-processing subsectors as focus

areas of the pilot initiative, which demonstrates that agriculture still remains the bedrock of Ethiopia's transformation plans. To address the various obstacles that have so far negatively affected private sector investment, the GoE has also embarked on the construction of industrial parks, including four integrated eco-friendly agro-industrial parks. ten years, reaching ETB 165.3 billion in 2014/15, albeit below the average for the East African countries (18%) in terms of the tax-GDP ratio (13.4%), and there is still space for mobilising additional domestic resources to support growth. 2.2.7 Export earnings doubled between 2003/04 and 2010/11, rising from USD 0.6 billion to USD 3.25 billion; these earnings were more diversified, although they have lost their momentum over the last three years, due to a decline in coffee and gold prices. Over the same period, imports increased four-fold, largely driven by capital goods, resulting in the widening of the current account deficit. The effect on the overall balance of payments deficit, however, was not pronounced, as surpluses in services and capital account had a mitigating effect. Private transfers, including remittances, also offset the rise in imports. Reserves hovered around two months of imports cover. An improved environment for foreign direct investment (FDI) in the manufacturing sector and potential electricity exports has boosted favorable prospects for export diversification. 2.2.8 The economy remains vulnerable to external shocks that mainly affect the prices and volume of coffee, gold and oilseeds exports. These challenges, coupled with ambitious high import content investment plan of GTP II, point to the need to diversify the country's export base and perhaps priorities some of the public mega projects at least in the medium term.

(Ethiopia Economy 2018)World Bank .Page last updated on February 28, 2018Economy - overview: Ethiopia - the second most populous country in Africa - is a one-party state with a planned economy. For more than a decade before 2016, Ethiopia grew at a rate between 8% and 11% annually – one of the fastest growing states among the 188 IMF member countries. This growth was driven by government investment in infrastructure, as well as sustained progress in the agricultural and service sectors. More than 70% of Ethiopia's population is still employed in the agricultural sector, but services have surpassed agriculture as the principal source of GDP. Ethiopia has the lowest level of income-inequality in Africa and one of the lowest in the world, with a Gini coefficient comparable to that of the Scandinavian countries. Yet despite progress toward eliminating extreme poverty, Ethiopia remains one of the poorest countries in the world, due both to rapid population growth and a low starting base. Changes in rainfall associated with world-wide weather patterns resulted in the worst drought in 30 years in 2015-16, creating food insecurity for millions of Ethiopians. The state is heavily engaged in the economy. Ongoing infrastructure projects include power production and distribution, roads, rails, airports and industrial parks. Key sectors are state-owned, including telecommunications, banking and insurance, and power distribution. Under Ethiopia's constitution, the state owns all land and provides long-term leases to tenants. Title rights in urban areas, particularly Addis Ababa, are poorly regulated, and subject to corruption. Ethiopia's foreign exchange earnings are led by the services sector - primarily the state-run Ethiopian Airlines - followed by exports of several commodities. While coffee remains the largest foreign exchange earner, Ethiopia is diversifying exports, and commodities such as gold, sesame, khat, livestock and horticulture products are becoming increasingly important. Manufacturing represented less than 8% of total exports in 2016, but manufacturing exports should increase in future years due to a growing international presence. The banking, insurance, telecommunications, and micro-credit industries are restricted to domestic investors, but Ethiopia has attracted roughly \$8.5 billion

in foreign direct investment, mostly from China, Turkey, India and the EU; US FDI is \$567 million. Investment has been primarily in infrastructure, construction, agriculture/horticulture, agricultural processing, textiles, leather and leather products. In the fall of 2015, the government finalized and published the current 2016-20 five-year plan, known as the Growth and Transformation Plan II, which emphasizes developing manufacturing in sectors where Ethiopia has a comparative advantage, such as textiles and garments, leather goods, and processed agricultural products. To support industrialization, Ethiopia plans to increase installed power generation capacity by 8,320 MW, up from a capacity of 2,000 MW, by building three more major dams and expanding to other sources of renewable energy. In 2017, the government devalued the birr by 15% to increase exports and alleviate a chronic foreign currency shortage in electricity exports has boosted favorable prospects for export diversification. 2.2.8 The economy remains vulnerable to external shocks that mainly affect the prices and volume of coffee, gold and oilseeds exports. These challenges, coupled with ambitious high import content investment plan of GTP II, point to the need to diversify the country's export base and perhaps priorities some of the public mega projects at least in the medium term.

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known as the Growth and Transformation Plan II, which emphasizes developing manufacturing in sectors where Ethiopia has a comparative advantage, such as textiles and garments, leather goods, and processed agricultural products. To support industrialization, Ethiopia plans to increase installed power generation capacity by 8,320 MW, up from a capacity of 2,000 MW, by building three more major dams and expanding to other sources of renewable energy. In 2017, the government devalued the birr by 15% to increase exports and alleviate a chronic foreign currency shortage in the country.

Many agree that agriculture is the backbone of the Ethiopian economy. The Federal Ministry of Economic Development and Cooperation (Medic), now called the Ministry of Finance and Economic Development (MoFED), twelve years ago (1999) revealed that agriculture contributes a lot in terms of export, employment and subsistence to the Ethiopian economy. It contributes 50% of GDP, 85% of employment (the rural population of Ethiopia), 90% of earnings from export, and 70% of raw material requirements for large and medium industries which are agro-processing (MEDaC,1999:145; WMU,2002:40).

The agricultural sector, due to its major contribution to the GDP, highly influences the performances of the other sectors of the economy. It, for example, accounts for more than 80% of employment, and 90% of exports. Ethiopian export commodities are agricultural outputs: coffee, hides and skins and seeds and nuts used for edible oil production. As these are the main sources of foreign earnings, they also automatically define the country's capacity to import other materials used in manufacturing. He also stresses that macro aggregates, like level of employment and inflation rates, are also influenced by the sector A Review of Ethiopian Agriculture: Roles, Policy and Small-scale Farming Systems Add is Ababa, Ethiopia Dec 2010 vol/0200/Food Security KOPIN Ethiopia Case Study.

3. Research Objectives

3.1. General objective

The main objective of this study is to identify the determinants of economic growth in Ethiopia.

3.1.1. Specific objectives

1. To know the contributions of economic sectors on economic growth in Ethiopia;
2. To show the progress of economic growth in Ethiopia;
3. To identify the constraints and opportunities of Ethiopian economy;
4. To see the collaborative effect of each sector to economic growth;

3.2. The Research Questions

1. What are the roles of agriculture sector in the Ethiopian economic growth?
2. What are the roles of industry sector in the Ethiopian economic growth?
3. What are the roles of service sector in the Ethiopian economic growth?
4. What is the collaborative impact of each sector to economic growth?
5. What are the major constraints facing Ethiopian economic growth and what are the strengths and opportunities?

3.3. Hypothesis

Our main hypotheses presented below

1. Each economic sector has no impact on economic growth?
2. There is no relationship between three sectors like agriculture, industry and service sector in Gross Domestic Production in Ethiopia.

4. Research Methodology

4.1. Data type and source

Data collection plays a very crucial role in the statistical analysis. In research, there are different methods used to gather information, all of which fall into two categories, i.e. primary and secondary data (Douglas, 2015). As the name suggests, primary data is one which is collected for the first time by the researcher while secondary data is the data already collected or produced by others for their purpose. The fundamental differences between primary and secondary data are; the term primary data refers to the data originated by the researcher for the first time while secondary data is the already existing data collected by the investigator and organizations earlier. Primary data source needs long time and large amount of cost. But secondary data is relatively cheaper. To do this paper our group uses secondary data that was collected by national bank of Ethiopia in order to monitoring and evaluation of the country past achievement and also to prepare the next growth transformation plan.

Variable types

A variable can be defined as any aspect of a theory that can vary or change as part of the interaction within the theory. In other words, variables are anything can effect or change the results of a study. Every study has variables as these are needed in order to understand differences. When we see the behavior of the data based on the dependant variable's property data may divided in to two groups. i.e qualitative and quantitative data types. **Qualitative variables** are variable types they can explain by category or type only or they cannot measure by numerical value. While **quantitative variables** are the numerical value of the variable and they can measure by standard unit. All variables included in these document (dependent and independent) variables are quantitative variables.

Dependent variable; the dependent variable is the type of variable which is explained by other variables called independent variable. In this research the dependent variable is gross domestic product (GDP) of Ethiopia.

Independent variable; All other variables that may impact the dependent variable are called independent variables. In our case we want to see three independent variables that are the economic sectors(agriculture, industry and service) sector.

4.2. Method of statistical analysis

After we finish data collection, data processing (editing, coding, cleaning and data entry) and summarizing the available data that would be transferred in to reliable and useful information with the following method of statistical analysis. The method of statistical analysis that we applied to do this paper are both descriptive statistics and inferential statistics.

4.2.1. Descriptive statistics

It deals with any method procedure used to organizing and summarizing data in to meaning full form by using various statistical techniques such as mean, median, chart and mode.

Mean; is the measure of central tendency it used to calculate the average value of all observations in the each variable.

Scatter plot/dot Scatter plot is the type of graphical representation of data. This is used to show the distribution of variables observation. In this document we used this graph to show the progress each sectors economic growth and GDP.

4.2.2. Inferential statistics

Inferential statistics is concerned with making predictions or inferences about population from observations and giving conclusion about the relationship between dependant variable

and independent variable. This document is analyzed by using one way ANOVAs and simple linear regression, multiple linear regressions by 0.1 level of significance (p-value).

Regression analysis; is a statistical technique used to describe relationships among variables. The simplest case to examine is one in which a variable, referred to as the dependent or target variable, may be related to one variable X, called an independent or explanatory variable, or simply a regress or. If the relationship between Y and X is believed to be linear, then the equation for a line may be appropriate: $Y = \beta_1 + \beta_2 X$, where β_1 is an intercept term and β_2 is a slope coefficient. When we are examining the relationship between a quantitative outcome and a single quantitative explanatory variable, simple linear regression is the most commonly considered analysis method. In linear regression we usually have many different values of the explanatory variable, and we usually assume that values between the observed values of the explanatory variables are also possible values of the explanatory variables. We postulate a linear relationship between the GDP and the value of the explanatory variables (economic sectors). **P value:** is the probability that the deviation of the observed from the expected is due to chance alone (no other force acting). **Level of significant (α):** is a statistical statement of whether observations reflect a pattern rather than chance.

5. Result and discussion

As we mentioned above our result is described by descriptive and inferential statistical analysis method by using statistical package for social science (SPSS) version 23.

5.1. Descriptive statistics

As we described in the methodology of this research descriptive analysis is a type of statistical data analysis that used to describe the value of each variable by using simple graphs and means.

Table 1; values of each sector from 2004-2017 G.C

Year	Agriculture	Industry	Service sector	Total
2004	114994.6	20615.7	88064.7	223675
2005	130734.6	22576.3	98936.2	252247.1
2006	145152.4	24835.9	112435.3	282423.6
2007	158764.7	26561	129465.1	314790.8
2008	170587.4	29632.9	149713	349933.3
2009	181276	32753.9	169657.9	383687.8
2010	195074	37379.5	190414.5	422868
2011	212469.7	44878.1	221519	478866.8
2012	222927.7	53990.2	242985.6	519903.5
2013	238752.1	67786.7	264954.3	571493.1
2014	251756.3	79969	298907.5	630632.8
2015	267812.7	96843.6	331874.4	696530.7
2016	535674.7	329633.2	573292	1438600
2017	571718.2	392026.4	632478.1	1596223

Source; National bank of Ethiopia GTP 2 plan(2004-2017 G.C)

Table2. The values of each sector and total GDP from(2004-2017)

	N	Range	Minimum	Maximum	mean
	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic
The income get from agriculture products in that year (in million birr)	14	456723.60	114994.60	571718.20	242692.5071
the income get from manufacturing product in that year (in million birr)	14	371410.70	20615.70	392026.40	89963.0286
service sector	14	544413.40	88064.70	632478.10	250335.5429
total yearly GDP in all sectors (agriculture, manufacture and service sector) in million birr in each year	14	1372547.70	223675.00	1596222.70	582991.0786
Valid N (listwise)	14				

Source; National bank of Ethiopia GTP 2 plan(2004-2017 G.c)

The above table result indicates that the total growth value of each sector. That include from (2004-2017 G.C). This table shows the minimum, maximum and the average data of GDP 223675.00, 1596222.70 and 582991.0786 in millions of birr respectively. Out of thus GDP 35.82% covers agriculture, 24.56% covers manufacturing and the remaining 39.62 % covers service sector. This indicates the service sector takes the largest share of GDP an average. The above line graph shows the progress of each economic sector and GDP in the last 14 years in Ethiopia and it shows the relation of each sector with economic growth at different years. The economy of Ethiopia increases correspondence to the increment of each sector. The growth of agriculture sector was greater than other sectors up to 2010. During this period the growth of the country was less or approximately constant. After 2010 the growth of service sector greater than that of agriculture and the hole economy was grow greater than before. Even if the growing progress manufacturing sector changing it is less than other sectors.

5.2. Inferential statistics

As we indicate in the methodology part of this paper the second method of statistical analysis is inferential statistics. In this part we want to show whether there is an association between agriculture, manufacture, service sector and GDP.

5.2.1. Simple Linear regression

In this part we use the impacts of each explanatory variable to the dependant variable one by one.

Table 3: The impact of agriculture to GDP

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		T	Sig.	90.0% Confidence Interval for B	
		B	Std. Error			Lower Bound	Upper Bound
1	(Constant)	-149780.686	11189.48	-13.386	.000	-169723.55	129837.82
	the income get from agriculture products in that year (in million birr)	3.02	.040	74.855	.000	2.947	3.091

The above spss output shows that the contributions of agriculture in to GDP. The model looks like; $GDP = -149,780.69 + 3.09 \text{agriculture} + \text{error}$

In this table we see the number -149,780.69 to the right of the “(Constant)” label and under the labels “Unstandardized Coefficients” and “B”. The slope 3.02 indicates if the income from agriculture increased by 1 million birr the country’s income will increase on average by 3.02 million birr at 90% confidence interval other factors remain constant.

To the right of the intercept and slope coefficients you will find their standard errors. As usual, standard errors are estimated standard deviations of the corresponding sampling distributions. For example, the SE of 0.040 for the income get from agriculture products in that year (in million birr) gives an idea of the scale of the variability of the estimate the income get from agriculture products in that year (in million birr), which is 3.02 here, but will vary with a standard deviation of approximately 0.040 around the true, unknown value of the income get from agriculture products in that year (in million birr) if we repeat the whole experiment many times at 90% confidence interval.

Table 4; The impact of industry to economic growth

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		T	Sig.	90.0% Confidence Interval for B	
		B	Std. Error			Lower Bound	Upper Bound
	(Constant)	264856.044	23938.962	11.06	.000	222189.93	307522.157
	the income get from Industry product in that year (in million birr)	3.536	.165	21.38	.000	3.241	3.831

The above table shows the relationship between economic growth and the manufacturing sector of Ethiopia. The regression model of this relation is

$GDP = 2,648,856.044 + 3.536 \text{ money get from manufacturing sector}$ the slope of the (3.536) indicates that when the value of manufacture increased by one million birr then the economy of the country will increase by 3.536 million birr at 90% confidence level when other factors remain constant. The sig. value is equal to .000 which is too small (<0.1) and indicates manufacture has significant factor to economic growth. The std. error value indicates that the probability of making error when we speak about the behavior of the dependent and independent variable at 0.1 level of significance.

Table 5: The impact of service sector to economic growth

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		T	Sig.	90.0% Confidence Interval for B	
		B	Std. Error			Lower Bound	Upper Bound
1	(Constant)	-43469.982	25736.122	-1.689	.117	-89339.152	2399.188
	service sector	2.502	.086	28.949	.000	2.348	2.657

This output also shows that the impact of service sector to economic growth of the country. As we see from the output the sig. value is .000 which is too small and indicates that service sector has significant effect to economic growth of the country. When we see the B value there is a constant term (-43469.982) and coefficient 2.502.

The model looks like $GDP = -43,469.982 + 2.502 \text{ money of service sector}$. In this model the coefficient 2.502 indicates that when the money that get from service sector increases by one million birr the value of GDP will increase by 2.502 birr assume other variables are constant at 0.1 level of significant.

5.2.2. Multiple regressions

Table 6; The cooperative impact of industry and agriculture

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		T	Sig.	95.0% Confidence Interval for B	
		B	Std. Error			Lower Bound	Upper Bound
1	(Constant)	-118876.223	34154.800	-3.481	.005	-194050.432	-43702.015
	the income get from Industry product in that year (in million birr)	.276	.288	.958	.359	-.358	.910
	the income get from agriculture products in that year (in million birr)	2.790	.243	11.475	.000	2.255	3.325

The output shows that the contribution of agriculture and manufacture. The coefficient 0.276 indicates that when the growth of manufacture increase by one million birr the growth of GDP will increase by 0.277 million birr and similarly the coefficient 2.79 indicates that when the value of agriculture increases by 1 million birr GDP will increased by 2.77 million birr at 90% level of significance keeping other factors remain constant.

Table 7: The cooperative impact of agriculture and service sector to economic growth

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		T	Sig.	95.0% Confidence Interval for B	
	B	Std. Error			Lower Bound	Upper Bound
(Constant)	-131001.146	12051.236	-10.870	.000	-157525.738	-104476.554
the income get from agriculture products in that year (in million birr)	2.430	.240	10.108	.000	1.901	2.959
service sector	.496	.200	2.476	.031	.055	.938

The above table shows that the agriculture and service sector have significant contribution to economic growth at 90% level of significance. The coefficient 2.43 indicates that when the values of agriculture increase by 1 million birr the economic growth will increased by 2.43 million birr.

6. Conclusion and recommendation

6.1. Conclusion

After we review different researches and analysis our data the researcher got the privous output. That is similar with other researches such as; Linden and Mahmood (2007) analyze the long run dynamic relationship between sector shares (agriculture, manufacturing and services) and economic growth for 15 Schengen countries in the period 1970 to 2004. Using panel co-integration techniques, there is evidence that the relationship between services-share growth and the growth rate of real per capita GDP is bi-directional. Hence, their study confirms that feedback impact exists between the services sector and the growth rate of real per capita GDP.

According to our study there is a positive relationship between economic sectors (agriculture, service and industry sector) and economic growth of Ethiopia.

As we describe the progress of the economic growth in the graph shows the progress of each economic sector and GDP in the last 14 years in Ethiopia and it shows the relation of each sector with economic growth at different years. The economy of Ethiopia increases correspondence to the increment of each sector. The growth of agriculture sector was greater than other sectors up to 2010. During this period the growth of the country was less or approximately constant. After 2010 the growth of service sector greater than that of agriculture and the hole economy was grow greater than before. Even if the growing progress manufacturing sector changing it is less than other sectors.

Additionally, we show that the collaboration of each sector has significant effect to the growth of the economy by the background of the country. In order to increase the agricultural economic growth the contribution of industry and service sector is significant. In conclusion, based on the discussion of previous researches, this study finds that agriculture, manufacturing and services sectors have positive relationship with economic growth. In other words, the development of these economic sectors will raise economic growth.

In order to improve the Ethiopian economic growth the government should expand the technology and service sector. To increase the agricultural product and productivity the government should give support services (training, inputs...) and technology.

There should be the efficient marketing system of agriculture products to increase Ethiopian economy. It may be significant if the researchers do further with regard to this topic and if the future national plan and strategy will prepare depend on the actual data.

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A Study To Identify The Factors Affecting Individual Investment Behaviour

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Abstract: The study aims to discuss the various factors which have a significant impact on the investment behavior of the individuals. Researchers has referred past studies, and discussed various theories to identify the factors. It was found that investors take their investment decision in a rational manner and hold diverse portfolios in order to maximize returns while minimizing risks. Also, they build up portfolios as per each individual's capacity to take risks. Not only that but they trade in a manner so as to minimize taxes. While the reality is far away from this, so far, individual investor behavior is concerned. In fact, their trading pattern is frequent and speculative in nature which increases their trading cost and often results in losses in the long term. Their tendency is to sell the shares where they are earning profit and keeps the loss making shares with them in the expectation of gaining on them in near future. In the process, while they generate tax liability on profit making shares, they lose the opportunity of balancing same with loss making shares. Not only that but many individual investors, in fact, go for additional purchase of loss making shares to average out the purchase costs.

Keywords: Investment, Investor, Individual Investors, Stock Market, Over Reaction, Over Confidence, and Behavioral Finance.

Introduction

A person who invests in small quantities of shares out of his own savings and purchases in his own account is considered as an Individual Investor. Apart from them there are Investment managers as well who participate in the equity market in bulk by investing on behalf of several individual investors. As per study conducted by Dimitrios I. M, (2007) while individual investor makes his investment decision based on market information available through newspaper and digital media, investment manager rely more on analysis of the fundamentals and technical parameters of a company. According to the conventional financial theory it is generally believed that people before taking a decision with regards to investment take help of various tools apart from using their own judgment. Apart from that they make use of fundamentals and technical analysis to arrive at a decision. Conventional financial theory is based on the assumption that the investor in order to maximize his wealth will always behave in a rational manner resting his decisions solely on the outcomes based on financial rules. Also it is assumed that market outcomes are purely dependent on market factors and information alone. However, in practicality it has been observed that despite all the above factors the investor often tends to behave irrationally and it is not that all investors will take the same decision under a given situation as all of them have different risk taking capabilities. Hence the information available will be interpreted differently by different

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investors depending on his individual traits and accordingly they will take a decision to buy or sell the shares. In other words, the decisions are highly psychologically influenced instead of being rational. This lead to another approach called behavioral finance which studies how the behavior of an investor gets affected by his own psychology (Shefrin, 2000). As per (Nofsinger and Richard, 2002) for an individual his behavior affects only his purchases which he does in small amounts. Further the investment decisions in case of individual investors are affected by internal and external behavioral factors as came out in various researches (Shefrin, 2000; Shleifer, 2000; Warneryd, 2001). The major factors or characteristics with regards to investment decisions which are considered as low priority by individual investors are as below:

- Accounting information has no role to play in case of individual investment decision,
- Others things like the performance of firm with regard to domestic and international operations, company ethics and track record are considered as factors of low importance.
- The advices coming from various quarters such as investment brokers, family and friends are the factors which are just ignored.

On the other hand, the factors which weigh heavily on the mind of individual customer while taking decision with regards to investment are as below:

- Individual risk appetite is a major factor as different individuals react differently to the same market information based on this.
- Individual's behavior is most influenced by his desire to multiplying wealth and various methods are employed by individual to select the right stocks Nagy and Obenberger, (1994).
- Expected corporate returns, ease of marketability, past performance, government share in the firm etc are some of the major factors that influence investors decision Hussein A. H, (2007).

At the same time there are many researchers such as Baker and Haslem (1974) who believe that the individual investor also behaves rationally and base their decisions on the financial soundness of company, expected returns and the firm's past performance with regards to dividends distribution to public while (Haargrove and Haslem, 1977) stated that an individual arrives at a decision by a rational analysis of the expected return with regards to the amount of risk taken. Further so far the risk taking tendency of an individual investor is concerned, the study conducted by Cohn et al. (1975) pointed out that risk taking tendency of employee increases as his wealth increases while the study by Riley and Chow pointed out that apart from wealth creation the other factors which have a positive effect on risk taking tendency are increase in income, education and age.

Review Literature

In order to contemplate the investment decision an individual will take, behavioral science has become an important tool and there have been numerous researches on this aspect of human behavior. Despite the importance of this subject and considering the fact that first research on this topic happened in 1970's wherein Potter, (1971) said that the various factors which prompt the individual investor to take a decision are dividends, rapid growth, investment for saving purposes, quick profits through trading, professional investment management and long-term growth, till date there is very little confidence on the factors that control it. Considering this review of literature tries to identify the various factors of behavioral finance based on analysis of various studies which have happened in past by both individuals as well as professional investors.

Objectives

The objective of the study was to establish and identify the various factors based on both experimental as well as empirical studies which influence the investment decisions of an individual investor. Apart from this the scope of the study included that how the decisions arising out of each such factor affects the outcome.

Theories Explaining Factors Affecting Investment Behavior Of Individuals

The various behavioral factors based on these studies can be defined as below:

- 1. Regret theory:** This applies to those investors who do not sell some stock since they purchased them at a high price and now do not want to face the embarrassment of selling it at a loss. Such investors in order to avoid this possibility of embarrassment in future resort to dependence on others wisdom that is they start investing where everyone else is investing (Pareto, 1997).
- 2. Mental Accounting theory:** This theory is applicable in case of those investors who have seen their share prices sky rocketing during a bull run. They make a mental framework that this is the worth of those shares though they did not sell at that price when they had an opportunity. Now when the market correction happens and the profit margins get reduced on those shares, such customers are hesitant to sell at the prevailing prices since the high prices existing at the time of bull run are embedded strongly in their minds. They would like to keep the shares will them till again those prices are reached in the market (Thaler, 2001).
- 3. Prospect/Loss-Aversion-Theory:** This theory claims that investors are not happy with a gain as much as they are stressed with an equivalent amount of loss. This is the reason why people keep holding their loss making stocks in expectation of getting a gain in future thereby increasing their risk further. Hence their main focus remains on selling stocks which are performing well and have great future. This behavior has been defined as disposition effect by Shefrin and Statman (1985) as this result into investors disposed to sell performing shares.

On the contrary they keep clinging to loss making shares which makes their portfolio unattractive. This by no way can be said to be a rational behavior but gives an answer to why money flow in high performing mutual funds far exceeds the money flowing out of low performing mutual funds (Kahneman and Tversky, 1979). This theory has been validated by both experimental and empirical studies. The studies by Chen et al. (2007) and Choe and Eom (2009) suggests that even corporate investors and dealers exhibit tis behavior though on a smaller scale.

- 4. Over/Under Reacting Theory:** This happens when the recent trends are stronger in the mind of customers than the historical trends. That makes an investor over confident in times of bull run whereas he becomes over pessimistic in times of bear run. This overreaction leads to prices of shares not reflecting the true worth of a share as their prices get overvalued on good news and undervalued on bad news (Hong and Stein, 1999).
- 5. Overconfidence theory:** As is clear from the name some investors due to overconfidence believe that they are better in analyzing the market as compared to others which is contrary to the reality and results in excess trading resulting in erosion in margins due to higher trading costs (Tapia and Yermo, 2007). This fact was further validated by the analysis done by Barber and Odean (2000) of the data's related to 78000 investors where he concluded that the stocks which were managed by the individual

investor based on his perception generally underperformed due to higher cost of trading involved.

Apart from this there have been various findings related to the investor's behavior based on empirical studies as well. As per that various behavior patterns are as below:

6. Neutral information: Two contradictory behavioral patterns have been identified during various researches by Kadiyala and Rau, (2004). In one of the pattern the investor overreacts to information which results into long term returns reversal when companies announce issuance of new stocks. In the other type the investor under reacts to information which results into long term continuation of returns when open market shares repurchase. Kadiyala and Rau, (2004) investigated investor reaction to corporate event announcements. They concluded that investors appear to under-react to prior information as well as to information conveyed by the event, leading to different patterns. Thus the behavioral finance literature has proposed two contradictory models of irrational investor behavior. In the first model, investors have a tendency to overreact to information, leading to a pattern of long term return reversals when firms announce corporate events such as new issues of stock. In the second model, investors under react to information, leading to long term return continuations when firms announce open-market share repurchases. Behavioral models have so far not able to explain above contradictory reactions. However, these contradictory reactions made, Fama, (1998) conclude that behavioral models are not able to explain this contradiction as these reactions imply an overall neutral reaction or unbiased approach to information by the investor.

Another study by Merikas et al. (2003) states that economic criterion along with some other variables are the factors which affects the investor behavior. Also a correlation was observed between the factors as propagated by the behavioral finance theory and the empirical studies.

7. The Accounting-Information: While as per the study by Lee and Tweedie, (1975, 1976, and 1977) the financial reporting of the corporate sector are not easily understandable by general public but on the other hand as per the findings by Baker and Haslem, (1973) earnings projections and historical data are of interest to investors in order to project the future expectations from the share of a given company. Individuals exhibit traits of investor rather than that of traders as they go for long term investments instead of short term gains as per Lease et al., (1974). Also it was observed by Schlarbaum et al. (1978) that even individual's decision making is based on considerable skills while Lewellen et al., (1977) found that fundamental and technical analysis of companies is their main source of information. Further individuals risk taking can be measured in terms of price and earning volatility as per the study done by Blume and Friend, (1978). In line with this is the finding by Antonides and Van der Sar, (1990) as per which a recent increase in value reflects a lowered perceived risk of investment.

8. The Self-Image/Firm-Image Coincidence: Daniel et al. states the behavior of overconfident investors is dominated by the private information they receive about a company. They do like to go through the Annual reports. However, they believe it only when it is in line with their private information. But in case the Annual report results do not match with their information they tend to ignore the report.

9. Advocate recommendation: Since analyst gets paid for a favorable report, the individual investor does not rely on them hundred percent. He tries to validate same with the opinion of stock brokers, brokerage houses apart from that from friends and co-

workers. On the other hand, large investors take a decision based on analyst report provided they are confident that he is unbiased (Malmendier and Shanthikumar, 2003).

10. Personal financial needs: As per prospects theory (Shefrin and Statman, 1985); (Weber and Camerer, 1998) certain outcomes should be give more weightage than uncertain outcomes. Based on that it is logical to believe that any investor would like to sell stocks that have uncertain future. However, the reality is that in some cases individual investor actually gets involved with shares of uncertain future to the extent that they not only retain such stocks but actually pump in more money into them thereby gambling on it's future (Arkes and Blumer 1985; Brockner 1992; Staw and Hoang 1995). The study done by Odean (1999) based on trading records of 10000 investors also validated the fact that poor performance of shared lead the individual investors to trade even more frequently.

Conclusion

Various theoretical models for investor behavior are based on the assumption that investors take their investment decision in a rational manner and hold diverse portfolios in order to maximize returns while minimizing risks. Also they build up portfolios as per each individual's capacity to take risks. Not only that but they trade in a manner so as to minimize taxes. While the reality is far away from this, so far, individual investor behavior is concerned. In fact, their trading pattern is frequent and speculative in nature which increases their trading cost and often results in losses in the long term. Their tendency is to sell the shares where they are earning profit and keeps the loss making shares with them in the expectation of gaining on them in near future. In the process, while they generate tax liability on profit making shares, they lose the opportunity of balancing same with loss making shares. Not only that but many individual investors, in fact, go for additional purchase of loss making shares to average out the purchase costs. Moreover, these individual investors are sometimes over reactive to market information as well resulting in the prices of stock either appreciating or depreciating from their real value in case of a bull run or bear run respectively. Various researches on the individual behavior directed at identifying the various factors which influence their investment decision have been studied in detail. It has been found that the factors affecting such decisions in most of the cases are irrational. However, the most important factors which came out of the various studies were information gathered by individual investors from various sources with regards to firm's historical and current performance, past data on returns on investments, expected profits of the company, loss minimization in view of adverse report, industry economic scenario etc. An important factor which came out was the recommendation from the peers and friends. Also it came out during various studies that there exists a correlation between the factors under the behavioral finance theory and the empirical studies conducted with respect to individual behavior towards investment.

Significance Of Study

Thus, we can see that the human behavior is a complex one and there are a lot of factors which have an influence on it so far the investment decisions are concerned. Hence it is of utmost importance to understand all those factors which come out of the theoretical as well as empirical studies so that a correct decision can be taken in order to achieve the objective of maximizing returns while minimizing the risks.

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Results on Bilateral Bailey Transform

Sunil Singh*

Abstract: In this paper, using symmetric and asymmetric bilateral Bailey transform, certain interesting transformations of basic bilateral hypergeometric functions have been established.

Keywords and Phrases: Basic hypergeometric series, Bailey transform, Bilateral Bailey transform, symmetric and asymmetric bilateral Bailey transform, transformation formula.

2010 Mathematics Subject Classification: 33A30, 33D15, 33D20.

Introduction, Notations and Definitions

Throughout this paper we shall adopt the following notations and definitions.

For any number a and q , real or complex and $|q| < 1$,

$$[a; q]_n = [\alpha]_n = \begin{cases} (1 - \alpha)(1 - \alpha q)(1 - \alpha q^2) \cdots (1 - \alpha q^{n-1}); & n > 0 \\ 1; & n = 0 \end{cases}$$

Accordingly, we have

$$[a; q]_\infty = \prod_{r=0}^{\infty} (1 - \alpha q^r)$$

Also

$$[a_1, a_2, \dots, a_r; q]_n = [a_1; q]_n [a_2; q]_n \cdots [a_r; q]_n.$$

and

$$[a; q]_{-n} = \frac{q^{\frac{n(n+1)}{2}}}{(-a)^n [a; q]_n}$$

and $[a_1, a_2, \dots, a_r; q]_n = [a_1; q]_n [a_2; q]_n \cdots [a_r; q]_n$, then following Gasper and Rahman [8], we define basic hypergeometric series by

$${}_r\Phi_s \left[\begin{matrix} a_1, & a_2, & \dots, & a_r; & q; & z \\ b_1, & b_2, & \dots, & b_s \end{matrix} \right] = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{[a_1, a_2, \dots, a_r; q]_n z^n}{[q, b_1, b_2, \dots, b_s; q]_n} \left[(-1)^n q^{\frac{n(n-1)}{2}} \right]^{1+s-r} \tag{1}$$

where $q \neq 0$ when $r > s + 1$.

A bilateral basic hypergeometric series is defined by

$${}_r\Psi_s \left[\begin{matrix} a_1, a_2, \dots, a_r; & q; & z \\ b_1, b_2, \dots, b_s \end{matrix} \right] = \sum_{n=-\infty}^{\infty} \frac{[a_1, a_2, \dots, a_r; q]_n z^n}{[q, b_1, b_2, \dots, b_s; q]_n} \left[(-1)^n q^{\frac{n(n-1)}{2}} \right]^{s-r} \tag{2}$$

where $\left| \frac{b_1, b_2, \dots, b_s}{a_1, a_2, \dots, a_r} \right| < |z| < 1$ justifies the convergence of the series (2).

Bailey [5, 6] established a very useful transform called as Bailey transform:

If

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$$\beta_n = \sum_{r=0}^n \alpha_r u_{n-r} v_{n+r} \text{ and } \gamma_n = \sum_{r=0}^{\infty} \delta_{r+n} u_r v_{r+2n}, \tag{3}$$

Then

$$\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \alpha_n \gamma_n = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \beta_n \delta_n \tag{4}$$

subject to conditions on the four sequences $\alpha_n, \beta_n, \gamma_n$ and δ_n which make all the relevant infinite series absolutely convergent.

This transformation leads to various results which play an important role in number theory and transformation theory of ordinary and basic hypergeometric series both. Making use of the transformation, Bailey [5, 6] developed technique to obtain transformations for both ordinary and basic hypergeometric series and successfully used this transformations to obtain a number of identities of Rogers-Ramanujan type. In 1951 and 1952, L. J. Slater [14, 15] derived one hundred and thirty identities of Rogers-Ramanujan type with the help of Bailey transformation formula.

After Bailey and Slater, a number of mathematicians working in the field of ordinary and basic hypergeometric series namely R. P. Agarwal [4], G. E. Andrews [1, 2], R. Y. Denis et al. [7], S. P. Singh [10, 11, 12], U. B. Singh [13], S. Ole Warnaar [3] have used Bailey transformation to develop a number of results for both ordinary and basic hypergeometric series with single and multiple bases.

In order to prove certain false theta identities found in the 'Los' notebook of Ramanujan, Andrews and Warnaar [3] defined two bilateral version of Bailey's transform:

(i) Symmetric bilateral Bailey transform,

If

$$\beta_n = \sum_{r=-n}^n \alpha_r u_{n-r} v_{n+r} \text{ and } \gamma_n = \sum_{r=0}^{\infty} \delta_{r+n} u_r v_{r+2n}, \tag{5}$$

then

$$\sum_{n=-\infty}^{\infty} \alpha_n \gamma_n = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \beta_n \delta_n \tag{6}$$

subject to conditions on the four sequences $\alpha_n, \gamma_n, \beta_n$ and δ_n which make all relevant infinite series absolutely convergent.

(ii) Asymmetric bilateral Bailey transform,

If $m = \max [n, -n - 1]$,

$$\beta_n = \sum_{r=-n-1}^n \alpha_r u_{n-r} v_{n+r} \text{ and } \gamma_n = \sum_{r=m}^{\infty} \delta_r u_{r-n} v_{r+n+1}, \tag{7}$$

then

$$\sum_{n=-\infty}^{\infty} \alpha_n \gamma_n = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \beta_n \delta_n \tag{8}$$

subject to conditions on the four sequences $\alpha_n, \beta_n, \gamma_n$ and δ_n which make all the relevant infinite series absolutely convergent.

We shall make use of following summation in our analysis.

Ramanujan's sum of ${}_1\Psi_1$ series is given by

$${}_1\Psi_1 [a; b; q; z] = \frac{[q, \frac{b}{a}, az, \frac{q}{az}; q]_{\infty}}{[b, \frac{q}{a}, z, \frac{b}{az}; q]_{\infty}} \tag{9}$$

[Gasper and Rahman {8} ; App.II (II.29) p.239]

The sum of a well poised ${}_2\Psi_2$ series is

$${}_2\Psi_2 \left[b; c; \frac{aq}{b}, \frac{aq}{c}; q; -\frac{aq}{bc} \right] = \frac{[\frac{aq}{bc}; q]_{\infty} [\frac{aq^2}{b^2}, \frac{aq^2}{c^2}, q^2, aq, \frac{q}{a}; q^2]_{\infty}}{[\frac{aq}{b}, \frac{aq}{c}, \frac{q}{b}, \frac{q}{c}, -\frac{aq}{bc}; q]_{\infty}} \tag{10}$$

[Gasper and Rahman 8 ; App.II (II.30) p.239]

Bailey's sum of a well poised ${}_3\Psi_3$ is,

$${}_3\Psi_3 \left[\begin{matrix} b, c, d; q; \frac{q}{bcd} \\ \frac{q}{b}, \frac{q}{c}, \frac{q}{d} \end{matrix} \right] = \frac{[q, \frac{q}{bc}, \frac{q}{bd}, \frac{q}{cd}; q]_{\infty}}{[\frac{q}{b}, \frac{q}{c}, \frac{q}{d}, \frac{q}{bcd}; q]_{\infty}} \tag{11}$$

[Gasper and Rahman 8 ; App.II (II.31)p.239]

A basic bilateral analogue of Dixon's sum is

$${}_4\Psi_4 \left[\begin{matrix} -q\sqrt{a}, b, c, d; q; \frac{qa^{\frac{3}{2}}}{bcd} \\ -\sqrt{a}, \frac{aq}{b}, \frac{aq}{c}, \frac{aq}{d} \end{matrix} \right] = \frac{[aq, \frac{aq}{bc}, \frac{aq}{bd}, \frac{aq}{cd}, \frac{q\sqrt{a}}{b}, \frac{q\sqrt{a}}{c}, \frac{q\sqrt{a}}{d}, q, \frac{q}{a}; q]_{\infty}}{[\frac{aq}{b}, \frac{aq}{c}, \frac{aq}{d}, \frac{q}{b}, \frac{q}{c}, \frac{q}{d}, q\sqrt{a}, \frac{q}{\sqrt{a}}, \frac{qa^{\frac{3}{2}}}{bcd}; q]_{\infty}} \tag{12}$$

[Gasper and Rahman 8 ; App.II (II.32)p.239]

$${}_3\Psi_3 \left[\begin{matrix} b, c, d; q; \frac{q^2}{bcd} \\ \frac{q^2}{b}, \frac{q^2}{c}, \frac{q^2}{d} \end{matrix} \right] = \frac{[q, \frac{q^2}{bc}, \frac{q^2}{bd}, \frac{q^2}{cd}; q]_{\infty}}{[\frac{q^2}{b}, \frac{q^2}{c}, \frac{q^2}{d}, \frac{q^2}{bcd}; q]_{\infty}}$$

(13)

[Gasper and Rahman 8 ; (5.18(II)),p.137]

2. Main Results

In this section we shall establish main transformation formulae.

(a) In equation (9) if we take $a = q^{-n}$, $b = q^{1+n}$ and replace z by zq^n then we get,

$$\sum_{r=-n}^n \frac{[q^{-n}; q]_r z^r q^{nr}}{[q^{1+n}; q]_r} = \left[q, z, \frac{q}{z}; q \right]_n \tag{14}$$

Now, taking

$$u_r = v_r = \frac{1}{[q; q]_r}, \quad \alpha_r = (-)^r q^{\frac{r(r-1)}{2}} z^r \quad \text{and} \quad \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{[-1, -q; q]_n q^{n^2}}{[q; q]_{2n}} = \frac{[-q, -q^2; q^3]_{\infty}}{[q, q^2; q^3]_{\infty}}$$

in (5) we find

$$\beta_n = \frac{\left[z, \frac{q}{z}; q \right]_n}{[q; q]_n} \tag{15}$$

and

$$\gamma_n = \frac{\left[\frac{q}{\alpha}, \frac{q}{\beta}; q \right]_{\infty} [\alpha, \beta; q]_n \left(\frac{q}{\alpha\beta} \right)^n}{\left[q, \frac{q}{\alpha\beta}; q \right]_{\infty} \left[\frac{q}{\alpha}, \frac{q}{\beta}; q \right]_n} \tag{16}$$

Putting these values in equation (6), we obtain

$$\frac{\left[\frac{q}{\alpha}, \frac{q}{\beta}; q \right]_{\infty}}{\left[q, \frac{q}{\alpha\beta}; q \right]_{\infty}} {}_2\Psi_3 \left[\begin{matrix} \alpha, \beta; q; \frac{qz}{\alpha\beta} \\ \frac{q}{\alpha}, \frac{q}{\beta}, 0 \end{matrix} \right] = {}_4\Phi_3 \left[\begin{matrix} z, \frac{q}{z}, \alpha, \beta; q; q/\alpha\beta \\ \sqrt{q}, -\sqrt{q}, -q \end{matrix} \right] \tag{17}$$

This is the first transformation formula.

(b) Taking $a = q^{-n}$, $b = q^{2+n}$ and replacing z by zq^n in equation (9), we get

$$\sum_{r=-n-1}^n \frac{[q^{-n}; q]_r z^n q^{nr}}{[q^{2+n}; q]_r} = \frac{[q; q]_n [q^2; q]_n \left[z, \frac{q^2}{z}; q \right]_n}{[q^2; q]_{2n}} \tag{18}$$

Now, taking $u_r = \frac{1}{[q; q]_r}$, $v_r = \frac{1}{[q^2; q]_r}$, $\alpha_r = (-)^r q^{r(r-1)/2} z^r$, $\delta_r = [\alpha, \beta; q]_r \left(\frac{q^3}{\alpha\beta} \right)^n$ and $m = n$ in equation (7), and using equation (18), we have

$$\beta_n = \frac{\left[z, \frac{q^2}{z}; q \right]_n}{[q^2; q]_{2n}} \quad \text{and} \quad \gamma_n = \frac{\left[\frac{q^3}{\alpha}, \frac{q^3}{\beta}; q \right]_{\infty} [\alpha, \beta; q]_n \left(\frac{q^3}{\alpha\beta} \right)^n}{\left[q^3, \frac{q^3}{\alpha\beta}; q \right]_{\infty} \left[\frac{q^3}{\alpha}, \frac{q^3}{\beta}; q \right]_n} \tag{19}$$

Putting these values in equation (8), we get

$$\frac{\left[\frac{q^3}{\alpha}, \frac{q^3}{\beta}; q \right]_{\infty}}{\left[q^3, \frac{q^3}{\alpha\beta}; q \right]_{\infty}} {}_2\Psi_3 \left[\begin{matrix} \alpha, \beta; q; \frac{q^3 z}{\alpha\beta} \\ \frac{q^3}{\alpha}, \frac{q^3}{\beta}, 0 \end{matrix} \right] = {}_4\Phi_3 \left[\begin{matrix} \alpha, \beta, \frac{q^2}{z}; q; \frac{q^3}{\alpha\beta} \\ \frac{q}{c}, \frac{q}{d} \end{matrix} \right] \tag{20}$$

This is the second required transformation formula.

(c) If we take $a = 1, b = q^{-n}$ in equation (10), we get

$$\sum_{r=-n}^n \frac{[q^{-n}; q]_r [c; q]_r (-)^r (q^{1+n})^r}{[q^{1+n}; q]_r \left[\frac{q}{c}; q \right]_r} \left(\frac{q^{1+n}}{c} \right)^r = \frac{\left[q, -\frac{q}{c}; q \right]_n}{\left[-q, \frac{q}{c}, q \right]_n} \tag{21}$$

Taking $u_r = v_r = \frac{1}{[q; q]_r}, \alpha_r = \frac{q^{\frac{r(r+1)}{2}} [c; q]_r}{\left[\frac{q}{c}; q \right]_r c^r}, \delta_r = [\alpha, \beta; q]_r \left(\frac{q}{\alpha\beta} \right)^r$ in equation (5), and using equation (21), we get

$$\beta_n = \frac{\left[-\frac{q}{c}; q \right]_n}{\left[\frac{q}{c}, q \right]_n [q^2; q^2]_n} \text{ and } \gamma_n = \frac{\left[\frac{q}{\alpha}, \frac{q}{\beta}; q \right]_{\infty} [\alpha, \beta; q]_n \left(\frac{q}{\alpha\beta} \right)^n}{\left[q, \frac{q}{\alpha\beta}; q \right]_{\infty} \left[\frac{q}{\alpha}, \frac{q}{\beta}; q \right]_n} \tag{22}$$

Putting these values in equation (6), we get

$$\frac{\left[\frac{q}{\alpha}, \frac{q}{\beta}; q \right]_{\infty}}{\left[q, \frac{q}{\alpha\beta}; q \right]_{\infty}} {}_3\Psi_4 \left[\begin{matrix} \alpha, \beta, c; q; -\frac{q^2}{\alpha\beta c} \\ \frac{q}{\alpha}, \frac{q}{\beta}, \frac{q}{c}, 0 \end{matrix} \right] = {}_3\Phi_2 \left[\begin{matrix} \alpha, \beta, -\frac{q}{c}; q; \frac{q}{\alpha\beta} \\ \frac{q}{c}, -q \end{matrix} \right] \tag{23}$$

which complete the analysis for the third formula.

(d) Taking $b = q^{-n}$ equation (11), we find

$$\sum_{r=-n}^n \frac{[q^{-n}, c, d; q]_r}{\left[q^{1+n}, \frac{q}{c}, \frac{q}{d}; q \right]_r} \left(\frac{q^{1+n}}{cd} \right)^r = \frac{\left[q, \frac{q}{cd}; q \right]_n}{\left[\frac{q}{c}, \frac{q}{d}; q \right]_n} \tag{24}$$

Now, taking $u_r = v_r = \frac{1}{[q; q]_r}, \alpha_r = \frac{q^{\frac{r(r+1)}{2}} [c, d; q]_r \left(-\frac{1}{cd} \right)^r}{\left[\frac{q}{c}, \frac{q}{d}; q \right]_r}, \delta_r = [\alpha, \beta; q]_r \left(\frac{q}{\alpha\beta} \right)^r$ in equation (5), and using equation (24), we get

$$\beta_n = \frac{\left[\frac{q}{cd}; q \right]_n}{\left[q, \frac{q}{c}, \frac{q}{d}; q \right]_n} \text{ and } \gamma_n = \frac{\left[\frac{q}{\alpha}, \frac{q}{\beta}; q \right]_{\infty} [\alpha, \beta; q]_n \left(\frac{q}{\alpha\beta} \right)^n}{\left[q, \frac{q}{\alpha\beta}; q \right]_{\infty} \left[\frac{q}{\alpha}, \frac{q}{\beta}; q \right]_n} \tag{25}$$

Putting these values in equation (6), we obtain

$$\frac{\left[\frac{q}{\alpha}, \frac{q}{\beta}; q\right]_{\infty}}{\left[q, \frac{q}{\alpha\beta}; q\right]_{\infty}} {}_4\Psi_5 \left[\begin{matrix} \alpha, \beta, c, d; q; \frac{q^2}{\alpha\beta cd} \\ \frac{q}{\alpha}, \frac{q}{\beta}, \frac{q}{c}, \frac{q}{d}, 0 \end{matrix} \right] = {}_3\Phi_2 \left[\begin{matrix} \alpha, \beta, \frac{q}{cd}; q; \frac{q}{\alpha\beta} \\ \frac{q}{c}, \frac{q}{d} \end{matrix} \right] \tag{26}$$

(e) Taking $a = 1$ and $b = q^{-n}$ in equation (12), we get

$$\sum_{r=-n}^n \frac{[q^{-n}, c, d; q]_r [-q; q]_r}{[q^{1+n}, \frac{q}{c}, \frac{q}{d}; q]_r [-1; q]_r} \left(\frac{q^{1+n}}{cd}\right)^r = \frac{[q, \frac{q}{cd}; q]_n}{[q, \frac{q}{d}; q]_n} \tag{27}$$

Now, taking $u_r = v_r = \frac{1}{[q; q]_r}$, $\alpha_r = \frac{(-)^r q^{\frac{r(r+1)}{2}} [-q; q]_r [c, d; q]_r}{(cd)^r [\frac{q}{c}, \frac{q}{d}; q]_r}$, $\delta_r = [\alpha, \beta; q]_r \left(\frac{q}{\alpha\beta}\right)^r$ in equation (5), and using equation (27), we have

$$\beta_n = \frac{\left[\frac{q}{cd}; q\right]_{\infty}}{\left[q, \frac{q}{c}, \frac{q}{d}; q\right]_{\infty}} \text{ and } \gamma_n = \frac{\left[\frac{q}{\alpha}, \frac{q}{\beta}; q\right]_{\infty} [\alpha, \beta; q]_n \left(\frac{q}{\alpha\beta}\right)^n}{\left[q, \frac{q}{\alpha\beta}; q\right]_{\infty} \left[\frac{q}{\alpha}, \frac{q}{\beta}; q\right]_n} \tag{28}$$

Putting these values in equation (6), we obtain

$$\frac{\left[\frac{q}{\alpha}, \frac{q}{\beta}; q\right]_{\infty}}{\left[q, \frac{q}{\alpha\beta}; q\right]_{\infty}} {}_5\Psi_6 \left[\begin{matrix} \alpha, \beta, c, d, -q; q; \frac{q^2}{\alpha\beta cd} \\ \frac{q}{\alpha}, \frac{q}{\beta}, \frac{q}{c}, \frac{q}{d}, -1, 0 \end{matrix} \right] = {}_3\Phi_2 \left[\begin{matrix} \alpha, \beta, \frac{q}{cd}; q; \frac{q}{\alpha\beta} \\ \frac{q}{c}, \frac{q}{d} \end{matrix} \right] \tag{29}$$

(f) Taking $b = q^{-n}$ in equation (13), we get

$$\sum_{r=-n-1}^n \frac{[q^{-n}, c, d; q]_r}{[q^{2+n}, \frac{q^2}{c}, \frac{q^2}{d}; q]_r} \left(\frac{q^{2+n}}{cd}\right)^r = \frac{[q; q]_{\infty} [q^2, \frac{q^2}{cd}; q]_n}{[q^2; q]_{\infty} [q^2, \frac{q^2}{d}; q]_n} \tag{30}$$

Now, taking $u_r = \frac{1}{[q; q]_r}$, $v_r = \frac{1}{[q^2; q]_r}$, $\alpha_r = \frac{[c, d; q]_r (-)^r q^{\frac{r(r+1)}{2}}}{[\frac{q^2}{c}, \frac{q^2}{d}; q]_r} \left(\frac{q}{cd}\right)^r$, $\delta_r = [\alpha, \beta; q]_r \left(\frac{q^3}{\alpha\beta}\right)^r$ and $m = n$ in equation (7), and using equation (30), we get

$$\beta_n = (1 - q) \frac{\left[\frac{q^2}{cd}; q\right]_n}{\left[q, \frac{q^2}{c}, \frac{q^2}{d}; q\right]_n} \text{ and } \gamma_n = \frac{\left[\frac{q^3}{\alpha}, \frac{q^3}{\beta}; q\right]_{\infty} [\alpha, \beta; q]_n \left(\frac{q^3}{\alpha\beta}\right)^n}{\left[q^2, \frac{q^3}{\alpha\beta}; q\right]_{\infty} \left[\frac{q^3}{\alpha}, \frac{q^3}{\beta}; q\right]_n} \tag{31}$$

Putting these value in equation (8), the sixth transformation formula is obtained as

$$\frac{\left[\frac{q^3}{\alpha}, \frac{q^3}{\beta}, q \right]_{\infty}}{\left[q, \frac{q^3}{\alpha\beta}; q \right]_{\infty}} {}_4\Psi_5 \left[\begin{matrix} \alpha, \beta, c, d; q; \frac{q^5}{\alpha\beta cd} \\ \frac{q^3}{\alpha}, \frac{q^3}{\beta}, \frac{q^2}{c}, \frac{q^2}{d}, 0 \end{matrix} \right] = {}_3\Phi_2 \left[\begin{matrix} \alpha, \beta, \frac{q^2}{cd}; q; \frac{q^3}{\alpha\beta} \\ \frac{q^2}{c}, \frac{q^2}{d} \end{matrix} \right] \tag{32}$$

3. Special Cases

Here we obtain some special case of transformation formulae (14) – (32).

In this section we shall obtain special cases of the results established in previous section by applying the Jacobi's triple product identity

$$\sum_{k=-\infty}^{\infty} q^{k^2} z^k = \left[q^2, -qz, -\frac{q}{z}; q^2 \right]_{\infty}$$

[Gasper and Rahman 8 ; App.II (II.28) p.239]

(i) As $\alpha, \beta \rightarrow \infty$, (17) yield

$$\frac{1}{[q; q]_{\infty}} \sum_{r=-\infty}^{\infty} (-)^r q^{\binom{3}{2}r^2} \left(zq^{-\frac{1}{2}} \right)^r = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{\left[z, \frac{q}{z}; q \right]_n q^{n^2}}{[q; q]_{2n}} \tag{33}$$

Now, applying Jacobi's triple product identity on the left hand side of equation (33), we get the following identity.

$$\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{\left[z, \frac{q}{z}; q \right]_n q^{n^2}}{[q; q]_{2n}} = \frac{\left[zq, \frac{q^2}{z}; q^3 \right]_{\infty}}{[q, q^2; q^3]_{\infty}} \tag{34}$$

Replacing q by q^2 and the taking $z = q$ in equation (34), we get

$$\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{[q; q^2]_n^2 q^{2n^2}}{[q^2; q^2]_{2n}} = \frac{[q^3; q^6]_{\infty}^2}{[q^2, q^4; q^6]_{\infty}} \tag{35}$$

Again, if we take $z = -1$ in equation (34), we get

$$\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{[-1, -q; q]_n q^{n^2}}{[q; q]_{2n}} = \frac{[-q, -q^2; q^3]_{\infty}}{[q, q^2; q^3]_{\infty}} \tag{36}$$

(ii) Taking $\alpha, \beta \rightarrow \infty$ in equation (20), we get

$$\frac{1}{[q^3; q]_{\infty}} \sum_{n=-\infty}^{\infty} (-)^n q^{\frac{3}{2}n^2} \left(zq^{\frac{3}{2}} \right)^n = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{\left[z, \frac{q^2}{z}; q \right]_n q^{n(n+2)}}{[q^2; q]_{2n}} \tag{37}$$

Applying equation (33) in equation (37), we get

$$\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{\left[z, \frac{q^2}{z}; q \right]_n q^{n(n+2)}}{[q^2; q]_{2n}} = \frac{\left[\frac{1}{z}, zq^3; q^3 \right]_{\infty}}{[q^4, q^5; q^3]_{\infty}} \tag{38}$$

Taking $z = q$ in equation (38), we obtain

$$\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{[q, q]_n^2 q^{(n+1)^2}}{[q; q]_{2n+1}} = (q^2 - 1) \tag{39}$$

(iii) As $\alpha, \beta, c \rightarrow \infty$ in equation (23) we get

$$\sum_{n=-\infty}^{\infty} (-1)^n q^{2n^2} = [q; q]_{\infty} \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{q^{n^2}}{[q^2; q^2]_n} \tag{40}$$

Applying equation (33) in equation (40) we get

$$\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{q^{n^2}}{[q^2; q^2]_n} = [-q; q^2]_{\infty} \tag{41}$$

which is $\lambda = 1$ case of a known result

[Andrews and Berndt 2; (6.2.23) p.150]

(iv) Taking $\alpha, \beta, c, d \rightarrow \infty$ in equation (26) and then applying Jacobi's triple product identity we find the well known Rogers and Ramanujan identity

$$\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{q^{n^2}}{[q; q]_n} = \frac{1}{[q, q^4; q^5]_{\infty}} \tag{42}$$

[Andrews and Berndt 2; (6.2.23) p.150]

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A Study on Impact of Consumer Behavior with Internet Marketing and Website Design

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Abstract

The theory of internet marketing and consumer behavior in online markets has been intensively observed over the years. However, a huge number of researches do not comprehensively study the view of the aspects of an effective and successful website. Each year the number of organizations that utilize the Internet for marketing purposes increases. A website is the front page, the first picture for organizations that operate online and it is better to be developed in a way that brings customers close to the online market and form good impressions. The study was conducted at Zinemind Technologies, a global ITS and Product company delivering quality tech solutions to customers across varied industry domains. The core of this study is the in depth investigation of the website features, which affect customer behavior and lead to higher levels of customer satisfaction. This paper tries to demonstrate the elements of a website as they impact on customer satisfaction, website trust, and loyalty in an online market. The revealed that the website studied and evaluated had good presentation features such as, consistent use of font color and background. Also, the website is structured in an easy to navigate layout by using menus and navigation bars. The website provides detailed information about the company and the products. Moreover, security and privacy statements have been widely adopted. The relationship between customer satisfaction and trust has been revealed as positive. Customer satisfaction has been related to greater levels of commitment and loyalty. An effective website is supported by the design of the website and the information content. Users feel satisfied if the website is well designed and the information provided is reliable, accurate and up to date.

Keywords: *Consumer Behavior, Internet Marketing, Website Design, India*

1.0 Introduction

An increasing number of consumers use the internet not only for gathering information but also for purchasing goods. A website is the front page, the first picture for organizations that operate online and it is better to be developed in a way that brings customers close to the online market and form good impressions. The Internet had become a vital marketing medium for businesses all over the world. Many studies have examined the online consumers' behavior. As a result, issues such as an effective website that has the potential of customer satisfaction and trust, commitment and loyalty become of immense importance. Internet offers multiple features (capacity, speed, precision and convenience) that help to attract a large number of potential customers. Consumer uses the internet for different reasons ranging from only gathering information to purchasing product online. Internet has changed the communication way of people.

There are large group of B2B customers online any time and they all are a potential consumer

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in the online market. Since there are so many providers, the most important thing for organizations is to understand what are consumer wants and needs in this competitive business environment. In the Internet market since there is no face-to-face contact, analyzing and identifying factors that influence the consumer is vital. Moreover, consumers have new demands. Therefore, it becomes more important to answer consumer's demands to retain the customer. In this study, research has been made comparing behaviors of consumers that are using website of Zinemind technologies, a global ITS and Product company delivering quality tech solutions to customers across varied industry domains. This study focuses on following problems, say, 1) to study the in depth investigation of the website features, which affect customer behavior and lead to higher levels of customer satisfaction, and 2) to propose a model to demonstrate the elements of a website as they impact on customer satisfaction, website trust, commitment and loyalty in an online market.

Although there have been several research proposals on the website elements affecting the consumer behavior, the identification of the factors related to an effective website are of immense importance. While Information Technologies grow, the marketing appears to be directly related to technology. It is important for businesses to know what satisfies a customer and what makes a website effective and successful. Despite the large amount of papers describing the factors of an effective website, no particular effort has been undertaken to connect the website element with the customer overall satisfaction, trust, commitment and loyalty. Therefore, in this paper we identify the key dimensions for a successful website which are related to the consumer behavior. Our goals are to propose a research framework, investigate its integrity by identifying factors that are critical to the success of a website and relate these factors with the satisfaction perceived by online users. Our aim is to examine a set of criteria that can be used for evaluating a website for its success and effectiveness. At the end, the objective of this particular study is to develop a model presenting the main factors that are concerned to influence customer satisfaction in online markets, which is then related to higher levels of trust, commitment and loyalty. And as Porter (2001) claims, "The established companies that will be most successful will be those that use Internet technology to make traditional activities better and those that find and implement new combinations of virtual and physical activities that were not previously possible".

Internet marketing or online marketing or web marketing, is becoming a turning point for every kind of business today. Today, Internet is widely used by organizations to promote the business and as sophisticated as it may seem, online promotion is one of the most effective and economical techniques of marketing for businesses. The most imperative benefit of this kind of marketing is that you can overcome the barriers or boundaries of distance and you can not only promote your products and services in any part of the world but, sell them also. Online marketing is inexpensive in contrast with other traditional methods, and there are more than a few creative and efficient ways in this marketing that you can exploit in advertising or promoting your company, brand, services and products. Online marketing also enables business, companies or individuals take advantage of the growing importance of social media sites like Facebook, Twitter, LinkedIn, Myspace, etc. With the accessibility of online marketing, companies or businesses can track their customers or clients and make contact with them easily. Social Media Marketing, Email Marketing, Affiliate Marketing, Content Marketing and Online Video Marketing are some of the creative tools, which are available for online businesses to integrate their overall Internet Marketing campaign. Some of the other effective Internet Marketing Tools are Blogs, Keywords, New updates, Domain

name, etc.

Online marketing is a fast-growing market, which always changes with time. Therefore, always update with new technology as well as upcoming, and use the latest technology or software's for taking more advantages of online marketing. Remember, people who are adopting and innovative are only ones triumphant in Internet marketing.

2.0 Review of Literature

Annual Report of NASSCOM (2012) pointed that Information Technology has made possible information access at gigabit speeds. It has made tremendous impact on the lives of millions of people who are poor, marginalized and living in rural and far flung topographies. Internet has made revolutionary changes with possibilities of e-government measures like e-health, e-education, e-agriculture, etc. Today, whether its filing Income Tax returns or applying for passports online or railway e-ticketing, it just need few clicks of the mouse. India's IT potential is on a steady march towards global competitiveness, improving defense capabilities and meeting up energy and environmental challenges amongst others.

Dianne Cyr (2008) performed an extensive study on the ways in which internet can help an organization in a number of activities ranging from development of new business models. Further explaining results of his research on instrumentality of internet for business organizations, Dianne Cyr (2008) asserted that internet can be used as an excellent channel of communicating with customers and can also help the business managers to obtain and maintain their information updated. Jarvenpaa *et al* (1999) also stated the same fact and reported that the importance of knowledge-based competitive advantage has never been undermined by any of the scholars and in the world of increasing competition, information and knowledge are the only organizational resources leading to competitive advantage that is sustainable and long term. Therefore, internet not only helps the business organizations in developing and maintaining customers but also helps to gain, store and utilize large volumes of useful information that can serve as the basis of strategy formulation in future. Rosen, D. and Purinton, E. (2004) reported that internet not only affects the way organizations design their business model, carry out their operations and manage the supply chain, but also casts a significant impact on how the products and services in today's marketplace should be promoted, marketed and advertised. He asserted that the new technology, particularly the changes in the world of internet and the ways organization are using it, have brought a revolution in the world of internet marketing.

Based on Chaffey *et al.*, (2006), we can say that "Marketing is the management process responsible for identifying, anticipating and satisfying customer requirements profitably". Hofacker (2001) divided Internet Marketing into four categories: communicating, selling, providing content and providing a network function.

Through a case study of social media as a part of the marketing mix, Mangold and Faulds (2009) concluded "social media is a hybrid element of the promotion mix because in a traditional sense it enables companies to talk to their customers, while in a non-traditional sense it enables customers to talk directly to one another." Today, it is a challenge for organizations to know their customers while when consumers are introduced to new technologies their behavior changes (Zinkhan and Watson, 1998).

Based on Chaffey *et al* (2006), 'Effective' means that the internet communications must deliver to their audience whatever they are looking for. Nelsen F(2013) identifies the important factors affecting the success of a website and introduces three primary areas: site design and structure, page design and content design. Rosen and Purinton (2004) have

grouped the design factors into three categories. These results are based on questionnaires of a group of students and the categories are as follows: 1) Coherence – this refers to the simplicity of design. The overall site structure must be easy to read by avoiding overcrowded information. In addition, the website should use an adequate font size and text color. 2) Complexity – the information provided should be categorized in different topics in order to reduce the complexity of the website structure and appearance, and 3) Legibility – users have to be able to easily read the information and navigate throughout the website. The use of a site map helps the user to know where he/she is and how to get to the page of his/her interest. Also, it provides a general structure of the website and shows the information and services provided. The user can easily identify the pages he/she wants to visit in order to satisfy his/her needs.

3.0 Research Methodology

The surveyed respondents were clients of Zinemind Technologies. Each client has evaluated the website of Zinemind Technologies according to the features mentioned in the research framework. More specific, it was examined the website design and mainly the information content of the website. By this, also measured the success of the website and collected data that helped us extract the desired results. The websites were evaluated for their functionality and innovation. The questionnaire was sent to the participants by mail. Each participant was requested to study and evaluate the website of Zinemind Technologies according to the Questionnaire. The participants were clients of the company.

The identified variables which affect Customer Satisfaction (CS) are Web Design and Information Content and then this CS leads to Trust and Loyalty.

It was framed and tested the following hypotheses: H1. Customer satisfaction is influenced by website design. H2. Customer satisfaction is influenced by information content. H3. Greater customer satisfaction is directly related to greater levels of trust. H4. Greater customer satisfaction is directly related to greater levels of loyalty.

Figure 1- Hypotheses framed

The research design is descriptive in nature with an empirical support. The sample size of selected clients for the study is 60 and the sampling technique used here is simple random sampling through lottery method from the 221 clients.

4.0 Data Analysis & Interpretation

The final tool for collecting data was set after a lot of dew deliberations and discussions. Then it was validated properly. The questions were grouped according to five variables each one related to the values presented in our framework and the hypotheses we wish to evaluate.

The five variables created are Website Design, Information Content, Customer Satisfaction, Trust and Loyalty. All the questions were then assigned to a variable to which the answer is related. The preliminary analysis has been made to check the reliability of the five variables. By observing the results, all five factors' α are higher than 0.7. so these are sound values to proceed further.

Table-1: Reliability statistics for all variables

Item-Total Statistics	
	Cronbach's Alpha (α)
Customer Satisfaction	.857
Information Content	.821
Loyalty	.867
Trust	.858
Website Design	.864

(Source: primary data)

Table-2 : Summary of Correlation Analysis

No.	Variables	Pearson Correlation Coefficient	P value	Status of Hypotheses
1	<i>Customer satisfaction Vs Website Design</i>	0.625	0.000**	H1 Accepted
2	<i>Customer satisfaction Vs Information Content</i>	0.702	0.000**	H2 Accepted
3	<i>Customer satisfaction Vs Trust</i>	0.679	0.000**	H3 Accepted
4	<i>Customer satisfaction Vs Loyalty</i>	0.663	0.000**	H4 Accepted

***. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).*

(Source: primary data)

It is so visible from table-2 that all 4 variables, namely - Website Design, Information Content, Trust & Loyalty, are positively correlated and all the p – values are less than 0.01. Hence all 4 framed hypotheses are accepted and true in nature.

This study considers two main website elements, which make a website effective and successful; website design and information content. Evaluating the websites and estimating the overall score for each one helped us in the investigation of the sub-elements that contribute to each of the elements mentioned. By observing the website evaluation we can claim that, the criteria used in evaluating the website could be used to determine the effectiveness of the website. Companies could use this set of criteria to evaluate their website and develop new features, which will help them retain their place in the internet marketing.

To sum up, the website studied and evaluated had good presentation features such as, consistent use of font color and background.

Also, the website is structured in an easy to navigate layout by using menus and navigation bars. The websites provide detailed information about the company and the products. Moreover, security and privacy statements have been widely adopted. The research provides an insight into the type of elements that make a website successful. Although, individuals might have different preferences, they may be influenced by their culture and perceptions. Despite that, we can draw some conclusions regarding the elements of an effective website:

- Detailed company description, including history of the organization, annual reports and many more.
- Detailed product and services descriptions. The customer must know what he/she is buying or interested in.
- A reach variety of online services offered, such as online customer support, FAQs, widespread help feature, updates and many more according to the type of website.
- Secure methods of payment and Privacy policy statements. Users must feel protected when interacting with the website. By providing detailed information about the company's security and privacy, users feel safe to provide the website with their personal details and consequently they trust the company for keeping their information out of threats.
- An effective, well-structured layout that enables the easy navigation through the website. Clear links and paths, search engine and site maps help users navigate and find the information needed.
- A consistent use of colors, fonts and background.

By observing the results from the evaluation of the Hypotheses 1 and 2, we can undoubtedly claim that customer satisfaction is positively influenced by website design and information content. The research results also provide evidence for the relationship between customer satisfaction and trust, commitment and loyalty respectively. The relationship between customer satisfaction and trust has been revealed as positive. This means that greater level of customer satisfaction is related to greater level of trust. Furthermore, customer satisfaction has been related to greater levels of commitment and loyalty. By observing the results from the evaluation of hypotheses 3 and 4, we declare that greater level of customer satisfaction is related to greater levels of trust and loyalty.

The results let somebody see that an effective website is supported by the design of the website and the information content. Users feel satisfied if the website is well designed and the information provided is reliable, accurate and up to date. The key element of our framework is the customer satisfaction.

5.0 Conclusion

This research can be useful to companies that strive to gain a competitive advantage in the age of the internet and market place. Our framework can be useful to both academics and practitioners. Website designers and developers can use the framework to classify issues that need more attention in developing a website. Our model provides a tangible tool to measure the elements affecting customer behavior and overall satisfaction. Online companies can identify the features that are mostly intended to influence customers and evaluate their website effectiveness. Hence, our findings endow businesses with the key elements for developing a website for meeting customers' needs and expectations, and increase company's profits.

The purpose of this study was to attempt to discover the factors that affect online consumer

behavior. Our efforts to uncover the elements of a website having an effect on customer satisfaction have been successful. Furthermore, by determining the key elements of a successful website, which effectively attract new customers, retain existing ones, satisfy them and enhance the feeling of trust, commitment and loyalty is an important step in the world of internet marketing. The key element of our framework is customer satisfaction. As mentioned in the literature, marketing aims to identify, anticipate and satisfy customers. The focal point of Internet marketing is the relationship between organizations and customers. A website is the communication tool between customers and businesses. For this reason, it is essential for a company that operates online to provide a decent communication tool to its customers and offer innovative features to attract new customers and retain existing ones by satisfying all their needs. Last but not least, it can be argued that a company which operates on internet can achieve a competitive advantage by taking all the aspects of the framework into consideration. Put in words, it requires careful analysis of the elements and features, which conduct a website and a thorough examination of the perspective users of the online market.

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A Research Synthesis on Components of Multimedia-instruction for Enhancing English Language Skills

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Abstract

English has been a part of the foreign language curriculum in most of the countries across the world. But learning English has always posed a challenge to non-native speakers. Lack of the effectiveness of traditional methods that involve teaching a language using ‘Chalk and Talk’ methods, and the resultant low level of achievement or proficiency in English have always been areas of concern for educators and policy-makers. For this reason, deliberations have been held, and researches have been conducted to assess the efficacy of newly emerging pedagogies, of which Computer-assisted, Multimedia-based language learning forms a major part. Such changes have also instigated researches on the effectiveness of such practices of using multimedia, which encompass the use of text, images, audio, video, graphics, animation etc. for the teaching of English. In the present paper, the synthesis of literature isolates a small segment of the available literature on Multimedia intervention for enhancing English Language Skills. Findings revealed that multimedia-based instructional packages are more effective than the traditional methods of the teaching of English. However, the efficacy of multimedia-based instruction largely depends on its design, selection and presentation of content and teacher-student dynamics in the classroom. Therefore, literature was studied to identify the principles of effective design, more useful content and the methods of successful presentation as also the role of the teacher in multimedia-based instruction for English language teaching.

Keywords: Multimedia, English language teaching, Multimedia-based Instructional Package, Components of Multimedia.

Introduction

English has been a part of the foreign language curriculum in most of the countries across the world. But learning English has always posed a challenge for non-native speakers. Lack of effectiveness of the traditional methods that involve teaching a language using ‘Chalk and Talk’ methods and the resultant low levels of achievement or proficiency in English have always been areas of concern for educators and policy-makers. For this reason, deliberations have been held, and researches have been conducted to assess the efficacy of newly emerging pedagogies of which Multimedia-based language-learning forms a major part. This scenario is more or less the same across the globe and India is no exception. Highlighting this issue in their paper, Sharma and Madan, (2018) expressed this concern by saying “Teaching of English as a foreign language has been quite an exceptional issue ever since its induction in the modern Indian Education System. Since Macaulay’s time, various techniques, methods and pedagogies have been tried over the centuries such as translation, grammar, direct

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structural approaches etc. of late, culminating in inter-active and communicative approach over the past few decades, voraciously adopted in thousands of English Medium schools mushrooming every nook and corner of country, besides thousands of Govt. and aided institutes of all types. Despite all that, the situation has by and large, remained as alarming as ever not only in India but also at the home ground of English soil, as the media reports tend to reveal. As many as 98 per cent of the very high scoring students at +2 stage seeking admission to B.A (Hon's) in English in Delhi university fail to qualify the admission entrance Test in English”.

“Previously, English was taught from fifth standard in the non-English medium schools of Maharashtra. Now it is taught from the first standard even in the non-English medium schools. In the past the syllabus was literature based but now it is skill-based. Earlier the evaluation system was centered on the written skill only, from the year 2006-07 the oral test is introduced in the secondary and higher secondary schools. People are aware of the importance of English. They are interested in learning the spoken English. As a result, various courses are developed for teaching spoken English. The use of Language Laboratory and Computer Assisted Language Learning (CALL) has created new changes in the teaching of English. The audio cassettes and CDs are being used on a large scale to learn the spoken language. Various software of English teaching are developed and used by a growing number of people.”(Vijayalakshmi & Babu, 2014) Such changes have also instigated researches on the effectiveness of such practices of using multimedia, which encompass the use of text, images, audio, video, graphics, animation etc. for the teaching of English, which found many advocates such as; Roden, (1991) who says that “Multimedia instructional material allows the learner to actually see, hear and use the content learned”. Sharing the same perception and experience Sharma and Pooja (2018) made a profound claim that “multimedia learning environments are destined to make substantial inroads into schools at all levels. It offers a transparent and repeatable way to study specific aspects of the teaching and learning processes”. In the present paper, the synthesis of literature isolates a small segment of available literature on Multimedia intervention for enhancing English Language Skills. Findings revealed that multimedia-based instructional packages are more effective than traditional methods of the teaching of English. The evidence in favour of the use of multimedia is so loud and clear that it is no longer a question as to whether or not to incorporate it in teaching and learning but of ‘How’ to use it so that maximum benefits can be harnessed from it. It was observed that effective use of online materials has the potential of providing a different kind of learning experience for learners much like the first-hand exposure of the target-language if they were immersed in the language and culture while studying abroad. Therefore, literature was studied to get important insights on the elements that are more effective in multimedia-based instructional package for enhancing English language skills.

Review of Related Literature

Arcario (1992) suggests criteria for selecting video materials for the transaction of syllabus to the students in his paper titled “*Video in Second Language Teaching: Using, Selecting and Producing Video for the Classroom*”. He maintains that “comprehensibility is a major criterion in selecting a video for language-learning purposes”. He listed the following drawbacks of using feature movies in EFL classes:

1. “Students do not learn language skills if the films are shown without any activities.

2. Careful selection and adoption of activities and tasks, the syllabus should be designed within the linguistic output expected.
3. Captioned and non-captioned aspects of movie-viewing should be determined.
4. Careful integration with the core syllabus should be done.
5. Enabling students to learn about cultural issues, linguistic and lexical elements and providing various language practice materials will make films more advantageous.
6. Non-captioned movies may hinder the learning opportunities of movies.
7. Captioned movies may cause students' distraction and become a 'screen reading' activity.
8. Offending scenes and non-standard articulation of language may decrease students' motivation and enthusiasm.
9. Teachers' unnecessary interruptions may distract students' attention and the audio-visual interactive session may become a classical in-class teaching."

Scheffler and Logan (1999) in their study, identified the computer competencies that were important for teachers. "A Delphi panel developed a survey instrument of 67 computer competencies. Fifteen of these competencies related to networks, the Internet, and e-mail. Survey responses came from 437 technology coordinators, teacher educators, and secondary teachers. The most important computer competencies dealt with integration of computers into curricula and using computers in instruction. The use of networks and the Internet for research and the use of e-mail were rated important, but ranked 22nd and 23rd in the list of 33 competencies that were rated Important or Very Important". "Changes in the teaching model will surely bring about changes in the teacher's roles and students' roles. In an EAVSC (English Audio-Visual Speaking class), the teacher was no longer the leader in class, but a guide and facilitator in students' performance during the whole learning process. Therefore, the teacher's role tended to be multi-dimensional: the designer and organiser of the activities, the coordinator, the resource of cultural knowledge and the assessor of the effectiveness of learning and teaching (Lu et al 2008)".

Deesri (2002) advocates use of games in a language classroom as "students can become so engrossed in a game and focused on how to play the game, working as a group and competing to ultimately win that the grammar and vocabulary being used becomes natural since the students are not focused on learning English, but on the task at hand. Students stop thinking about language and begin using it in a spontaneous and natural manner within the classroom". Rao (2006) explains that in China games have been used to assist students in learning in new ways to help open up their minds.

Quiang et al (2007) in their paper titled "China EFL: Teaching through Movies" observed that "the use of motion pictures or other captioned films as part of teaching English as a foreign language has markedly increased in recent years in China. Because of this, we undertook a four-year experiment to determine how effective the use of English-language movies has been in the teaching of business. From this experiment it became clear that a cavalier use of movies in effect *misused* them. The appropriate and effective use of motion pictures requires a range of elements: (1) movies that are at one and the same time educational, informative, and entertaining; (2) a workbook linked to such movies that enables students to get ready beforehand; (3) most importantly, a range of classroom activities to induce and elicit timely and optimal output from the students, so as to make talking and writing about communication easier and more effective. Activities such as dubbing, story retelling, acting, discussing, debating, and role playing are only a few of the effective techniques a teacher can employ to engage the students".

Nicolas Guichon and McLornan, (2008) presented the results of a study on “the effects of multimodality upon second language comprehension” which was designed with a purpose to present some crucial recommendations for the future instructional design. “An experiment was designed to compare the understanding of an authentic BBC audiovisual recording, which was presented to four groups of French undergraduate students (N= 40). Group 1 was exposed to sound alone, Group 2 to image and sound, Group 3 to image, sound and L1 subtitles and Group 4 to image, sound and L2 subtitles. Students were asked to produce a detailed written summary in English with the help of their own notes. The results indicate that comprehension improves when learners are exposed to a text in several modalities. In addition, they suggest that L2 subtitling is more beneficial than L1 because it causes less lexical interference”.

Yang and Fang (2008) in their study titled, “Optimization of Multimedia English Teaching in Context Creation” explored the characteristics of multimedia and how to use multimedia to optimize the context of English teaching as its purpose. In this study, eight principles, specifically Systematization, Authenticity, Appropriateness, Interactivity, Coordination, Pluralism, Intelligibility, and Penetrability, are summarized to fulfill this purpose. The principle of systematisation emphasizes that “the purpose of English teaching is the development of students’ Meaning Potential, which uses the cultural significance of the target language to raise the English communicative competence. Multimedia and network teaching provide a more advantageous condition for the development of Meaning Potential to students”. The Principle of Authenticity means that “the real context can meet students’ practical needs in communication. In ELT, teachers have various choices of multimedia software, videos, films, slides, photographs, and other media. They can also use multimedia tools to provide vivid materials, creating real contexts and giving background information in order to help students to create an atmosphere of participation and exchange in different contexts.” The Principle of Appropriateness suggests that “in order to optimize multimedia English teaching in context-creation in terms of the appropriate selection of information, we should take care to classify and organize information effectively and make choices according to students’ needs. Otherwise, there will be too much information for them”. The Principle of Interactivity is that “the goal of interaction between teachers and students is to achieve exchanges in the real language context. Teaching content should be designed with consideration of how to achieve interaction between teachers and students, among students themselves, and between students and modern technology. Through these different types of interaction, personalized learning, collaborative learning and other modes of learning can be combined in order to help students to take the initiative”. The Principle of Coordination says that “it is inappropriate to change the classroom into a platform for information exchange between students and modern machinery. Multimedia language teaching is not simply a ‘means of introducing multimedia’. Attention should be paid to coordination between teachers and students, teaching materials and methods, theory and practice and multimedia teaching and the real learning environment. Students learn to take the initiative to promote exchanges with teachers, and vice versa; it is not appropriate to apply too many teaching methods or provide too much courseware to students. It is important to choose the most suitable teaching method for creating a real teaching and learning environment to help students gain the most intuitive and cultural information using various functions and forms of multimedia presentation. In this way, students can develop self-confidence in communication and improve their overall English skills.” The Principle of Pluralism

“requires teachers to choose and create appropriate and comprehensive educational methods to promote the full development of students based on the educational content, their intelligence structure, their interests, and their different characteristics. English teachers should constantly make use of the advantages of multimedia teaching to update English teaching concepts and teaching strategies, and produce scenario-style, animation-style, case-style, analogue-style, and game-show-style films as self-supporting material to inspire students. This will create multimedia English teaching context conducive to the development of Multiple Intelligence”. The Principle of Intelligibility suggests that “English teachers should socialize and contextualize the multimedia classroom, as well as trying to transplant the real use of English into an in-classroom multimedia environment to improve interpretative skills of students. Teachers can also use multimedia to help students to predict the text in order to grasp the context and enhance their comprehensive skills”. The Principle of Penetrability advocates that “English teachers should involve their own sincere feelings in the classroom and make use of multimedia to stimulate students’ emotions. The learning process can stimulate desire to learn, so that students leave with positive feelings after class. English teachers should also learn to explore aesthetic factors in the context creation in multimedia language teaching, and make use of the display functions of multimedia to make timely demonstrations to help students learn about the aesthetic capacity of English, so that they are able to express their personalities in the foreign language”.

In order to assess the effectiveness of multimedia programmes in children's vocabulary-acquisition in the second language, Acha (2009) investigated “the effect of three different presentation modes on children's vocabulary learning with a self-guided multimedia programme” on a sample consisting of 135 students of class 3 and 4. “Students were presented a short English language story on a computer with twelve previously unknown words (key words) embedded within the story, and presented with verbal annotations (written translation), visual annotations (picture representation), and a combination of the two to assist in their understanding of the twelve key words. The results revealed that ‘Recall’ of word translations was the highest for students who received verbal annotations only;” suggesting thereby that a self-learning multimedia programme may not always be effective in second language vocabulary-acquisition as students learnt better with verbal annotations only.

Wyle (2009), in his paper titled “Exploring the English-Speaking World through the Biography: Course Methodology” attempts to examine “the ongoing development and adaptation of methods and materials, particularly the use of ‘authentic texts’ and multimedia, for Exploring the English Speaking World through the Biography course taught at Kanda University”. The paper shares the experience of the course which follows a multimedia approach by utilizing the audio, video, CDROM, teacher-talk to explore the enhancement of proficiency in English through biographies.

Sato & Suzuki (2010) conducted a comparative study to investigate whether “multimedia-oriented visual glosses really facilitate EFL vocabulary learning” or not and did “a comparison of planar images with three-dimensional images” and also of multimedia-oriented class and traditional classes. The study treated “three-dimensional images as a multimedia gloss to demonstrate the spatial relationship of prepositions such as above, across, below, in, on, and over”. Two multimedia dictionaries were developed by the researcher for the purpose of investigation which covered spatial prepositions; “one with planar images, and the other with three-dimensional images of spatial relationships for each

language item". To verify the effectiveness of multimedia gloss, the sample was randomly divided into control group and experimental group, followed by a vocabulary test in each group to choose appropriate spatial prepositions with reference to these dictionaries. The "results of t-test to assess the significant differences between control groups (referring to planar image glosses) and experimental group (referring to stereoscopic image glosses) found that there is no difference in the linguistic knowledge of special prepositions between control and experimental groups ($p=0.9115$). It was also found that there is no statistical significance between those who refer to planar and 3D dictionaries and there is no significant difference between the use of planar schematic image and that of multimedia-oriented tridimensional image in EFL preposition learning."

In an experiment conducted by Adegoke (2011), to assess "the effect of multimedia instruction on cognitive achievement of senior secondary school students in physics", on a sample of 198 consisting of 106 male and 92 female students in three experimental groups and a control group, the results revealed that, on an average, "students in the group for which animation was presented with on-screen text and narration took best quality notes" which apparently, "influenced their superior cognitive achievement in physics". Generally, "students under multimedia instruction performed better than their colleagues who were taught using lecture method". Three different types of course-wares were developed to examine the interface effects which involved, "animation + on-screen text", "animation + narration", "animation + on-screen text + narration". The findings of the study revealed that "learning outcomes of students in physics can be enhanced with multimedia instruction".

Kumud and Sharma (2012), in their paper titled "Power Point's Power in the class-room" establish the effectiveness of power-point presentations over the traditional method. They claimed that use of a combination of text, picture, audio, video, animation improved the achievement of the students to a greater extent as compared to the traditional method.

Sorden (2012) cited that "Mayer argues that meaningful learning from words and pictures happens when the learner engages in five cognitive processes: 1. selecting relevant words for processing in verbal working memory 2. selecting relevant images for processing in visual working memory 3. organizing selected words into a verbal model 4. organizing selected images into a pictorial model 5. integrating the verbal and pictorial representations with each other and with prior knowledge".

Tuncay (2014) in his paper titled "An Integrated Skills Approach Using Feature Movies in EFL at Tertiary Level" presented the results of a case study which involved 100 students by concluding that "the integration of feature movies in the syllabus helped students in several ways: (1) improve language competence by watching, listening and speaking, (2) understand authentic language and culture, (3) increase fluency and integrated writing skill, (4) practice English for various functions and purposes, (5) learn vocabulary and authentic expressions, (6) distinguish between artificial and natural use of language, and (7) use the language in social exchanges and different interactional settings". He further recommends that "Feature Movies should be easy to understand, and the comprehensibility of the dialogues and the language used should not contain heavy accent."

In response to the question on "What do you think about a teacher's job in an EAVSC?", the response was that only 16% students agreed that the teachers' primary task is to impart knowledge and educate the students. "This indicates that in an ICT-based language lab, the teacher should not only act as the knowledge provider, for the new teaching philosophy and an ICT-driven curriculum demand new roles of the teacher".

Around 30% of the students reckoned that one of the teacher's main responsibilities was to organise interactive activities among students. The reason was that in a foreign language learning community, what students needed most were authentic or nearly authentic speaking environment and sufficient opportunities for communication. Egbert et al. (1999) have discussed eight conditions for creating optimal language learning environments, opportunities for interaction and negotiation of meaning, interaction with authentic audiences in the target language, students' involvement in authentic tasks, exposure to and encouragement to produce varied and creative language, feedback, meta-cognitive guidance, and an ideal anxiety or stress level.

In the meantime, more than 40% of the students held that apart from organising in-class activities, another important job for the teacher was to introduce topic-related background information and cultural knowledge. The concept of a "student-centred" classroom does not mean that students take full responsibilities of the class. The teacher should make well arrangements, organise whole class activities, and guide the students in most learning procedures. Hughes (2005) reported that apart from language skills, culture, social interaction, and the politeness norms which exist in the target language and a large number of other things also need to be adjusted for successful communication. "As an advanced target language teacher, she/he is also expected to be knowledgeable both in language ability and cultural competence. As an intermediate linkage, the teacher connects the culture of the target language and the learners' mother tongue culture. During students' interaction process, the teacher had one important job: to monitor what the students were doing and how well they were doing. The teacher took different measures in different situations, such as participating in those activities so as to know the ongoing situation in that pair or group, or providing necessary help in order to promote the discussion. From this perspective, the teacher was not only the designer and organiser of activities, but also an effective classroom manager and coordinator – to arrange the classroom time appropriately, to organise in-class speaking activities effectively, and to maximise students' involvement in communicating in the target language."

Gomez (2016), in her paper titled "*How working collaboratively with technology can foster a creative learning environment*", shares the results of an experiment funded by the European Union within the project PopuLLar. "In this experience, music and ICTs are combined; schoolchildren worked autonomously and collaboratively in order to create lyrics for songs of their choice in their L2. They sang their songs, recorded them and uploaded their creations to a wiki. Children from other countries later translated those songs from the L2 to their L1. The conclusions of the piloting (both local and large-scale) were very positive and went beyond the expectations of the researchers involved. Excellent feedback was received from all participants in the project, due to its humanistic approach to teamwork and creativity".

Sharma and Kiran (2016), in their paper titled "Tracing the conceptual framework of multimedia-based instructional package for enhancing English language skills" quoted Sorden (2012), "Mayer argues that meaningful learning from words and pictures happens when the learner engages in five cognitive processes: 1. selecting relevant words for processing in verbal working memory 2. selecting relevant images for processing in visual working memory 3. organizing selected words into a verbal model 4. organizing selected images into a pictorial model 5. integrating the verbal and pictorial representations with each other and with prior knowledge".

Study conducted by Cho (2017), aimed at “examining the effects of multimedia in video form in addition to textual information on Second language vocabulary instruction for English words among Korean learners of English”, observed that multimedia presentation had a greater positive effect on learning than text-only presentation, supporting the dual-coding theory. Among the types of multimedia support, the combination of Text, Audio, Video was found to be better than Text and Audio or Text and Video, thereby, suggesting the benefit of the combination of audio and video along with text. Moreover, multimedia audio-visual support was found to be more advantageous when supplemented with a linguistic cue in the form of a precise definition or synonym of an unknown word. Findings have both theoretical and pedagogical implications in the second language vocabulary acquisition of English words as the study addressed the ways to design effective multimedia materials and offered instructional guidelines for multimedia language teaching.

Significant insights from the literature review

- In a multimedia based instructional package for enhancing English language skills, students' active involvement in viewing, reviewing and editing a movie in the classroom promotes language learning. Therefore, a multimedia package for teaching L2 should incorporate age-appropriate short movies and students should be allowed to view, review, edit and engage with the movie.
- Videos can be used to motivate ESL learners, create their interest, bring the real world into the classroom, contextualize the target language naturally and enable the learners to experience authentic language.
- Studies revealed that Power-point presentations using a combination of text, picture, audio, video, animation are more effective over the traditional method. Therefore, some complex concepts of English can be explained using power point presentation in the multimedia package.
- Comprehension improves when learners are exposed to a text in several modalities such as Text+Text, Audio, Video was found to be better than Text and Audio or Text and Video.
- Biographical text provides opportunities to associate expressions associated with life stories while introducing content-specific vocabulary and discourse patterns. This results in fluency development and language-focused learning. Therefore, multimedia package for teaching L2 should incorporate biographical text in one form or the other.
- If music and ICTs are combined in a second language classroom; in which school-children can work autonomously and collaboratively in order to create lyrics for songs of their choice in their L2, this activity can enhance their familiarity and fluency in the target language. Therefore, multimedia package for teaching L2 should incorporate songs in the target language.
- Games can be used effectively for language learning because students become so engrossed in playing a game, working as a group and competing to ultimately win that the grammar and vocabulary being used becomes natural since the students are not focused on learning English, but on the task at hand. Students stop thinking about language and begin using it in a spontaneous and natural manner within the classroom. Therefore, multimedia package for teaching L2 should incorporate language games in the target language.
- Speaking skills can be improved more if learners are motivated and given autonomy to speak in the given context. Therefore, multimedia instruction can be designed for

improving speaking skills of learners in such a way that multimedia facilitates and motivates the learners to use English in a given context.

- Result of study related to reading skill indicated that students who received the reading intervention program with computer materials significantly improved their phonological awareness, word-recognition, and letter-naming skills relative to their peers who received a reading intervention programme with only printed materials and those who received no formal reading intervention programme. Therefore, multimedia instruction can be designed for improving reading skills of learners.
- In general, authentic texts were found to be more effective in a language classroom than non-authentic texts but it was observed that teachers cannot depend only on authentic materials for teaching in the classroom. Therefore, they can use both: authentic and artificial (non-authentic) materials, because learners need to get accustomed to both types.
- Multimedia can be used to facilitate a range of classroom activities to induce and elicit timely and optimal output from the students, so as to make talking and writing about communication easier and more effective. Activities such as dubbing, story retelling, acting, discussing, debating, and role playing are only a few of the effective techniques a teacher can employ to engage the students.
- The results of most of the studies indicate a positive attitudinal change for a multimedia-enhanced mode of learning.
- The teacher connects the culture of the target language and the learners' mother tongue culture. Therefore, teacher mediated multimedia packages are more useful than learner-controlled multimedia packages.

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A Comparative Study of Stress Level and its Coping Techniques in Public (LIC) and Private (ICICI Prudential) Life Insurance Companies

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Abstract

In today's competitive era, stress is inevitable. Stress is much in the news at present scenario but it is not a new problem. Today workplace stress is becoming a major issue and a matter of concern for the employees and their employing organizations. Work-related stress has become an issue which increasingly features on the agenda of efficient managers. There is a realization that stress plays a central role in shaping contemporary business world. Understanding the phenomenon, its causes and consequences, is considered vital for improving the quality of life for employees and the effectiveness of the organizations. Training and employee assistance programs dealing with stress should satisfy the employees' needs. Various workshops, seminars and conferences should increase employees' awareness of the costs associated with employee stress, and should teach them how to cope with stressful situations.

This study makes a review of The Employees Stress in public and private Insurance Sector by conducting a comparative study of LIC and ICICI Prudential representing the public & private sector respectively. Employees have been experiencing high level of stress due to various factors such as high workload, tight deadlines, high targets, lack of job satisfaction, long working hours, pressure of performance etc. These are the internal and external factors which are correlated with the job performance of the employees.

The study employs both primary and secondary sources for collecting facts and figures relating to the topic under research. The Lucknow region of Life Insurance Corporation and ICICI Prudential life insurance companies has been selected for the purpose of primary data collection. For the secondary data sources various studies covering insurance sector were scanned. Business newspaper like Business Standard, Economics Times and Business Lines, and business magazines and journals such as Business Today, Business World, Economic & Political Weekly and IRDA journal were also perused. Such information provides the basis for building up the theoretical and conceptual framework of the study.

A sample of 100 insurance professionals working in both public (LIC) and private (ICICI Prudential) life insurance companies was examined. A structured questionnaire was designed to gather information on the socio demographic profile of the respondents.

The study revealed that insurance personnel in both Public (LIC) and Private (ICICI Prudential) Life Insurance Sector are experiencing moderate to high level of stress. However, a significant chunk of insurance personnel are experiencing rather moderate level of stress.

Keywords: Stress, Occupational Stress Index, Insurance, LIC, ICICI Prudential

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1. Introduction

Stress is the condition in which an individual is confronted with an environmental demand related to him and he perceives the outcome as uncertain but important. This uncertainty is a cause for anxiety that usually leads to stress. According to Selye "Stress is any critical event or any internal drive, which threatens to upset the organism's equilibrium". Stress is an old phenomenon which pervades the human life right from birth to death. Its mention is also found in Vedic Literature as "Dukha" (Grief) and "Dushchinta"(Anxiety). Its occurrence is not limited to a specific time period. It is a phenomenon, which is as old as human life. From the birth till death, an individual encounters different types of threats in his life. He/she tries to neutralize the stresses by changing perceptions, attitudes and resorting to various other coping mechanisms. During prehistoric age, there was stress due to factors like threats of wild animals, natural calamities, climatic dangers, inter group conflict for searching foods and living resources etc. In the present era, human beings are under stress not only from work pressure and tension but also due to threats like nuclear threat, political & economic uncertainty, regionalism, communalism, economic and political crises, and urbanization, threat of war, unemployment, and poverty and job insecurity. We are living in the age of 'Science and Development' but in the age of 'Anxiety' and 'Stress' as well (Cooper, Deve & O' Driscoll, 2001).

2. Literature Review

The term stress is derived from Latin word "*stringere*" (Edworthy, 2000). Earlier the term was used to denote a stimulus (a force or pressure that causes distress) and response to that stimulus (Adversity, affliction) (Keefe, 1988). The term stress was first employed in a biological context by the endocrinological Hans Selye in the 1930's. He later broadened and popularized the concept to include inappropriate physiological response to any demand. Stress a word derived from Latin word '*Stringere*' meaning to '*to draw tight*' was popularly used in the 17th century to mean hardships, straits, adversity, or affliction. Later in the 18th and 19th centuries stress as used in the physical sciences, equated it with internal force or pressure generated within a solid body by the action of any external force causing rupture or distortion of the body (Uma Gulati, 2005).

Hans Selye was one of the founding fathers of research on stress. He stated in 1956 that "Stress is not necessarily something bad - it all depends on how we take it." Since then, a great deal of further research has been conducted on the subject, and new ideas have come to light. A commonly used definition of stress is that of Selye (1956). Who has defined it as any external event or any internal drive, which threatens to upset the organism's equilibrium. Hans Selye, a pioneer in stress research, first described the physiological syndrome of stress in 1936. He defined stress as "the nonspecific response of the body to any demand made upon it" (Selye, 1974, p. 151). The body's reaction to a stressor became known as the "general adaptation syndrome" (G.A.S.) or the "biological stress syndrome." Dr. Selye described the syndrome as progressing through three stages:

1. The alarm reaction (the first response to a new situation, the stressor)
2. The stage of resistance (the continued exposure to the stressor and learning to cope)
3. The stage of exhaustion (the depletion of energy reserves which leads to fatigue and eventually death).

Even though the stressors may be different, they all elicit the same biological stress response. It does not matter whether the situation is pleasant or unpleasant. The body must adapt to

change in order to maintain its homeostasis. Pleasurable events may be thought of as “stress” while unpleasurable events may be thought of as “distress” (Selye, 1974).

Figure: 1 Shows the three stages of General Adaptation Syndrome (GAS)-

Duration of Exposure to stress

Source: Uma, Gulati (2005), *Management of Organizational Stress*, New Century Publications, page no. 9

Cooper and Marshall (1976) described seven categories of stress, six external and one internal to the manager's concerned. These are:

- I. Intrinsic to job (too much or too little work, poor working conditions and time pressure etc)
- II. Role in organization (role ambiguity, no participation in decision making etc.) Career Development (under or over promotion, job insecurity etc.)
- III. Organizational interface (company vs. family demands, company vs. own interests)
- IV. Organizational structure (restriction on behavior, office politics etc.)
- V. Relations with in organization (poor relationship with boss, peers and subordinates)
- VI. Individual manager (personality, ability to cope with change and behavioral patterns)

3. Present Scenario of Employees Stress

In modern time stress has become a part of life. Stress in work atmosphere has received considerable attention in recent years. A major source of such stress is the work role or role assigned to each employee. Work role may create stress because they are in conflict with each other, or with the employee's own needs, values, or abilities. Work stress originates in organizational demands which are experienced by the employees. Mismanaged employee stress can produce strain which is detrimental for the human resources in the organization. This has negative economic implications such as poor quality of work, low productivity, absenteeism, etc. When an organization is able to manage stress, it can lead to improved performance, work satisfaction, involvement and productivity. The harmful and costly consequences of stress demonstrate the need for strategies to limit stressors within the organization, as well as to deal with stress that already occurred. Namely, those organizations which fully address the issue of work-related stress through problem recognition and problem-solving activities will be better placed to deal with the demands of a rapidly changing world and thus enhance their chances of gaining competitive advantage.

4. Potential Sources of Employee Stress

There are three sets of factors -environmental, organizational, and individual- that act as potential sources of employee stress.

A. Environmental factors: Just as environmental uncertainty influences the design of an organization's structure, it also influences stress levels among employees in that organization. Changes in the business cycle create economic uncertainties. When the economy is contracting, for example, employees become increasingly anxious about their security. Potential uncertainties, political uncertainties are the second type of environmental factors. Technological uncertainty is the third type of environmental factors that can cause stress.

B. Organizational factors: There is no shortage of factors within the organization that can cause employees stress. Pressures to avoid errors or complete tasks in a limited time period, work overload, a demanding and insensitive boss, and unpleasant co-workers are few examples.

Some of such factors are

- a. Discrimination in pay/salary structure
- b. Strict rules and regulations
- c. Ineffective communication
- d. Peer pressure
- e. Goals conflicts/goals ambiguity
- f. More of centralized and formal organization structure
- g. Less promotional opportunities
- h. Lack of employees participation in decision-making
- i. Excessive control over the employees by the managers

C. Individual factors: Primarily these factors are family issues, personal economic problems, and inherent personality characteristics etc.

5. Strategies Helping Employees to Manage Stress at Workplace

Many employees feel some sort of work-related stress at some point in their working lives, particularly when deadlines are looming. Generally, infrequent and short bouts of stress are manageable for most people. However, when stress becomes prolonged or more intense, it can start to cause physical and mental health issues. Engaging with employees on a regular basis (e.g. by having regular reviews in order to discuss any on-going concerns) will allow employers/managers to keep up-to-date with how employees are feeling about their job role, the organisation as a whole, relationships with colleagues, personal issues, etc. It can also help employers understand the personalities of individuals, how they interact with each other, and how- these factors are relevant to potential stressful situations. Stress experienced by the employees in their job has negative impact on their health, performance and their behaviour in the organization. Thus, stress needs to be managed effectively so as to set off these harmful consequences.

Employers need to learn to recognize the signs that stress may be getting the better of an employee, for example:

A. Organizational strategies for managing stress

1. Encouraging more of organizational communication with the employees so that there is no role ambiguity/conflict. Effective communication can also change employee views. Managers can use better signs and symbols which are not misinterpreted by the employees.

2. Encourage employees' participation in decision-making. This will reduce role stress.
3. Grant the employees greater independence, meaningful and timely feedback, and greater responsibility.
4. The organizational goals should be realistic, stimulating and particular. The employees must be given feedback on how well they are heading towards these goals.
5. Encourage decentralization.
6. Have a fair and just distribution of incentives and salary structure.
7. Promote job rotation and job enrichment,
8. Create a just and safe working environment.
9. Have effective hiring and orientation procedure.
10. Appreciate the employees on accomplishing and over.-exceeding their targets.

B. Individual strategies for managing stress

1. The employees should make a "to-do" list daily, prioritize the acts in the list and plan the acts accordingly. Take regular breaks during work to relax you. By effective time management, the employees can achieve their targets timely and can meet work pressures and, thus, avoid stress.
2. Do hard work, strive to achieve your goals but do' not do it to the harm of family, health, or peer.
3. Indulge in physical exercises, it helps in effective blood circulation, keeps you fit, diverts mind from work pressures.
4. Encourage a healthy lifestyle, take a regular sleep, have plenty of water, have healthy eating habits. Promote relaxation techniques such as yoga, listening music and meditation.
5. The employees should have optimistic approach about their work. They should avoid connections with negative approach employees.
6. The employees should have emotional intelligence at workplace. They should have self-awareness, self-confidence and self-control at workplace.
7. The employees should build social support. They should have close connections with trustworthy peer who can listen to their problems and boost their confidence level. This social network will help the employees to overcome stress.
8. Employee counselling is a very good strategy to overcome employee stress. Through counselling, employees can become aware of their strengths and how to develop those strengths; their weaknesses and how to eliminate them; and they can develop strategies for changing their behaviour. Employees are also given career counselling which helps in reducing their ambiguities with regard to career.
9. Find a fun way to release stress, such as, cracking jokes, playing tennis, golf, etc.
10. Do not remain pre-occupied with yourself, turn your focus outwards, help others. This will release some stress.

At last, but not the least it can be concluded that stressful situations at workplace are real and inevitable. It is not feasible to eliminate stress totally from the workplace.

Further, various research studies have repeatedly confirmed that some amount of stress is necessary for the employees as well as the organization to stay alive and perform well. However, excessive levels of stress lead to biological malfunctioning and dysfunctioning behaviour patterns on the part of employees and the organizational performance and survival. Thus, there is need to manage stress. Stress that is effectively managed by an

employee is a positive symptom and requires the knowledge of “Stress Coping Strategies” for reducing stress at workplace.

Factual information will be collected from the insurance sector through primary and secondary sources. The research study is designed to measure the intensity of stress in this important component of India's service sector i.e. insurance industry

The present study has been undertaken to make a review of the employee stress in the public and private insurance sector with the comparative study of LIC and ICICI Prudential. It also examines the management and working of the Insurance Industry in India. Prospects and challenges of Insurance Industry in India are also the focus of this study. The present work also explores as to how the Indian Insurance Industry competes at global level. It also measures the comparative performance of public and private life insurance sector. Among public and private sector insurance companies, the changes in employee's attitude and adaptability are critical concern. Every change influences employee mindset. It is imperative that the organisations addressed these issues on an urgent basis. If unmanaged, this has potential for creating stress among employees. Occupational Stress Index is considered as most important instrument to measure the level of stress among insurance personnel in this study. Accordingly, the Srivastava and Singh's Occupational Stress Index is applied in this study to assess the significant difference in the stress perception of the employees serving in both public and private sector's turbulent and comparatively stable environments.

The study also contemplates to put the conclusions drawn through the academic analysis and discussion to further test of the stress among employees who are working in the insurance sector. Their opinions will be elicited on various aspects of insurance sector practices followed by insurance personnel as emerge from this study. The test will be accomplished by means of administering a well-designed questionnaire having direct bearing on the subject matter of this study. The questionnaire shall be simple to understand and answer. Question will be put in each field of the hypotheses of this study. Against each question a scale of preference mentioning options will be given and the respondents shall answer the perception of their choice very conveniently by putting simply a tick. Employees stress level is measured through questionnaire on Occupational Stress dimensions. The primary data so collected will be analyzed through application of statistical tools. The inferences drawn will have impact in so far as the hypothesis of this study will come out as void or valid.

The work ahead, accordingly, proceeds in the aforesaid direction in a structured manner divided into chapters and unveils the results of the study in the end chapter of conclusion.

6. Research Objectives

The objectives of the study are as under:

1. To study the conceptual framework of employees stress in public (LIC) and private (ICICI prudential) life insurance sector.
2. To identify stressful job conditions and organizational factors perceived by employees working in public (LIC) and private (ICICI Prudential) Insurance sector.
3. To compare the level of stress experienced by employees in public (LIC) and private (ICICI Prudential) life insurance sector.
4. To examine if there is any significant difference in the stress perception of the employees serving in both public (LIC) and private (ICICI Prudential).
5. To provide suggestions to improve upon the existing sources of employee stress and to make it manageable in the light of analysis of findings and conclusions.

7. Research Methodology

The study uses both primary and secondary sources for collecting facts and figures relating to the topic under research. Geographically, the areas of primary data collection have been selected keeping in view the financial and time restraints impacting this study. Hence Lucknow and nearby areas have been chosen.

For the secondary data sources, various studies covering insurance and banking sector were scanned. Business newspaper like Business Standard, Economics Times and Business Lines, and business magazines and journals such as Business Today, Business World, Economic & Political Weekly and IRDA journal, Different books, journals, official statistics, reports, articles, publications and other documents, and electronic data have also been used.

8. Data Analysis

1.

Fig 1: Age range of Respondents

Interpretation: The data suggests that majority of respondents in LIC(30%) and ICICI Pru(35%) was of age range between 26-30 years.

2.

Fig 2: Stress Suffering

Interpretation: The data suggests that majority of respondents in LIC(50%) and ICICI Pru (65%) were generally suffering from Stress.

3.

Fig 3: Workload

Interpretation: The data suggests that majority of respondents in LIC(60%) and ICICI Pru (65%) were having a lot of work in their job.

4.

Fig 4: Contradictory Instruction

Interpretation: The data suggests that majority of respondents in LIC(45%) and ICICI Pru (55%) were generally getting contradictory statement related to their work.

5.

Fig 5: Responsibility for efficiency and productivity of other employees

Interpretation: The data suggests that respondents in LIC(35%) and ICICI Pru (55%) were responsible for efficiency and productivity of other employees.

6.

Fig 6: Self-respect of Employees

Interpretation: The data suggests that the respondent's self-respect in LIC (55%) and ICICI Pru (40%) were taken care by higher authorities.

7.

Fig 7: Salary in comparison to quantum of work

Interpretation: The data suggests that majority of respondents in LIC (40%) and ICICI Pru (50%) were not getting salary in comparison to quantum of work they do.

8.

Fig 8: Role and Objective of work

Interpretation: The data suggests that majority of respondents in LIC (45%) and ICICI Pru (45%) say that role and objective of work is not adequately planned.

9.

Fig 9: Defamation and malign Image

Interpretation: The data suggests that majority of respondents in LIC (45%) and ICICI Pru (60%) say that their image was defamed and malign buy their colleague.

10.

Fig 10: Reward for hard work and efficient performance

Interpretation: The data suggests that majority of respondents in LIC (50%) and ICICI Pru (65%) were generally not rewarded for their hard work and efficient performance.

11.

Fig 11: Hurried work due to excessive pressure

Interpretation: The data suggests that majority of respondents in LIC (60%) and ICICI Pru (75%) were generally disposing off their work hurriedly due to excessive workload.

12.

Fig12: Opportunity to develop skill and proficiency

Interpretation: The data suggests that majority of respondents in LIC (65%) and ICICI Pru (71%) were not getting ample opportunity to develop their skills and proficiency properly.

13.

Fig 13: Due Importance to suggestions

Interpretation: The data suggests that majority of respondents in LIC (52%) say that due importance was given to their suggestions where as in case of ICICI Pru (65%) said that due importance was not given to their suggestions.

14.

Fig 2: Unsatisfactory work due to excessive work load

Interpretation: The data suggests that majority of respondents in LIC(70%) and ICICI Pru (85%) were unable to do their work to their fullest satisfaction due to excessive work load and lack of time.

9. Findings

The main findings of the study are as follows:

1. According to our demographic analysis majority of respondents are between 26 – 30 years old.
2. Majority of respondents in LIC (50%) and ICICI Pru (65%) were generally suffering from Stress.
3. Majority of respondents in LIC (60%) and ICICI Pru (65%) were having a lot of work in their job.
4. The data suggest that respondents in LIC (45%) and ICICI Pru (55%) were generally getting contradictory statement related to their work.

5. The data suggests that respondents in LIC (35%) and ICICI Pru (55%) were responsible for efficiency and productivity of other employees.
6. The data suggests that the respondent's self respect in LIC (55%) and ICICI Pru (40%) were taken care by higher authorities.
7. The data suggests that majority of respondents in LIC (40%) and ICICI Pru (50%) was not getting salary in comparison to quantum of work they do.
8. The data suggests that majority of respondents in LIC (45%) and ICICI Pru (45%) say that role and objective of work is not adequately planned.
9. The data suggests that majority of respondents in LIC (45%) and ICICI Pru (60%) say that their image was defamed and malign buy their colleague.
10. The data suggests that majority of respondents in LIC (50%) and ICICI Pru (65%) was generally not rewarded for their hard work and efficient performance.
11. The data suggests that majority of respondents in LIC (60%) and ICICI Pru (75%) was generally disposing off their work hurriedly due to excessive workload.
12. The data suggests that majority of respondents in LIC (65%) and ICICI Pru (71%) was not getting ample opportunity to develop their skills and proficiency properly.
13. The data suggests that majority of respondents in LIC (52%) say that due importance was given to their suggestions where as in case of ICICI Pru (65%) said that due importance was not given to their suggestions.
14. The data suggests that majority of respondents in LIC(70%) and ICICI Pru (85%) were unable to do their work to their fullest satisfaction due to excessive work load and lack of time

10. Conclusion

As per study it is clear that insurance personnel in both Public (LIC) and Private (ICICI Prudential) Life Insurance sector are accustomed to stress level which varies from moderate to high. However Majority insurance personnel are experiencing rather moderate level of stress. From study it is clear that Private (ICICI Prudential) life insurance personnel are experiencing slightly more stress than Public (LIC) life insurance sector personnel. As per various diminutions of employees stress it is found that Role Overload, Role Ambiguity, Powerlessness, Intrinsic Impoverishment, Low Status and Strenuous working condition have significant effect on employees work stress in both Public and Private Life Insurance companies.

Since insurance sector is growing at rapid pace leading source of employment in India. A lot of changes are taking place in insurance sector due to international exposure, expansion and Government Intervention which has resulted into stiff completion. As a result of all these employees are going through stressful working conditions such as pressure to perform and work life balance. Identifying and addressing at individual level as well as organization level is very important for wellness of employees and also for better perforce and productivity for organization.

The effort on part of individual to manage stress level is called coping and the effort of organization to manage stress is among its employees is called Organizational intervention or stress management intervention. Both Coping and Organizational intervention is important for successful management of stress.

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An Analytical Study On Financial Performance Of Bajaj Allianz General Insurance Company Limited

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Abstract

Finance is considered to be the lifeline of any economy, whether the country is developed or under developed is highly depends on the financial performance of the particular sector or industry. So far the finance is concerned, level of risk can be observed in it. To overcome the risk and future uncertainties insurance is required to cover the level of loss. To hedge the risk of uncertainty an individual is advised to have an insurance policy. Insurance can be of life or non-life, and it may be Indian company or may be foreign. The objectives of present study are to analyze and evaluate the financial performance of Bajaj Allianz general insurance company limited through CAMEL Framework, to examine the trend of the indicators for the duration of the study and to make suggestions on the basis of interpretation of data. The indicators which represent the financial performance of insurance company are presented through CAMEL (Capital adequacy, Asset quality, Reinsurance and Actuarial issues, Management soundness, Earnings and profitability and Liquidity) framework.

Key Words: Financial performance, IRDA, Private General Insurer, CAMEL

Introduction

Finance is considered to be the lifeline of any economy. The development of any country is highly depended on the financial system of it. Financial system of any country depends on financial performance of particular sector or industry. To overcome future uncertainties and to reduce the level of risk and loss insurance is required. It is useful for both individuals as well as the corporates. Insurance can be of life, non-life and reinsurance. It can be from private sector or public sector. As a result of privatization i.e. economic reform of 1991, the importance of private sector increased. At present, 30 General insurance companies are working in India and from that 24 general insurance companies are from private sector. Bajaj Allianz general insurance company falls under the category of India's one of the top leading, most trusted, Asia's most valuable brand and general insurance company of the year in the 2018. The company was established in the year 2001 in Pune, Maharashtra. The vision of the company is to be the first choice for customers among all non-life insurance company and also to be the number one insurance company by creating shareholders value. This paper focuses on the analysis of financial performance of the Bajaj Allianz general insurance company limited through CAMEL (Capital adequacy, Asset quality, Reinsurance and Actuarial issues, Management soundness, Earnings and profitability and Liquidity) framework.

Literature Review

KETAN POPAT (2014) has studied the assessment of financial soundness and liquidity of selected general insurance companies of India. The sample size of the study was total 4

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companies of private as well as from public sector both. He has used secondary data of 7 years ranging from 2006 to 2012. For the analysis of data he has used ratio analysis, F test as well as one way ANOVA test. He concluded that the financial and liquidity performance of the taken companies was average and poor respectively as compared to standard norms of general insurance industrial sector. (popat, 2014)

NIKOLINA SMAJLA (2014) has studied on the topic of measuring financial soundness of insurance companies by using CAMELS model- case of Croatia. The main objective of the study is to measure and analyze the financial performance of Croatian insurance companies through CAMELS model. The suggestion of the study is to pay proper attention on capital adequacy, management soundness and liquidity indicators as they play major role for measuring financial performance. she recommended that insurance companies must be aware regarding their financial performances and soundness and also recommended that to make deeper analysis for both life and general insurance companies further research should be done because the study is only related with one country and the data of one year.(smajla, 2014)

PROF. VALEED A. ANSARI AND MR. WUBSHET FOLA(2014) studied on the topic of financial soundness and performance of life insurance companies in India. The time duration of the study was from 2009 to 2013. They studied that there is a significant differences in CAMEL Framework of private and public sector life insurance companies. They suggested that instead of giving excessive attention on marketing focus should be on risk management of investment portfolios. (FOLA, 2014)

SHOWKET AHMAD DAR AND ISHFAQ AHMAD THAKU (2015) have analyzed and evaluated the financial performance of selected private and public sector in India through CAMEL model. They have selected 6 companies from public sector and 4 companies from private sector. They have used the method of ratio analysis, its mean and standard deviation as well as f-test for the purpose of study. They concluded that in terms of liquidity private sector companies show insignificant difference and public sector companies show significant liquidity. In terms of variability public sector companies show insignificant differences as compared to private sector companies. (THAKY, 2015)

JENITA MONTERIO AND NIJUMON K JOHN (2017) studied on the topic of a study on the financial performance of general insurance companies in India. The objective of the study is to see the impact of incomes and expenses on the operating efficiency of the selected companies. They have used tools and techniques like ratio analysis through CAMEL Framework, mean and standard deviation of it, multiple regression, correlation and descriptive analysis. They concluded that as compared to private sector companies, public sector companies have better management soundness and profitability. (JOHN, 2017)

Objectives Of The Study

- To analyze and evaluate the financial performance of Bajaj Allianz general insurance company limited through CAMEL Framework
- To examine the trend of CAMEL indicators for the time period of 2007-08 to 2016-17
- To make suggestions on the basis of interpretation of data

Research Methodology

Research Design

The present study is based on descriptive research design along with the analysis of financial performance of Bajaj Allianz General Insurance Company Limited. It is also based on accounting techniques of ratio analysis and statistical technique of trend analysis.

Sampling Design

To analyze and evaluate the financial performance of the Bajaj Allianz General Insurance Company Limited the data has been taken from 2007-08 to 2016-17. The study is purely based on secondary data collected from the journals published by IRDA (Insurance Regulatory Authority of India) and annual reports for the said period of the selected company. The analysis is mainly based on ratios. The indicators which represent the financial performance of insurance company are presented through CAMEL framework are as under.

Caramel Framework

1. CAPITAL ADEQUACY RATIO

Capital adequacy ratio shows the capacity of the company to absorb the unexpected losses. We can measure the capital adequacy of the company by share capital to total asset ratio and share capital to mathematical reserves ratio. The formula to calculate the ratios are as under.

<i>Share capital to total assets ratio</i>	$= \text{Share capital} / \text{total assets} * 100$
<i>Share capital to mathematical reserves ratio</i>	$= \text{Share capital} / \text{mathematical reserves} * 100$

Here, mathematical reserves include reserve and surplus and other undistributed profit. Higher the ratios, better the condition of the company to absorb the unforeseen losses.

2. ASSET QUALITY RATIO

Asset quality ratio shows the degree of exposure of equity risk. It can be calculated with the help of equities and total assets. The formula to find out asset quality ratios is given below.

<i>Asset quality ratio</i>	$= \text{Equities} / \text{total assets} * 100$
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Here, Equities means share capital as well as reserves and surplus excluding other undistributed profit. Higher ratio shows better the quality of the assets of the company.

3. REINSURANCE AND ACTUARIAL ISSUES

Under the head of reinsurance and actuarial issues risk retention ratio and mathematical reserves to net premium ratios are included. Risk retention ratio measures insurance risk management policies of insurance companies. While mathematical reserve to net premium ratio indicates the adequacy of mathematical reserve. The formulas to calculate following ratios are as under.

<i>Risk retention ratio</i>	$= \text{Net premium} / \text{gross premium} * 100$
<i>Mathematical reserves to net premium ratio</i>	$= \text{Mathematical reserves} / \text{net premium} * 100$

Higher risk retention ratio shows better capacity of the company to retain risk. Mathematical reserves are required to cover uncertainty of net premium. Higher mathematical reserve to net premium ratio shows sufficient proportion of reserves for risk of uncertainty.

4. MANAGEMENT SOUNDNESS ANALYSIS

The success, ability, efficiency and effectiveness of management can be measured by management soundness ratio. Management soundness ratio can be measured by following formula.

<i>Management soundness ratio</i>	$= \text{Operation expenses} / \text{gross premium} * 100$
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Higher ratio shows better management soundness.

5. EARNINGS/PROFITABILITY RATIO

The ratios which measure earnings or profitability of the company include expense and income ratios.

A. EXPENSE RATIOS

The relationship between expenses and net premium can be expressed by expenses ratio which are as under.

<i>Commission to net premium ratio</i>	$= \text{Commission} / \text{net premium} * 100$
<i>Operating expenses to net premium ratio</i>	$= \text{Operating expenses} / \text{net premium} * 100$
<i>Other expenses to net premium ratio</i>	$= \text{Other expenses} / \text{net premium} * 100$

Expenses should be lower as compared to gross premium are preferable. Thus, lower expense ratios should be preferable.

B. INCOME RATIOS

Income ratio includes return on total investments and return on equities. Return on total investments indicates the proportion of income as compared to total investments while profitability of funds belonging to equity shareholders can be measured by return on equities.

<i>Return on total investments</i>	$= \text{Investment income} / \text{investment assets} * 100$
<i>Return on equity</i>	$= \text{Earnings after tax} / \text{share capital} * 100$

Higher income ratios should be preferable.

6. LIQUIDITY RATIO

The ratio which measures the weakness of loss resulting from sale of fixed asset is called liquidity ratio. The formula to calculate the liquidity ratio is as under.

<i>Liquid ratio</i>	$= \text{Liquid assets} / \text{current liabilities}$
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The ideal measure of liquidity ratio is 1:1.

Data Analysis, Interpretation And Suggestions

The present paper attempts to analyze the financial performance of Bajaj Allianz general insurance company limited for the time period of 2007-08 to 2016-17 through CAMEL Framework (Ratio analysis) and its trend analysis. The results of the analysis are discussed as below.

1. CAPITAL ADEQUACY RATIO

YEAR	SHARE CAPITAL TO TOTAL ASSETS RATIO	SHARE CAPITAL TO MATHEMATICAL RESERVES RATIO
2007-08	19.177%	23.599%
2008-09	16.391%	19.605%
2009-10	13.904%	16.137%
2010-11	13.191%	15.176%
2011-12	11.497%	12.968%
2012-13	8.781%	9.626%
2013-14	6.623%	7.093%
2014-15	4.953%	5.211%
2015-16	3.951%	4.114%
2016-17	3.118%	3.235%
TOTAL	101.588%	116.763%
AVERAGE	10.159%	11.676%
MAX	19.177%	23.599%
MIN	3.118%	3.235%
RANGE	16.059%	20.364%
MEAN DEVIATION	0.046734315	0.058205424

The trend of both ratios is found to be decreasing which means as compared to share capital of the company the proportion of total assets and other undistributed profit under the head of mathematical reserves is constantly increased. The increasing trend of undistributed profit is safe side for the company. The reason behind decreasing trend of the ratios is the stable share capital of the company.

2. ASSET QUALITY RATIO

YEAR	ASSET QUALITY RATIO
2007-08	48.166%
2008-09	41.169%
2009-10	34.921%
2010-11	33.131%
2011-12	28.877%
2012-13	22.054%
2013-14	16.634%
2014-15	12.440%
2015-16	9.924%
2016-17	7.832%
TOTAL	255.148%
AVERAGE	25.515%
MAX	48.166%
MIN	7.832%
RANGE	40.333%
MEAN DEVIATION	0.117377953

As we already observed stable share capital of the company in the capital adequacy ratio for the relevant time period. But along with it reserves and surplus excluding other undistributed profit also remains stable. As total assets are constantly increasing every year, we found negative trend of asset quality ratio which indicates higher degree of equity risk.

3. REINSURANCE AND ACTUARIAL ISSUES

YEAR	RISK RETENTION RATIO	MATHEMATICAL RESERVES TO NET PREMIUM RATIO
2007-08	59.474%	32.999%
2008-09	72.205%	29.728%
2009-10	75.904%	36.253%
2010-11	74.902%	33.789%
2011-12	75.296%	34.348%
2012-13	73.083%	39.157%
2013-14	77.341%	44.490%
2014-15	73.270%	55.201%
2015-16	72.420%	63.440%
2016-17	64.678%	69.015%
TOTAL	718.573%	438.421%
AVERAGE	71.857%	43.842%
MAX	77.341%	69.015%
MIN	59.474%	29.728%
RANGE	17.866%	39.287%
MEAN DEVIATION	0.0391247	0.113556823

The level of risk retention ratio was higher in the year 2008-09 and 2011-12. It was highest in the year 2013-14. After 2015-16 there was decrease in the capacity of risk retention. But overall capacity to bear risk of the company seems to be good. The trend of mathematical reserves to net premium ratio is found to be positive which shows the company has enough mathematical reserves to cover the uncertainty of net premium.

4. MANAGEMENT SOUNDNESS RATIO

YEAR	MANAGEMENT SOUNDNESS RATIO
2007-08	21.827%
2008-09	22.862%
2009-10	22.097%
2010-11	22.513%
2011-12	20.454%
2012-13	19.212%
2013-14	18.516%
2014-15	18.037%
2015-16	19.559%
2016-17	17.836%
TOTAL	202.913%
AVERAGE	20.291%
MAX	22.862%
MIN	17.836%
RANGE	5.027%
MEAN DEVIATION	0.016593095

The trend of management soundness ratio is observed to be fluctuating. But overall the average of the company indicates efficient and effective management.

5. EARNINGS/PROFITABILITY RATIO

A) EXPENSE RATIOS

YEAR	COMMISSION TO NET PREMIUM RATIO	OPERATING EXPENSES TO NET PREMIUM RATIO	OTHER EXPENSES TO NET PREMIUM RATIO
2007-08	-1.325%	36.701%	0.252%
2008-09	1.257%	31.663%	0.147%
2009-10	1.686%	29.111%	0.132%
2010-11	1.878%	30.057%	0.070%
2011-12	3.020%	27.164%	0.058%
2012-13	3.389%	26.288%	0.037%
2013-14	3.871%	23.941%	0.056%
2014-15	1.285%	24.617%	0.214%
2015-16	2.224%	27.008%	0.370%
2016-17	0.722%	27.576%	0.399%
TOTAL	18.006%	284.126%	1.735%
AVERAGE	1.801%	28.413%	0.174%
MAX	3.871%	36.701%	0.399%
IMIN	-1.325%	23.941%	0.037%
RANGE	5.196%	12.759%	0.362%
MEAN DEVIATION	0.010756392	0.027762166	0.001081435

The commission to net premium ratio is found to be negative in the year 2007-08. It was increased till the year 2014-15. After that it fluctuates and was of 0.722% in the year 2016-17. Overall average of this ratio is found to be normal i.e. 1.801% of commission on net premium earned. The overall trend of operating expenses to net premium ratio is found to be fluctuating. The range of operating expenses to net premium ratio is 23.941% to 36.701%. The overall trend of other expenses to net premium ratio is also found to be fluctuating during the study period.

B.) INCOME RATIO

YEAR	RETURN ON TOTAL INVESTMENT RATIO	RETURN ON EQUITY
2007-08	8.110%	95.818%
2008-09	8.144%	86.328%
2009-10	7.285%	109.617%
2010-11	7.576%	39.257%
2011-12	7.777%	112.181%
2012-13	6.738%	267.702%
2013-14	6.835%	371.042%
2014-15	7.089%	510.145%
2015-16	7.766%	511.874%
2016-17	7.787%	660.307%
TOTAL	75.107%	2764.270%
AVERAGE	7.511%	276.427%
MAX	8.144%	660.307%
MIN	6.738%	39.257%
RANGE	1.406%	621.049%
MEAN DEVIATION	0.004191272	1.89531831

From the study period from the year 2006-07 to 2016-17, it is observed that the trend of return on total investment ratio is found to be fluctuating till 2013-14. After that it was constantly increased. While the return on equity shows lot of variations. It reduced heavily in the year 2010-11. But company's management made efforts to increase it and was successful as the ratio increased to 112.181% then onwards it was increased every year and reached to 660.307% in the year 2016-17.

6. LIQUIDITY RATIO

YEAR	LIQUID RATIO
2007-08	0.543
2008-09	0.572
2009-10	0.559
2010-11	0.407
2011-12	0.436
2012-13	0.431
2013-14	0.357
2014-15	0.354
2015-16	0.292
2016-17	0.336
TOTAL	428.656%
AVERAGE	42.866%
MAX	57.228%
MIN	29.156%
RANGE	28.072%
MEAN DEVIATION	0.079663514

The overall trend of liquidity ratio is found to be fluctuating during the study period. The ideal proportion is not met by the company and also it is at its lowest in the year 2015-16 which indicates that the company's current assets are not sufficient to pay its current liabilities.

Suggestions

- The company has to add more share capital and increase the proportion of reserves and surplus to minimize the risk of equities so that it can deal with future uncertainties and unexpected losses.
- The company has to maintain the level of risk retention ratio, mathematical reserves, proportion of other expenses and the level of return on equity. It is also advisable to the company to minimize the level of operating expenses in relation to gross premium and net premium so that efficiency of the management can be increased.
- Management should make efforts to increase the level of its current assets from various sources of finance so that it can pay its current liabilities.

Conclusion

This paper has analyzed the financial performance of Bajaj Allianz General Insurance Company Limited through various ratios fall under the category of CAMEL Framework. The study reveals the good financial position of the company and it can be improved if the company will adopt the above suggestions. The said ratios can be helpful to various stakeholders as it shows the strength of the company's operations and financial performance.

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Factors Affecting Academic Performance of Kendriya Vidyalayas (Central Government Schools): Evidence from India

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Abstract

Education is the foundation of any society. Educational system is instrumental in the development of a child. In India, Kendriya Vidyalayas is playing a pivotal role in improving the educational standards. The objective of this research is to study the relationship between student-teacher ratio, gender ratio and student-computer ratio with academic results. The research design is descriptive in nature. The data is collected through secondary sources. The population of the survey is class 12th results across India. Judgemental sampling technique is used for the selection of data. Correlation and regression is done using SPSS-20 for the analysis purpose. The findings of the study show that there is a correlation between exams performance (results) and teacher-student ratio. The paper also provides evidence that increase in the proportion of girls improves cognitive outcomes.

Keywords: Exams performance, Kendriya Vidyalayas, teacher-student ratio, cognitive.

Introduction

Education is the foundation of any society. The growth of society and ultimately nation depends on the quality of education being imparted to its young ones. The quality of the education system of a country builds the knowledgeable children for the future. Learning process in schools helps in shaping bright students. Education facilitate healthy mind and groom cognition in children. Current educational system is instrumental in the development of a child. Hence play an important role in moulding a nation's future. The school system in India has four levels: lower primary, upper primary, high and higher secondary. There are mainly three streams in school education in India. Two of these are coordinated at the national level, of which one is under the Central Board of Secondary Education (CBSE). A number of "central schools" named Kendriya Vidyalayas have been established for the purpose in all main urban areas in the country, and they follow a common schedule. Schools' academic results have always received considerable attention by parents, students and institutions as for various reasons. There are factors which has an impact on the academic results of the institutions. These factors vary from institution to institution and country to country. Over the years Kendriya Vidyalaya Sangathan is continuously showing excellent academic results. Kendriya Vidyalayas are improving the educational level and are in high demand by the parents for their wards to get admissions. That's a reason the researcher tries to study the factors which affect the academic result of Kendriya Vidyalayas across India. Earlier the researches were being conducted to measure the academic performance. The findings of those studies varied across the various regions. Researchers used academic

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results of the learning institutions to measure the student performance. In general, performance indicators of an institution are the data indices of information by which functional quality of institutions or system may be measured and evaluated. In world education conference in Daker in April 2000, the eighteen core EFA (UNESCO Education for All) indicators were specified. Among these eighteen indicators, indicator eleventh and indicator eighteenth are chosen for this study. Due to the importance of computers in today's education system the third determinant as computer-student ratio is also included for this research.

Research Question

To study the relationship between student-teacher ratio, gender ratio (girls: boys students) and student-computers ratio with academic result.

Hypotheses

H₀₁: There is no correlation between student-teacher ratio and academic result.

H₀₂: There is no correlation between gender ratio and academic result.

H₀₃: There is no correlation between student-computer and academic result.

This research, studies the factors affecting the academic result of class twelfth of Kendriya Vidyalayas. The study will help academic institutions specially schools to design and implement the policies to improve their results and quality of education. Parents may get benefitted, so as to choose the schools for enrolling their wards.

Literature Review

Class factors are important in teaching-learning activities. These factors in one way or the other affect the academic result of that class. When academic performance is considered as an output of the institution's teacher-student ratio, gender ratio (Girls: Boys) and student-computer ratio plays vital role. There is a consensus among various researchers and educationists as far as the importance of these factors are considered.

Student-teacher ratio refers to the number of students enrolled per teacher in an institution of learning. This ratio can be obtained by dividing the total number of students enrolled in a class by the number of teachers available. Ojoawa (1989) and Fabunmi (2000), in their study have pointed out the significance of teacher-student ratio to cognitive learning in the school. According to Cuban (2004), student-teacher ratio has a great impact on the quality of education and academic success of students. Withal (2009) found student-teacher ratio affects the quality of education and hence academic performance of an institution. Every formal education setting involves student-teacher relationship. Idienumah (1978) has reported the positive relationship between teacher-student ratio and performance in examination.

In particular, cognizance is being taken of the argument that the provision of student and teacher (of high quality) ratio should be given top priority and that ultimately results in higher academic performance of the institution (Dave, 2008). Lesser the ratio of student-teacher in a class, quality of education is much better. Best part is that it further improves academic achievement of both the educational institute and students. The literature review states that there is a relationship between student-teacher ratio and academic achievements. Gender ratio (Girls: Boys student ratio) is the ratio of number of girl student to that of boy students. Generally it is observed that girls get higher scores and complete higher secondary school with higher rate compared to boys. Hoxby (2000), who estimates gender and race peer effects in Texas elementary schools and finds that boys and girls have higher test scores when classroom have more female students. Whitmore (2005), on the other hand find mixed

results for the effects of the proportion of female students using gender variation across classrooms. Researchers have shown the proportion of girls in a class has a positive and significant effect on the academic achievement of girls and of boys. Ultimately higher girls: boys ratio improves academic institution's result.

Grace (2001), Fried (2008) and Kraushaar and Novak (2010) attempted to measure the effect of computer usage in an actual classroom environment. It also adds to the existing literature concerning the effects of classroom technology usage on study performance and hence institution's result. The study of indicates that using a computer device reduces final exam scores by roughly one-fourth of a standard deviation. Randomized controlled trial in most similar laboratory-style studies, demonstrates the potentially negative effect of computer usage on students outcomes (Hembrooke and Gay 2003; Sana et al., 2013; Mueller and Oppenheiner, 2014). This suggests that improving the computer-student ratio may affect the academic performance of students' and thereby impacts the school results negatively.

The study of literatures indicates that there is a positive relationship between low student-teacher ratio and better academic result of an institution. As well the positive relationship is observed between high girls-boys ratio and academic performance. The usage of computer has shown a negative relationship with the students' academic results and affects result of the institute. However this is debatable amongst the researchers. Most of these studies were conducted in the western culture.

Research Methodology

Kerlinger (1992) describes research design as the plan and structure of investigation so conceived to obtain answers to research questions. The research design is exploratory cum descriptive in nature. It is therefore to examine the relationship between student-teacher ratio, gender ratio (boys: girls students) and computer-student ratio with academic performance (over all result) of an institution using data of twelfth standard of all regional Kendriya Vidyalaya Schools across India as a case study.

The data is based on the annual report (2015-16) submitted by Kendriya Vidyalayas Sangathan, New Delhi to the Ministry of Education. The researcher has analysed the data of twelfth standard result, across twenty six regional centres and headquarters for this study which incorporates fifty Kendriya Vidyalayas using judgemental sampling. The finding of this research would be analyzed quantitatively using correlation and regression analysis. The appropriate statistical test is conducted to answer the research questions and to test research hypotheses. The importance is given for the generalizability of the results. SPSS-20 is used for the analysis purposes.

Analysis

Table 1.1 reveals the mean and standard deviation of each variable in the data set. It is a useful summary of the data. The mean result of class XII is 95.38% with standard deviation of 1.56. The teacher, student ratio is 5.7944 with standard deviation of 0.4326. The ratio of girls to boys is 69 (which mean for every 100 number of boys there are 69 girls) and its standard deviation is 5.30. Against 100 students there are 5.9 computers available with standard deviation 0.71

Table 1.1: Shows Descriptive Statistics

	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
Class XII Result	95.3826	1.55709	50
Teacher-Student Ratio	5.7944	.43260	50
Girls- Boys Ratio	69.2547	5.30223	50
Computer-Student Ratio	5.9259	.71035	50

Table 1.2: Shows Correlations Matrix between Dependent and Independent Factors

	Result of Class XII	Teacher: Student Ratio	Girls: Boys Ratio	Computer: Student Ratio
Result of Class XII	1	.889***	.701***	.406**
Teacher: Student Ratio	50	1	.634***	.344**
Girls: Boys Ratio	50	50	1	.185 ^{Ns}
Computer: Student Ratio	50	50	50	1

Ns= Not significant ($p > .05$), * $p < .05$, ** $p < .01$, *** $p < .001$

Table 1.2 shows the result of class XII which is significantly correlated with teacher-student ratio, $r = .889$ ($p < .001$) and girls-boys ratio, $r = .701$ ($p < .001$) and also significantly correlated with computer-student ratio, $r = .406$ ($p < .01$). Teacher-student ratio is significantly correlated with girls-boys ratio, $r = .634$ ($p < .001$); and with computer-student ratio, $r = .344$ ($p < .01$). But girls-boys ratio is not significantly correlated with computer-student ratio, $r = .185$ ($p > .05$).

In table 1.3, Model 1 refers to the first stage in the hierarchy when only teacher-student is used as a predictor. Model 2 refers to when teacher-student ratio, computer-student ratio and girls-boys ratio predicts the model. When only teacher-student ratio is used as a predictor, this is the simple correlation between teacher-student ratio and result of class XII (.889). The value of R^2 measures the variability in the outcome. For the first model its value is .791, which means that teacher-student ratio accounts for 79.1% of the variation on the results of class XII. However when girls-boys ratio is included this value increases to .836 or 83.6% of the variance in exam results.

Table 1.3: Shows Regression Model Summary^c

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Change Statistics					Durbin-Watson
					R Square Change	F Change	df1	df2	Sig. Change	
1	.889 ^a	.791	.787	.71912	.791	181.730	1	48	.000	
2	.914 ^b	.836	.825	.65056	.045	6.325	2	46	.004	1.96

a. Predictors: (Constant), Teacher-Student Ratio

b. Predictors: (Constant), Teacher-Student Ratio, Computer-Student Ratio, Girls- Boys Ratio

c. Dependent Variable: XII Result

The change in F for model 1 causes to change from 0 to .791 and this change in the amount of variance explained gives only to an F-ratio 181.73, which is significant with probability

.001. Whereas the change in F value for model 2 causes to change from 0 to .836 and this change in the amount of variance explained give F-ratio 6.325 which is significant at $p < .01$. Durbin-Watson statistic informs whether the assumption of independent error is tenable. Value less than 1 or greater than 3 should definitely raise alarm bells. The closer to 2 the value is, the better, and for these data the value is 1.96, which means that the assumption has met.

ANOVA tests in table 1.4 states whether the model is significantly better at predicting the outcome. For model 1 the F-ratio is 181.730, which is significant ($p < .001$) and there is a little improvement when girls-boys ratio is included it changes the F-ratio to 78.234 which is also significant at $p < .001$. The ANOVA tells the model is significantly fit of the data overall.

Table 1.4: Shows ANOVA^a Statistics

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	93.979	1	93.979	181.730	.000 ^b
	Residual	24.823	48	.517		
	Total	118.801	49			
2	Regression	99.333	3	33.111	78.234	.000 ^c
	Residual	19.469	46	.423		
	Total	118.801	49			

a. Dependent Variable: XII Result

b. Predictors: (Constant), Teacher-Student Ratio

c. Predictors: (Constant), Teacher-Student Ratio, Computer-Student Ratio, Girls- Boys Ratio

Table 1.5 a and table 1.5 b shows the model for both steps in the hierarchy. The b-values tell us about the relationship between class XII exam results and each predictor. The positive values tell that there is a positive relationship between the predictor and the outcome. The three predictors have positive b-values indicating positive relationships. The b-values also tell us to what degree each predictor affects the outcome if the effects of all other predictors are held constant.

Table 1.5 a: Shows Coefficients^a Statistics

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	95.0% Confidence Interval for B	
		B	Std. Error				Beta	Lower Bound
1	(Constant)	76.833	1.380		55.686	.000	74.059	79.607
	Teacher-Student Ratio	3.201	.237	.889	13.481	.000	2.724	3.679
2	(Constant)	74.428	1.420		52.416	.000	71.570	77.287
	Teacher-Student Ratio	2.508	.291	.697	8.619	.000	1.922	3.094
	Girls- Boys Ratio	.070	.023	.237	3.070	.004	.024	.115
	Computer-Student Ratio	.270	.139	.123	1.934	.059	-.011	.551

a. Dependent Variable: XII Result

- Teacher-student ratio (b=2.508): This value indicates that as teacher-student ratio increases by one unit, result of class XII increases by 2.508 units. This interpretation is true only if the effects of girls-boys ratio and computer-student ratios are held constant.
- Girls-boys ratio (b= 0.070): This value indicates that as girls-boys ratio increases by one unit, exam result increases by 0.070 units when teacher-student ratio and computer-student ratios are held constant.
- Computer-student ratio (b=.270): This value indicates that as computer-student ratio increases by one unit, exam result increases by 0.270 units when teacher-student ratio and girls-boys ratios are held constant.

For the model, teacher-student ratio ($t(50) = 8.619, p < .001$) is significant predictor of exam results. Whereas girls-boys ratio ($t(50) = 3.070, p < .05$) is also a significant predictor of exam result of class XII. Whereas computer-student ratio ($t(50) = 1.934, p > .05$) is not significant predictor of exam results.

The standardized beta value provides a better insight into the 'importance' of a predictor in the model. The standardized beta values for teacher-student ratio, girls-boys ratio and computer-student ratios are .697, .237 and .123 respectively, indicating that teacher-student ratio has more importance than girls-boys ratio and computer-student ratio (this concurs with what the magnitude of the t-statistics told us). In this model, the predictor teacher-student ratio and girls-boys ratio has tight confidence intervals indicating that the estimate for the current model is likely to be representative of the true population values. The interval for computer-student ratio is wider indicating that the parameter for this variable is less representative and is insignificant.

Table 1.5 b, the zero-order correlation is the simple Pearson's correlation coefficients. The part correlations represent the relationship between each predictor and the outcome, controlling for the effects that the other variable have on the outcome. Teacher-student ratio predictor would be entered first (because it has the largest zero-order correlation which is .889), then the girls-boys ratio and finally computer-student ratio. The VIF values are all well below 10 and the tolerance statistics all well above 0.2; therefore, we can safely conclude that there is no collinearity within the data. The average VIF is very close to 1 and this confirms that Collinearity is not a problem for this model.

Table 1.5 b: Shows Coefficients^a Statistics

Model	Correlations			Collinearity Statistics	
	Zero-order	Partial	Part	Tolerance	VIF
1	(Constant)				
	Teacher-Student Ratio	.889	.889	1.000	1.000
2	(Constant)				
	Teacher-Student Ratio	.889	.786	.545	1.835
	Girls- Boys Ratio	.701	.412	.597	1.675
	Computer-Student Ratio	.406	.274	.880	1.137

a. Dependent Variable: XII Result

Table 1.6 shows the summary of the excluded variables for the first stage and the second stage. In stepwise regression the predictor with the highest t-statistic should be entered and will continue entering predictors until there are none left with t-statics that have significance

values less than .05. In model 1 and model 2, girls-boys ratio and computer-student ratio is therefore excluded.

Table 1.6: Shows Excluded Variables^a

Model	Beta In t	Sig.	Partial Correlation	Collinearity Statistics				
				Tolerance	VIF	Minimum Tolerance		
1	Girls- Boys Ratio	.230 ^b	2.901	.006	.390	.598	1.671	.598
	Computer-Student Ratio	.114 ^b	1.653	.105	.234	.882	1.134	.882

a. Dependent Variable: XII Result

b. Predictors in the Model: (Constant), Teacher-Student Ratio

In table 1.7 look at for large variance proportion on the same small eigenvalues. The variance proportions vary between 0 and 1. Teacher-student ratio has 84% of variance on dimension 4, girls-boys ratio has 77% variance on dimension 3 and computer-student ratio has 92% variance on dimension 2. These data represent a classic example of no multicollinearity.

Table 1.7: Shows Collinearity Diagnostics^a

Model Dimension	Eigenvalue	Condition Index	Variance Proportions				
			(Constant)	Teacher-Student Ratio	Girls-Boys Ratio	Computer-Student Ratio	
1	1	1.997	1.000	.00	.00		
	2	.003	27.097	1.00	1.00		
2	1	3.985	1.000	.00	.00	.00	.00
	2	.010	20.197	.02	.02	.05	.92
	3	.003	36.435	.98	.14	.77	.02
	4	.002	45.316	.00	.84	.18	.06

a. Dependent Variable: XII Result

Conclusion

The study shows that there is a correlation between exams performance (results) and teacher-student ratio, girls-boys ratio and computer-student ratio. Although it is strongly significant in case of teacher-student ratio and gender ratio, but less significant in case of computer-student ratio. Teacher-student ratio is the most beneficial setting for exams performance. Greater is the teacher-student ratio the better the educational performance. This finding conforms with the findings of Idienuman (1978), Ojoawa (1989), Fabunmi (2000), Cuban (2004), Dave (2008) and Withal (2009). While teacher-student ratios are important, it is hard to say whether there is an ideal ratio. The paper also provides evidence that higher number of girl students improves the academic performance of the class. Increase in the proportion of girls improves cognitive outcomes; this suggests positive effects of girl students. The effect of gender ratio on performance of academic results strengthens the findings of Hoxby (2000) and Whitmore (2005). The study of literatures indicates that usage of computer has shown a negative relationship with the students' academic results and affects result of the institute. However our findings state it otherwise.

Further Research

This study is based on the secondary data of Kendriya Vidyalaya Sangathan. Further in-depth research can be carried out on the following:

- (a) The research can be carried out in a particular region with same culture.
- (b) Other parameters of teacher-student ratio may be further researched.
- (c) Impact of computer-student ratio on academic performance may further be investigated.
- (d) Qualitative research may be carried out studying the effect of gender ratio on academic performance.

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Towards Developing A Time Series Performance Index Of Indian Ferro Metal Industries Using TOPSIS Integrated With Entropic Weights

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Abstract

Performance of Indian manufacturing sector has been a concern since the time its contribution to GDP has started stagnating. Obvious question on its sustainability in development with special emphasis on employment generation have surfaced. While manufacturing has been replaced by services sector as the growth engine for the Indian economy, the importance to analyze performance of key industries within the former category is felt. In this regard the present paper aims to evaluate manufacturing industry performance over 20 years starting 1997 across three time periods with a decadal gap in between them. This study focuses on analyzing metal sector, especially the ferrous segment which meets the requirement of other industries like heavy engineering, infrastructure, electrical, automobile to name a few. The Indian ferrous metal sector is highly fragmented and competitive in nature and holds a key advantage over others with respect to its growing market demand. Using Technique for Order Preference by Similarity to Ideal Solution, a multi criteria decision making approach, the ensuing study considers six industries and eight criteria. Selection of criteria is based on the famous industrial organization theory of structure conduct performance. The TOPSIS method also considers relative weights of criteria which have been calculated from entropic considerations. The results reveal that the performance of castings and forgings industry is the best while steel industry has been a poor performer. The study outcome over the three time periods also helped in developing time series performance index that not only shows performance trend but also creates a platform for predictive analytics.

Keywords: Performance index; ferro metals; MCDM; TOPSIS; Shannon's weight; structure conduct performance

1. Introduction

The importance of industrialization as means of achieving rapid growth has long been recognized as a development strategy in India. The Industrial policies, through various Five Year Plans and Industrial Policy Resolutions, have reflected these objectives. It is indeed difficult to assess the performance of the broad objectives of industrialization over the past six-decades and relate them to the structural changes that have occurred during this period. Industrial scenario represents a broad picture of continuity and change. Indian manufacturing sector has not performed well like that of other large emerging economies. Before liberalization a series of structural distortion like concentrated market structure and stringent regulatory policy did depress the performance of the manufacturing industry. But after liberalization the scenario of Indian Economy has been changed. India has become one of

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the fastest growing economies in the world over the last two decades, which has undoubtedly been aided obviously by the nation's economic reforms. The dynamism of service sector contributed much in the aspect of India's recent growth whereas manufacturing sector's contribution to the GDP has stagnated at 16%, thus raising questions about India's sustainability in development with special emphasis on employment generation (CSO, Govt. of India, 2017). From 2.9% in 1991, the contribution of service sector to India's GDP has increased to 62.5% (CSO, Govt. of India, 2017). In Asian context, the manufacturing industry in China contributes 34% to its GDP and 13.7% to global manufacturing while India's share to world manufacturing is only 1.8%. These statistics clearly indicate that while manufacturing has not been the engine of growth for the Indian economy, it now needs to grow at a much faster rate. In this perspective it is an emergent need to assess performance of Indian manufacturing industry. This study focuses on analyzing metal sector, especially the ferrous segment which meets the requirement of other industries like heavy engineering, infrastructure, electrical, automobile etc and is thus considered important by the researchers. The ferrous metal segment primarily consists of different varieties of iron and steel and other associated industries based on iron and steel. The Indian ferrous metal sector is highly fragmented and competitive in nature and the key advantages of this sector are the growing market demand, presence of related and supported industries, government support and stimulating industry environment (IBEF, 2006).

The aim of the paper is to assess the performance of six industries in the ferrous metal segment of Indian Manufacturing industry. The six industries (also called alternatives) include Pig Iron, Sponge Iron, Steel, Casting & Forgings, Steel Pipes & Tubes and Ferro Alloys and their performance evaluated against eight chosen criteria. This essentially forms a Multi Criteria Decision Making environment (MCDM) and the researchers have used a highly intuitive approach for the same. Of the numerous MCDM methods, Technique for Order Preference by Similarity to Ideal Solution (TOPSIS) has been deployed in this study. Further, the paper follows the theoretical framework of the famous Industrial Organization theory of Structure Conduct Performance while identifying the variables (criteria). The efficiency structure hypothesis of structure Conduct Performance theory states that performance of the firm is positively related to its efficiency. This is because market concentration emerges from competition where firms with low cost structure increase profits by reducing prices and expanding market share. A positive relationship between firm profits and market structure is attributed to the gains made in market share. Early studies by Bain (1951; 1956) hypothesized a positive relationship between industry concentration, barriers to entry and profits. The three aspects of industrial organization viz. Structure, conduct and Performance are interrelated and a full structural model incorporates simultaneous causation between the three aspects. Structural factors may result in high profitability which on the one hand might attract new entry and on the other enable the existing firms to strengthening the barriers to entry for example by increasing advertising expenditure (Apte & Vaidyanathan, 1982)

Following the SCP theory the chosen variables (criteria) of the current study are Herfindahl Hirshman Index (HHI) denotes the industry concentration which is representative of the industry structure. The Conduct variables considered are Sales, Efficiency in use of Total Assets (EFTA), Capital Structure (Debt-Equity Ratio, DER), Efficiency in Using Human Resources (EUHR), Distribution Expenses and Advertising expenses. The logic for consideration of the conduct variables includes those from finance, marketing and human

resources. Performance has been assessed from the relative closeness values from which ranks have been derived for the six industries named as Pig iron, Sponge Iron, Steel, Casting & Forgings, Steel Pipes & Tubes and Ferro Alloys by analyzing the conduct variables.

2. Review of Literature

Structured review of literature was conducted to have an expansive knowledge base on the area of study with special focus on the industrial organization theory and structure conduct performance to be precise. Such review was also aimed at finding the gap area where research would be meaningful and would help in objective formulation. With economic reforms that arguably began in the 1980s, but gained prominence after 1991, many sectors in Indian industry have been progressively deregulated and exposed to foreign competition. It is reasonable to expect that, after deregulation, the market structure would be determined less by government policy and more by normal competitive processes. The study of Athreye and Kapur 2004 explored the determinants of industrial concentration which denotes the structure of any industry before and after liberalization. The investigation shows that one factor that plays a major role is the aggregate size of the market. If the market is large relative to setup costs in an industry, competitive entry tends to create a fragmented market structure. This suggests that the degree of concentration may be inversely related to the size of the market. Sutton (1991, 1998) argued that this traditional size-structure relationship may not hold in industries that are technology intensive or advertising intensive. In such industries larger markets may provide incentives for competitive escalation of advertising and technology expenditures, and the escalated levels of such expenditures may not be compatible with a fragmented market structure. In other words, the market structure in countries like India may be in a transitional process.

Analysis of the causes of differential performance across industries has a long history in the economics of industrial organization. Addressing these issues the typical model (Apte and Vaidyanathan, 1982) explains variations in performance emphasizes three sets of variables concentration, entry barriers and demand growth. The three aspects of industrial organization viz. structure conduct and performance are interrelated and a full structural model should incorporate simultaneous causation between the three modules. Structural factors may result in high profitability which on the one hand might attract new entry and on the other hand enable the exiting firms to invest in strengthening the barriers to entry. The structure performance relation may be non-linear particularly through the interaction of concentration and entry barriers. Weiss (1972) contained examples of models which takes this into account. It has been argued that a relationship between concentration and profitability even if found to be significant might reflect the underlying fact that firm size and profitability are positively correlated.

Sutton (1991) argued that this size-structure relation may break down in industries in which advertising play an important role. Suppose the nature of the industry or product is such that firms have an incentive to increase advertising expenditures to gain market shares. In the long run, the increased level of expenditures is sustainable only if profitability in that industry is high enough. Relatively fragmented market structures are unlikely to sustain such high levels of profitability. In such industries, larger market size may be associated with an escalated expenditure on advertising rather than competition.

The model of Dasgupta and Titman (1998) is based on the argument that a firm can improve short-term profits at the expense of long-term profits by increasing its price today. Raising long-term debt increases a firm's discount rate for future profits, because outstanding debt

raises the cost of new borrowing. The increase in borrowing costs due to existing debt can be traced back to the debt overhang problem of Myers (1977), who argues that debt removes the incentive to invest in positive net present value projects, because when debt repayments are large enough, the benefits from profitable investments go straight to creditors. The higher discount rate decreases the relative importance of long-term profits.

Based on the various studies the researchers have considered 8 criteria in the present study, representing structure (one variable) and conduct (seven variables). The details of the chosen variables are explained in section 3.i. (Variable Selection within the SCP Framework). A time study on Indian industry performance have not been found. With respect to ferrous metal the same is also missing and the same has thus been selected as the core of this research with three prime objectives of (i) evaluating the performance of ferrous metal industries across three time periods of 1997, 2007 and 2017; (ii) estimate the relative importance of the chosen criteria and (iii) develop a time series performance index of the industries included in the study. The rest of the paper is organized as follows. Section 3 deals with the research methodology with detailing of the variables chosen for this study, section 4 elaborates the findings and analysis of the study while section 5 concludes.

3. Research Methodology

The present research is descriptive in nature and is relies on cross sectional study design. Secondary data for a particular time frame is used. Three time frames have been considered which captures data after a gap of a decade. Centre for Monitoring Indian Economy (CMIE) data base have been referred in this study. The data pertains to six industries and eight criteria. The selection of criteria is based on the much acclaimed Structure – Conduct – Performance (SCP) model and these eight criteria represent structure and conduct variables and performance of industries have been evaluated using an MCDM model. The data scan shows no cases missing values. Finally, this data was processed in R software. For evaluating the performance of alternatives i.e. Ferrous Metal Industries, an MCDM approach, TOPSIS, is used, details of which is presented in the section 3.ii. The next section (3.i.) discusses the selection of criteria.

3.i. Variable Selection within SCP Framework

To establish the theoretical framework some important microeconomic concepts has been used. In this research work six industries in the ferrous metal sector have been considered named as Pig iron, Sponge Iron, Steel, Casting & Forgings, Steel Pipes & Tubes and Ferro Alloys. The paper aimed to evaluate the performance of these specific industries in the ferrous metal segment of Indian Manufacturing Industries. In order to assess the relative position on the basis of performance of the industries stated above three specific time frames 1997,2007 and 2017 has been selected with the gap of decade and eight variables or criterions have been chosen. Multi Criteria Decision Methods have been used to assign rank on the basis of relative closeness. A total of eight variables that form the multi criteria environment and help in assessing the performance of the industries in this study are:

- I.** Sales (SALES): Sales represent an important marketing conduct. The value of sales revenue is indicative of the extent of efforts put in by a firm or an organization in extracting revenue from the market. Higher value of sales denotes greater efforts in the market place. This conduct by firms eventually leads to enhancement of market share.
- II.** Herfindahl–Hirschman Index (HHI): The industry concentration measured by relative market share of the firms consisting the specific industry, and this relative

market share is measured by the index called Herfindahl-Hirschman Index. The value of HHI has been collected from the periodical database published by Centre for Monitoring Indian Economy. To measure the industry concentration, Herfindahl-Hirschman Index has been considered taking into account both the number of firms and the inequality of market shares. The HHI provides measure of industrial concentration for any industry and this index is computed as the sum of the squared market shares of all firms in any industry. In a market economy,

$$HHI = S_1^2 + S_2^2 + \dots + S_k^2 = \sum_{i=1}^K S_i^2$$

Here, K is the number of firms in the industry and Si denotes the market share of firm i. HHI is measured by industry and by year. Industrial concentration refers to the extent to which production is concentrated amongst firms in an industry. The number of active firms in the industry provides a simple measure of concentration; the greater is the number of firms the less concentrated (more competitive) is market structure. High concentration is usually indicative of lack of competition, with direct implications for prices, profits and economic welfare. The value of industrial concentration ranges from 0 (denoting extreme fragmentation) to 1 (extreme concentration).

III. Debt Equity Ratio (DER): The debt-equity ratio is a measure of the relative contribution of the creditors and shareholders or owners in the capital employed in business. Simply stated, ratio of the total long term debt and equity capital in the business is called the debt-equity ratio. It can be calculated using a simple formula:

Debt Equity Ratio = Short term debt + Long term debt / Shareholder's Equity

This financial tool gives an idea of how much borrowed capital (debt) can be fulfilled in the event of liquidation using shareholder contributions. It is used for the assessment of financial leverage and soundness of a firm and is typically calculated using previous fiscal year's data.

IV. Size Setup (SSU): It measures the size of the market relative to the setup cost of a typical production unit. The size of the market for any industry is measured by aggregating the sales in that industry, while setup costs are measured as net fixed assets in that industry. Set up costs refer to the cost of setting up a plant of minimum efficient scale. If the size of the market (the average level of demand) is large relative to set up costs, a large number of firms may be able to exist profitably creating a more fragmented structure. On the other hand if the market is small relative to setup costs, the industry would be more concentrated.

V. Efficiency in use of Total Assets (EFTA i.e. Asset to Turnover Ratio): It is an efficiency ratio that measures ability to generate sales from its assets. The asset turnover ratio is calculated by dividing net sales by average total assets. $EFTA = \frac{\text{net sales}}{\text{average total assets}}$

VI. Efficiency in using Human Resource (EUHR): This variable denotes the efficiency of an industry in using its employees. It is measured by total income as percentage of compensation of employees.

Another two variables has been considered to represent the entry barrier aspect for individual industry which are marketing, selling and distribution expenses to sales ratio (DESR), and advertising expenses to sales ratio (ADESR). Industries in the dataset report these two expenses (distribution and advertising) separately.

VII. Distribution Expenses to Sales Ratio (DETSR): These are the expenses related to the selling, promoting and delivering of a product to produce the level of sales. SDSR computed as ratio of total selling distribution expenses to the industry sales.

VIII. Advertising Expenses to Sales Ratio (AETSR): The advertising-to-sales ratio is a measurement of the effectiveness of an advertising campaign calculated by dividing total advertising expenses by sales. The advertising to-sales ratio is designed to show whether the resources a firm spends on an advertising campaign helped to generate new sales.

3.ii. The TOPSIS Approach

The Technique for order performance by similarity to ideal solution (TOPSIS), one of the known classical MCDM methods, was first developed by Hwang and Yoon (1981) and later used by large number of researchers across diverse disciplines (Shidpour et. al., 2013; Pinter & Psunder, 2013; Park, Park, Kwun & Tan, 2011). It is based upon the concept that the chosen alternative should have the shortest distance from the positive ideal solution and farthest distance from the negative ideal solution. This method is highly intuitive, practical and an effective one. In this method (TOPSIS), the performance and the weights of each criterion are given as exact (precise) values. A review of the TOPSIS approach and its algorithm is presented in the below section.

The TOPSIS Algorithm

The best decision alternative may be evaluated using TOPSIS through a series of steps:

Step 1: Normalization of Decision Matrix

$$n_{ij} = \frac{x_{ij}}{\sqrt{\sum_{j=1}^m x_{ij}^2}}; j = 1, 2, \dots, m \text{ \& } i = 1, 2, \dots, n$$

Step 2: Weighted normalized decision matrix. The weighted normalized values are calculated as

$$v_{ij} = w_i n_{ij}, j = 1, 2, \dots, m; i = 1, 2, \dots, n \text{ \& }$$

$$w_i = \text{weight of the } i^{\text{th}} \text{ attribute or criterion and } \sum_{i=1}^n w_i = 1$$

In an MCDM environment, weights of criteria reflect their relative importance in the overall decision making process. In realistic sense, one should not assume equal importance of each criterion (Chen, Tzeng, & Ding, 2003). Of the two approaches to calculating weights, the subjective and objective methods, the researchers chose an objective method that uses mathematical model to determine weights without any consideration of the decision maker's preferences, which is expected to be biased. Many methods have been proposed by researchers, but the entropic consideration (Shannon & Weaver, 1947) is well suited to an MCDM environment. Shannon entropy is a measure of uncertainty in information formulated in terms of probability theory. The stepwise computation of Shannon's entropy is shown next.

Step i. Normalization of the data matrix as $p_{ij} = \frac{x_{ij}}{\sum_{j=1}^m x_{ij}}, j = 1, 2, \dots, m \text{ \& } i = 1, 2, \dots, n$

Raw data normalizing is done to rationalize the disparate units of measurement of criteria.

Step ii. Entropy E_i is calculated as $E_i = -h_0 \sum_{j=1}^m p_{ij} \cdot \ln p_{ij}$

$$\text{i.e. } E_i = -h_0 \sum_{j=1}^m \frac{x_{ij}}{\sum_{j=1}^m x_{ij}} \ln \frac{x_{ij}}{\sum_{j=1}^m x_{ij}}, i = 1, 2, \dots, n \text{ and}$$

h_0 is the entropy constant and is defined as $h_0 = (\ln m)^{-1}$

Step iii. Defining d_i as $d_i = 1 - E_i$ and

Step iv. Defining Shannon's Entropy Weight W_i as $W_i = \frac{d_i}{\sum_{i=1}^n d_i}$

Step 3: Determination of Positive and Negative Ideal solution

$$A^+ = \{v_1^+, \dots, v_n^+\} = \left\{ \left(\max_j v_{ij} \mid i \in I \right), \left(\min_j v_{ij} \mid i \in J \right) \right\}$$

$$A^- = \{v_1^-, \dots, v_n^-\} = \left\{ \left(\min_j v_{ij} \mid i \in I \right), \left(\max_j v_{ij} \mid i \in J \right) \right\}$$

where I is associated with the benefit criteria, and J is associated with the loss criteria.

Step 4: Calculation of separation measures, using the n-dimensional Euclidean distance.

The separation of each alternative from the positive and negative ideal solutions are given by

$$d_j^+ = \left\{ \sum_{i=1}^n (v_{ij} - v_i^+)^2 \right\}^{\frac{1}{2}}, j = 1, \dots, m \text{ and } d_j^- = \left\{ \sum_{i=1}^n (v_{ij} - v_i^-)^2 \right\}^{\frac{1}{2}}, j = 1, \dots, m$$

Step 5: Calculation of Relative Closeness (Index) to Ideal Solution. The relative closeness of the alternative A_j with respect to A^+ is defined as

$$R_j = \frac{d_j^-}{(d_j^+ + d_j^-)}, j = 1, \dots, m$$

Since $d_j^- \geq 0$ and $d_j^+ \geq 0$, then clearly, $R_j \in [0, 1]$

Step 6: Ranking the preference order. For ranking using relative closeness (index) value, the larger the value, better is the alternative as it is relatively closer to the ideal solution. Thus, the alternatives are ranked in decreasing order.

3. Findings and Analysis

The operationalization of the input data is as per the steps mentioned in TOPSIS algorithm. The input data is the decision matrix, also called performance matrix, as shown in Table 1. There are three decision matrices each for the years 1997, 2007 and 2017. The second operational step involves normalization of decision matrix and is shown in Table 2.

Table 1. Decision/ Performance Matrix

1997	HHI	SALES	AETSR	DETSR	DER	SSU	EUHR	EFTA
PIR	0.10	6869.20	0.00	0.01	3.04	1.04	31.54	0.27
SIR	0.11	4170.60	0.00	0.02	18.97	1.24	14.56	0.50
STL	0.13	417850.30	0.01	2.52	1.98	0.55	11.05	0.54
CNF	0.06	21218.10	0.00	0.05	2.82	0.50	9.81	0.66
SPNT	0.04	27995.60	0.00	0.09	2.21	0.58	26.39	0.85
FEAL	0.08	13297.60	0.00	0.04	1.78	0.42	12.70	0.83
2007								
PIR	0.03	63447.10	0.00	0.02	2.92	0.75	43.27	0.84
SIR	0.01	52175.00	0.00	0.01	4.26	0.50	40.17	0.81
STL	0.06	1951810.40	0.01	0.64	1.11	0.35	15.25	0.97
CNF	0.05	107824.40	0.00	0.03	1.03	0.24	17.74	1.12
SPNT	0.06	293975.60	0.00	0.15	1.03	0.18	41.81	1.33
FEAL	0.03	67256.00	0.00	0.02	0.64	0.23	22.06	1.14
2017								
PIR	0.15	24268.1	0.0053	0.0148	3.96	0.63	19.41	0.88
SIR	0.08	36991.2	0.0002	0.0133	4.89	1.17	22.34	0.43
STL	0.05	3253030.9	0.0432	4.157	2.17	1.14	14.84	0.51
CNF	0.12	90518	0.0008	0.0599	2.55	1.36	14.51	0.4
SPNT	0.05	254963.5	0.0055	0.3604	0.65	0.57	19.52	0.74
FEAL	0.04	84941.1	0.0009	0.0806	1.51	0.45	17.35	0.76

Source: Author's Computation

Table 2. Normalized Decision Matrix

1997	HHI	SALES	AETSR	DETSR	DER	SSU	EUHR	EFTA
PIR	0.445	0.016	0.131	0.005	0.154	0.542	0.660	0.172
SIR	0.489	0.010	0.000	0.007	0.962	0.646	0.305	0.319
STL	0.578	0.996	0.919	0.999	0.100	0.287	0.231	0.344
CNF	0.267	0.051	0.263	0.019	0.143	0.260	0.205	0.421
SPNT	0.178	0.067	0.263	0.036	0.112	0.302	0.552	0.542
FEAL	0.356	0.032	0.000	0.017	0.090	0.219	0.266	0.529
2007								
PIR	0.279	0.032	0.007	0.036	0.529	0.722	0.547	0.326
SIR	0.093	0.026	0.007	0.015	0.772	0.482	0.507	0.315
STL	0.557	0.986	0.997	0.972	0.201	0.337	0.193	0.377
CNF	0.464	0.054	0.033	0.042	0.187	0.231	0.224	0.435
SPNT	0.557	0.149	0.074	0.223	0.187	0.173	0.528	0.517
FEAL	0.279	0.034	0.013	0.036	0.116	0.222	0.279	0.443
2017								
PIR	0.671	0.007	0.121	0.004	0.541	0.270	0.435	0.556
SIR	0.358	0.011	0.005	0.003	0.668	0.502	0.501	0.272
STL	0.224	0.996	0.984	0.996	0.297	0.489	0.333	0.322
CNF	0.537	0.028	0.018	0.014	0.349	0.583	0.325	0.253
SPNT	0.224	0.078	0.125	0.086	0.089	0.244	0.438	0.468
FEAL	0.179	0.026	0.021	0.019	0.206	0.193	0.389	0.480

Source: Author's Computation

In the third stage, the relative importance of criteria is calculated (Table 3) before evaluating the normalized weighted decision matrix (NWDM), as depicted in Table 4. Using NWDM, the relative closeness is calculated for all the three years. Finally, the TOPSIS rank is evaluated for the six industries in the ferrous metal segment and the same derived for three years. The ranking of these industries for 1997, 2007 and 2017 indicates a trend of their performance over a period of 20 years. It is observed that in 1997, FEAL has the best performance, while in 2007 and 2017, CNF's performance is the finest. CNF has improved its performance from third position in 1997 to first position in 2007 and has retained it even in 2017. FEAL has slipped from first to second in 2007 but has retained this spot in 2017 also. STL industry has shown the worst performance in all the three years. It is found to occupy the sixth position in all these three years. Both PIR and SIR have moderate to low performance in the time frame considered. However, SIR has improved from fifth position both in 1997 and 2007 to the third place in 2017 while PIR held fourth position both in 1997 and 2007 but dropped to fifth place in 2017. The performance of SPNT has been sliding every year starting 1997 when it was at second spot, then slipped to third and fourth spot in 2007 and 2017 respectively.

Table 3. Shannon's Entropy Weights

YEAR	HHI	SALES	AETSR	DETSR	DER	SSU	EUHR	EFTA
1997	0.017	0.295	0.134	0.360	0.131	0.021	0.026	0.015
2007	0.032	0.253	0.347	0.245	0.062	0.035	0.022	0.004
2017	0.030	0.311	0.251	0.335	0.039	0.020	0.003	0.011

Source: Author's Computation

Table 4. Weighted Normalized Decision Matrix

1997	HHI	SALES	AETSR	DETSR	DER	SSU	EUHR	EFTA
PIR	0.007	0.005	0.009	0.001	0.020	0.012	0.017	0.003
SIR	0.008	0.003	0.009	0.003	0.126	0.014	0.008	0.005
STL	0.010	0.294	0.126	0.360	0.013	0.006	0.006	0.005
CNF	0.004	0.015	0.030	0.007	0.019	0.006	0.005	0.006
SPNT	0.003	0.020	0.033	0.013	0.015	0.006	0.014	0.008
FEAL	0.006	0.009	0.009	0.006	0.012	0.005	0.007	0.008
2007								
PIR	0.009	0.008	0.002	0.009	0.033	0.025	0.012	0.001
SIR	0.003	0.007	0.002	0.004	0.048	0.017	0.011	0.001
STL	0.018	0.250	0.346	0.238	0.013	0.012	0.004	0.002
CNF	0.015	0.014	0.012	0.010	0.012	0.008	0.005	0.002
SPNT	0.018	0.038	0.026	0.055	0.012	0.006	0.012	0.002
FEAL	0.009	0.009	0.005	0.009	0.007	0.008	0.006	0.002
2017								
PIR	0.022	0.002	0.042	0.001	0.034	0.009	0.010	0.002
SIR	0.012	0.003	0.002	0.001	0.042	0.017	0.011	0.001
STL	0.007	0.252	0.342	0.244	0.019	0.017	0.007	0.001
CNF	0.017	0.007	0.006	0.004	0.022	0.020	0.007	0.001
SPNT	0.007	0.020	0.043	0.021	0.006	0.008	0.010	0.002
FEAL	0.006	0.007	0.007	0.005	0.013	0.007	0.009	0.002

Source: Author's Computation

Table 5. Relative Closeness

YEAR	PIR	SIR	STL	CNF	SPNT	FEAL
1997	0.575	0.546	0.453	0.577	0.578	0.578
2007	0.629	0.627	0.372	0.632	0.630	0.631
2017	0.602	0.624	0.375	0.627	0.612	0.626

Source: Author's Computation

Table 6. TOPSIS Rank

YEAR	PIR	SIR	STL	CNF	SPNT	FEAL
1997	4	5	6	3	2	1
2007	4	5	6	1	3	2
2017	5	3	6	1	4	2

Source: Author's Computation

4. Conclusion

The goal of the present study is to evaluate the performance of six ferrous metal industries across three time periods of 1997, 2007 and 2017; thereby developing a time series performance index of the industries included in the study. Further, it was also aimed to estimate the relative importance of the chosen criteria While performance analysis was based on TOPSIS, an intuitive MCDM approach, the relative importance of criteria were estimated from entropic considerations of Shannon. It is indeed a huge task to assess the performance of specific six industries manufacturing industries over the broad time period of 20 years from 1997-2017 taking decadal gap and conclude on the structural changes with the association of eight variables that led to affect performance.

From this study it may be concluded that though the relative importance of criteria have changed across three different time periods, the average weights in the 20 year time frame suggests distribution expense to sales ratio, sales and advertising expense to sales ratio are

the three most important criteria in diminishing order of importance. These three account for over 84% of the criteria importance. Also, casting and forging industry has been determined as the best performing industry while steel industry is at the bottom among the six industries studies.

The study was conducted with selection of six manufacturing industries in the ferrous metal segment. If similar industries be clubbed in different segments as well as sectors, emphasizing on the broader classification according to the Planning Commission (NITI Aayog), Government of India, in manufacturing industries the output would give a sharper and conclusive deduction about the policy framing of the Indian government. Future researches may focus on this aspect. Furthermore the number of criteria or variables included in the present study is eight following the theoretical domain of SCP paradigm. There is a scope to include further criteria covering other domains of other theories of business also. The scope mentioned is just an indication; however researcher's prerogative is of prime importance.

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A Study of Pressure in employees of Insurance Sector in Jalandhar, Punjab

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Abstract

The inspiration driving this paper is to consider pressure in Insurance sectors in Jalandhar. The investigation is centered on to take a gander at the purposes behind pressure, signs of pressure and intercessions that can be associated by organization and agents of Insurance sectors in Jalandhar, India remembering the true objective to regulate push sufficiently in affiliations. The essential convergence of this examination is to perceive the dimension of repeat of the movement stressors for Insurance sector delegates and pursue out the alarming component that impacts for the most part individuals. The paper also hurls light onto the regions examined where changes can be made by the agents, boss, and the Human Resources (HR) division to diminish the uneasiness factors by revealing an improvement. The data was assembled by examining Insurance sector delegates of open and private Insurance sectors in Punjab, India through a sorted out review. The example measure was 100. Both basic and assistant wellsprings of data were comprehensively used for analyzing this examination.

Introduction

Stress is reliably started as a medicinal term or a psychological wonder in view of its potential outcomes in decaying the success state of a man and the container that triggers the battle reaction autonomously. Current time is basically the season of uneasiness and stress which itself will be affected by number of stressors. Word related stress in the work space can impact individuals to fear strolling around the workplace each morning and sometime later impacts them to stress over their occupations around evening time. It has wound up being more globalized and will in general effect all bosses paying little regard to the occupation profile or class, the guideline separate being the power levels. Pressure is depicted as a circumstance which drives a man to get diverted its common working because of development in mental or physiological condition. Right when staff is sad, they are less gainful, not so much powerful but rather progressively slanted to misuse work hours or at last quit. Stress impacts soul, yet rather an affiliation's essential concern. The basic area of this review is pressure accomplished to an individual in context of the corporate culture in the present plausibility. As delighting and bewildering it might appear, this bundle runs with explicit cons for a large portion of the general open. Juggling between their work and life to strike that modify, managing the dimensions of acclaim of the market, surrendering to the opposition at working environment to display their regard et al. With this and different more battles which the corporate culture offers in this way to what it offers, makes it difficult to satisfy the objective for a couple.

Stress has been of surprising stress to the association, specialists, and unmistakable assistants of affiliations. Stress specialists concur that tension is a troublesome issue in different affiliations. The expense of pressure is high in different affiliations. At an individual dimension, stress may impel to broadened depressions and mortality.

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Stress is depicted as the impression of a botch between ecological requesting stressors and individual abilities to satisfy these sales. Chang and Lu (2007) inferred that the reasons behind pressure join saw loss of business, and security, sitting for drawn out reaches out of time or truly troublesome work, nonattendance of thriving, multifaceted structure of gruffness and nonappearance of poise in the occupation. Furthermore, stress is acknowledged by nonappearance of advantages and gear; work date-books, for example, working late moves or extra minutes and real atmosphere are considered as supporters to delegates extend. Stress consistently demonstrates high dissatisfaction among the representatives, work flexibility, burnout, and poor work execution and less powerful social relations at work. It is battled that intercessions like perceiving or picking the indications of stress, seeing the conceivable clarifications behind the signs and making conceivable proposed answers for each sign are required. These measures enable people to create adjusting limits and make methodologies to make individualized nervousness association arranges that join taking out the wellsprings of stress. In addition, expanding singular adjusting limits is another intervention which will be utilized by the association to keep push. Stress is a general issue in current life which can be depicted as unsavory or negative perception and it infers work pressure and occupation extend. Today Occupational stress has become vital matter of concern for the organizations as it can be seen in varying degrees and at different levels. Minimum level of pressure results in occupational stress which occurs due to monotony in the job. Occupational stress is the resultant of maximum pressure on a person when the mind and body are at uncomfortable and unstable state and causes various physical and psychological disorders in the employees that may lead to employee anxiety, frustration and dissatisfaction. Acute stress is the condition of stress that comes at once with there is sudden change in routine work. It is intense but of short duration. Chronic stress is the condition of stress which results due to some continuous and regular change of routine work. It has long term effect on the person. Stress is not one shot activity rather it builds up over a passage of time. It is a silent-killer Occupation stress occurs when there is mismatch between the employee's expectations and jobs demands and later on it results into malfunctioning. It influences the achievement of organizational and individual goals. It affects the healthiness and effectiveness of the organisation. Unhealthy work environment and poor quality of work life affects the productivity and performance of employees resulting in low organizational effectiveness. The survival of low performing organizations becomes difficult in the competitive market. The occupational stress can be due to several sets of factors that become the potential sources of stress. There are extra-organizational environmental factors as economic, political and technological uncertainties which affect the organization structure and induce employee stress. Some Intra organizational factors of the organization as task demands, Physical work layout, working conditions, role demand, role conflicts, role ambiguity role overload interpersonal demands, organization climate, and culture, leadership, and structure and life stage also contributes to occupational stress. Individual factors as personality, family marital difficulties, locus of control, economic problem self-efficacy also adds to employee stress. Stress has become globalized in this global village called world. Now days it is experienced in every part of the world- all the nations' people, organizations ,professions feel the heat of stress in one or another way and Insurance sectoring sector is not an exception to it. The changing rules, procedures, polices technological advancement, liberalization, privatization, restructuring downsizing in the Insurance sectoring sector has given birth to occupational stress, resulting into low

motivation, low morale, low sense of belongingness, low job commitment and job involvement. Stress influences the achievement of organizational and individual goals. It affects the healthiness and effectiveness of the organization. Unhealthy work environment and poor Quality of work life affects the productivity and performance of employees resulting in low organizational effectiveness which leads to decrease in economic growth. The survival of low performing organizations has become difficult in the competitive market. The organizations should address the stress related problems and should manage it effectively and efficiently. As an individual feels the work stretch, it will make them delicate physiologically, behaviorally and mentally. Consequently, stress driving issues as despair and burnout, musculoskeletal messes, cardiovascular diseases, and gastrointestinal are the essential issues.

Literature Review

Hans Selye (1956), the pioneer of pressure utilized this term in the wake of finishing his medicinal preparing at college of Montreal in 1920. He gave tolerating contentions that Stress impacts health. G. S. Das (1982) called attention to that hierarchical atmosphere and power is factors in charge of administrative pressure. He examined that Indian open division supervisors can manage higher level of job ambiguity. Rajinder et al (1993) called attention to those components as entomb job remove, job disengagement job over-burden are fundamental driver of pressure in private part while in open area, job disintegration, individual and asset deficiency are reasons for pressure. Job disintegration is basic reason in both the segments so assignment of power, obligation and participative basic leadership process expands the representative association and commitment. Borown et al (1998) pointed that fulfilled workers encounters similar less pressure after finishing of work when contrasted with less fulfilled workers whose face progressively distressing after consummation of their job. Das et al (2003) concluded that the director who are offered opportunity to take every necessary step in their own specific manner feel low dimension of pressure when contrasted with administrators who work under absolutist system. Abhilasha Singh (2005) announced that so as to have high caliber of work life authoritative pressure ought to be managed help of analysts, instructor and specialists Richardson (2008) uncovered that pressure techniques ought to be embraced to control hierarchical pressure. He pointed that distinctive unwinding methods ought to be embraced to oversee pressure. Ahsan et al (2009) considered diverse elements of occupation pressure too weight entomb individual relationship cooperation of the executives and job uncertainty and reasoned that there is negative connection between employment stress and fulfillment. AP Singh et al (2009) explored that word related pressure decides the representative employment fulfillment and his profitability. He distinguished that pressure can be valuable just as ruinous. Utilitarian pressure is testing and adds to development and dangerous pressure prompts awkward and insecure state. Pratibha Garg (2010) in her investigation pointed that in private Insurance sectors useless pressure has negative effect on the nature of work life of representative. Stress the executives strategies ought to be received to stay away from burnout in the organizations. Juliet Gladies et al (2011) examined that hierarchical workplace influences the representative pressure of females in IT industry. Stress the executives ought to be made viable to improve worker morale. Dr. Krishna. A. Goyal and Vijay Joshi (2012) reasoned that financial industry faces different difficulties as hazard the board, client maintenance, worldwide challenge, and innovative progression, human social, moral and mental viewpoint. It was proposed that so as to address the difficulties the Indian financial

industry must pick imaginative items, decline the expense of administrations offered, grow their branches and should utilize their image value as their quality. Khurram Zaffar Awan et al (2012) explored that representatives of private segment Insurance sectors are progressively distressing as contrast with open division workers however there is distinction of factors which influence private and open Insurance sector representatives. Dr. Beulah Viji Christiana et al (2013) presumed that instructive foundation and professional training of both open and private area Insurance sector workers have vital effect on their dimensions of pressure. Supervisors ought to recognize the wellspring of job pressure to oversee it viably which prompts high representative productivity. Rashmi Ghamawala et al (2014) researched that there is extremely less challenge in open division as contrast with private segment Insurance sector as there is more challenge, stress, mindful culture and development in private Insurance sector which eventually prompts more noteworthy worker commitment. The private Insurance sector workers are progressively dedicated for their execution and they have faith in criticism framework as contrast with open part Insurance sectors. Private segment workers are more exposed to pressure as contrast with open division representatives.

Research Methodology

Research system is an exact method in overseeing explanation of perceiving an investigation issue, social event of substances or data, separating this data and arriving at on a particular resolution either in sort of game plans towards the issue concerned or certain theories for some theoretical enumerating. It similarly contains different choice methodologies and interrelated and a significant part of the time relating frameworks and practices. Since, there are various pieces of research framework; the line of action must be investigated a combination of choices. The decision of a suitable technique can be arrived at through the assessment of targets and examination of various alternatives.

Research Design

Research plan of the present examination is exploratory in nature. The looking at size for this investigation is of 100 respondents through helpful testing from various Insurance sectors in Jalandhar. The region of research is the work environment of Insurance sectors who have experienced pressure in their activity. Rate Analysis technique is utilized to lead the exploration investigation and for translating the outcomes. Thusly, this examination will endeavor to find the dimension of pressure, and mediations that can be associated by organization and delegates of Insurance sectors in Jalandhar.

Discoveries Of The Study

In the midst of the examination that is gathered that 97% of Insurance sector workers were over constrained with the undertaking. The vast majority of the representatives feel that they question their effectiveness at work. 50% of workers were worried due to non – satisfaction of the objectives given to them. 30% of representatives are worried because of the residential issues. The local issues and business related weight both go about as double stressor on the worker. Relational Conflict among the Insurance sector representatives is another factor of pressure as 60% of workers face disappointment in their relational relations. 50% of Insurance sector workers are of the view that the viable pressure adapting plans, for example, yoga, contemplation, unwinding procedures are given by the Insurance sector specialists to relieve the pressure. 45% of the representatives concur that they need to prioritize their activity work as opposed to their own work. In end it is discovered that pressure capacities as an electric globule. On the off chance that legitimately edified up, at that point it spreads even

light all over the place however in the event that it is given high intensity of power, at that point it burns. Similarly stress ought to be as Eustress and not Burnout.

Analysis of Factors causing pressure

Factors No.	FACTORS	AGREE	NOT AGREE	NO COMMENTS
F1	Does your exertion at working environment fulfill you?	90%	7%	3%
F2	Do you doubt your efficiency at work?	90%	10%	10%
F3	Do you work overtime?	95%	3%	2%
F4	Does the criticism of your associates influence you?	30%	65%	5%
F5	Does your work atmosphere results in stress?	75%	20%	5%
F6	Are you over-burdening in your job?	60%	30%	10%
F7	Do you share about work issues with your precious ones?	85%	5%	10%
F8	Does non- satisfaction of objectives results in stress	50%	40%	10%
F9	Does your working environment stress influence you rationally and physically?	70%	25%	5%
F10	Do your Prioritize and calendar your tasks?	90%	5%	5%
F11	Do you face bury individual clash at job?	60%	30%	10%
F12	Do you have appropriate complaint redressed mechanism?	80%	8%	12%
F13	Do your specialists offer viable adapting strategies?	50%	30%	20%
F14	Do your local issues and issues cause stress?	30%	65%	5%
F15	Do you spoil yourself at clubs, spas and cinemas?	75%	20%	5%
F16	Do you priotize your activity work or individual work.	45%	30%	25%

Constraints And Suggestions

In spite of the fact that the endeavors were made to direct confinement free investigation yet at the same time because of certain components it is colorized with couple of impediments. Numerous angles in the investigation are unexplored because of brief time term and on the grounds that the examination was led not on expansive scale but rather just on 100 respondents .Convenient Sampling technique was utilized for information accumulation so the subjectivity of the respondent has shaded the outcomes which can't be summed up. It is proposed that Insurance sector specialists should take legitimate measures to assist the

representatives with relieving their pressure. Insurance sector representatives should accept pressure as positive and ought to abstain from spreading it inside. Stress adapting techniques as yoga, contemplation mindfulness classes, great nature of work life and legitimate association atmosphere builds worker productivity and viability.

Conclusion

This investigation has recognized the dimension of repeat of the action stressors for Insurance sector delegates and pursues out the disturbing component that impacts for the most part laborers. Thusly, chiefs in different Insurance sectors must consider various interventions to coordinate word related tension. The standard methodology of organizing specialists is missing to manage push. Therefore, there is a need for viewpoint change in managing word related stress with a specific genuine goal to compel its effect on the delegates' lives. The revelations demonstrated that pressure is overwhelmingly made by the expansion of work stack, instability about the future, poor correspondence in Insurance sectors, lacking assets and clashes. The disclosures moreover uncovered that delegates in Insurance sectors felt stressed with business related issues which clearly plots the specialists who are centered around because of work and who feel concentrated on because of particular issues. The revelations in like way uncover that the results related with pressure antagonistically sway the connection, particularly in lessening sufficiency in association activities, expanding laborer turnover, and the usage of thriving expenses of delegates, low inspiration and incident. The review disclosures in like way demanded that pressure costs are high and its effect on laborers can't be ignored. Different leveled inability to control pressure may separate the authoritative gainfulness through case, repulsiveness and mortality. Regardless, chiefs in different Insurance sectors remain to get in the event that they can see the indications of word related stress among the laborers at their starting driving force. This will help in checking the stress before its effects make issues on an individual agent. The Insurance sectors can utilize the associations of masters like instructors to see the side effects of stress in specialists well early. The mediations, which are reliably utilized as a bit of numerous Insurance sectors, have been named basic, assistant and tertiary. Basic interventions are the best in coordinating pressure toward the begin create. On the off chance that these fundamental intercessions are seen as imperative to a specific degree, pressure in Insurance sectors will be lessened.

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A Survey on Security in Internet of Things (IoT) Layers

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Abstract: In the past decade, main focus of research has been IoT, where physical objects are to be connected using various existing wireless technologies. The IoT can connect anyone with anything at anywhere in anytime. IoT has four layers architecture and at each layer some security principles should be applied in order to secure from unauthorized attacks and to provide accurate data. The future of IoT framework can only be ensured if the security associated with it is confirmed. This paper presents an overview of security issues at each layer of architecture, security measures and protocols and well defined security architecture.

Keyword: Internet of Things (IoT); Security; Confidentiality; Threats

Introduction: Internet of Things means a system of interconnected devices. By using IoT, technological revolution will come. It has changed the meaning of current internet to much more advanced computing network in which all the physical objects can be uniquely identified and communicate to other objects. By using this technology, everything around us like cars, home, traffic signals, roads etc will collect data accordingly to their use with the help of various existing technologies and autonomously data will flow to the concerned devices and then concerned devices will action automatically. So the main purpose of IoT is to transform our living style by developing ambient intelligent devices which will perform our daily task and chores automatically. It will bring huge changes to future society and future business infrastructure. But IoT will be failed with security issues because of the IoT has updated the internet to mobile network and sensor network and soon everything is connected to other though internet. That's why security problems will arise. Devices have a great impact on our living, so security protocols can limit the threats and attention to confidentiality, reliability, privacy, integrity of data and authenticity should be paid. In this paper, architecture and several issues related to IoTs has been defined.

IoT's General Architecture: Normally, IoT has four major layers. Fig. 1 shows the layer architecture of it.

Fig. 1 Architecture of IoT

Perception layer: It is also known as "Sensor" layer. This layer consist sensors like RFID, Barcodes. The idea of this layer is to collect all information from the physical objects and identify the real world with the help of object properties, physical equipment like RFID

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reader, Sensor, GPS etc. This layer captures the physical world using sensor and represents in the digital world.

Network Layer: This network layer provides data routing and reliable transmission of information to different IoT hubs and devices over the internet through perceptual layer. To exchange information between devices, internet, mobile network infrastructure and communication protocol are required.

Processing Layer: It is the middle layer between application layer upward and network layer downward. In this layer, all types of intelligent computing power is to be organized using network grid and cloud computing.

Application layer : It is user level layer. User can access IoT through the direct interaction by application layer. This layer provides authenticity, integrity and confidentiality of data. This layer guarantees services to user according to their requirements.

Security Criteria: The major security criteria of IoT is to ensure security by identify authentication mechanisms and confidentiality, availability and integrity of the data .A beach in the system could cause a serious problem.

Confidentiality: It refers data is secure and protected from being accessed by unauthorized users. User can be human, machine etc. In other words, it provides confidence to user that sensitive information is secured and prevented unauthorized party to acces the data. A failure to maintain confidentiality means that unauthorized party managed to get confidetal data, through intentionally or by accidentelly. Such a failure is called breach. So different security mechanism like data encryption (plaintext is converted into ciphertext so that unauthorized parties can not be able to acces the data). Two- step verification (in it two authentication methods are performed one after the other to verify user) Biometric verification etc. are necessary to provide confidentiality to the data.

Authentication: Each object in the IoT must recognize a user's identity. In it, incoming request comparision is carried out in the database of the authorized user's information. It ensures that the individual is who. It does not detetmine the task, the individual can do but it identifies and verifies who the pereson or system is.

Integrity: During transmitting the data between different devices, data could be altered by the cyber criminals or could be affected intentionally or unintentionally interference or different other factors that are beyond the control of humans. So it is very important to provide accurate data and ensure that data is not tempered during transmission. Data is coming from the right sender and not altered data is transmitted. This thing and data traffic is managed by the firewalls and other protocols like TCP/IP, checksum, cyclic redundancy check, odd parity bits are some mechanism to ensure accuracy of data. These mechanisms detect error in data and using other mechanism like hamming code, correct the data.

Data Availability: Data should be available to its users, whenever they required. Data availability means information should be immediate accessible to authorized user in all conditions whether normal or disastrous. Denial-of-Service (DoS) attack denies the availability of data to user. So firewalls should be in the system which protects the system from the attack. Not only information but also devices and services should be available at the back end of the services.

Security Issues at Each Layer of IoTs: Some security threats and attacks in each architectural layer are susceptible. Attack can be passive or active attack. In active attack, service is stopped directly. In passive attack, network information is monitored without hindering its services. In this section, analysis of the security issues at each layer is presented.

Perception layer: Hardware attacks are most common in this layer. Perception layer consists RFIDs, WSN, so IoTs storage capacity, computation power and consumption power are so much limited that any type of attack and threat can damage or influence them and due to lack of power, authentication mechanism tags can be accessed by any unauthorized party. Tag's data can access by any cybercriminal who can create clone of the tag in the way that user cannot make difference between original and relic of tag.

Malevolent code can be inserted to access the network and because of this, network becomes unavailable. Denial of Services of the IoT can be created by jamming the wireless sensor signals. In it, nodes are placed at large distance, so data is transmitted over wireless network because of that data may contain incomplete or false information and sensor nodes can be tapped by the attackers.

Network layer: In this layer, reliability of data is the major issue and different types of attack are discussed which are common to this layer. Due to sinkhole attack, packets that are going to destination are dropped. It is also susceptible to DoS attack. In it, system becomes unable to provide services to the user. In Man-in-the-Middle attack, attacker uses the communication protocol of IoT and access the classified information, without actually appearing on the network location. In IoT, communication take place not only machine to human, but also machine to machine. That's why compatibility issue is also created in IoT. Sybil attacker manipulates the node to produce different identities of a single node because of it; user gets information about the redundancy.

Processing layer: In this layer, data is sent to the cloud. So cloud attack is one of the most dangerous attacks. Various security issues on cloud software as a Service (SAAS) also applied on this layer. Attackers can access the IoT network by using the web. SAAS providers are responsible to ensure the data security that is stored on cloud. The attacker can easily damage to the data or delete the existing data by forbidding the access to the related services of IoT. Platform as a Service provides third party web service and source is combined which increase the security risk. In Sleep Deprivation attack, sensor node are powered with batteries, keep awake the nodes so that battery consumption goes high and batteries get downs which causes the nodes to shut down.

Application layer: IoT does not have standards that supervise the interaction through applications. Different applications have different authentication mechanism so that it is difficult to ensure security and data authentication. Spear-phishing attack is common at this layer. It is email spoofing attack. In it, when victim opens the email then his credentials get accessed by cybercriminals. System attackers may also intend to infect the system with malicious software which result in DoS or corrupt data and programmer's nonstandard code while development, can increase the software vulnerabilities. In summary, security technology is major and full of challenges in IoTs.

Conclusion: The IoT has great potential to reform our living style. But for this smart framework, security is required. If security concerns like confidentiality, authentication, privacy and end-to-end security are addressed completely, everything can be transformed by IoT in the near future. This paper focused on security in the IoT and analyzed architecture and security issues at four layers. All in one, the development of IoT will bring major security problems, which are always the primary and main task of the research.

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Risk And Return Analysis Of Selected Stocks In India: A Comparative Study

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Abstract

Today there are number of choices available to the investors to invest it in stock market whether there are equities, debt, mutual funds, exchange traded funds etc. On one hand it increases the investment alternatives and on the other hand it also make it complex for the investor so as to which option one should choose and in line with that the main purpose of this paper is to analyze the risk and returns of selected stocks and compare it with the benchmark index. Secondary data of monthly closing prices of stocks and market index for 4 years i.e. from 2015-2018 have been used. The method of data analysis includes Average Annual returns, Standard deviation, Beta, Correlation. The study concludes that 4 out of 6 stocks were having positive stock returns and HDFC bank and SBI bank were giving more returns than the market and in case of Beta, ICICI bank, SBI bank, PNB bank and Bank of Baroda were having more volatility as compared to the market Index. Further all stocks were positively correlated with the market.

Keywords: Average Annual returns, Standard deviation, Beta, Risk, Benchmark.

Introduction

Banks and stock market are the two major investment avenues as far as the country like India is concerned. The former caters the need of the investors having low risk taking ability while high risk takers prefer the latter. But now a day's most of the banks are having their shares listed in stock market of India, as a result a new horizon of investment is created and this will give the benefit to the investors to take the advantage of both the avenues i.e. banks as well as stock market. Today, there are over 35 banks listed in stock exchanges of India and moreover separate indices are there which are reflecting only the performances of bank stocks that are listed. BSE BANKEX and BANKNIFTY are the 2 indices of BSE and NSE which can be used to know the listed banks performance for a particular time. The purpose of the study is to analyze the returns of the selected bank stocks and compare it with the benchmark index.

Literature Review

- **SHAINI NAVEEN and T. MALLIKARJUNAPPA (2016)** had examined the performance of 12 listed banks in NSE in their paper. They collected secondary data for 5 years i.e. from 2011-2015 in their study from the official website of NSE. Their objective was to study the performances of selected bank stocks. They used various tools like average return, standard deviation, beta. They concluded that Beta for 8 out of 12 stocks was more than market and all stocks were having positive returns over the study.
- **PATJOSHI, P. (2016)** had examined the performance of 4 bank stocks listed in BSE in their paper. They collected secondary data for 15 years i.e. from 2001-2015 in their study

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from the official website of BSE. Their objective was to study the performances of selected bank stocks. They used various tools like standard deviation, beta, correlation etc. They concluded that all stocks were having positive returns as well as positive correlation with index except ICICI bank. Further Axis Bank was giving high returns as compared to all and SBI bank was having the highest volatility over the study period.

Statement Of The Problem

Banks are playing 2 major roles simultaneously i.e. role of Financial Institution and Body corporate. As a financial institution, they provide sufficient amount of return with least risk but as a corporate body when their shares are listed in stock markets, whether they are able to provide the same as compared to the benchmark of stock market or not is the central theme of this research paper.

Objectives Of The Study

1. To analyze the risk and returns of selected stocks.
2. To compare the risk and returns of selected stocks with benchmark index.
3. To analyze the association of selected stocks with benchmark index.

Research Methodology

The present study includes 3 private sector and 3 public sector banks listed stocks on Bombay Stock Exchange which have been selected on the basis of market capitalization and BSE Sensex have been used as the benchmark index. Secondary data of monthly closing prices have been collected for the study from the official website of BSE for 4 years i.e. from 2015-2018. The method of data analysis includes Average Annual returns, Standard deviation, Beta, Correlation.

Sample Size

Sr.no.	BANK STOCKS	SECTOR
1	HDFC	PRIVATE
2	ICICI	PRIVATE
3	KOTAK MAHINDRA	PRIVATE
4	SBI	PUBLIC
5	PNB	PUBLIC
6	BOB	PUBLIC

Tools

• **RETURNS**

It reflects the change in prices over a period of time.

$$\frac{\text{Ending price of investment} - \text{Beginning price of investment}}{\text{Beginning price of investment}}$$

• **STANDARD DEVIATION**

It reflects the sum of systematic risk (uncontrollable) and unsystematic risk (controllable).

$$\left[\frac{\sum (\text{RETURNS} - \text{AVERAGE RETURNS})^2}{n - 1} \right]^{1/2}$$

• **BETA**

It reflects the systematic risk which can't be controlled.

$$\frac{\text{Covariance (Returns of stock, Returns on market index)}}{\text{Variance (Returns on market index)}}$$

• **CORRELATION**

It reflects the association between 2 variables. Positive correlation indicates the movement in same direction i.e. as one goes up, other will also go up and vice versa. Negative correlation indicates movement in opposite direction i.e. if one goes up, then other will go down.

$$\frac{\Sigma (X-\bar{X}) (Y-\bar{Y})}{\sqrt{\Sigma (X-\bar{X})^2} \sqrt{\Sigma (Y-\bar{Y})^2}}$$

X = Stock returns

\bar{X} = Average of stock returns

Y = Index returns

\bar{Y} = Average of index returns

Analysis And Interpretation

1. To analyze the risk and returns of selected stocks.

BANK STOCKS	STOCK RETURNS	STANDARD DEVIATION	BETA
HDFC	16.7	20.13	0.90
ICICI	0.51	19.70	1.42
KOTAK MAHINDRA	0.86	32.73	0.99
SBI	6.19	28.90	1.56
PNB	-10.13	42.74	1.98
BOB	-6.12	20.56	1.03

Interpretations

From the above table it can be concluded that returns of 4 out of 6 banks were positive during study period and HDFC bank was at the top followed by SBI bank. As far as the risk is concerned PNB bank had the highest risk followed by Kotak Mahindra bank. Further in case of volatility, ICICI bank, SBI bank, PNB bank and Bank of Baroda were the most volatile stocks.

2. To compare the risk and returns of selected stocks with benchmark index

Interpretation

From the above graph it can be concluded that the benchmark index i.e. BSE Sensex was giving 5% average annual return over the study period. As far as the comparison of stock

returns is concerned only HDFC bank and SBI bank was giving more returns than BSE Sensex.

Interpretation

From the above graph it can be concluded that the benchmark index i.e. BSE Sensex was having 14.10% standard deviation over the study period. As far as the comparison of total risk is concerned all the bank stock were having more risk than market. PNB bank was having the highest standard deviation followed by Kotak Mahindra and SBI bank.

Interpretation

From the above graph it can be concluded that the as far as the comparison of volatility is concerned, 4 out of 6 bank stock were more volatile than market i.e. ICICI bank, SBI bank, PNB bank and Bank of Baroda.

4. To analyze the association of selected stocks with benchmark index.

Interpretation

From the above graph it can be concluded that as far as the relationship of stocks with benchmark index is concerned, all banks were having positive correlation with BSE sensex. Further HDFC bank, ICICI bank and SBI bank were having high correlation, PNB bank and Kotak Mahindra bank were having moderate correlation and Bank of Baroda was having low correlation with BSE sensex.

Conclusion

At last it can be concluded that during the study period, stock returns of 4 out of 6 i.e. HDFC bank, ICICI bank, KOTAK MAHINDRA bank, SBI bank were having positive returns and as far as standard deviation is concerned, all banks were having more standard deviation than market index while in case of volatility, ICICI bank, SBI bank, PNB bank and Bank of Baroda were having high volatility as compared to BSE Sensex. Further all stocks were positively correlated with the market.

Suggestions

- Investors or potential investors who are the moderate risk takers a wants to earn a good amount of return should invest in HDFC bank.
- Investors or potential investors who are the low risk takers a wants to earn a good amount of return should invest in Kotak Mahindra bank.

Limitations Of The Study

The study is limited to the sample of 6 banking stocks only and also the period of study is only 4 years. Hence more information will be needed in order to generalize the results.

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आतंकवाद एक चुनौती

Anju*

Dr. Ashok Kumar(Guide)

घरों को उजड़ते देखा,
लेगों को बिलखते देखा,

शायद चिराग छिन गया था उनके घरों का,

आतंकी हमलों में एक बार फिर घरों को जलते देखा

‘आतंक’ और ‘भय’ का घनिष्ठ संबंध है। या ये कहें कि दोनों एक ही सिक्के के दो पहलू हैं। आतंक पैदा ही लोगों को भयभीत करने के लिए किया जाता है। इस तरह आतंक कैसा भी हो, भय पैदा करना ही उसका उद्देश्य होता है। आतंकवाद का अर्थ किसी विनाशकारी शक्ति द्वारा विभिन्न तरीकों से भय की स्थिति को उत्पन्न करना है। किसी भी प्रकार के आतंकवाद से चाहे वे क्षेत्रीय हो, राष्ट्रीय या अंतर्राष्ट्रीय हो— सभी के कारण देश में असुरक्षा, भय और संकट की स्थिति उत्पन्न हो जाती है।

आतंकवाद के अनेक रूप हैं। राजनीति आतंकवाद, आर्थिक आतंकवाद, धार्मिक आतंकवाद इत्यादि। आज यदि कोई चर्चा का विषय है तो वह है आतंकवाद। आतंक धीरे-धीरे समूचे विश्व में अपने पैर पसार रहा है। आतंक का इतना बड़ा संगठन समूचे विश्व में फै गया और विश्व को प्रमुख खुफिया एजेंसियाँ हाथ पर हाथ धरे बैठी रही, सारी गुप्तचर व्यवस्था आतंक के आगे असफल हो गई। आतंकवाद की सीमा कोई एक राज्य, देश अथवा क्षेत्र नहीं है। आज यह एक अंतर्राष्ट्रीय समस्या के रूप में उभर रही है। यदि किसी एक देश पर दूसरा देश आक्रमण करता है, तो समस्या का समाधान दोनों देशों की सरकारों की बातचीत, संधि आदि से हो जाता है। लेकिन आतंकवाद का कोई हल नहीं है। आतंकवाद का लक्ष्य केवल आतंक फैलाना है।

भारत भी इससे अछूता नहीं रहा है। भारत में आतंकवाद ने कब जड़े जमा लीं, पता ही नहीं चला। आज भारत का प्रत्येक कोना आतंकवाद के साये में है।

सिनेमाघरों, रेलगाड़ियों, भीड़-भाड़ वाले इलाकों में बम विस्फोट द्वारा आतंक फैलाना एक आम घटना बन गई है। सिनेमाघर में फिल्म देखते हजारों दर्शकों की बम के विस्फोट के कारण मृत्यु हो जाती है। रेल अथवा वायुयान में अपने गंतव्य की ओर बढ़ते यात्रियों की यात्रा बम के धमाके के साथ ही समाप्त हो जाती है।

यह दुर्भाग्यपूर्ण है कि स्वतंत्र भारत में भी पुलिस तथा अन्य कानून संबंधी संगठन निर्दोष जनता पर अत्याचार करते हैं। बहुत से राजनीतिक शक्तियाँ द्वारा पथभ्रष्ट युवकों को काम समाप्त हो जाने के बाद तथाकथित ‘मुठभेड़ों’ में पुलिस की गोली का शिकार होना पड़ता है। इनमें कई बेकसूर लोगों की जानें चली जाती हैं और अपराधी फरार हो जाता है। यह भी देखा गया है कि मारे गए निर्दोष व्यक्तियों के मित्र या भाई बदले की भावना से स्वयं आतंकवादी बन जाते हैं। जिस देश में रक्षक ही भक्षक बन जाए, वहाँ आतंकवाद का विस्तार और अधिक होता जाएगा। भारत का प्रत्येक नागरिक आतंकवाद का विरोधी है। इससे कुछ भी प्राप्त नहीं होता है। लेकिन कुछ देश यह मानते हैं कि यह सरकारी तंत्र के आतंकवाद का जवाब है। इन देशों में अपराधी, भ्रष्ट राजनीतिज्ञ, तस्कर खुले आम घूमते रहते हैं, उनको पकड़ने के लिए कानून के पास कोई सबूत नहीं है। कई बार अपराधी राजनीतिज्ञों के साथ मिलकर देश में आतंक फैलाते हैं। इस प्रकार के भ्रष्ट शासन तंत्र में अपराधी कभी भी गिरफ्त में नहीं आते हैं।

प्राचीनकाल में आतंकवाद के संबंध में कोई जानता भी नहीं था। पिछले कुछ वर्षों से इसने भयंकर रूप धारण कर लिया है। निस्संदेह आतंकवाद शासन-विरोध का एक विकृत रूप है। आतंकवादियों की मांग कितनी भी उचित क्यों न हो, लेकिन आतंक फैलाकर उन्हें मनवाने का तरीका बहुत ही निर्दयता और कायरतापूर्ण है।

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भारत में कब-कब हुए बड़े आतंकवादी हमले

जम्मू-कश्मीर के उड़ी सेक्टर में सेना के कैंप पर हुए भीषण आतंकवादी हमले ने पूरे देश को दहला दिया। इस हमले में कम से कम 20 सैनिक शहीद हो गए और कई सैनिक घायल हो गए। आइए जानते हैं भारत में हुए कुछ प्रमुख आतंकवादी हमलों के बारे में –

मुंबई सीरियल ब्लास्ट : 12 मार्च, 1993 को पूरे मुंबई में सीरियल धमाके हुए। इन धमाकों के पीछे डी कंपनी का हाथ था। इस हमले में 257 लोग मारे गए थे, जबकि 713 लोग घायल हुए थे।

कोयम्बटूर धमाका : 14 फरवरी, 1998 में इस्लामिक ग्रुप अल उम्माह ने कोयंबटूर में 11 अलग-अलग जगहों पर 12 बम धमाके किए। इसमें 60 लोगों की मौत हो गई, जबकि 200 लोग घायल हुए थे।

3 नवंबर, 1999 को श्रीनगर के बादाम बाग में हुए आतंकवादी हमले में 10 जवान शहीद हो गए।

जम्मू कश्मीर विधानसभा पर हमला : 1 अक्टूबर, 2001 को भवन जैश ए मोहम्मद ने 3 आत्मघाती हमलावरों ने विधानसभा भवन पर कार बम हमला किया। इसमें 38 लोग मारे गए।

भारतीय संसद पर हमला : 13 दिसंबर 2001 में लश्करे तैयबा और जैश मोहम्मद के 5 आतंकवादी भारत के सबसे सुरक्षित माने जाने वाले संसद भवन परिसर में घुस गए। हालांकि सुरक्षा बलों ने आतंकियों को मार गिराया और आतंकी अपने मंसूबे में नाकाम हो गए। हमले के समय संसद भवन में 100 राजनेता मौजूद थे। इस हमले में 6 पुलिसकर्मी और 3 संसद भवन कर्मी मारे गए।

14 मई, 2002 को जम्मू कश्मीर के कालूचक में हुए हमले में 21 जवान शहीद हो गए और जबकि 36 अन्य लोगों की मौत को गई।

अक्षरधाम मंदिर पर हमला : 24 सितंबर 2002 में लश्कर और जैश ए मोहम्मद के 2 आतंकी मुर्तजा हाफिस यासिन और अशरफ अली मोहम्मद फारूख दोपहर 3 बजे अक्षरधाम मंदिर में घुस गए। इनके हमले में 31 लोग मारे गए जबकि 80 लोग घायल हो गए थे।

22 जुलाई, 2003 को जम्मू कश्मीर के अखनूर में हुए आतंकी हमले में 8 सुरक्षाकर्मी शहीद हो गए।

दिल्ली सीरियल बम ब्लास्ट : 29 अक्टूबर 2005 में दीवाली से 2 दिन पहले आतंकियों ने 3 बम धमाके किए। 2 धमाके सरोजनी नगर और पहाड़गंज जैसे मुख्य बाजारों में हुए। तीसरा धमाका गोविंदपुरी में एक बस में हुआ। इसमें कुल 63 लोग मारे गए जबकि 210 लोग घायल हुए थे।

मुंबई ट्रेन धमाका : 11 जुलाई, 2006 में मुंबई की लोकल ट्रेनों में अलग-अलग 7 बम विस्फोट हुए। सभी विस्फोटक फर्स्ट क्लास कोच में बम रखे गए थे। इन धमाकों में इंडियन मुजाहिदीन का हाथ था। इसमें कुल 210 लोग मारे गए थे और 715 लोग जख्मी हुए थे।

महाराष्ट्र के मालेगांव में 8 सितंबर, 2006 को हुए तीन धमाकों में 32 लोग मारे गए और सौ से अधिक घायल हुए।

5 अक्टूबर 2006 श्रीनगर में हुए हमले 7 सुरक्षाकर्मी शहीद हो गए।

भारत और पाकिस्तान के बीच चलने वाली समझौता एक्सप्रेस में 19 फरवरी, 2007 को हुए धमाके में 66 यात्री मारे गए। आंध्रप्रदेश के हैदराबाद में 25 अगस्त, 2007 को हुए धमाके में 35 लोग मारे गए और कई अन्य घायल हो गए। हैदराबाद में ही 18 मई, 2007 को मक्का मस्जिद धमाके में 13 लोगों की मौत हो गई।

उत्तर प्रदेश में 1 जनवरी, 2008 को रामपुर में केंद्रीय रिजर्व पुलिस बल के कैंप पर हुए हमले में आठ लोग मारे गए।

जयपुर विस्फोट : गुलाबी नगरी जयपुर में 13 मई, 2008 में 15 मिनट के अंदर 9 बम धमाके हुए। इन धमाकों में कुल 63 लोग मारे गए थे जबकि 210 लोग घायल हुए थे।

अहमदाबाद में 26 जुलाई, 2008 के दिन दो घंटे के भीतर 20 बम विस्फोट होने से 50 से अधिक लोग मारे गए। इस दौरान सूरत और बड़ौदा से भी बम बरामद हुए थे।

इंफाल में 21 अक्टूबर, 2008 को मणिपुर पुलिस कमांडों परिसर पर हुए हमले में 17 लोगों की मौत हो गई।

असम में धमाके

राजधानी गुवाहाटी में 30 अक्टूबर 2008 को विभिन्न जगहों पर कुल 18 धमाके आतंकियों द्वारा किए गए। इन धमाकों में कुल 81 लोग मारे गए जबकि 470 लोग घायल हुए।

26/11 मुंबई आतंकी हमला : 26 नवंबर, 2008 को पाकिस्तान से आए 10 आत्मघाती हमलावरों ने सीरियल बम धमाकों के अलावा कई जहड़ों पर अंधाधुंध फायरिंग की।

आतंकियों ने नरीमन हाउस, होटल ताज और होटल ओबेराय को कब्जे में ले लिया था। इस हमले में करीब 180 लोग मारे गए थे और करीब 300 लोग घायल हुए थे। आतंकवादी कसाब पकड़ा गया था, जिसे मुकदमें के बाद फांसी दे दी गई।

पुणे की जर्मन बेकरी में 10 फरवरी, 2010 को हुए बम धमाके में नौ लोग मारे गए और 45 घायल हुए।

बंगलुरु के विन्नास्वामी स्टेडियम के बाहर 17 अप्रैल, 2010 में हुए दो बम धमाकों में 15 लोगों की मौत हो गई।

31 मार्च, 2013 में श्रीनगर में हुए आतंकवादी हमले में 5 जवान शहीद हुए।

24 जून, 2013 को श्रीनगर में हुए आतंकवादी हमले में 8 जवान शहीद हो गए।

26 सितंबर, 2013 में हुए एक आत्मघाती हमले में 10 सुरक्षाकर्मी शहीद हो गए। इनमें ले. कर्नल बिक्रमजीतसिंह भी शामिल थे। सुरक्षाबलों ने तीन आतंकियों को भी मार गिराया था।

5 दिसंबर 2014 में उड़ी सेक्टर में हुए हमले में 7 सैनिक शहीद हो गए।

पठानकोट हमला : 2 जनवरी को 2015 को पठानकोट एयरबेस पर 7 पाकिस्तानी आतंकवादियों हमला कर कई लोगों को घायल कर दिया जिसमें 7 जवान शहीद हो गए।

गुरदासपुर हमला : पाकिस्तान की सीमा से महज 10-20 किलोमीटर दूर पंजाब के गुरदासपुर में 27 जुलाई 2015 को बड़ा आतंकी हमला हुआ। हमले में गुरदासपुर के एस. पी. डिटेक्टिव बलजीत सिंह सहित 4 जवान शहीद हो गए थे। पाकिस्तान से आए आतंकियों ने सबसे पहले जम्मू जा रही बस को निशाना बनाया और फिर दीनानगर पुलिस थाने में घुस गए। वहां उन्होंने अंधाधुंध फायरिंग की। 11 घंटे चली लड़ाई में कुल सात लोगों की जान चली गई और 3 आतंकवादी मारे गए।

7 दिसंबर 2015 में अनंतनाग में हुए आतंकवादी हमले में 6 जवान शहीद हुए।

25 जून, 2016 पंपोर में सीआरपीएफ के काफिले पर हुए आतंकवादी हमले में 8 जवान शहीद हुए।

18 सितंबर 2016 में उड़ी सेक्टर सेना के कैंप पर हुए एक आतंकवादी हमले में कम से कम 20 जवान शहीद हो गए।

2019 पुलामा हमला : 14 फरवरी, 2019 को जम्मू श्रीनगर राष्ट्रीय राजमार्ग पर भारतीय सुरक्षा कर्मियों को ले जाने वाले सी. आर. पी. एफ. के वाहनों के काफिले पर आत्मघाती हमला पाकिस्तानी आतंकवादियों द्वारा किया गया, जिसमें केन्द्रीय रिजर्व पुलिस बल के 42 सुरक्षा कर्मियों की जान गयी थी। इस हमले की जिम्मेदारी पाकिस्तान स्थित इस्लामिक आतंकवादी समूह जैश-ए-मोहम्मद ने ली है।

बड़ों-2 को लोहों के चने चबवा देने वाली, भारत की प्रखर प्रतिष्ठित प्रधानमंत्री इंदिरा गांधी आतंकवाद की भेंट चढ़ गईं। समय बीता और उनकी ही कोख से जन्में राजीव गांधी प्रगति की राह पर चलते हुए उन्हें नहीं सुहाए और वे भी आतंक के शिकार हुए। इतना ही नहीं, भारत के उच्च सभा सदन (संसद भवन) पर आतंकियों ने आक्रमण किया। देश की संप्रभुता को तहस-नहस करने के प्रयास हुए। आज भारत आतंक के साए में हैं, उसे नित्य धमकी मिलती है। मौत का भीषण तांडव, फटते हुए बम, चीखते लोग, जलत घर, लाशों के ढेर आदि आतंकवाद की ही तो देन है। इन पंक्तियों में आतंक का भय साफ दिखाई देता है।

उनकी आँखों में बम, उनकी साँसों में बम,

सिक रहे नित नए, अब सलाखों में बम।

हम दीवाली मनाएँ भला किस तरह -

रख दिए हैं किसी ने पटाखों में बम।।

आज आतंक इतना शक्तिशाली हो गया है कि वह वायुयान का अपहरण कर कंधार ले गया और निर्दोष यात्रियों की जान की कीमत के बदले उसने अपने कुछ आतंकी साथियों को जेल से रिहा करा लिया और समूचा देश देखता रह गया। किसी भी देश ने न तो इस ओर कोई कदम उठाया और न ही विश्व-स्तर पर कोई योजना बनाई और अब आतंकवाद विश्व स्तर तक अपनी जड़ें जमा चुका है। उसके तार आज विश्व स्तर पर फैले हुए हैं। अमेरिका सबसे ताकतवर, समृद्ध और सुरक्षा की दृष्टि से सशक्त माना जाता है। वह दूसरे देशों में पनपते हुए आतंक की खिल्ली उड़ाता था। आतंक ने अपने परों को फड़फड़ाया और अमेरिका में बम धमाके कर यह सिद्ध कर दिया कि दुनिया पर साम्राज्य करने का स्वप्न देखने वाला अमेरिका भी अब आतंकवाद की मार से सुरक्षित नहीं है। स्वयं आतंक से बेखबर अमेरिका की गगनचुंबी इमारतें धू-धू करके धरती में समा गईं, तब उसके कान खड़े हुए।

प्रश्न उठता है कि अमेरिका का गुप्तचर विभाग इतना सक्रिय है कि आकाश को प्रत्येक गतिविधि की रिपोर्ट रखता है, लेकिन जब अमेरिका पर आतंकी हमला हुआ तो अमेरिका को गुप्तचर एजेंसियाँ कँहा थी? मानव बम बने हवाई जहाजों सहित आतंकियों ने हमला कर अमेरिका ही नहीं, समूचे विश्व को हिलाकर रख दिया। कवि ने इस पर लिखा-

मानव बम लेकर आतंकी, अमेरिका में छाया।

इस आतंकी घटना से था, व्हाइट हाउस थर्राया।।

अमेरिका के बाद आतंकियों ने निशाना बनाया लंदन को। एक के बाद एक आतंकी हमले कर उसने लंदन को हिला कर रख दिया। इस तरह आतंकियों की अंतर्राष्ट्रीय शक्ति जोर पकड़ती जा रही है।

निष्कर्ष

आतंकवाद को रोकने का एकमात्र उपाय यह है कि शासन तंत्र अपने दायित्वों को समझे और यह प्रयास करे कि समाज के प्रत्येक वर्ग के व्यक्ति को समान अधिकार प्राप्त हो और सभी को समान रूप से कानून का संरक्षण प्राप्त हो। जनता ने अपने जिन प्रतिनिधियों को अपने बहुमूल्य समर्थन द्वारा चुना है, उनका कर्तव्य है कि वे जनता को अच्छा जीवन और सुरक्षा प्रदान करें। यदि सभी नागरिकों के साथ समान ढंग से व्यवहार किया जाए, उनके पिछड़ेपन को संवैधानिक तरीकों से सुधारा जाए तो बहुत हद तक यह समस्या सुलझ सकती है।

आतंक को समाप्त हेतु संयुक्त राष्ट्र संघ को आगे आना होगा क्योंकि आतंकियों की मंशा केवल विनाश की है, जबकि धरती पर सृजन की आवश्यकता है। सृजन केवल शांति से ही संभव है। इसके लिए समूचे विश्व को एकजुट होकर आतंकवाद को समाप्त कर विश्व को बचाने का सार्थक प्रयास करना होगा। अगर समय रहते राष्ट्रों ने एक-जुट होकर

आतंकवाद के विरुद्ध दृढ़ इच्छाशक्ति नहीं दिखाई तो आतंकवाद पूरी मानवता को निगल लेगा। ऐसी स्थिति में प्रत्येक नागरिक का भी यह कर्तव्य है कि वह सावधानी से रहे और सरकार की हर स्तर पर मदद करे।

सन्दर्भ सूची

1. हरिभूमि
2. दैनिक भास्कर
3. दैनिक टिब्यून
4. पलपल
5. अमर उजाला

Workers' Participation in Management

Nisha Pawaria*

Abstract

There is no denying the fact that in each and every organisation, Workers' participation has been gaining popularity all over the world. In Yugoslavia, this scheme is known as Self-Management, on the other hand, in Germany it is called Co-determination. The International Labour Organisation (ILO) is continuously doing efforts to encourage all those nations which are its members to implement the Workers' participation in its management. WPM is getting popular day by day as no organization can achieve its objectives without workers' active participation in management. Workers feel privileged when they are considered an important part of the organization. Management shares its authority and responsibility of managing with its workers. Participation is mentally and emotionally involvement rather than only physical involvement of workers. By giving them role to participate in decision-making, their ambitions and emotions have been duly recognized by the management. The management has realized that the organizational objectives can be achieved only if the workers cooperate with them in decision making also. Therefore, all the efforts are made to get their cooperation. Workers participation is an important device to the management. This paper concentrates on the evolution and importance of workers' active participation in management in India.

Key words –workers' participation, cooperation, Industrial relations, ILO, recognition.

Introduction

No doubt, Workers' participation in management is a vital factor for efficient functioning of any organisation. It is very important phenomena in Human Resource Management. It has proved itself in maintaining better industrial relations in organizations. This concept is known by different authorities by different names. For example, employers interpret it as the joint consultation but experts often regard it as association of labour without the final responsibility and authority in decision making process. Workers' participation can be formal and informal. In both situations, it is considered as a system of consultation and communication where, workers and employees have full liberty to raise their voice in management's decision-making process mechanism where workers have a say in the decision-making.

The objectives of workers' participation in management are as follows:

- 1)Economic objective** - WPM targets at enhancing productivity of labour by making smooth relations between employer and employees. Productivity will be increased when there will be job satisfaction and better industrial relations.
- 2)Social objective** – Under participation, industry is assumed as a social institution in which each worker has a vested interest. To get the workers' a respectable and renewable status in a society is the main purpose of participation.
- 3)Psychological objective** – By getting involvement in decision-making, the attitude of employees gets changed. Just because of getting participated, they start considering

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themselves an integral part of the industry rather than mere working hands. Participation provide them opportunity to express themselves so that their non-economic needs could be satisfied. Participation provides them a sense of belonging, pride and accomplishment.

Importance of Worker's Participation in Management-

1)Mutual Understanding- Usually, both the parties, employer and employees have a doubt at the integrity of each other due to unawareness of each other's difficulties. Participation helps in taking them much closer and helps in making them aware of each other's problems. As a result of which, a better understanding and mutual trust may be created between employer and workers.

2)Higher Productivity- Cooperation between management and labour helps to increase production and profits of industry. Only through involvement, workers are able to learn the problems of industry and can better understand their role. Employee motivation can be improved by giving value to their contributions and ultimately.

3)Industrial Harmony- WPM plays a very significant role in reducing industrial disputes and helps in improving workers' loyalty. Continuous dialogue between management and workers improves peace and calm in industry.

4)Industrial Democracy- In management, participation of workers ushers in industrial democracy which is equally necessary for political democracy. Need for outside intervention between employer and employees is eliminated and workers get freedom from exploitation.

Forms of Participation-

1)Suggestion Schemes- Under this system, workers are offered invitation to provide their suggestions so that the working of the enterprise can be improved. In each enterprise, a suggestion box is installed. Every worker is free enough to express his suggestions and put into the box. Periodically, all the suggestions are scrutinized by the Suggestion Committee. If suggestions are really good, those are accepted for getting implemented and suitable rewards are provided to the concerned workers. Suggestion schemes persuade workers interest in the functioning of the enterprise.

2) Seat on board of directors- Here, the representative of workers is provided a seat on the boards of directors. This scheme is not followed by advanced nations. It has been observed that the workers are not able to understand the complicity prevailing in management.

Although, their representatives being in few in numbers, do not take active participation in the decision making process but such decisions will be applicable for all the employees. By remaining out of the board, they can have a better control on the management.

The Sachar Committee analysed the problems of workers' participation in management and observed "Conditions must be created where the worker directors are able to play a helpful and effective role. It is apparent that as a member of the board, the worker director will familiarise himself with subjects with which he was not associated before. The training of the employees must, therefore, be immediately taken in hand".

3)Works Committee-A works committee is constituted whereas number of workers is hundred or more than hundred. Here number of representatives of both the parties is equal. This committee is established so that the mutual relations between employers and employees could be maintained. Its main objective is to maintain an amicable environment in the establishments.

4)Worker Directors-Under this method, one or two representatives of workers are nominated or elected on the Board of Directors.

5)Co-Partnership-Here, workers are made shareholders in the company in which they are employed. As partners, they take part in the management of the enterprise. They can elect their representatives to the board of directors. They also share the company's profits in the form of dividend. Trade Unions in India do not favour the scheme of worker shareholders on the ground that a nominal shareholding by the workers cannot give them any say in management.

There are different levels of workers' Participation in organizations-Workers' participation is possible at all levels of management; the only difference is that of degree and nature of application. For instance, it may be vigorous at lower level and faint at top level. Broadly speaking there are following five levels of participation:

1)Information Participation-It enables employees to get timely information and express their opinions, suggestions which are related to economic matters.

2)Consultative Participation- Under this type of participation, workers are given full freedom to raise their voice on matters related to their welfare, safety, working hours and health. Although, the final decision will be taken by top level, but advises given by workers are considered.

3)Associative Participation- It is only a revised form of consultative participation because top level management has to take decisions while keeping morality into consideration.

4)Administrative Participation- In this type of participation, top level administration take ultimate decisions but they share a lot of works with their workers so that they don't feel themselves unimportant part of the organisation. Here, workers are given chances to select best alternative among various options presented by management

5)Decisive Participation- This is the highest level of participation where decisions are taken jointly by both parties on the issues associated with their comforts, safety, capacity to work etc.

Rationale of the Study

1-To give significance to the participative management which ultimately helps in resolving conflicts between employer and employees which has a positive impact on functioning of enterprise.

2-To ascertain relevance of the cooperation given by workers which is very essential for the peace in industry and greater efficiency in the favour of the whole organisation

3-To go through the implications of workers participation in the common interest of whole enterprise.

4-To explore the impact of Management's participative role so that the efficiency of their work can be assessed.

5-To decide those issues which are helpful and which are useless in participation of workers.

Drawbacks in Workers' Participation in India -

1- Employers continuously refused workers' active participation in decision-making process. They don't think them efficient enough to take accurate decisions.

2- Managers have always a doubt on the value of participative management whether it could really lead to higher productivity and profitability or not.

3- The needs of workers at lower levels are just ignored. Therefore a large number of our Indian workers do not get persuasion enough to take authority of decision-making. They neither do it directly or indirectly.

- 4- Workers' representatives need to act the double role of workers' spokesmen's as well as co-managers also. A minority of representatives will be capable to tackle both indifferent roles simultaneously.
- 5- Usually, members of such unions are also considered a part of political parties. Due to this reason, they give preference to their political interests as compared to interests of workers while participating in management.

Challenges

In view of the problems discussed above, a wider look is needed to the problems involved in the coming years if worker participation is to succeed. Many of the problems have been raised previously. But they have to be again raised, debated, and articulated without which it is futile to pursue the democratisation of workplace. The posterity will have to address to the following questions:

1. The forum works committee has to be reviewed in view of its ineffectiveness, lack of interest on the part of trade unionists, and the misuse of some unscrupulous employers as a device to stall formation of unions.
2. No second thoughts are needed on the inevitability of law on workers' participation, as the same would quite be in consonance with the spirit of democratic and participatory way of life enshrined in the Constitution. Though, working of the system would require a high level of motivation of the actors in the participation system, designing of appropriate system would be essential as a first stage. The proposed law should be supplemented by removal of the contradictions in the Indian labour policy, mentioned above.
3. It is important to understand that since participation may be possible only with the flourishing of professional management, the nuisance value of autocratic and paternalistic managements can be counteracted only by strong trade union movement. For this, wider questions of dejuridification of the industrial relations system will have to be examined on a priority basis for developing environment whereby the parties can fully appreciate the value of participation.
4. The five year plans have put greater emphasis on participation mechanism to be used as instruments for increasing production and productivity. The National Front Government has underlined 'a culture of participatory decision making and a sense of belonging with the enterprise' as the goal of workers' participation in management. The working of the future labour policy shall have to adhere to such a goal because productivity-linked participation has proved to be a mere rhetoric.
5. A review of two of the most successful workers' participation experiments of the world -- Yugoslav and West German -- reveal that the Yugoslav system of worker self-management postulate no collective bargaining, and in case of West German co-determination, trade unions' role has considerably changed from a purely adversary power group to an assimilation of it with a positive role of making workers better performers at the participation forums. Unless dichotomy between negotiation and participation is strictly adhered to, the future of worker participation in India is quite bleak.
6. Since Indian trade unions suffer from the weakness of poor finances, they cannot effectively organize workers education on their own. It is, therefore, worthwhile to consider levying of a cess on the value of industrial production to finance a state-created autonomous agency for managing worker education on a priority basis.

7. The rulers have to set examples by resorting to, and encouraging the use of, elections for selecting representatives for various forums, to be followed by workers. They will have to be viewed more positively than has been the case so far.

Requirements of Successful Worker's Participation:

- 1) Top management' support is vital for ensuring the success of such schemes. The employers must regard the whole organisation a common purpose entity where employees must get an equal opportunity to express their views.
- 2) Employers must be aware of their duties towards lower level management only then they could take advantage of Participative management. Their assurance of security of job to workers is very essential.
- 3) Such a trade union be developed which really represent workers. It should be active enough to raise its voice in the favour of workers whenever they need.
- 4) Both the parties should consider organisation's objective as their own personal objective. They must give value to each other's points of view.
- 5) Effective training must be provided to workers and their representatives so that they can function efficiently and contribute in achieving organisation's common target.
- 6) Only legislation is not enough to make participation of employees successful. The most required thing is mutual understanding. An amicable environment should be maintained from both sides.
- 7) It should be an ongoing process. Proper time must be allowed to get into its effective form. This process should not start in a haste. It should be carried on with proper care and with due diligence.so that it may not prove a failure concept.

Conclusion

The phenomena of workers' participation in the management is very important from the organization's and from the individual's point of view. The participation satisfies the employees each and every type of needs. Workers feel themselves privileged after getting opportunity to take part in important decisions of the organization. The employers can't deny this fact that workers also have an equal say. Through participation, both the parties recognise and respect the rights and obligations of each other. The scheme of participation promotes industrial and human relations and thus helps minimizing the labour disputes because they participate in each and every important decisions and become the partners in those decisions. All types of problems concerning the workers are settled amicably. Only because of participative partnership, employers and workers get agree on the objectives of industry. In India, each and every organization is getting advantage of these schemes as workers are quite important assets of the organization and it is very crucial to give them proper recognition and status.

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A Study on issue related to Self-Help Groups in India

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Abstract: A SHG is an informal association to enhance the member's financial security as primary focus and other common interest of members such as area development, awareness, motivation, leadership, training and associating in other social inter-mediation programmes for The SHGs broadly go through three stages of evolution such as, Group formation, Capital formation (through the revolving fund), Skill development and taking up of economic activity for income generation .The Self Help Groups Project has both Economic/Development and Social objectives like promote saving, improve management skills, improve living standard, encourage community, sharing ideas and knowledge, solve problems. There are so many challenges faced by self-help groups but apart from challenges self-help groups also has many opportunities. Central and state governments starts many schemes for self-help groups. If govt. and SHGs work seriously then no SHGs can be failed. So in this regard the SHGs can play a vital role. As there are many challenges faced by SHGs but they also enhance the equality of status of women as participants, decision maker and beneficiaries in the democratic, economic, socia and cultural spheres of life. So long the self -help groups has played a major role in the awareness creating and economic upliftment of women.

Keywords: project, participation , economic, social, equality, awareness, skill, income, development .

Introduction of Self-Help Group (SHG):SHG is a holistic programme of micro-enterprises covering all aspects of self-employment, organization of the rural poor into self Help groups and their capacity building, planning of activity clusters, infrastructure build up, technology, credit and marketing. A self -help group may be registered or unregistered.

It lays emphasis on activity clusters based on the resources and the occupational skills of the people and availability of markets. Self-Help Group refers to self-governed, peer controlled, informal group of people with same socio-economic background and having a desire to collectively perform common purposes. Here poor people voluntarily come together to save whatever amount they can save conveniently out of their earnings, to mutually agree to contribute to a common fund and to lend to the members

SHGs have been able to mobilize small savings either on weekly or monthly basis from persons who were not expected to have any savings. They have been able to effectively recycle the resources generated among the members for meeting the emergent credit needs of members of the group. SHG is a group formed by the community women, which has specific number of members like 15 or 20. In such a group the poorest women would come together for emergency, disaster, social reasons, economic support to each other have ease of conversation, social interaction and economic interaction.

A SHG is an informal association to enhance the member's financial security as primary focus and other common interest of members such as area development, awareness,

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motivation, leadership, training and associating in other social inter-mediation programmes for the benefit of the entire community.

Objectives of study

To study the various objectives of the self -help groups.

To study the various challenges faced by the self- help groups.

To examine the growth of self-help group;

The SHGs broadly go through three stages of evolution such as:

I. Group formation.

II. Capital formation (through the revolving fund).

iii. Skill development and taking up of economic activity for income generation.

As SHG are formed under the Swarna Jayanti Swarojgar Yojana (SGSY), for SHGs subsidy would be 50 percent of the project cost subject to a ceiling of Rs. 1.25 lakh or per capital subsidy of Rs. 10,000 whichever is less. There is no monetary ceiling on subsidy for minor irrigation projects for SHGs as well as individual swarojgar is (self-employed).

The SHGs may consist of 10-20 members and in case of minor irrigation, and in case of disabled persons and difficult areas, i.e. hilly, desert and sparsely populated areas, this number may be a minimum of five. Self Help Groups should also be drawn from the BPL list approved by the Gram Sabha.

Since the inception of the programme of SGSY (1st April, 1999) 22.52 lakh self-help groups have been formed covering 66.97 lakh swarojgaries. These include 35.54 lakh members of the SHGs and 31.43 lakh Individual swarojgaries who have been assisted with a total investment of Rs. 14403.73 crore. Out of total swarojgaries assisted, SCs/STs were 45.54 percent and women 47.85 percent. During 2006-07, the central allocation scheme is Rs.1200 crore.

Mission

- 1) To promote saving amongst the poor women .
- 2) To help the poor realize their entrepreneurial and business management skills through training and access to capital.
- 3) To reduce gender inequality in the society.

Objectives

The Self Help Groups Project has both Economic/Development and Social objectives.

Economic/Development

- To promote saving.
- To give management skills.
- To improve credit services.
- To improve living standards.
- To reduce poverty in times of crisis (sickness, death etc.)
- To further economic self-reliance.

Social

- To encourage community work with unity.
- To provide a forum for the sharing of ideas and knowledge.
- To provide support for members in difficulty.
- To help the community in identifying and resolving their own problems.

opportunities of self-help group

E-market : PM MODI interact with women of self -help group via video conference, in this talked he talk about the importance of value addition and value chain approach. He says that SHG to register in govt. e-market place to sell their product and expand their market share.

Mahila kisan sashktikaran pariyojna : Through it training has been given to over 33 lakh women farmers. At present there are 45 lakh SHG with active participation of around 5 crore women all over rural India.

Sahyog niwas: The Sahyog Niwas Scheme is a home loan scheme specially designed by the State Bank of India to provide home loan and housing finance solutions to Self Help Groups who reside in rural locations and areas. Self Help Groups that possess a good track record of at least two years with regards to payments can avail of this scheme. Objectives Of The SBI Sahyog Niwas Home Loan Scheme.

Scheme for promotion of SHGs in backward &LWE districts of India: announcement made by Hon. Finance minister in the union budget 2011-2012,the scheme aim at saturating the districts with viable and self- sustainable WSHGs by involving Anchor agencies who shall promote & facilitate credit linkage of these groups with banks. The identified NGOs will be eligible for grant assistant upto a maximum 10,000rs.per WSHGs. As on 31 march the total numbers of SHGs promoted and credit linked are 1.88 lakh and 1.04 lakh respectively.

Women SHGs development fund : the fund will be operated by NABARD and kept in a separate account.

A suitable MIS system shall be put in place by NABARD.

NABARD will be entitiled to receive service charge @ .30% . the payments of refinance and interest received by bank will be credited to the fund .

Rural development : people of rural area of facing so many problems related to poverty, illiteracy, lack of skills, healthcare , basic infrastructure etc. self -help group are able to work for the development of rural area. Firstly, SHGs provide self -employment to the rural poor to have sustained income to meet their urgent needs. As far as the educational level is concerned ,90% of SHGs beneficiaries were below 10th, 8% under secondary level and only 2% were under graduate level.

Pradhan Mantri Van Dhan Yojana – Govt. to Setup 30,000 SHGs:

Govt. has proposed to undertake grass root level procurement through SHGs in association of other Implementing Agencies. Other govt. departments will also work simultaneously to utilize the services of existing SHGs like Ajeevika. All SHGs will also be provided appropriate training on sustainable harvesting / collection, primary processing & value addition.

These SHGs will work in clusters and thus will fulfill the stock availability in tradable quantity. Moreover, govt. will also provide them with a facility of primary processing in all of these newly established Van Dhan Vikas Kendras

Major challenges faced by SHGs

Poor Marketing: When asked about the major challenges faced by SHGs during the CII-IWN's NGO Mentoring Event in association with SIMSREE, Surekha, a member of a Self Help Group under Mahila Arthik Vikas Mahamandal (MAVIM) said "Marketing is a hurdle for us. We do not know how to market our products and the different channels used for it." Marketing plays a crucial role to gain visibility for the products. Lack of effective marketing is a hindrance as this poses a challenge for getting sales orders for the products.

Lack of Product Standardization and Quality Issues: Most of the products made by SHGs are not uniform in their specifications and look & feel. This is so because most of the SHG products are hand-made, and hence it becomes difficult to maintain uniformity. Also, to cut costs, SHGs compromise on quality of raw materials used. This results in products of inferior quality thus affecting customer perception about the SHG.

Lack of Vision and Professionalism: Members of SHGs are mostly semi-literate or illiterate and are ignorant of basic rules pertaining to the formation and conduct of SHGs. This lack of awareness is further compounded by their myopic vision. Beyond immediate financial gains, they are blind towards the vast potential of what they can achieve through a SHG. Usually, running the business is of low priority for many members during festivals and vacation periods in spite of high demand. This lack of professionalism adversely impacts the SHG's business.

Inadequate Training Facilities: The training facilities given to the members of SHGs in the specific areas of product selection, quality of products, production techniques, managerial ability, packing, other technical knowledge etc are not adequate to compete with that of strong units.

Problems Related with Raw Materials: Normally each SHG procures raw materials individually from the suppliers. They purchase raw materials in smaller quantities and hence they may not be able to enjoy the benefits of large scale purchase like discount, credit facilities etc. Moreover, there is no systematic arrangement to collect raw materials in bulk quantities and preserve them properly. There is no linkage with major suppliers of raw materials. Most of the SHGs are Ignorant about the major raw material suppliers and their terms and conditions. All these causes high cost of raw materials.

Lack of Stability and Unity Especially among women SHGs: In the case of SHGs dominated by women, it is found that there is no stability of the units as, many married women are not in a position to associate with the group due to the shift of their place of residence. Moreover, there is no unity among women members owing to personal reasons.

Exploitation by Strong Members: It is also observed that in the case of many SHGs, strong members try to earn a lion's share of the profit of the group, by exploiting the ignorance and illiterate members.

Weak Financial Management: It is also found that in certain units the return from the business is not properly invested further in the units, and the funds diverted for other personal and domestic purposes like marriage, construction of house etc.

Low Return: The return on investment is not attractive in certain groups due to inefficient management, high cost of production, absence of quality consciousness etc.

Inadequate Financial Assistance: It is found that in most of the SHGs, the financial assistance provided to them by the agencies concerned is not adequate to meet their actual requirements. The financial authorities are not giving adequate subsidy to meet even the labour cost requirements.

Non-co-operative Attitude of the Financial Institutions: The Financial Institutions do not consider SHGs seriously while providing finance and other help.

Suggestions to Minimize the Problems Faced by SHGs

- It is necessary that govt. may form a regularity authority to monitor the functions of the SHGs especially in income generation and in social activities in all areas.

- Govt. through the panchayat could provide training of the group member in producing consumable goods. The product of the group could be marked in the town area by providing rent -free govt. building.
- Meetings and seminar may be organized where the member will get a chance to exchange their views and be able to develop their group strength by interactions.
- The members should be given necessary training and guidance for the successful operation of the group.

Conclusion: In most of the developing countries today, more and more emphasis is laid on the need for women's active participation in the main stream development progress. Women's empowerment can not be ignored while devising various policies for rural and socio-economic development . in this regard the SHGs can play a vital role. As there are many challenges faced by SHGs but they also enhance the equality of status of women as participants, decision maker and beneficiaries in the democratic, economic, social and cultural spheres of life. So long the self -help group has played a major role in the awareness creating and economic upliftment of women.

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A Study on Socio-Economic Development in Nizamabad District

YarlagaddaSrinivasu*

Abstract

According to World Bank 2017, nearly 68.84 % of the population lives in the rural parts of the country. It is therefore essential that the government pushes forward and develops sustainable infrastructure as an economic enabler. These infrastructure facilities do not just create a strong economy but also they facilitate rural people more efficient so that they can be more productive with their time.

This research study is based upon the empirical survey of geographical area known as Nizamabad district in the state of Telangana, India. This study tries to examine the impact of infrastructural development on the Economic and Social development in rural areas. The justification of this study comes from the fact that this study will help in understanding the relation between infrastructural development and economic and social development.

Introduction

In the recent years, India has been the most prominent developing and fast growing economies of the world. India's economic growth, primarily in the manufacturing and services sector which has improved the country's growth both within the country and overseas.

The overall development of Indian economy is dependent on the some of the major infrastructure sectors such as power, roads and bridges, dams etc. Because of its fast growth and sustainable economic progress, infrastructure sector has also attracted foreign investors. Government of India estimates to invest over \$100 billion on developing country's infrastructure every year as a significant number of industries directly or indirectly depend on this sector. Therefore, growth in India is unimaginable without the backbone of infrastructure sector.

As demand for critical infrastructure has considerably grown, the country's constant growth has shown good results well beyond its ability to deliver the necessary number of power generation plants, housing and waste management, drainage and garbage collection facilities, availability of drinking water etc.

According to World Bank 2017, nearly 68.84 % of the population lives in the rural parts of the country. It is therefore essential that the government pushes forward and develops sustainable infrastructure as an economic enabler. These infrastructure facilities do not just create a strong economy but also they facilitate rural people more efficient so that they can be more productive with their time.

However, due to improper and inadequate infrastructure facilities in the rural areas the GDP contribution from the rural sector has always been lower. Hence, it is important to encourage reverse migration to the rural areas by developing and providing basic amenities for human survival in remote parts of the country. Rural infrastructure is not only an important element for rural villages development but also an important ingredient in ensuring sustainable

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poverty reduction. The systematic development of infrastructure in rural areas improves rural economy and quality of life in masses.

Literature review

The concept of infrastructure is often used to define economic development, yet a proper definition of infrastructure is still debatable. Sometimes the term is interchangeably used to define 'Social Overheads', 'Economic Overheads', 'Overhead Capital', 'Basic economic facilities' etc. The concept of 'overhead capital' was first used by author H.W. Singer who identified it with certain kinds of investments that are necessary or development. To quote him: "Any economic system requires a certain number of installations or capital formation which is not itself directly productive, which is in the nature of an overhead cost, there are certain overhead installations which must be present to enable production to take place, but which do not themselves directly result in the production of useable goods".

In recent literature, the term infrastructure is used to define economic or social development in order to distinguish the types of infrastructure. Author North has listed banking, insurance, tele-communicating facilities, storage, a distribution system for imports and roads connecting the rural area with major ports or regions across the nation. Healey in addition he has enclosed soil speech, minor irrigation, irrigation and control, power, railways, roads, ports, civil, air, transport, posts, communication and water distribution systems.

Kindleberger in his study makes a distinction between economic and social overhead capital. He identifies transportation majorly includes ports, roads, railroads, electricity and gas production capacity, pipe line, transmission lines, communication network and also buildings needed for government, fire and police protection facilities to maintain roads, etc. In his study, author Shah has made a broader categorization of infrastructure as, viz., power, irrigation, transport, communication, education, research and development, health and other facilities. Often infrastructure is divided into two broad categories, viz., economic and social. Other authors such as Rosenstein Rodan have made the classification based on different stages of development, i.e., development and rehabilitative.

The economic aspects of the rural development plan aim at the economic well-being of the rural population particularly improvements related to their livelihood, availability of resources and economic development.

- Agricultural Productivity
- Land Improvement
- Minor Irrigation
- Animal Husbandry
- Fisheries
- Minor Forest Products, etc.

The social aspects aim at welfare of the people, provision of good education facilities, health services, recreational facilities, etc. and change in social customs, practices and attitudes of the people. These can be listed as follows:

- Rural Housing
- Drinking Water
- Rural Electrification
- Education
- Technical and Vocational Education

- Adult & Non-formal Education
- Family Welfare
- Women & Child Development, etc.

Research Methodology

This research study is based upon the empirical survey of geographical area known as Nizamabad district in the state of Telangana, India. Nizamabad district is a particularly famous princely district in Telangana State located at a distance of about one hundred seventy five kms from North-West of the capital town of Hyderabad. The administration of Nizamabad is divided into three zones: Nizamabad North, Nizamabad South and Nizamabad Rural Division. This constitutes an area of 0.795 million hectares covering 27 mandals which include over 438 villages.

Justification of the Study

Right from the Independence, agriculture has been on the top of list for every government and rural development has been one of the top priorities. This study tries to examine the impact of infrastructural development on the Economic and Social development in rural areas. The justification of this study comes from the fact that this study will help in understanding the relation between infrastructural development and economic and social development.

Research Objective

This paper focuses on the objective:

- To study the existing rural development scenario in Nizamabad District.

Scope of the Study

This study covers four mandals Yedapally, Bodhan, Kotagiri and Varni from Nizamabad district. Two villages from each mandal totalling eight villages Taglepalli, Bellal, Erappally, Kallur, Kodcharla, Kurnapally, Mangalpahad and Sankora were studied.

Research Design

This research is exploratory in nature as it explores and attempts to identify patterns in the existing situation in rural area focusing on infrastructural, economic and social development. The study depends heavily on secondary data from various sources including panchayat records, district planning offices, revenue records etc.

Analysis

Descriptive statistics helped us in identifying the variables at a micro level and the existing scenario at a macro level. The data has been collected from eight villages pertaining to four mandals of Nizamabad district. For a simple and better understanding of the data, descriptive statistics are presented on time plots as the data pertains to seventeen years i.e. 2001 to 2017. The socio-economic activities covered in this current study are agriculture, housing, livestock, employment, savings, factories and private vehicle ownerships.

Figure1: Graph depicting the growth of socio-economic activities for Taglepalli village

From the above diagram we can see that agriculture production has remained moreover same over the seventeen years. A similar pattern can be seen for housing too. Live stock has been moreover turbulent and a declining pattern can be seen. Interestingly, private vehicles have risen phenomenally. Employment in government offices has risen marginally along with people savings.

Figure 2: Graph depicting the growth of socio-economic activities for Bellal village

The above plot demonstrates the mean values for the village Bellal from the years 2001 to 2017. It could be seen that the total agriculture production between the years 2001 to 2017 has been vastly unchanging. However, over the 17 years the total no. of houses, employment in government offices, total people savings and total vehicles has shown a steady increase. Interestingly, the total livestock for the village Bellal has initially shown a increasing pattern in the early 2000s and had started to decline by the mid-2000s.

Figure 3: Graph depicting the growth of socio-economic activities for Erajpally village

The above plot demonstrates the mean values for the village Erajpally from the years 2001 to 2017. It could be seen that the total agriculture production between the years 2001 to 2017 has been vastly unchanging. The total no. of houses has increased marginally in line with total people savings. On the other hand, employment in government offices and total vehicles remained same throughout the decade (from 2001-2010) and showed a marginal increase from 2013 onwards. Interestingly, the total livestock shows a steep rise between the years 2001 to 2002. However, the livestock could be seen to decline by 2005 and eventually plunge rapidly.

Figure 4: Graph depicting the growth of socio-economic activities for Kallur village

The above plot demonstrates the mean values for the village Kallur from the years 2001 to 2017. It could be seen that the total agriculture production between the years 2001 to 2017 has been vastly unchanging. Interestingly, the total no. of houses, total people savings, employment in government offices & total vehicles has vastly remained the same and showed only marginal growth between the years 2010 to 2017. The total livestock, on the other hand, showed a steady growth until 2005 and started to rapidly decline thereafter.

Figure 5: Graph depicting the growth of socio-economic activities for Kodcharla village

The above plot demonstrates the mean values for the village Kodcharla from the years 2001 to 2017. It could be seen that the total agriculture production between the years 2001 to 2017 has been vastly unchanging. Interestingly, the total no. of houses, total people savings, employment in government offices & total vehicles has also remained more or less the same throughout the years. The total livestock, on the other hand, steeply increased in the early 2000s and continued to stumble downwards by the year 2005.

Figure 6: Graph depicting the growth of socio-economic activities for Kurnapally village

The above plot demonstrates the mean values for the village Kurnapally from the years 2001 to 2017. It could be seen that the total agriculture production between the years 2001 to 2017 has been vastly unchanging. Interestingly, the total no. of houses slightly declined in 2007 but the growth returned and stayed stable up until 2017. Whereas employment in government offices & total vehicles remained more or less the same and showed marginal increase starting year 2014. The total livestock, on the other hand, steadily increased between the years 2001 to 2006 but soon rapidly declined up until 2009. However, by year 2010 the total livestock projected an upward trend and increased gradually.

Figure 7: Graph depicting the growth of socio-economic activities for Mangalpahad village

The above plot demonstrates the mean values for the village Mangalpahad from the years 2001 to 2017. It could be seen that the total agriculture production between the years 2001 to 2017 has been vastly unchanging. Interestingly, the total no. of houses and employment in government offices remained stable as well. The total vehicles remained the same and showed marginal increase in the mid-2000s. The total livestock, on the other hand, showed a declining trend during the early 2000s with a brief growth period between 2002-2014. However, the total livestock continued the downward trend between the years 2015-2017.

Figure 8: Graph depicting the growth of socio-economic activities for Sankora village

The above plot demonstrates the mean values for the village Sankora from the years 2001 to 2017. It could be seen that the total agriculture production between the years 2001 to 2017 has been vastly unchanging. By 2016, the total no. of houses decreased slightly and the employment in government offices remained stable throughout. The total vehicles showed marginal increase by early 2010. The total livestock, on the other hand, showed a declining trend starting the early 2000s up until 2017.

Conclusion

Rural development has been on the country's agenda since independence. Further development is a continuous process. However care has to be taken at the pace of development, as too slow or too fast development will destroy the basic essence of rural areas. In this perspective, it becomes imperative that research should continue on rural areas and from various perspectives. This research is from one perspective i.e. the impact of infrastructure development on economic and social development.

The study was conducted in eight villages belonging to four mandals of Nizamabad district. It would be useful to include other villages, mandals, districts and states in a future study may be undertaken, especially given that India is a vast country with a population of more than 1.2 billion (approx.), 117 officially recognized languages, 29 states, 7 union territories 5412 mandals and 649481 villages. Further studies can study other factors like technological, cultural, political and legal development.

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Human Resource Accounting And Its Disclosure: A Debatable Concept

CA. Ajay Dogra*

Abstract

For any Organization irrespective of its size the requirement of basic resources such as money, material, machine, man etc. is inevitable. No source can be placed at upper importance in comparison to other. These resources are interdependent and the operations and activities cannot be carried if there is absence of any of these resources. Money is required to buy machine, a machine requires material to operate and above all a human being is needed to carry out all these activities. So we can say that "Human Being" is one of the most significant resource in any organization. But here comes the dilemma for such "most significant" resource whereby every other resource such as money, material and machine has given an appropriate place in the accounting system to record and recognize but not human resource/personnel. However few organizations have started recording and recognizing it but the matter becomes debatable as many scholars, unions, employees etc think that human resources are no doubt valuable but their worth cannot be measured as other resources such as material, machine and money. This research paper tries to focus on not so new practice of accounting for human resources and how much it is possible, ethical and genuine.

Keywords: HRA, Methods, Accounting Standards, IFRS, Disclosure.

Introduction

Number of accounting fields are there for recording business activities as per the nature of transactions such as Financial Accounting for recording basic accounting information like journal entries, ledgers, trial balance, profit and loss account and balance sheet; Corporate Accounting for valuation of shares, goodwill, amalgamation, banking companies accounts etc; Management Accounting for marginal costing, standard costing, responsibility accounting; Cost Accounting for unit and output costing, batch and process costing etc. Every discipline of accounting however follows the basic principles of accounting provided by various accounting bodies all over the world. The common things in all these are that they record all transactions which are of monetary nature. But the question arises among all one resource left which is of utmost importance in any organization that is "personnel" left recorded and recognized because of it being in non-monetary nature. To resolve this issue a concept which is still in revolutionised phase "Human Resource Accounting" develops.

Few definitions:

The American Accounting Association's Committee on Human Resource Accounting as "the process of identifying and measuring data about human resources and communicating this information to interested parties".

Flamholtz (1971) defined it as "the measurement and reporting of the cost and value of the people in organizational resources".

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Thus we can conclude that Human Resource Accounting is that accounting which deals with identifying, recording and recognizing the investment made in human resources and the relative worth of personnel to the organization. The concept of Human Resource Accounting need was felt way back somewhere in 1960's as human relationship management was then starts considering important.

Now the question arises can an organization is truly and reliably able to calculate the cost and worth of human resource because it is a subjective matter and one cannot measure it precisely. But does that mean that it cannot be measured? The answer to this debatable question is different for different people and their opinions.

Many people is of the opinion that human resource is a valuable resource thus they are "assets" for the organization because an asset is a resource that brings long term economic benefits to the organization so does the human resource. Now the opinions against this theory propagates that Human resources are not like money, material, machine etc. that have monetary and quantitative characteristics and therefore can not be measured and recorded. But subjective assessment can be made. Efforts have been made since ages to calculate, measures and recording of human resources.

There are two main approaches towards the valuation of human resources, one is cost approach which takes into account the acquisition and replacement cost of personnel and another one is value approach that considers the present value of future earning method, discounted future wage model etc.

Some Measures for the valuation of human resources

- ✓ **Historical Cost Method:** This method was developed by Rensis Likert . It takes into account all the cost of recruitment, training, development and considers all are of capital nature thereby should be write off over the period of service of the employee. In case the employee leave before the expected period, balance amount will be write off completely. This method has a major drawback that it considers only acquisition cost and ignores other factor such as skill and capabilities of employees.
- ✓ **Replacement Cost method :** Replacement cost is the cost arises when organization replaces an employee with another employee for same kind of services. Replacement involves recruitment cost, training and development cost, loss of work till the joining of new employee and thus opportunity cost for the organization.
- ✓ **Opportunity Cost Method:** This method was advocated by Hekimian and Jones . In this method heads of organization bids for the scarce employee they want and one who is able to acquire his services puts the bids price. Actual and expected rate of capitalization of earnings supposed to be earned by the employee is taken for the purpose of calculation. However this method suffer from a limitation of bid price being misleading or inaccurate.
- ✓ **Asset Multiplier Method:** four categories are used for the classification of employees i.e. top level, middle level, supervisory management, operative and clerical Staff. This method is based on the assumption that there is no direct relationship between value of an employee and the cost incurred because of the reasons that there value depends upon other factors such as attitude towards work, motivation, working conditions etc.
- ✓ **Discounted present value of future earning method:** In This method first employees are classified into same nature group based on age, nature of job, experience skills needed etc. then earnings of each group is estimated then calculation of present values of each group till retirement is made with the help of taking an appropriate discounting

rate. Companies such as ONGC, NTPC, MMTC, BHEL etc. uses this method for the valuation of human resources.

- ✓ **Expected realizable value method:** This method says that productivity, transferability and promotability can be measured through personnel research, appraisal techniques etc. Productivity can be measured by objective indices, promotability and transferability can be measured in terms of potential tests.

The above list not conclusive rather there are other methods also for the valuation of human resources. Many companies in India are currently using these discussed methods for such valuation purpose. These methods proves to be very significant and effective for the valuation purpose. Let us see its importance in Infosys Technologies Ltd.

HRA at INFOSYS TECHNOLOGIES LTD. (LEV and SCHWARTZ METHOD) **

The organization measures the net present value of an employee is calculated from the date of joining till the date of retirement on estimation basis. Some key points taken by Infosys are:

- All the employees of Infosys were divided into five groups based on their average age. For each group's average compensation was calculated.
- Infosys also calculated the compensation of each employee at retirement by using an average rate of increment.
- The increments were based on industry standards, employee's performance and productivity.
- Finally the total compensation Of each group was calculated and discounted at the rate percent per annum which was the cost of capital at Infosys to arrive at the total human resources of Infosys.
- Infosys could determine whether its human asset appreciating over the years or not. This information was important for the company as its success depended totally on the knowledge of the employees.
- The company could also use this information internally to compare the performances and productivity of employees in various departments.
- HRA also helped Infosys to decide the compensation of employees and in identifying and retaining valuable employees.
- It helped organization to take managerial decisions based on the availability and the necessity of human resources.
- When human resources get quantified it gave Infosys investors and other clients true insight into the organization and its future potential. It restored faith among shareholders.
- By adopting HRS the following information could be obtained: (1) cost per employee (2) human capital investment ratio (3) the amount of wealth created by each employee (4) the profit created by each employee (5) the ratio of total salary paid to the total revenue generated.

***Source: [http://www.scribd.com/doc/211743874/HRA- in Infosys](http://www.scribd.com/doc/211743874/HRA-in-Infosys)

Concluding Remarks

In India there are number of accounting standards (old) and new Indian accounting standards which governs the treatment of accounts and their presentation to bring out uniformity, transparency and reliability of financial statements, but till date there is no accounting standard prescribed by Institute of Chartered Accountants of India or by Accounting Standard board which provides the accounting standards to be used for the accurate recording and presentation of human resources in financial statements. In fact the international Financial Reporting Standards (IFRS) does not provide for the treatment and placement of human resources in the balance sheet. In fact with the availability of so many methods for valuation, employees and unions sometimes do not like the idea as they think "their measurement" shows that they are like other resources and assigning them with values ("numbers") brings down their morale.

Thus there is one approach which considers that human resources are "valuable assets" for any organization and another one is that considers that a human being cannot be termed as "asset" like other in an organization and thereby cannot be assigned values. Hence in my opinion it creates a PARADOX. Human resource accounting is still in revolutionary stage and trying to developed a more systematic and scientific method or solution for the problem. Still in the absence of specifically designed accounting principles and accounting standards we cannot place human resource in balance sheet. However many organizations shows the human resource data in their annual report.

Hoping for more accurate, unbiased, scientific and universally accepted law or methods that govern the recognition and disclosure of human resources in companies accounts.

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FMCG Industry In India: An Analysis

Amritpal Kaur*

Abstract

This study is undertaken with an objective to highlight the changing trends in FMCG industry in India. The study is a conceptual one and based on secondary data. Having an excellent distribution network is one of the strengths of FMCG sector. So this paper is carrying an in-depth study in dynamics of distribution and the trends in FMCG industry along with its achievements and also Government role in promoting FMCG sector of India.

Keywords: - FMCG, Distribution network , Government Initiatives

Introduction

FMCG refers to consumer non- durables goods required for daily or frequent use. The sector covers a wide gamut of products such as detergents, toilet soaps, toothpaste and shampoos.

Typical characteristics of FMCG products

- Significant part of consumer's budget.
- The customer prefers to purchase them frequently because of perishable nature of many of the products. The customers spend little time on the buying decision.
- These products meet the demand of the entire cross section of the population because these products cater to the necessities comforts as well as luxuries.

The FMCG sector has been the cornerstone of the Indian Economy. Though the sector has been in existence for quite a long time it began to take shape only during the last sixty years. The sector touches every aspect of life from looks to hygiene to palate. Perhaps defining an industry whose scope is so vast is not easy.

The Indian Fast moving consumer goods(FMCG) sector is the fourth largest sector in the economy with a total market size in excess of US \$13.1 billion.

Trends

- ***Global base*** Major global consumer product companies(such as Unilever P&G Colgate Nestle Heinz) have a lion share of the global market .These companies have been established for a very long time and possess a clutch of strong brands with popularity technology. Most of these companies are cash rich and well managed. Their brands generate strong cash flows and allow promotions/advertisements(*Harvard Business Review sep. Oct. 2014*).These maintain their edge in the business.
- ***Adapting to local conditions*** In the last two decades process of adapting to local conditions has accelerated. MNC's are adapting their products process and marketing communication to the local conditions. They alter the manufacturing process to maximize use of local raw materials and suit their products to the taste and preferences of local consumers.
- ***Packaging*** The role of packaging has increased significantly in recent times. Traditionally packaging was expected to serve the purpose of protection then packaging was expected to fulfil the objection of convenience (*Kotler Philip 2003*). Today

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packaging is used as an effective tool for promotion. Besides new packaging technology has enabled most FMCG companies to significantly reduce their packaging cost.

- **Distribution network** In FMCG sector one of the most critical success factor is the ability to build develop and maintain a robust distribution network. Availability near the customer is vital for wider penetration as most products are low unit value products and frequently purchased. Distribution network refers to the consumer buying points where products are available. It takes establish their loyalties (*Poirer C. Charles 2004*). Thus distribution is the critical factor that at times even drives the brand equity factor.
- **Market Size** The retail market in India is estimated to reach US \$ 1.1 trillion by 2020 from US \$ 840 billion in 2017 with modern trade expected to grow at 20% to 25% p.a. which is likely to boost revenues of FMCG companies. Revenues of FMCG sector reached RS. 3.4 lakh crore in FY 2018 and are estimated to reach US \$ 103.7 billion in 2020. The sector witnessed growth of 16.5% in value terms between July-sep 2018 supported by modern inflation increase in private consumption and rural income.
- **Investments/developments** The Government has allowed 100% FDI in food processing and single brand retail and 51% in multi-brand retail. This would bolster employment and supply chains and also provide high visibility for FMCG brands in organised retail markets bolstering consumer spending and encouraging more product launches .The sector witnessed healthy FDI inflows of US \$14.42 billion during April 2000 to dec 2018. Some of the recent developments in FMCG sector are as follows:-
 - In FY 2019 ITC made more than 60 launches in FMCG segment in India.
 - In Feb. 2019 India's leading FMCG contract manufacturer Hindustan foods limited received investment of US \$ 22 million from Convergent Finance LLP.
 - Patanjali will spend US \$ 743.72 million in various food parks in Maharashtra Madhya Pradesh Assam Andhra Pradesh and Uttar Pradesh.
 - In May 2018 RP-Sanjiv Goenka Group created a Rs. 1 billion (US \$ 14.92 million) venture capital fund to invest in FMCG start-ups.
 - In August 2018 Fonterra announced a joint venture with future consumer limited which will produce a range of consumer and foodservice dairy products.
- **Government Initiatives** Some of the Major initiatives taken by government to promote the FMCG sector in India are as follows:-
 - The minimum capitalisation rate for foreign FMCG companies to invest in India is US \$ 100 million.
 - The Government of India has approved 100% FDI in the cash and carry segment and in single brand retail along with 51% FDI in multi-brand retail.
 - The GST is beneficial for the FMCG industry as many of the FMCG products such as soap, toothpaste and hair oil now come under 18% tax bracket against the previous 23-24% rate.
- **Achievements** Following are the achievements of the Government in the past four years concerned with FMCG industry:-
 - Number of Mega food parks increased from 2 during, 2008-2014 to 13 during 2014-2018.
 - Preservation and processing capacity increased 308000 during 2008-14 to 1.41 million during 2014-2018.
 - The number of food labs increased from 31 during 2008-14 to 42 during 2014-18.

- **Road Ahead** Rural consumption has increased led by a combination of increase in income and higher aspiration levels. There is an increased demand for branded products in rural India.
- The rural FMCG market in India is expected to grow to US \$ 220 billion by 2025 from US \$ 23.6 billion in FY 2018.
- Another major factor propelling the demand for food services in India is the growing Youth population. India has a large base of young consumers who form the majority of workforce and due to time constraints they barely get time for cooking.
- Online portals are expected to play a key role for companies trying to enter the hinterlands. The outline FMCG market is forecasted to reach US \$ 45 billion in 2020 from US \$ 20 billion in 2017.

Findings of the study

- One Major finding is that while branding differentiates the image of the product the distribution network will determine its success to a large extent.
- Rural markets would be the cornerstone of all FMCG strategies in the near future.
- Online portals proved a boom for FMCG sector.
- Government has a soft eye towards FMCG sector and FDI has contributed a lot to its growth and a lot more is there to do.

Conclusion On the basis of the above study it can be concluded that the distribution management has emerged from back benches of the marketing discipline that is all set to become a specialized area of expertise critical to the success of any brand. Today it seems that IT cannot be separated from any discipline or function. IT enables integration of disparate process successfully. Demand for quality goods and services have been going up in the rural areas of India on the back of improved distribution of FMCG companies.

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Analysing the Recruiters' Perspectives on Employability Skills of Management Graduates in North-East India

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Abstract

This study focuses on the expectations of the recruiters in the field of different employability skills and how far these skills have been fulfilled by the students during the campus placement drive by the recruiters. From the study we found that out of the main attributes of Knowledge, Skill and Attitude, the sub-attributes had varied mean scores. The mean score shows that the students have not achieved the bench mark set by the recruiters in the field of Business Environment under the domain of knowledge. The mean score shows that the students have not achieved the bench mark set by the recruiters in the field of Managerial skills. Out of 3 skills, which shows that the students have achieved only 67% of the bench mark set for various skills, whereas, the mean scores shows that the students have not achieved the bench mark set by the recruiters in the field of Commitment and Dedication and High Thinking and Creativity under the main attribute of attitude. The students have achieved only 33% of the bench mark as set for attitude.

Keywords: Employability, Skills, Knowledge, Attitude, Recruiters, North-East India

Introduction

Employability skills are very valuable and essential for every job seeker to seek the employment into a new world of work, which is of mainly basic and generic in nature. These skills are transferable in nature and also known as non-technical soft skills which are also refer as core employability skills (Robinson, 2006). The recruiters prefer those skills which help to solve the problems independently and able to supervise the work effectively in an organization and they also expect that management graduate should have the additional skills of team work, risk taking, networking abilities and continuous learning habits to face the flexibility and uncertainties in the organization (Asuquo and Inaja 2013). Employers also prefer the candidates having the capability to own the responsibility beyond the expectations of the organization. It is very essential to equip with practical knowledge about the Industry along with the academic knowledge, which students are lacking.

The recruiter also gives more emphasis to the speaking and listening quality of an employee apart from the other employability skills like supervision, coordinating, managing the conflicts as these skills are basis for application of other important skills (Andelt et al. 1997). The new emerging trends of the industries have changed the expectation of employer and they not only confine to the academic or technical performance but expect a new set of knowledge requires for innovative approaches to meet the competencies needed by the employers.

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In the recent years, the government is giving special attention to develop the North-Eastern part of India and many big corporate houses are also spreading their business wings, formidable among them belongs to the industries related to Banking, Insurance, Telecommunications and Hospitality. Hence, there is a demand for more and more management professionals to run the show. To take the benefit of the situation, there is an immediate need to study the gap between the desired skill and the value added skill by the management institutes of the North-Eastern region of India. This study focuses on the expectations of the recruiters in the field of different employability skills and how far these skills have been fulfilled by the students during the campus placement drive by the employers.

Review of Literature

Employability skills are representing the essential knowledge, skills and attitudes for operational requirement and successful career achievement in an organization, but there are certain core skills which are also essential like honesty, punctuality, loyalty, reliability to perform the duty in an organization and these skills are not separable from the organizational needs (Overtoom, 2000).

Peddle (2000) has also stated that changing environment of an organization require various types of skills to enhance the employability of an employee and also the combination of basic skills like information and communication skills, interpersonal skills, motivation skills, knowledge of basic arithmetic, writing and reading plays important role to support enhancing the skills. Rubin & Dierdorff (2009), in their study found that the curriculum of business management course often fails to provide managerial skill which a management graduate is expected to apply in real life problem solving cases.

The current business environment is dynamic and looking to the changing scenario of job market, employers prefer to recruit professionally qualified person for the growth and sustainability of the business. In this context, Jabeen (2011) studied the mismatch between graduating university students' perception and employers' expectations regarding skills that qualify them to be employed and found significant differences between employer's expectations and students' perceptions about the needed skills. More importantly discipline positive attitude, punctuality, time management and oral communications are the skills highly ranked by the employers that are significant.

Based on the above explanations, it is important to discuss about bench mark of the different employability skill set by the recruiters and how far these bench mark of the skills have been achieved by the student during the campus placement drive by the recruiters.

Objective of the Study

To measure the skill and competency gap between the employers' expectation and the performance of fresh management graduates in the NE Region.

Hypothesis

The following hypothesis has been framed:

H₀: There is no significant difference in the skill and competency as per industry expectation and the performance of fresh management graduates.

Method and Design

The list of the employer visiting the institutes for campus placement has been collected from individual institutes. The potential recruiters have been identified from the placement brochure of the respective institutes. In selecting the sample size from the population in case of companies, purposive sampling has been adopted. On the basis of the trend of last

five years frequency of company placements by the respective institutes, the following population and sample estimate has been considered for the study.

Table 1

S.No	Name of Recruiters	Population	Sample Size
1	Private Banks	6	3
2	Private Insurance Companies	7	3
3	Private Telecom Companies	4	3
	Total	17	9

Analysis Tools

After proper tabulation of data, statistical tools were used for the analysis purpose. SPSS software version 20 was used for the overall analysis of the data. The data collected from the corporate recruiters is less than 30 and hence t-test was considered. The comparison made between the expectation of recruiters and actual level of students' was found by analysis of paired t-test.

Framing the Research Questionnaire

The information from the recruiters has been collected about the parameters and bench mark of various factors set to test the skills and competencies required for selection of fresh management graduates and we found that the knowledge, skills and attitude approach were considered by the recruiters as shown in the following set of variables references:

Knowledge:- Knowledge of planning and organizing, Knowledge of market competition and organizational process, products, knowledge of organizational changes and development, Domain knowledge in the Specialized area, Accounting information, Knowledge of business analysis of a company, Implementation of information technology to present business system, Knowledge of various policies and Acts related to business, Knowledge of international business opportunities and globalization (Siriwaiprapan , 2000; Lankard, 1990; Natarajan, 2012; Murphy, 2001; Tariq and Cochrane, 2003; Tomkins, 2004; Hasan, 1993).

Skill: Effective writing and verbal communication, Quantitative aptitude skills, Basic information and technological skills, The ability to function effectively in the capacity of a leader or manager, Applying professionalism in the workplace, Identification of problem and finding out the solution, Willingness to take risk, Presentation and analysis of cases, Decision making skill based on information and documentation (Robinson, 2006; Lankard, 1990; Natarajan, 2012; Byrnes, 1965; Murphy, 2001; Tariq and Cochrane, 2003; Siriwaiprapan, 2000; Tomkins, 2004).

Attitude: Self- discipline and punctuality, Integrity and Accountability, Positive attitude and willingness to learn overall work culture, Self-motivation and dedication, Understanding of professional and ethical commitment, Taking initiative and responsibility, Generating the new ideas and application of knowledge and skills to find out the solution for unfamiliar problems, Strategic thinking, Strategic planning and implementation, Flexibility in planning and tolerance towards the ambiguity (Hasan, 1993; Bikson, 1994; Stasz, McArthur, Lewis & Ramsey, 1990; Siriwaiprapan, 2000; Bikson & Law, 1995).

Reliability Test

Cronbach Alpha test has been considered to measure the reliability of the questions and we can see that the value of Cronbach Alpha to be more than 0.7 in each cases and it was acceptable by the researchers in order to test the reliability of the questionnaire. A

Cronbach's alpha coefficient of .70 and above indicates a high degree of internal consistency among the data collected (Kline, 1999; George, 2003).

Table 2: Table showing Recruiters' Expected and Actual Results on Knowledge, Skills and Attitude

S.No	Attributes	No of Item	Cronbach Alpha
1	Knowledge Expected by Recruiters from Students	9	0.959
2	Actual Knowledge Found by Recruiters from Students	9	.840
3	Skill Expected by Recruiters from Students	9	0.941
4	Actual Skill Found by Recruiters from Students	9	0.790
5	Attitude Expected by Recruiters from Students	9	0.882
6	Actual Attitude Found by Recruiters from Students	9	0.735

Source: Primary data

Data Analysis

Table 3: Paired Sample t-test

S.No	Main Skills		Sub-Skills	Sig. (2-tailed)	Result Significant or non-Significant Rejection of Null Hypothesis
1	Knowledge	1A	Understanding the Organization	.500	Not Significant
		1B	Domain Knowledge	.708	Not Significant
		1C	Business Environment	.037	Significant
2	Skill	2A	Basic Employability Skill	.403	Not Significant
		2B	Interpersonal Skills	.386	Not Significant
		2C	Managerial Skills	.038	Significant
3	Attitude	3A	Personal Attitude	.288	Not Significant
		3B	Commitment and Dedication	.011	Significant
		3C	High Thinking & Creativity	.261	Not Significant

Source: Primary data

Null Hypothesis H0: There is no significant difference in the knowledge regarding understanding the organization as per industry expectation and the performance of fresh management graduates.

Results of paired t-test 1A (Understanding the Organization):

From paired t-test p-value is calculated at .50, which is more than standard value 0.05. Therefore, we fail to reject the null hypothesis.

Null Hypothesis H0: There is no significant difference in the domain knowledge in specialized area as per industry expectation and the performance of fresh management graduates.

Results of paired t-test 1B (Domain Knowledge)

From paired t-test p-value is calculated at .708 which is more than standard value 0.05. Therefore we fail to reject the null hypothesis.

Null Hypothesis H₀: There is no significant difference in the knowledge regarding Business Environment as per industry expectation and the performance of fresh management graduates.

Results of paired t-test 1C (Business Environment)

From paired t-test p-value is calculated at .037 which is less than standard value 0.05. Therefore we reject the null hypothesis.

Null Hypothesis H₀: There is no significant difference in the Basic Employability Skill as per industry expectation and the performance of fresh management graduates.

Results of paired test 2A (Basic Employability Skill):

From paired t-test p-value is .403 which is greater than standard value 0.05. Therefore we fail to reject the null hypothesis.

Null Hypothesis H₀: There is no significant difference in the Interpersonal Skills as per industry expectation and the performance of fresh management graduates.

Results of pair test 2B (Interpersonal Skills)

From paired t-test p-value is calculated .386 which is greater than standard value 0.05. Therefore we fail to reject the null hypothesis and alternate hypothesis is rejected.

Null Hypothesis H₀: There is no significant difference in the managerial skills as per industry expectation and the performance of fresh management graduates.

Results of pair test 2C (Managerial Skills)

The mean scores of managerial skills between expected and actual are tested. The p-value is calculated .038 which is less than standard value 0.05. Therefore we reject the null hypothesis.

Null Hypothesis H₁: There is no significant difference in the personal attitude as per industry expectation and the performance of fresh management graduates

Results of pair test 3A (Personal Attitude)

From paired t-test the p-value is calculated at .288 which is greater than standard value 0.05. Therefore we fail to reject the null hypothesis.

Null Hypothesis H₀: There is no significant difference in the commitment and dedication as per industry expectation and the performance of fresh management graduates.

Results of paired t-test 3B (Commitment and Dedication)

From paired t-test the p-value was calculated at .011 which is less than standard value 0.05. Therefore we reject the null hypothesis.

Null Hypothesis H₀: There is no significant difference in the high thinking & creativity as per industry expectation and the performance of fresh management graduates.

Results of paired t-test 3C (High Thinking & Creativity)

From paired t-test, the p-value was calculated at .261 which is greater than standard value 0.05. Therefore we fail to reject the null hypothesis.

Findings

The benchmark for various skill and competency as considered by the recruiters for selection of the management graduates and actual skills as found during the campus placement were compared for each type of skills which are considered under various domain of knowledge, skill and attitude. The result of the analysis shows the following findings in Table 4.

Table 4: Table showing Bench mark of the Recruiters Achieved or Not Achieved

S.No	Main Attributes	Sub-attributes	Mean		Bench mark of the Recruiters Achieved or Not Achieved
			Bench mark set by the Recruiters	Actual Mean of Students found	
1	Knowledge	Understanding the Organization	12.6667	13.0000	Achieved
		Domain Knowledge	12.7778	13.0000	Achieved
		Business Environment	12.1111	10.4444	Not Achieved
2	Skill	Basic Employability Skill	12.7778	13.2222	Achieved
		Interpersonal Skills	12.2222	12.8889	Achieved
		Managerial Skills	12.7778	11.5556	Not Achieved
3	Attitude	Personal Attitude	12.6667	13.4444	Achieved
		Commitment and Dedication	12.3333	11.0000	Not Achieved
		High Thinking & Creativity	11.7778	10.8889	Not Achieved

Source: Primary data

From the study we found that out of the main attributes of Knowledge, Skill and Attitude, the sub-attributes had varied mean scores. The mean score shows that the students have not achieved the bench mark set by the recruiters in the field of Business Environment under the domain of knowledge. The mean score shows that the students have not achieved the bench mark set by the recruiters in the field of Managerial skill out of 3 skills, which shows that the students have achieved only 67% of the bench mark set for various skills. Whereas, the mean scores shows that the students have not achieved the bench mark set by the recruiters in the field of Commitment and Dedication and High Thinking & Creativity under the main skill of attitude. The students have achieved only 33% of the bench mark as set for attitude.

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An Empirical Study Of Financial Performance Of IOCL and HPCL- A Comparative Analysis

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Abstract

Oil and gas/gasoline is the most preferred form of fuel all the countries over the globe, and at the same time it is the economic driver. After America, China and Japan, India is at fourth place in terms of oil and gas consumption. HPCL and IOC (Hindustan Petroleum Corporation Limited and Indian Oil Corporation) are two major oil companies in India which are into production and distribution of oil and gas in the country. In the present study the researcher had tried to evaluate the financial performance of the above mentioned companies, in a view to get the parameters of financial performance for the oil companies and express the spread of business in terms of profit and liquidity. This present study is of exploratory nature and the trial of secondary data has been followed for last 10 years i.e. 2008-09 to 2018-19. The basic components of comparison are liquidity, solvency and efficiency ratio. Basic ratios of the above given parameters and t-test is used for analysis of data.

Keywords: Financial Performance, Multiple Regression Analysis.

Introduction

This is a well-known fact that more than 63% of the global energy needs are catered by petroleum products in the form of gas and oil. Beyond this there are other petroleum products also which are in extreme demand like, coal, natural gas, nuclear energy and hydroelectricity that constitutes to around 37% of the total demand and on the other hand there are some other important form of energy like wind energy, solar energy, dry wood, etc. constitutes to less than 1% of the total energy consumption and demand. After USA, China and Japan, India is at fourth place in terms of oil and gas consumption. As from the virtue of different international agencies like UNO and others, it is an established fact that the oil and natural gas are in the list of scarce resources so many of the developing countries like India are looking forward for alternate sources of energy including renewable energy. EIA (2014). Regardless of all the precautions taken by worldwide agencies, the overall consumption of oil is expected to grow by about 4% in the next 5 years and the consumption of natural gas is expected to grow by almost 3% for the same period.

Here in this present study the researcher had tried to judge the financial performance of the petroleum companies like HPCL and IOC and the results of this analysis are being normalized to rest of the companies.

Concept of Financial Performance

There are a number of benefits related to the evaluation of financial performance like for the sake of stakeholders of the company, management of the company and many others and at

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the far end it is somewhere related to business performance of the company in the near future. Then on the other hand it is also a tool to evaluate the difference between the financial objectives stated by the management of the company and the achievements made for the same.

This can be understood in terms of policies that a particular company frames, various parameters of financial performance use to provide the measurement of objectives stated in the policies and achievement of the same in terms of profits and other terms of financial growth. In such types of evaluation, time is an important factors, like evaluation of financial performance in the span of one year or so. Here it is very important to mention that the evaluation of financial performance also presents a comparison with other companies operating in the same industry.

HPCL (*Hindustan Petroleum Corporation Limited*)

HPCL was started in 1952 with the name of Standard Vacuum Refining Company of India Ltd. and after 10 years of its incorporation it was named as ESSO Standard Refining Company of India Ltd. then finally in the year 1974 it was named as HPCL. In the year 1976 Kosan Gas Company became the sister concern of HPCL and operated in the local LPG market then in the year 1978 Caltex Oil Company also was taken over by HPCL and in the due course of time it became the Navratna of Government of India and took place in the fortune 500 companies and listed on the BSE (*Bombay Stock Exchange*) and NSE (*National Stock Exchange*).

By the year 2015 HPCL became the industry leader with and also acquired 20% of market share and became one of the strongest PSUs of Indian origin with an burgeoning return of 2 lac crores.

IOC (*Indian Oil Corporation*)

IOC is one of the apex organizations in the field of oil and gas business. The range of operations includes refining, distribution, pipelines and exploration of oil and natural gas. Like HPCL this is also included in the fortune 500 companies of the world at the position of 83. The company is in operation for last 50 years. IOC is one of the prominent companies of Indian origin that has put a mark on the global horizons and is engaged in the components of refining, pipeline transportation and marketing of petroleum products to exploration & production of crude oil & gas, marketing of natural gas and petrochemicals. It is the leading Indian corporate in the Fortune 'Global 500' listing, ranked at the 83rd position in the year 2015 with an annual sale of about 4 lakh crores. IOC is not only operating in India rather it had spread its operations in Sri Lanka, UAE and even in Mauritius.

Literature Review

Ahmad et al (2015) the researcher stated that HPCL is in the practice of testing the effect of business governance on the performance and efficiency of the company in terms of profits and goodwill. The results of this testing process gave the favorable result and stated that the increased attention to the corporate governance of the company has increased the financial performance of the company and also the faith of various stakeholders of the company. The results of this study stated that for most of the organizations corporate governance is having positive effect on the financial performance of the company.

Kumar et al (2014) this study was based on the evaluation of financial performance of IOC for the period of 10 years. The researcher had considered debt and equity and compared the same with other companies in the industry. The respective ratio analysis of the study stated that except IOC none of the companies are focusing on raising of capital whereas IOC is

focusing on raising its capital by the way of debt capital and share capital and still able to increase the wealth of respective shareholders.

Taqi (2013) this study compares the financial performance of IOC and HPCL considering ratio analysis as a tool and a number of ratios like current ratio, WC turnover ratio were used for the same. The findings of the study stated that in terms of financial performance and increasing the wealth of shareholders, HPCL is a better company. HPCL is having a great thrust on increasing its capital by the way of share capital because by this way they can increase the capital and also the wealth of their shareholders.

Objectives of the Study

1. To know the important financial parameters of petroleum industry.
2. To evaluate the effect of macro environment on business of petroleum companies.
3. To compare the financial performance of IOC and HPCL.

Research Methodology

- As stated earlier, this is a study based on secondary data and the major sources of data are annual reports of the sampled companies and even the yearly and quarterly balance sheets for the year 2009 to 2018.
- This study undertook the data for last ten years i.e. 2008-2009 to 2017-2018.
- IOC and HPCL were considered as sample for the study,
- The tools used in the study include Correlation analysis and ratio analysis related to profitability.

Data Analysis and Interpretation

Profitability

This is a well-known fact that the ratios of profitability are undertaken to judge the financial efficiency of the company and in this present study following profitability ratios are used:

- Net profit ratio
- Return on capital employed
- Debt Equity ratio

Gross Profit Ratio

Gross profit ratio is calculated to measure the difference between the profit and cost of goods sold.

Table – 1: Gross Profit Ratio (in Percentage)

Year	HPCL	IOCL
2009	5.65	6.84
2010	6.29	8.01
2011	7.11	6.56
2012	7.97	6.65
2013	8.12	6.63
2014	7.55	7.93
2015	7.49	8.04
2016	5.73	7.15
2017	4.72	5.25
2018	5.03	7.37
Average	6.56	7.04
S. D	1.24	0.86
CV	19.3	11.42

As per the analysis shown in the above given table, it presents the evaluation of gross profit to sales, the minimum ratio of HPCL is 4.72 in the year 2017 and the maximum is 8.12 in 2013. The same for IOC is minimum 5.25 in 2017 and 8.04 in 2015 is maximum. As can be seen from the above table that the trend is not saturated it is fluctuating throughout the study period and this stands true for both the companies. Stating in terms of average, it is 6.6% for HPCL and 7% for IOC and we can state that IOC is a better company in terms of sales and gross profit.

Table 2: Gross Profit Ratio -'t' value

Group	t value	S/NS
IOC Vs HPCL	0.13	Not Significant
IOC Vs IOC (Year wise)	0.85	Not Significant
HPCL Vs HPCL (Year wise)	0.79	Not Significant

@ 5 % level. S – Significant NS - Not Significant

The result of 't' test shown in the above table states that the amount of variation in gross profit is significant enough to effect the financial operations of the company.

Net profit ratio

Net profit ratio is calculated to measure the difference between the net profit and actual sales. The decision rule states that if the ratio is high then the profitability of the firm is better and vice-versa.

Table – 3: Gross Profit Ratio (in Percentage)

Year	HPCL	IOCL
2009	2.27	3.03
2010	2.72	3.56
2011	3.18	2.77
2012	3.76	2.91
2013	3.73	2.55
2014	3.77	3.26
2015	3.69	3.55
2016	3.51	2.92
2017	2.40	2.43
2018	1.95	2.82
Average	3.04	3.17
S.D	0.70	0.38
CV	22.72	13.27

As per the analysis shown in the above given table, it presents the evaluation of net profit to sales, the minimum ratio of HPCL is 1.95 in the year 2018 and the maximum is 3.77 in 2014. The same for IOC is minimum 2.43 in 2017 and 3.56 in 2015 is maximum. As can be seen from the above table that the trend is not saturated it is fluctuating throughout the study period and this stands true for both the companies.

The average value for the given period is about 3.17% and 3.04% for HPCL and IOCL respectively.

The analysis given in the above table shows that HPCL is a better company in terms of NET profit.

Table 4: Net Profit Ratio -'t' value

Group	t value	S/NS
IOC Vs HPCL	1.43	Not Significant
HPCL Vs HPCL (Year wise)	1.02	Not Significant
IOCL Vs IOCL (Year wise)	0.7	Not Significant

The result of 't' test shown in the above table states that the amount of variation in net profit is significant enough to effect the financial operations of the company.

Net Profit to Total Assets

This ratio is an assessment of the phenomenon that the respective company is using its effectively to gain profit or not.

Table 5: Net Profit to Total Assets (in Percentage)

Year	HPCL	IOC
2009	7.14	3.98
2010	8.43	5.02
2011	9.98	6.01
2012	9.87	4.93
2013	7.98	5.12
2014	9.01	5.29
2015	10.95	7.10
2016	8.93	5.04
2017	6.97	5.29
2018	6.01	6.02
Average	9.02	4.98
S.D	2.09	0.82
CV	19.73	17.01

As per the analysis shown in the above given table, it presents the evaluation of net profit to Total assets, the minimum ratio of HPCL is 6.01 in the year 2018 and the maximum is 10.95 in 2015. The same for IOC is minimum 3.98 in 2009 and 7.10 in 2015 is maximum. As can be seen from the above table that the trend is not saturated it is fluctuating throughout the study period and this stands true for both the companies.

The average value for the given period is about 9.02% and 4.98% for HPCL and IOCL respectively.

The analysis given in the above table shows that HPCL is a better company in terms of using its assets to gain profitability.

Table 6: Net Profit to total assets -'t' value

Group	t value	S/NS
BPCL Vs HPCL	1.31	Not Significant
HPCL Vs HPCL (Year wise)	4.97	Significant
IOCL Vs IOCL (Year wise)	4.6	Significant

The result of 't' test shown in the above table states that the amount of variation in net profit is significant enough to effect the financial operations of the company.

Table 7: Correlation Matrix - HPCL

	NFA	IS	IN	RC	C/B	MSA	TA
NFA	1.000	0.715	0.892	0.801	-0.409	-0.512	0.859
IS		1.000	0.473	0.321	-0.162	-0.198	0.785
IN			1.000	0.854	-0.408	-0.437	0.967
RC				1.000	0.347	-0.097	0.981
C/B					1.000	0.732	-0.138
MSA						1.000	-0.319
TA							1.000

NFA-Net Fixed Assets, IS-Investment, IN-Inventory, RC-Receivables, C/B-Cash/Bank, MSA-Miscellaneous Assets, TA-Total Assets

As can be seen from the above table that in case of HPCL there is a significant degree of positive correlation between the components of TA, RC and C/B and on the other hand there is not a significant positive correlation of higher degree between MSA and C/B. This shows that all the other variables are having independent slopes and are not subject to change in the same direction of MSA and C/B.

The evaluation of the above table shows that in all TA, RC, IN and NFA are of great importance for HPCL.

Table 8: Correlation Matrix – IOCL

	NFA	IS	IN	RC	C/B	MSA	TA
NFA	1.00	0.542	0.893	0.742	0.862	0.831	0.857
IS		1.000	0.297	0.187	0.234	0.472	0.547
IN			1.000	0.892	0.864	0.832	0.912
RC				1.000	0.931	0.814	0.831
C/B					1.000	0.820	0.904
MSA						1.000	0.931
TA							1.000

NFA-Net Fixed Assets, IS-Investment, IN-Inventory, RC-Receivables, C/B-Cash/Bank, MSA-Miscellaneous Assets, TA-Total Assets

As can be seen from the above table that in case of IOC there is a significant degree of positive correlation between the component of TA with other stated variables and MSA is having a high degree of positive correlation with rest of the variables excluding investment. The evaluation of the above table shows that in all IN and RC are of great importance for IOC.

Conclusion

An attempt has been made to evaluate the “Financial Performance of the Public Sector Petroleum Industry”. The petro-chemical companies are the economic driver for any of the given country. The uniqueness of the sample units are that, they are engaged in refining, marketing and distribution of petroleum products whereas other corporations do not engage themselves in the above said activities. Both the sampled companies are from the ‘Navratnas’ of the Indian government and this is a clear indication that even the public sector companies of India are having the capability to receive the status of global players and meet the international competitions. Both the companies have shown good performance during the period of study. In order to meet the global challenges, the Public Sector must be given

more capital, more autonomy to expand and grow. If positive steps are taken by the corporations and the Government accepts the suggestions of the study, it will not only benefit to the Government and the Corporations but also to the society at large. The researcher believes that, this study will certainly prompt, further similar as well as related studies.

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Constitutional Amendments: An Instrument For Social Transformation

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▪ Abstract

A century of amendments that have been incorporated into the Constitution in a span of 67 years' exhibit the polity's inclination to upgrade the quality of the supreme law for better situation. Although there were aberrations of authoritarian amendments in the past, the way in which they were rectified by subsequent amendments or by judicial review to reinforce the enduring values with more extensive safeguards reflects the maturity and competence of a throbbing democracy. That the thrust towards social transformation is clear in major constitutional amendments can be inferred by looking to their context and content.

▪ Introduction

Accommodating for future changes through the mechanism of constitutional amendment is one of the prominent requisites of an ideal constitution. A century of amendments that have been incorporated into the Constitution in a span of 67 years' exhibit the polity's inclination to upgrade the quality of the supreme law for better situation. Although there were aberrations of authoritarian amendments in the past, the way in which they were rectified by subsequent amendments or by judicial review to reinforce the enduring values with more extensive safeguards reflects the maturity and competence of a throbbing democracy. That the thrust towards social transformation is clear in major constitutional amendments can be inferred by looking to their context and content. A brief theme-wise survey is attempted for this purpose.

▪ Property Amendments

The issue of subjecting the property right to the goal of economic justice had occupied considerable space in early constitutional development. While the original property right clauses had such orientation, narrow and legalistic interpretations[†] of them by judiciary had repeatedly obstructed the process of realising this goal. Equality clause had been used in *Kameshwar Singh v. State of Bihar*[‡] to quash the **Bihar Land Reforms Act**, 1950 which had provided for differential rates of compensation to land owners whose property had been acquired in the course of land reforms. **Nehru's** fury that the magnificent Constitution was kidnapped and purloined by the lawyers[§] symbolised dissatisfaction of the people and their representatives. Finding that the protection accorded to land reform legislations was inadequate, Articles 31-A and 31-B were added by the **Constitution (1st Amendment) Act**, 1951. Special technique of the 9th Schedule protection was employed for the purpose to protect the agrarian and economic reform legislation from constitutional litigation. From a modest list of 13 legislations originally incorporated, its size has grown stupendously to 284 because of subsequent additions through constitutional amendments. Some of the entries are

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†. Sathe S.P. [1989], **Constitutional Amendments 1950-1988**, N.M. Tripathi, Bombay, at p. 16.

‡. AIR 1951 Pat 91.

§. Parliamentary Debates, Vol. XII (Part 2), 16th May, 1951.

controversial, as they do not fall within the culture, spirit and pattern of economic reforms. Because of the interpretation of the words “*taken possession of*” and “*acquisition*” in *State of West Bengal v. Subodh Gopal Bose*** and *Dwarkadas Shrinivas v. Sholapur Spg. and Wvg. Co. Ltd.*,†† to include the situations of economic regulation of substantial type even for limited period, there was a need to provide through insertion of Clause (2–A) to Article 31 by the **Constitution (4th Amendment) Act**, 1955 to the effect that when ownership was not transferred it did not amount to deprivation of property. In order to counter the judicial approach in *State of West Bengal v. Bella Banerjee*‡‡ insisting on just and equivalent compensation in case of acquisition of property it also made the question of adequacy of compensation in Clause (2) non–justiceable. The protection given to laws reforming estate under Article 31–A was found to be inadequate because of pedantic view taken about that term in *Karimbil Kunhikoman v. State of Kerala*.§§ By amending the definition of the term “*estate*” to include ryotwari holding also, the **Constitution (7th Amendment) Act**, 1964 covered up the deficiency.

In view of the judgment in *Rustom Cavasjee Cooper v. Union of India**** which opened up the issue of justiciability of compensation by scrutinising whether there was compensation or fraudulent expropriation the necessity of substituting the word compensation by a neutral word “*amount*” was felt by the makers of the **Constitution (25th Amendment) Act**, 1971. In *Kesavananda Bharati v. State of Kerala*,††† the Supreme Court insisted that the “*amount*” should not be arbitrary. Article 31–C was also added by this amendment to the effect that legislation implementing the objectives of Articles 39(b) and (c) would enjoy immunity against challenges based on Articles 14, 19 and 31. Repeal of the provisions relating to Privy Purses through the **Constitution (26th Amendment) Act**, 1971 is another radical measure to establish an egalitarian society rejecting the vestiges of hierarchy. The **Constitution (44th Amendment) Act**, 1978 repealed Articles 19(1)(f) and Article 31, manifestly to strengthen the commitment to socialistic pattern of society. The sober status given to property right in Article 300-A could not drive off the arguments relating to reasonableness in the application of property expropriation legislation.††† Although the decline of property right in the scale of values has its own impact on constitutional litigation on property right, in the light of liberalisation, the policy of legislative assurance has come into vogue for fair return to property acquired. Retention of clauses regulative of property right under Articles 31–A and 31–C has served the cause of economic justice. The whole story of property right amendments and its ultimate “*deletion*” from Part III of the **Indian Constitution** depicts the saga of representative bodies to bring reforms in property relations, the conflicts with conservative approach of judiciary and gradual triumph of popular measure to control property owners’ interests for the larger benefits of the society. Property became the first site for removing the obstacles of conservatism in the path of mammoth reforms. The creative and facilitative contribution of constitutional amendments in shifting the focus from property to welfare and liberty is one of the clearest examples of instrumental role of law.

** . AIR 1954 SC 92.

†† . AIR 1954 SC 119.

‡‡ . AIR 1954 SC 170.

§§ . AIR 1962 SC 723: (1962) Suppl SCR 829.

*** . (1970) 1 SCC 248: AIR 1970 SC 564.

††† . (1973) 4 SCC 225: AIR 1973 SC 1461.

††† . *State of Maharashtra v. Basantibai Mohanlal Khetan* (1986) 2 SCC 516: AIR 1986 SC 1466; also see, Bhat P. Ishwara (2004), **Fundamental Rights**, Eastern Law House, Kolkata, at pp. 531–33.

▪ Reservation Policy and Amendments

Provisions on reservation policy constituted another site of frequent amendments^{§§§} either to overcome restrictive interpretations or to expand the area of its operation both in time and space. Political reservation to the SC/STs has been extended decennially from time to time while the original intention was to confine its prevalence only for first 10 years'. In response to *State of Madras v. Champakam Dorairajan*^{****} decision ruling out state's power to provide for reservation in educational institutions Clause (4) was added to Article 15 by the **Constitution (1st Amendment) Act, 1955**. Three amendments were brought to scale down the effect of *Indra Sawhney* judgment on the questions of levels and quantum of reservation in the matter of public employment.^{††††} In order to extend reservation policy to the level of promotion for SC/STs Clause (4-A) was added by the **Constitution (77th Amendment) Act, 1995**. When consequential seniority was not given because of the formal equality rule in *Ajit Singh I v. State of Punjab*^{††††} the Parliament again amended this clause in 2001 by safeguarding the seniority of the reservation promotees. For ensuring that relaxation of promotion rules will not be hit by the requirement of safeguarding administrative efficiency under Article 335 through the application of *Preeti Srivastava (Dr.) v. State of Madhya Pradesh*^{§§§§} ruling, a proviso was added to that effect by the **Constitution (82nd Amendment) Act, 2000**. Unusual method of using 9th Schedule technique was employed by the **Constitution (76th Amendment) Act, 1994** to safeguard the Tamil Nadu legislation on reservation exceeding the 50 percent rule. The **Constitution (81st Amendment) Act, 2000** facilitated to fill up backlog vacancies by going beyond the 50 percent rule as an extraordinary measure by adding Clause (4-B). The fact that as many as five amendments were brought in a span of six years' in the matter of reservation in public employment speaks about the readiness of Parliament and enthusiasm of the political parties to respond to the cause of assisting the SC/STs going beyond the balanced approach taken in *Indra Sawhney* which aimed to satisfy the interests of the society as a whole along with implementing the reservation policy. The Supreme Court has upheld the constitutionality of the amendments to Article 16(4) in *M. Nagaraj v. Union of India*^{*****} but subjected the state measures to a scrutiny about the existence of compelling state interest.

Another landmark development is inclusion of Clause (5) to Article 15 by the **Constitution (93rd Amendment) Act, 2005**, which enables the state to make special provision through law for the advancement of SEBC, SC/STs in the context of admission to educational institutions including private educational institutions whether aided or unaided by the State, other than the minority educational institutions under Article 30(1). Although there was public agitation against this amendment, unanimity of political parties on the policy had enabled its smooth sail. There have been criticisms on this measure on account of undermining the interests of merit, imposition of unjustified burden upon the private institutions, which also have right of administration including admission, and exclusion of the minority institutions from the social

§§§. As many as 16 amendments have been on the matter of reservation.

****. AIR 1951 SC 226.

††††. It has ruled in *Indra Sawhney v. Union of India* (1992) Supp 3 SCC 217: (1992) SCC (L&S) Supp 1: AIR 1993 SC 477 that reservation shall not be extended to the level of promotion and that reservation shall not exceed 50 percent of vacancies.

††††. (1996) 2 SCC 715: AIR 1996 SC 1189, also see, *Ajit Singh II v. State of Punjab* (1999) 7 SCC 209: AIR 1999 SC 3471.

§§§§. (1999) 7 SCC 120: AIR 1999 SC 2894.

*****. (2006) 8 SCC 212.

responsibility of participating in reservation programme. Its constitutional validity was examined by the Supreme Court in *Ashok Kumar Thakur v. Union of India*^{††††} on these counts. The Court upheld the constitutionality of the amendment insofar as it is applicable to public educational institutions.

The overall development exhibits that political decision-making has more traversed the path of vote bank appeasement rather than using the instrument of reservation only as a means to an end and a policy to be balanced with other egalitarian norms for building a harmonious society equipped with competitive ability to face the challenges of globalisation. Anyway, use of amendatory power to go ahead with pro-active policy regarding reservation exhibits its role as a catalyst in social transformation.

▪ **Expanding the Welfare Canvas**

Inclusion of the term “*socialist*” in the Preamble and Clause (2) to Article 38 by constitutional amendments has reinforced the commitment to socialistic pattern of society. Incorporation of Article 48–A gave a great fillip to the invigorating jurisprudence of environmental protection. Addition of Article 39–A has expanded the opportunities to have access to equal justice and free legal aid. By prescribing fundamental duties of citizens to traverse the path of good citizenship and balanced modernisation, the Article 51–A, added by 42nd amendment, has aimed to develop the welfare canvas through people’s participation. About these attempts of retraditionalisation, **Werner Menski** comments:

“*One could read almost all of these statements on Hindu dharma, which shows that recent developments in Indian constitutional law have begun to combine, more explicitly than ever before, new elements of the modern Constitution and ancient holistic concepts.*”^{†††††}

The place of newly incorporated right to free and compulsory primary education under Article 21–A is also crucial for societal preparation for better order.^{§§§§§} The value addition made by amendments has significant social content.

▪ **Strengthening of Democracy**

The amendments aimed at strengthening of the safeguards against abuse of power to impose or implement emergency, combating against political defection, and introduction of grass root democracy with compulsory and periodic election through *Panchayatiraj* and *Nagarpalika amendments* have widened the base and efficacy of democratic institution in India.^{*****} In turn, the competence of participatory democracy for pro-people social transformation is revalorised. Their socio-political inputs consist in establishing mechanisms for better people-government relations, creation of additional forum or method of accountability, and expanding of people’s participation in decision making or policy implementation.

▪ **Socio-Political Preparation for Amendments**

The change management involved in some of the constitutional amendments reflects efforts to take people into confidence by inquiry and discussion initiated and coordinated by special committees and commissions constituted for the purpose. Swaran Singh

^{††††}. (2008) 6 SCC 1.

^{†††††}. Menski Werner (2000), **Comparative Law in a Global Context: The Legal Systems of Asia and Africa**, Platinum, London, at p. 205.

^{§§§§§}. Inserted by the **Constitution (86th Amendment) Act**, 2002.

^{*****}. The **Constitution (44th Amendment) Act**, 1978; the **Constitution (52nd Amendment) Act**, 1985; the **Constitution (73rd Amendment) Act**, 1992; the **Constitution (74th Amendment) Act**, 1992.

Committee preceding the **Constitution (42nd Amendment) Act, 1976**, the **Sarkaria Commission on Centre–State Relations, 1985** and the **National Commission to Review the Working of the Constitution (NCRWC), 2000** headed by Justice **M.N. Venkatachaliah** have contributed to public discussion on need and desirability of amendments. But majority of amendments are not preceded by systematic popular discussion, but are outcome of limited discussion within Parliament although with media publicity. While the Swaran Singh Committee recommendations could not be discussed in free atmosphere due to internal emergency situation, the outcome of the latter two in terms of constitutional changes has not been enormous.

The NCRWC recommendation for incorporation of right to primary education as Fundamental Right has materialised. Its suggestion for scheme of rural employment guarantee is also given practical shape and legal status in the form of a law.^{†††††} The Commission expressed disappointment about inadequate implementation of the constitutional goals. Three observations made by NCRWC can be remembered here regarding building up a developed and inclusive society with commitment to human rights and welfare:

- 1) The first and the foremost need are to place the citizens of this country at centre stage and demonstrate this prioritisation in all manifestation of governance.
- 2) The sociology of pluralism is not inimical to strong democracy, but, on the contrary, is in itself a strong sustaining factor of democracy. It is essential to promote participatory institutions, and
- 3) In the changing context of globalised economy, the Fundamental Law should address itself in action to relocate the sources of the social obligations of the State.

As a part of implementation strategy for the Directive Principles it suggested annual scrutiny of the governmental efforts through interactive seminars participated by civil society. It should be noted that the need to fill the gap between people and the Constitution shall be properly addressed as a part of social transformation discourse and exercise.^{†††††}

General elections have also supplied opportunities for people's choice about constitutional amendments. Election manifestos of political parties often refer to future constitutional amendments. Although it is not well established that political promises really influence people's voting behaviour, parties in power claim people's specific mandate to bring the promised constitutional change after the election. Abolition of Privy Purse and of right to property and restoration of democratic features of the Constitution after the internal emergency has been the products of ballot. Public debate involved in the electoral process makes people participants in the change process.

^{†††††}. The **National Rural Employment Guarantee Act, 2005**, later renamed as the **Mahatma Gandhi National Rural Employment Guarantee Act**.

^{†††††}. Bhat P. Ishwara (2007), *Towards bridging the Gap between People and the Constitution*, 1 Legal Opus 14.

Performance Of Tourism Industry In Uttarakhand: Special Reference To Char Dham Yatra

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Abstract

Tourism and Religion are two different aspects of Human life. Religion is the set of rules and lifestyle followed by its believers, it incorporates emotional feelings and ritualistic behaviours as well as providing a moral compass for communities and Tourism is a social, cultural and economic phenomenon which entails the movement of people to countries or places outside their usual environment for personal or business/professional purposes. Thus the incorporation of religion with tourism called religious tourism or pilgrimage tourism. Uttarakhand State has lots of important religious tourist visit sites. Tourist around the year come here on their religious belief to visit fulfil their religious belief and to visit religious places. Tourism as an industry is a generator of economic as well as social inclusion at the national and international level and also the fastest growing industry in the global economy This paper is going to study the performance of the tourism industry of Uttarakhand based on tourist arrival and its contribution to the state's gross domestic product.

Key Words: Religious Tourism; Pilgrimage; Gross State Domestic Product

Introduction

Uttarakhand considered being the 'Devbhoomi' or 'Land of God' because here in Uttarakhand many religious places situated. Pilgrimage Tourism or religious Tourism is one of the integral parts of Uttarakhand tourism industry as well as it is economy. It consists of travel to different destinations for religious purposes. Tourism is being a significant economic activity in Uttarakhand Economy. People here, around the year, indulge in religious activities like celebrating different festivals, pilgrimage to sacred places, religious yatras (journey) and other religious activities. The significance of Tourism is one of the significant items of commercial growth in the region. Tourism industry earns the gross revenue and provide jobs, and play an essential role in economic development.

Methodology

This research paper is mostly based on secondary data, which have been collected from many sources. These sources included online published resources and government official websites. This research is descriptive.

Objective

The prime objective of this paper is going to ascertain the performance of the Tourism Industry of Uttarakhand state by tourist arrival and change in Gross State Domestic Product (GSDP).

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Study Area

Uttarakhand is the 27th State of India and parted out from the Uttara Pradesh state on 09 November 2000. It is a favourite state for its scenic beauty and religious places. It is mostly the hilly state as it situated in Himalayan Hill Region. In ancient literature, it is described as 'Kedarkhand' and 'Kurmanchal'. This region belonged to many sacred places of Hindus before the Vedas and got status of Dev Bhoomi, and it also has sacred places belongs to other religions also. Uttarakhand was formed from the North-Western part of Uttar Pradesh State of India. It located between 30°03'N to 30 °05'N and 79°19'E 79°31'E having a total geographic area of 51,125 square km, of which 93% is mountainous, and 64% is covered by forest. There are 13 districts in Uttarakhand: Pithoragarh, Almora, Bageshwar, Champawat, Uttarkashi, Udham Singh Nagar, Chamoli, Dehradun, Pauri Garhwal, Tehri Garhwal, Rudraprayag, and Haridwar. Uttarakhand shares its borders with Tibet in the north, Nepal in the east, and the states of Himachal Pradesh and Uttar Pradesh in the west and south respectively. The region is traditionally referred to as Uttarakhand in Hindu scriptures and old literature, a term which is derived from the Sanskrit for Northern Country or Section. The capital of Uttarakhand is Dehradun which is also a rail-head and the largest city in the region. The population of Uttarakhand as per the Census of 2011 of India is 10,116,752, in which 5,154,178 are males, and 4,962,574 are females.

Uttarakhand has everything to offer to every kind of tourist, whether one interested in pilgrimage, spirituality, adventure sports, camping, etc. The tourist places that are known among the visitors are Dehradun, Nainital, Almora, Uttarkashi, Chamoli, Rudraprayag, Haridwar, Auli, Badrinath, Kedarnath, Yamnotri, Gangotri, PanchBadri, PanchKedar.

Uttarakhand And Religious Tourism

Travelling for a religious purpose is one of the integral parts of tourism in Uttarakhand. Many important religious sites of different religions are situated in the State Uttarakhand. Badrinath, Kedarnath, Yamunotri, Gangotri, Haridwar, Hemkund Lokpal, Nanakmatta, Piran Kaliyar, Punyagiri are some of the best known religious destinations. Many important religious yatras (journey), of which Nanda Devi Raj Jat and Kailash Mansarovar Yatra are the most popular, also take Place in the State.

Char Dham

Char Dham of Uttarakhand or also known as Chota Char Dham (small four abodes) are important religious Hindu Pilgrimages. Badrinath, Kedarnath, Gangotri, and Yamunotri are the places includes in it.

BADRINATH: Badrinath is considered one of the holiest places in the Hindu religion. One of the 108 Divya Desams, Badrinath temple is part of both Char Dham and Chota Char Dham. Adi Shankaracharya found the idol of Lord Badri in Alaknanda River and put it up in a cave near the Tapt Kund. In the 16th century, a Garhwal King got the temple erected, which has been renovated many times as a result of natural calamities. Sandwiched between Nar and Narayan peaks, the beauty of Badrinath Dham is further enhanced with the glorious background of Neelkanth peak.

KEDARNATH: Situated in the Rudraprayag district of Uttarakhand, Kedarnath is the most remote pilgrimage spot in the yatra. It is believed that originally the temple of Kedarnath was built by Pandavas. Moreover, Adi Shankaracharya got the present structure constructed in the 8th century adjacent to the old temple site. The grey stone structure is an architectural marvel because of its imposing design and its ability to survive for so many centuries in such harsh terrain.

YAMUNOTRI: Yamunotri is where the second most holy of the river of India, the River Yamuna, takes birth. Situated in the Uttarkashi district of Uttarakhand, Yamunotri Dham is the first stop in the pilgrimage. It is believed that bathing in its water cleanses all sins and protects from an untimely and painful death. The shrine of Yamunotri is believed to be built in 1839 by the king of Tehri, Naresh Sudarshan Shah. Besides the Yamuna Devi (goddess), the idol of Ganga Devi to is housed in the revered temple. There are many hot water springs near the temple; Surya Kund is the most important among them. Devotees boil rice and potatoes in the kind and accept it as a Prasad of the device.

GANGOTRI: Dham is dedicated to Goddess Ganga, who is said to have descended on earth to absolve the sins of humankind. The river originates at Gaumukh from the Gangotri glacier which is some 18 km from the town of Gangotri. Situated in Uttarkashi district of Uttarakhand, the original temple of Gangotri was built by Amar Singh Thapa, a Gurkha general, in the early 19th century.

In the Uttarakhand, tourism has grown since the new state formed and become the fastest growing sector in the state. Religious tourism fetches a huge revenue to the state. The state always attracts tourist and pilgrims from all over the world. Table 1.1 shows tourist arrival trends in the state from the year 2011 to the year 2015.

TABLE 1

Tourist arrival trends in the Uttarakhand					
Uttarakhand	Year				
	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015
	26070907	26951884	20038811	22093281	29602820

Source: Ministry of Tourism, Government of India

As we see from table 1, there was an increasing trend in tourist visited Uttarakhand from the year 2011 to 2012 but in the year 2013, data shows all-time low tourist arrival to the State. In 2013, the state faced Kedarnath disaster which is one of the major cause to all-time low-level tourist arrival to the state. After 2013 again there is the increasing trend in the tourist arrival in the state.

Table 2 shows the religious tourism data about tourist arrival to ‘Badrinath’ and ‘Kedarnath’ dham visit. From the data table we could conclude that from the year 2011 to 2012 there were increasing numbers of tourists visit in both places but after that in the year 2013 to 2014 due to ‘Kedarnath Disaster’ tourist industry deeply hit and tourist arrival come to a shallow level. After that both places maintaining increasing tourist arrival in the State.

TABLE 2: SHRI BADRINATH KEDARNATH TOURIST ARRIVAL TRENDS

YEAR	BADRINATH	KEDARNATH
2011	9,80,667	5,71,583
2012	9,85,631	5,83,176
2013	4,97,744	3,12,201
2014	1,80,000	40,832
2015	3,59,146	1,54,430
2016	6,24,745	3,09,746
2017	8,84,788	4,71,235

Source: *Badriker Mandir Samit*

The Contribution Of Tourism To The State Economy

Tourism is an important industry for developing nations. The Indian Himalayan region attracts a mass of tourists. The contribution of tourism to the state economy could be ascertained from the table 3. The table reveals the data about tourism contribution to the state’s gross state domestic product from the year 2010-11 to the year 2014-15. The data shows that the contribution of tourism in the state economy shows an increasing trend and it is going to big and big every year.

Gross state domestic product (GSDP) at factor cost 'trade, hotel and restaurants' (current price)					
Uttarakhand	GSDP (₹ in Lacs)				
	2010-11	2011-12	2012-13	2013-14	2014-15
	1939254	2375533	2550948	2840372	3056268

Source: Reserve Bank of India

Conclusion

The Study concluded that the tourist industry in the state growing day by day. Tourist arrival to the religious places is growing, but the industry is fragile as the natural disasters show hindrance to the tourism industry. Also in the economic front, tourism is going to be the major contributor to the state economy.

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Biochemical Analysis Of *Trichosanthes Cucumerina*. The Plant Extract Was Used For Resuding Sugar Level In The Human Blood In Empty Stomach.

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Introduction and Process

Trichosanthes Cucumerina is locally known as 'Amrit Phla or Kastbhanjan'. It is a member of the family cucurbitaceae. Local Vaidyas and Hakims of Dhanbad district used this plant for diabetic patients. The stem and leaves of this plant are dipped in the night and drinking water and extract of plant with drinking water is taken by the diabetic patient in the morning in empty stomach. One diabetic patient in Dhanbad district told us that the extract of this plant has positive effect. He told us that 25 days before my blood sugar level was 371 when I examined blood sugar level at Dhanbad yesterday, my blood sugar level slashed to 167. I used this plant extract regularly in the morning in empty stomach. Besides it is used in diabetic patient the extract of this plant is used as blood purifier, febrifuge, vermifuge and in stomach disorder.

Chemical analysis

The extract of this plant was prepared according to methodology suggested by Ranjan and Loraya (1960) 10 μ alcoholic extract of healthy leaves was loaded on Watman Chromatography paper No.1 along with standard amino acids. The Chromatogram to run with solvent system containing n-butanol : acid : distilled water [4:1:1 V/V/V top layer]. They were dried, sprayed with 0.3% ninhydrin solution (300mg ninhydrin dissolved in 100 ml of n-butanol to which then 3ml of glacial acetic acid added. The chromatography was allowed to air dry. Subsequently they were transferred to oven at 105 $^{\circ}$ C for 5 minutes.

Free Amino acid

Amino acid analysis spots of various amino acids were identified by comparing the colour and as R_f value done on the basis of intensities which were by visual observations recorded in 4 categories i.e. 3⁺, 2⁺, + acid +tr.

Bound amino acids

The processes were followed for bound amino acids. Result of amino acids analysis has been given in Table No-1

Protein analysis

The seeds and other proteins (Water Soluble) were determined quantitatively by disc electrophoretic method (Ornstein and Davis, 1961) the result of protein analysis of *Andropogon Parucula* has been in Table No.2 and finger print Fig. No.1.

Alkaloid analysis

Estimation and identification of alkaloids were done according to methods recommended by Clarke (1970). The result of the alkaloid analysis has been given in Table No. 3.

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Ultraviolet measurement

Confirm the presence of alkaloid by measuring UV spectrum of the sample dissolved in NH₂ So₄. Typical maxima values ranges from 250 to 303 nm. Alkaloids with aromatic rings in their structure may be absorbed by longer wave length. For the purpose Beekman spectrophotometer was used noted and colour of emitted light was noted on visual observation of both marker and unknown alkaloids

Inorganic analysis

Analysis of detectable chemicals of *Trichosanthes Cucumerina* has been given with the help of methods suggested by Bhatia and Parashar (1971). Resulted of inorganic analysis has been given in Table No. 4.

Table No. 1. Showing data of amino acids present plant extract of *Trichosanthes Cucumerina* collected from Topchachi of Dhanbad district.

Sport Nos	Amino acids	Rt values	Concentration of Amino acids on visual observalia							
			Pree Amino acids				Bound Amino acids			
			T ₁	T ₂	T ₃	Mean	T ₁	T ₂	T ₃	Mean
1.	Lysine	0.04	+	3+	3+	3+	-	-	-	-
2.	LHistidine	0.06	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
3.	Aspartic acid	0.09	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
4.	L-argenine	0.12	+	-	+	+	-	-	-	-
5.	Cysteine	0.16	3+	3+	3+	3+	+	-	+	+
6.	DL-asparagine	0.18	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
7.	Proline	0.21	2+	2+	2+	2+	-	-	-	-
8.	L-glutamine	0.23	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
9.	Serine	0.24	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
10.	Hydroxyproline	0.26	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-

(Cont.....Table -1.)

Sport Nos	Amino acids	Rt values	Concentration of Amino acids on visual observalia							
			Pree Amino acids				Bound Amino acids			
			T ₁	T ₂	T ₃	Mean	T ₁	T ₂	T ₃	Mean
11.	DL-threonine	0.28	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
12.	Glycine	0.31	3+	3+	3+	3+	+	+	2+	+
13.	L-glutamic acid	0.33	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
14.	Ornithin	0.34	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
15.	Dihydroxy phenylamine	0.37	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
16.	DL-alanine	0.45	2+	2+	2+	2+	-	-	-	-
17.	DL-methionine	0.49	+	+	+	+	-	-	-	-
18.	Amino-n-butric acid	0.56	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
19.	L-valine	0.61	3+	2+	3+	3+	2+	2+	2+	2+
20.	Tyrosine	0.63	2+	2+	2+	2+	-	-	-	-

21.	Phenylalaine	0.67	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
22.	DL-tryptophan	0.71	2+	+	2+	2+	+	2+	2+	2+
23.	Iso-leucine	0.76	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
24.	Leucine	.80	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-

Table -2 Showing data of protein analysis of the plant extract of *Trichosanthes Cucumerina* collected from Topchanchi of Dhanbad district.

Protein band Nos	Rp value	Visual observation
1.	1.3	-
2.	2.5	3+
3.	6.0	3+
4.	0.8	-
5.	3.8	-
6	5.3	2+
7	0.4	-
8.	3.0	-
9.	2.0	-
10.	2.3	-

Fig No.1. :- finger print of Electrophoretic protein analysis of the plant of extract of *Trichosanthes Cucumerina*.

Table No. 3. Biochemical analysis of alkaloids of plant extract *Trichosanthes Cucumerina* collected from Topchanchi of Dhanbad District.

Alkaloids	Chromotographed Rf Value $\times 100$	Visual observation	Nature in uv light	Reagent used for the detections
Cystisine	03	-	Blue	Dragen dorff
Nicotine	07	-	Absorbed	Iodoplatinate
Tomative	08	-	Invisible	Do
Morphine	14	-	Absorbed	Dragen dorff
Solanine	15	-	Invisible	Do
Berberine	25	-	Flourescond	Do
Atrophine	37	-	Absorbed	Do
Quinine Conine	56	-	Invisible	Do
Unknown extract	17	+	Absorbed	Dragan-dorff
	23	3+	Flurescent	Do
	48	2+	Invisible	Iodoplatinate

The plant extract of *Trichosanthes Cucumerina*. In this extrac three type of alkaloied could be detected. They were 17, 23, 48 of Rf values.

Table No 4: Showing result of inorganic analysis Analysis *Trichosanthes Cucumerina* from Topchanchi of Dhanbad district.

Types of the elements	Visual observation
Nitrogen	2+
Calcium	+
Ferous (Iron)	3+
Postassiuur	3+
Phosphorus	3+

Discussion

In nineteenth and twentieth centuries chemical nature of natural products were developed by Weygard (1940); Shemyakin (1965); Miller and Orgel (1972); Jorns and Hersh (1974) and Fsicher (1984). Currently, most of the investigation are applying there expertise to examining biochemical nature and biosynthesis of phyto-chemicals to solving the Stereo-Chemical and mechanistic problems posed. However, seeing the vast member of forms of form of plants relatively little has been made in this regard due to the fact that some of the principles and philosophies are often compounded by lack of the familiarity with biochemical terminology and methods. In spite of that, an even increasing of chemists are being attracted to the challenges of Synthetic Structural, and Stereo chemical and other problems of organic chemistry.

The data presented of medicinal plant i.e. *Trichosanthes Cucumerina* Linn. Which is used by diabetes patients in Dhanbad district. One cup of the plant juice was used in empty stomach. One patient was silting on the verandah of a local vaidya at Topchanchi. When we enquired about that patient he told us one cup of AmritPhla was used in empty stomach by diabetic patient, he told us that one month ago my blood sugar level was 371 but when I

AmritPhla or kastbhanjan one month ago my sugar level was dropped to 167 on the advice of this vaidya. I came here show my report of blood sugar level to Vaidya.

Amino acids

In *Trichosanthes Cucumerina* only 12 type of amine acids could detected. Those were Lysine, Aspartic acid, Larginine, cystine praline, DL-theonine, glycine, Alarine out of there Aspartic acid, cystun, DL- theonine, glyline valine both the forms. While Lysine, Proline, DL-alanine, DL-metheorine, Trosine were recorded his free form only. Among the 12 types of amino acid Lysine, Cystein, Glyeine and Lvaline were recorded in high potencial i.e. 3+ level while other types of amino acids were recorded at + or 2+ level. Although more than 100 amino acids are known but only 20 amino acids take part is synthesis of proteins.

Protein analysis

in protein analysis of *Trichosanthes Cucumerina* were recorded the Table No2 and Fig-No1. in protein band No.2 and 3 were recorded at 3+ level while band No 6 was recorded in 2+ level. Having Rp value 2.5, 6.0 and 5.3.

The term protein is derived from the Greek noun protein measuring "holding first place" the term was suggested by Berzeliurls (1838) and first used by G.J. Mulder in his book in 1939. Protein has very important in all the living cells. It is essential in diet for another metabolic processes in living organisms. It has varieties of roles, as proteins are of specific nature viz. nutritive, enzymatic, hormonal, the making anti-bodies, medicinal, genetical etc. The way all basic functions of life depends upon specific protein. Indeed we do not know life without proteins. After the works of Neurath (1936-66), Linskens and tracey (1967), Leggett and Baily (1970), Harborne *et.al.* (1971), Arison and Edsall (1973) and Kaziell *et.al.* (1993) the details of protein structure and function could be known. According to them protein is a macromolecule of polypeptide chain. Therefore, polypeptide chain assume specific configuration to perform specific functions assigned to them.

Protein constituents of any plant may be very helpful in tracing the phylogeny on the unknown plant. In this regard commendable works have been done by Boulter (1972) MC Leester *et. al* (1983), fair brother (1984) and Naish (1996).

Alkaloid analysis

The chemistry of alkaloid began with the announcement of isolation of morphine form optimum in 1805 by F.W. Sertuner.

The term alkaloid was proposed by a pharmacist, C.F.W meissner in 1819. Today more than five thousand alkaloid are known to occur more then 4000 species of Angiosperms. Alkaloids are mostly loxic substances having primary effect on central nervous system are of the organisms.

The noticeable works regarding alkaloids are of Hegnaur (1967), Henery (1969), Clarke (1970) and Luning (1987). The detailed chemistry of alkaloids could be known with the work of above biochemists. In *Trichosanthes Cucumerina* there type of alkaloid could be noticed in plant extracts. These were with Rf value 17, 23 and 48. in Uv light Rf value 17 was absorbed while Rf value 23 was with highest potencies on visual observation i.e. 3+ while Rf value 48 has lower potencies ie 2+.

Perhaps these alkaloids lower blower blood sugar level in human beings.

Inorganic analysis

The detectable inorganic constituents of *Trichosanthes Cucumerina* on methodology suggested by Bhatia and parasar collected from Topchanchi, of Dhanbad District in terms of calcium, phosphorus, potassium, nitrogen and Iorn could be detected, this plant was

recommended to diabetic patients. Calcium is useful in growth of the bones in human beings and milking cattle and this plant is recommended by local vaidyas and Hakims of tribal belt of Deoghar district to diabetic patients.

In *Trichosanthes Cucumerina* phosphorous is detected and visual observation it was detected at 2+ level. Like wise is this plant potassium is detected in this plant. On visual observation it was detected at '+' level only.

In *Trichosanthes Cucumerina* nitrogen could be detected. On visual observation it was detected at 3+ level. In this plant iron could be detected and on visual observation it was detected at 3+ level.

Besides diabetes, the plant extract was very much used in high fever, in inflammation, used in Jaundice and in vermin-fuse. Root extract was used in hemorrhoids, rubbed after burning on the palm and sole of the feet and used as cardiac tonic. The seed extracts were used as paste for leper patients, used in snake bite and skin diseases.

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A study on Dynamic Kinematics and Motion of Missile and its Mathematical Modeling

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Abstract

The objective of autopilot design in missile is to provide better stability for miss distance, robustness and satisfactory performance, so that the missile only hit the target with more accuracy. Missile autopilots can command body rates, flight angle path, acceleration and incident angles. In this study, motion of missile and kinematics for the missile dynamic model has been studied and governing differential equations have been derived. For the analysis and modeling the missile is considered as combination of two bodies connected by free rotating bearing. The first body considered contains seeker and guidance control while second body contains rocket motor and fixed tail wings. Using the model control actuation model system is discussed. Basic mathematics modeling with basic equations defining kinematics and dynamics for control are structured.

Keywords—Missile dynamic control, autopilot control, missile motion control, Kinematics.

I. Introduction

Missile is any object which can be fired, thrown or projected towards anything (target). With manual or automatic means, the projectile with payload (warhead) is guided towards target with a motive to provide damage to target [1-2]. Depending upon orientation towards target, the missiles are classified into guided and unguided missiles. Unguided missiles (rockets) can be aimed towards the direction of target only before firing, once fired they cannot be controlled and can be aimed towards the direction of moving [3].

II. Missile Dynamic Modeling And Missile Kinematics

For the modeling, body of missile is considered as combination of two parts which is connected by free rotating bearing [4-5]. The body in front acts as guidance and control unit while rear body takes necessary output from front section and controls thrust and tail wings [6-7]. Figure 1 shows considered missile model.

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Figure 1. Missile model for analysis

Mass centers of front and rear body (body 1 and body 2) are represented by C1 and C2. While CM denotes mass center of the entire missile. At missile point C1 the reference frame of front body (body 1) is denoted as Fb. F0 is earth's fixed reference frame with origin point Oe. The intermediate reference frame between Fb and F0 is given as Fn and Fm respectively [8-10]. The relevant rotating frame based Euler angle sequence can be written as

$$\begin{matrix}
 \vec{u}_3^{(0)} & \vec{u}_2^{(m)} & \vec{u}_1^{(n)} \\
 F_0 & \rightarrow F_m & \rightarrow F_n & \rightarrow F_b \\
 \psi_1 & \theta_1 & \phi_1 &
 \end{matrix} \quad (1)$$

ψ_1 , θ_1 and ϕ_1 are Euler angles in yaw, pitch and roll directions of front body.

The reference frames are taken as orthogonal and right handed. Considering rotation sequence and using basic rotation matrices, for front body overall rotation matrix can be written [11-12]

$$\hat{C}^{(0,b)} = \hat{C}^{(0,m)} \hat{C}^{(m,n)} \hat{C}^{(n,b)} = \hat{R}_3(\psi_1) \hat{R}_2(\theta_1) \hat{R}_1(\phi_1) \quad (2)$$

The matrices of rotation about pitch, yaw and roll axis can be given as

$$\hat{C}^{(m,n)} = \begin{bmatrix} \cos(\theta_1) & 0 & \sin(\theta_1) \\ 0 & 1 & 0 \\ -\sin(\theta_1) & 0 & \cos(\theta_1) \end{bmatrix} \quad (3)$$

$$\hat{C}^{(0,m)} = \begin{bmatrix} \cos(\psi_1) & -\sin(\psi_1) & 0 \\ \sin(\psi_1) & \cos(\psi_1) & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \quad (4)$$

$$\hat{C}^{(n,b)} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \cos(\phi_1) & -\sin(\phi_1) \\ 0 & \sin(\phi_1) & \cos(\phi_1) \end{bmatrix} \quad (5)$$

For front body the angular velocity with respect to F0 can be determined in terms of rates of Euler angles

$$\vec{\omega}_{b/0} = \dot{\psi}_1 \vec{u}_3^{(0)} + \dot{\theta}_1 \vec{u}_2^{(m)} + \dot{\phi}_1 \vec{u}_1^{(n)} \quad (6)$$

In F0, $\vec{\omega}_{b/0}$ can be re written as

$$\vec{\omega}_{b/0}^{(b)} = [p_1 \quad q_1 \quad r_1]^T \quad (7)$$

Roll, pitch and yaw rates of front body can be expressed as

$$p_1 = \dot{\phi}_1 - \dot{\psi}_1 \sin(\theta_1) \quad (8)$$

$$q_1 = \dot{\theta}_1 \cos(\phi_1) + \dot{\psi}_1 \cos(\theta_1) \sin(\phi_1) \quad (9)$$

$$r_1 = -\dot{\theta}_1 \sin(\phi_1) + \dot{\psi}_1 \cos(\theta_1) \cos(\phi_1) \quad (10)$$

Considering, $\cos(\theta_1) \neq 0$, the euler angles can be obtained as

$$\dot{\psi}_1 = [q_1 \sin(\phi_1) + r_1 \cos(\phi_1)] / \cos(\theta_1) \quad (11)$$

$$\dot{\theta}_1 = q_1 \cos(\phi_1) - r_1 \sin(\phi_1) \quad (12)$$

$$\dot{\phi}_1 = p_1 + [q_1 \sin(\phi_1) + r_1 \cos(\phi_1)] \tan(\theta_1) \quad (13)$$

By taking time derivative of $\vec{\omega}_{b/0}$ in F_0 the angular acceleration vector of front body can be determined as

$$\vec{\alpha}_{b/0} = D_0(\vec{\omega}_{b/0}) \quad (14)$$

D_0 denotes time derivative operator.

Expressing $\vec{\alpha}_{b/0}$ in F_b

$$D_0(\vec{\omega}_{b/0}) = D_b(\vec{\omega}_{b/0}) + \vec{\omega}_{b/0} \times \vec{\omega}_{b/0} = D_b(\vec{\omega}_{b/0}) \quad (15)$$

The resulting column $\vec{\alpha}_{b/0}^{(b)}$ can be obtained as

$$\vec{\alpha}_{b/0}^{(b)} = \begin{bmatrix} \dot{p}_1 \\ \dot{q}_1 \\ \dot{r}_1 \end{bmatrix} \quad (16)$$

Where, $\dot{p}_1 = \ddot{\phi}_1 - \dot{\psi}_1 \sin(\theta_1) - \dot{\psi}_1 \dot{\theta}_1 \cos(\theta_1)$ (17)

$$\dot{q}_1 = \ddot{\theta}_1 \cos(\phi_1) + [\dot{\psi}_1 \sin(\phi_1) + \dot{\psi}_1 \dot{\phi}_1 \cos(\phi_1)] \cos(\theta_1) - \dot{\theta}_1 [\dot{\phi}_1 + \dot{\psi}_1 \sin(\theta_1)] \sin(\phi_1) \quad (18)$$

$$\dot{r}_1 = -\ddot{\theta}_1 \sin(\phi_1) + [\dot{\psi}_1 \cos(\phi_1) - \dot{\psi}_1 \dot{\phi}_1 \sin(\phi_1)] \cos(\theta_1) - \dot{\theta}_1 [\dot{\phi}_1 + \dot{\psi}_1 \sin(\theta_1)] \cos(\phi_1) \quad (19)$$

As front body is controlled body, the entire missile can be taken be coincident with F_b . [13] therefore,

$$\begin{aligned} p &= p_1 \\ q &= q_1 \\ r &= r_1 \end{aligned}$$

like C_1 and C_2 , assuming C_M lies on $\vec{u}_1^{(b)}$, distance between C_1 and C_M can be given as

$$X_M = \frac{m_2}{m_1} d_{12} \quad (20)$$

Where $X_M=C_M$, and m and m_2 are mass of entire missile and rear body respectively. Distance between points C_1 and C_2 is given by d_{12} .

Velocity vector of C_M and C_1 w.r.t O_e can be related as

$$\vec{V}_{C_1/O_e} = \vec{V}_{C_M/O_e} + X_M [\vec{\omega}_{b/0} \times \vec{u}_1^{(b)}] \quad (21)$$

And this equation can be expressed in F_b as

$$\vec{V}_{C_1/O_e}^{(b)} = \vec{V}_{C_M/O_e}^{(b)} + X_M [\vec{\omega}_{b/0}^{(b)} \vec{u}_1] \quad (22)$$

Where

$$\vec{V}_{C_1/O_e}^{(b)} = [u_1 \quad v_1 \quad w_1]^T \text{ and } \vec{\omega}_{b/0}^{(b)} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & -r & q \\ r & 0 & -p \\ -q & p & 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

With

$$\vec{V}_{C_M/O_e}^{(b)} = [u \quad v \quad w]^T \quad (23)$$

, above equation yields

$$u_1 = u$$

$$v_1 = v + X_M r$$

$$w_1 = w - X_M q$$

Taking time derivatives

$$\dot{u}_1 - r v_1 + q w_1 = \dot{u} - r v + q w - X_M (q^2 + r^2) \tag{24}$$

$$\dot{v}_1 - r u_1 - p w_1 = \dot{v} - r u + p w - X_M (\dot{r} + p q) \tag{25}$$

$$\dot{w}_1 - q u_1 + p v_1 = \dot{w} - q u + p v - X_M (\dot{q} - p r) \tag{26}$$

III. Equations For Missile Motion

The equations for motion can be derived using Newton-Euler equations from kinematic analysis [14-15].

For front body, Newton-Euler equations can be expressed as

$$\vec{F}_{A1} + \vec{F}_{21} + m_1 \vec{g} = m_1 \vec{a}_{C_1/O_e} \tag{27}$$

$$\vec{M}_{A1} + \vec{M}_{21} + \vec{r}_{B/C_1} \times \vec{F}_{21} = \check{J}_{C_1} \cdot \vec{\alpha}_{b/0} + \vec{\omega}_{b/0} \times \check{J}_{C_1} \cdot \vec{\omega}_{b/0} \tag{28}$$

Similarly for rear body

$$\vec{F}_{A2} + \vec{F}_{T2} + \vec{F}_{12} + m_2 \vec{g} = m_2 \vec{a}_{C_2/O_e} \tag{29}$$

$$\vec{M}_{A2} + \vec{M}_{T2} + \vec{M}_{12} + \vec{r}_{B/C_2} \times \vec{F}_{12} = \check{J}_{C_2} \cdot \vec{\alpha}_{S/0} + \vec{\omega}_{S/0} \times \check{J}_{C_2} \cdot \vec{\omega}_{S/0} \tag{30}$$

$\vec{F}_{Ai}, \vec{M}_{Ai}$: Aerodynamic force and moment vectors acting on body i

$\vec{F}_{ij}, \vec{M}_{ij}$: Reaction force and moment vectors Applied by body i on body j

$\vec{F}_{T2}, \vec{M}_{T2}$: Thrust force and thrust misalignment Moment vectors acting on body 2

m_i =body i mass

\check{J}_{C_i} : Inertia dyadic of body I about its own mass center

\vec{g} : Acceleration of gravity

\vec{r}_{B/C_i} : Position vector between the mass center of body i and The midpoint of the bearing (point B)

By looking the above equations the moment terms and thrust force occurs in rear body because rocket motor is mounted on rear body [16]. The vectors \vec{r}_{B/C_1} and \vec{r}_{B/C_2} can be expressed as

$$\vec{r}_{B/C_1} = -d_1 \vec{u}_1^{(b)} \tag{30}$$

$$\vec{r}_{B/C_2} = d_2 \vec{u}_1^{(b)} \tag{31}$$

In F_b

$$\vec{F}_{A1}^{(b)} + \vec{F}_{21}^{(b)} + m_1 \vec{g}^{(b)} = m_1 \vec{a}_{C_1/O_e}^{(b)} \tag{32}$$

$$\vec{M}_{A1}^{(b)} + \vec{M}_{21}^{(b)} - d_1 \tilde{u}_1 \vec{F}_{21}^{(b)} = \hat{J}_{C_1}^{(b)} \vec{\alpha}_{b/0}^{(b)} + \tilde{\omega}_{b/0}^{(b)} \hat{J}_{C_1}^{(b)} \vec{\omega}_{b/0}^{(b)} \tag{33}$$

$$\vec{F}_{A2}^{(b)} + \vec{F}_{T2}^{(b)} + \vec{F}_{12}^{(b)} + m_2 \vec{g}^{(b)} = m_2 \vec{a}_{C_2/O_e}^{(b)} \tag{34}$$

$$\vec{M}_{A2}^{(b)} + \vec{M}_{T2}^{(b)} + \vec{M}_{12}^{(b)} + d_2 \tilde{u}_1 \vec{F}_{12}^{(b)} = \hat{f}_{c_2}^{(b)} \vec{\alpha}_{S/0}^{(b)} + \tilde{\omega}_{S/0}^{(b)} \hat{f}_{c_2}^{(b)} \vec{\omega}_{S/0}^{(b)} \quad (35)$$

For aerodynamic and thrust effects the force and motion are expressed as

$$\vec{F}_{A1}^{(b)} = \begin{bmatrix} X_1 \\ Y_1 \\ Z_1 \end{bmatrix} \quad (36)$$

$$\vec{M}_{A1}^{(b)} = \begin{bmatrix} L_1 \\ M_1 \\ N_1 \end{bmatrix} \quad (37)$$

$$\vec{F}_{A2}^{(b)} = \begin{bmatrix} X_2 \\ Y_2' \\ Z_2' \end{bmatrix} \quad (38)$$

$$\vec{M}_{A2}^{(b)} = \begin{bmatrix} L_2 \\ M_2' \\ N_2' \end{bmatrix} \quad (39)$$

$$\vec{F}_{T2}^{(b)} = \begin{bmatrix} X_{T2} \\ Y_{T2}' \\ Z_{T2}' \end{bmatrix} \quad (40)$$

$$\vec{M}_{T2}^{(b)} = \begin{bmatrix} L_{T2} \\ M_{T2}' \\ N_{T2}' \end{bmatrix} \quad (41)$$

IV. Control Acquisition System Model

To convert commands signals generated by guidance unit (front body) into reliable mechanical responses and desired fin deflections to guide missile towards target, control acquisition system is required [17-18]. The equation of motion of servomotor can be written as

$$J_e \ddot{\delta}_m + B_m \dot{\delta}_m + T_{HM}' = T_m \quad (42)$$

δ_m is Angular deflection of output shaft, J_e is equivalent moment of inertia, B_m is viscous damping coefficient of rotor, T_{HM} is Hinge moment, T_m is generated torque [19].

By the autopilot, the command signals to the control acquisition system are sent in form of voltages [20]. A (input) and B (output) are ports of CAS and the equation between voltages are given by

$$V_B = V_A - R_{Ai} \quad (43)$$

Where R_A is effective resistance of circuit between A and B and I is flow of current from A to B.

The relationship between $\dot{\delta}_m$ and V_B is given by

$$\dot{\delta}_m = \frac{V_B}{K_b} \quad (44)$$

And between T_m and i

$$T_m = K_T i \quad (45)$$

K_b and K_T are called DC motor constant and

$$K_b = K_T$$

so

$$T_m = \left(\frac{K_T}{R_A}\right) V_A - \left(\frac{K_T K_b}{R_A}\right) \dot{\delta}_m \quad (46)$$

The equation can be rewritten as

$$(J_e \ddot{\delta}_m + B_e \dot{\delta}_m) = \left(\frac{K_T}{R_A}\right) V_A - T'_{HM} \quad (47)$$

Where $B_e = B_m + \frac{K_T K_b}{R_A}$

In laplace domain the equation can be written as

$$(J_e s^2 + B_e) \dot{\delta}_m(s) = \left(\frac{K_T}{R_A}\right) V_A(s) - T'_{HM}(s) \quad (48)$$

Type 1 control system can be built with these equations which is shown in figure 2.

Using block diagram algebra, closed loop transfer function of Control Acquisition system can be obtained as

$$\frac{\delta_f(s)}{\delta_{fd}(s)} = \frac{n_2 s^2 + n_1 s + 1}{d_3 s^3 + d_2 s^2 + d_1 s + 1} \quad (49)$$

Where $n_1 = T_i$ and $n_2 = T_i T_d$,

$$d_1 = T_i \left(\frac{K_{HM} R_A}{N K_T K_P K}\right) + 1 \quad (50)$$

$$d_2 = T_i \left(\frac{N R_A B_e}{K_T K_P K}\right) + T_d \quad (51)$$

$$d_3 = \frac{N R_A T_i J_e}{K_T K_P K} \quad (52)$$

V. Conclusion

In this article, mathematical modeling using basic equations in space has been derived. The control body takes input from a seeker and provides the error adjustment to steer the missile towards the target. With the objective of providing more accurate system for autopilot of missile, mathematical equations and the closed loop function is structured. Using the basic equations and derived equations of autopilot, a type 1 control acquisition model is framed. During all probable engagements, the missile should sense the target and taking the values of target the flight path should change in towards the target.

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